

ANALELE UNIVERSITĂȚII DIN ORADEA

FASCICULA: PROTECȚIA MEDIULUI

**VOL XXXVIII
ANUL 27**

**Editura Universității din Oradea
2022**

INFLUENCE OF THE CROP ROTATION AND THE REGIME OF NUTRITION LEVEL ON THE CONTENT OF NITROGEN, PHOSPHORUS, POTASSIUM AND RAW PROTEIN OF SEEDS IN WINTER WHEAT CULTIVATED ON THE PRELUVOSOILS IN THE WESTERN PLAIN OF ROMANIA

Ileana ARDELEAN^{1#}, Ioana Maria BORZA¹, Gheorghe Emil BANDICI¹, Cristian Gabriel DOMUȚA¹

¹ University of Oradea, Faculty of Environmental Protection, 26 General Magheru St., 410048 Oradea, Romania

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

The quality of production is related to a series of physical and chemical characteristics of plants which gives a positive mark to the applied agrotechnical methods for the correlation of the latter to the production obtained on the surface unit.

A more intense accumulation of the biomass which determines an intensification of the photosynthesis positively influences the chemical composition of the final product – the grains.

The total content of N (nitrogen) in the winter wheat grains was influenced by the crop rotation and the nutrition system. The raw protein content follows the natural way similarly to nitrogen total content being influenced mainly by the crop rotation and the regime of nutrition level.

There weren't observed any essential changes of the total P (phosphorus) and K (potassium) content under the influence of the crop rotation and the regime of nutrition level.

Keywords: crop rotation, regime of nutrition level, raw protein, seeds, winter wheat

#Corresponding author: ardeleanileana@gmail.com

INTRODUCTION

Some analyses have been made to establish the quality of the final product regarding the content of N, P, K in wheat seeds and raw protein (Oproiu, Cernescu, 1970; Bandici, Domuța, Ardelean, 2003).

The main component of the chemical composition of the seeds is represented by the glucides (62-75 %) of the fresh wheat grain mass, the proteins 10-16 %, lipids 1.8-2.6 %, cellulose 2-3.5 % and mineral substances 1.5-2.3 % (Hera, 1986 b). A series of analyses of the N, P, K and raw protein content in the wheat grains have been made in order to specify the quality of the final product (Austin, 1978, Zăhan, Zăhan, 1989; Bandici, 1997; 2001).

The production quality is related to a series of physical and chemical characteristics of the plants which gives a positive mark to the agrotechnical applied measures for the correlation of this with the production obtained for/on the surface unit (Munteanu, Cernea, Morar et al., 2008).

The research performed in this field made clear the fact that quality is conditioned by the species and the cultivated hybrid, the climatic

conditions of the cultivating year and also by the technology applied to the agricultural plants. To justify some of these aspects with consequences regarding the quality of the final production, we make some references to the specialised scientific literature, i.e. Hera Cr. et al.(1986a) underline the importance of nitrogen for the increase of the protein content, wet and dry gluten and for the improvement of the quality indicators of gluten. The authors also mention the importance of the ameliorative plant (the pea) for the quality indicators of the wheat. Boldea Eleonora et al. (1986) also mention the importance of the new species of wheat for the quality of raw protein and gluten.

The twinning of the plants is stimulated by the optimum moisture as well as by the presence in proper quantities and proportions of nourishing elements, especially nitrogen and phosphorus (Lazany, 2000, Lazany, 2003).

Their balanced combination, as well as an appropriate agrotechnical system adapted to edaphic and climatic characteristics of the zone lead to increased yields of superior quality.

The quality of the yield is influenced by many factors. Protein accumulation in the grains is influenced by wheat type, cultivar,

climate conditions, natural fertility of the soil, nitrogen doses used, irrigation (Ionescu, 1985). The gluten content of the wheat grain is influenced first of all by climate conditions (Bandici, 1997, Domuța et. al., 2007, 2008).

Usually, the level of protein from wheat grains is a very important parameter of the yield, the protein content of the wheat grain can be 10-16% (Muntean et. al, 2008) but it can have the limits of 4-25% (Bandici, 1997, Bandici et. al., 2003). Protein accumulation in the grains is influenced by the wheat type, cultivar, climate conditions, natural fertility of the soil, nitrogen doses used, irrigation (Domuța and al., 2007, 2008, Bandici, 2018).

The paper analyses the crop rotation and irrigation influence on the protein content of the wheat grain in the conditions of the moderate wet area of the Crisurilor Plain (Domuța, 2012)

The production quality is a feature connected to several physical and chemical characteristics of plants and confers a positive note to the applied agrotechnical measures, having in view the correlation of quality with the obtained production on a surface unit (Soltner, 1990, Salisbury, Ross., 1995).

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The experiment was made at Agricultural Research and Development Station (A.R.D.S.) Oradea, Romania, on the preluvosoil, in the period 2019-2021.

On the ploughing depth, the soil is low acid (pH=6.8), humus content is low (1.75 %), phosphorus (22.0 ppm) and potassium (845.4 ppm) have medium values; macroagregates

hydrostability is high and bulk density (1.44 g/cm³) is high, too.

For species "Delia" winter wheat grains, a series of chemical tests were made regarding the content of N (nitrogen), P (phosphorus), K (potassium) and raw protein according to the precursory and the nutrition system. The nitrogen was determined using the Kjeldahl method, the phosphorus was determined by colorimetry with ammonium molybdate and tin chloride reduction. The potassium was determined through flame photometry and the raw protein was determined through calculation (Nt x 5.7 %).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Analysing the data in Table 1, regarding the influence of crop rotation and regime of nutrition level on the total N (nitrogen) content in the wheat seeds, we can see that both the crop rotation and regime of nutrition level influenced the content of this element in seeds. Therefore, comparing the wheat monoculture with wheat cultivation that was preceded by corn = maize or pea (3 and 4 years crop rotation) the latter induces an increased production of 22.4-53.8 %.

As an ameliorative plant, pea determined the increase of N (nitrogen) content in the crop as a consequence of its symbiotic particularities. Compared to the unfertilized type, with a value of 1.37 g/100 g.d.w. (grains of dry substance = wheat), mineral and organo-mineral fertilization determine important increase of N, i.e. 38.7 % and 62 %.

Table 1

The influence of crop rotation and regime of nutrition level of the content of *nitrogen* of the seeds in winter wheat cultivated on preluvosols, Oradea, 2019-2021

Investigated factors	Total N, g/100 g.d.w.	Nitrogen %	Difference +/-
a. Rotation			
Wheat – Monoculture (Control)	1.43	100	-
Maize (W-M)	1.75	122.4	+0.32
Pea (P-W-M)	2.20	153.8	+0.77
Pea (P-W-M-M)	1.95	136.4	+0.52
b. Regime of nutrition level			
N ₀ P ₀ (Control)	1.37	100	-
N ₁₂₀ P ₈₀	1.90	138.7	+0.53
N ₁₂₀ P ₈₀ +10 t/ha manure	2.27	162.0	+0.85
	LSD 5% = 0.66 g/100 g.d.w. LSD 1% = 1.25 g/100 g.d.w. LSD 0.1 % = 2.35 g/100 g.d.w.		

Note: Non-significant=under 0.66; * Significant =0.66-1.25; ** = Significantly different =1.25 – 2.35; ***very significant = over 2.35.

In point of the factors interaction: crop rotation x regime of nutrition level (Table 2), we note that no matter the forerunner plant used, mineral or organo-mineral fertilisation increase by 12.1-86.7 %. The lowest values of total nitrogen content can be found in the wheat

monoculture (1.24-1.65 g/100 g.d.w.) compared to short wheat – maize rotation (1.27-2.07 g/100 g.d.w) or to 3 and 4 year wheat – pea crop rotation – (1.70-2.78 g/100 g.d.w. and 1.28-2.39 g/100 g.d.w.).

Table 2

Influence of the factors interaction: crop rotation x regime of nutrition level on the content of nitrogen of the seeds in wheat cultivated on preluvosoils, Oradea, 2019-2022

Regime of nutrition level	To,tal Nitrogen g/100 g.d.w.	Nitrogen, %	Difference +/-
a. Wheat – Monoculture (Control)			
N ₀ P ₀ (Control)	1.24	100	-
N ₁₂₀ P ₈₀	1.39	12.1	+0.15
N ₁₂₀ P ₈₀ +10 t/ha manure	1.65	33.1	
b. Maize (W-M)			
N ₀ P ₀ (Control)	1,27	100	-
N ₁₂₀ P ₈₀	1.90	49.6	+0.63
N ₁₂₀ P ₈₀ +10 t/ha manure	2.07	63.0	+0.80
c. Pea (P-W-M)			
N ₀ P ₀ (Control)	1.70	100	-
N ₁₂₀ P ₈₀	2.13	25.3	+0.43
N ₁₂₀ P ₈₀ +10 t/ha manure	2.78	63.5	+1.08
d. Pea (P-W-M-M)			
N ₀ P ₀ (Control)	1.28	100	-
N ₁₂₀ P ₈₀	2.18	70.3	+0.90
N ₁₂₀ P ₈₀ +10 t/ha manure	2.39	86.7	+1.11
	LSD 5% = 0.66 g/100 g.d.w. LSD 1% = 1.25 g/100 g.d.w. LSD 0.1 % = 2.35 g/100 g.d.w.		

Note: Non-significant=under 0.66; * Significant =0.66-1.25; ** = Significantly different =1.25 – 2.35; ***very significant = over 2.35.

Concerning the total raw protein content (Nt x 5.7), in *Table 3 and 4*, we note the direct link between the N content and raw protein.

In this case, the crop rotation and the regime of nutrition level in the process induce important raw protein increase, which, in case of 3 year wheat-pea crop rotation may rise up to 12.58 g/100 g.d.w., compared to monoculture of 8.15 g/100 g.d.w. The highest

values of raw protein increase were established in the organo-mineral fertilisation process of 12.58g/100 g.d.w., compared to the witness/control (N₀P₀) 7.92 g/100 g.d.w. In the case of raw protein, no matter what the precursory was, the organo-mineral fertilisation determined the highest values of raw protein content which varied between 9.43 g/100 g.d.w., in wheat monoculture and 15.84 g/100 g.d.w., in pea (3 year crop rotation).

Table 3

The influence of crop rotation and regime of nutrition level on the content of raw protein of the seeds in wheat cultivated on preluvosoils, Oradea 2019– 2022

Investigated factors	Raw protein , g/100 g.d.w.	Raw protein, %	Difference +/-
a. Crop rotation			
Wheat – Monoculture (Control)	8.15	100	-
Maize (W-M)	9.96	118.5	+1.81
Pea (P-W-M)	12.58	154.3	+4.43
Pea (P-W-M-M)	11.23	137.8	+3.08
b. Regime of nutrition level			
N ₀ P ₀ (Control)	7.92	100	-
N ₁₂₀ P ₈₀	10.84	136.9	+2.92
N ₁₂₀ P ₈₀ +10 t/ha manure	12.68	160.1	+4.76
	LSD 5% = 0.66 g/100 g.d.w. LSD 1% = 2.25 g/100 g.d.w. LSD 0.1 % = 4.35 g/100 g.d.w.		

Note: Non-significant=under 0.66; * Significant =0.66-2.25; ** = Significantly different =2.55 – 4.35; ***very significant = over 4.35.

Table 4

Influence of the factors interaction: crop rotation x regime of nutrition level on the content of raw protein of the seeds in wheat cultivated on preluvosoils, Oradea 2019-2022

Investigated factors	Raw protein g/100 g.d.w.	Raw protein %	Difference +/-
a. Wheat – Monoculture (M _t)			
N ₀ P ₀ (Control)	7.07	100	-
N ₁₂₀ P ₈₀	7.95	112.4	+0.88
N ₁₂₀ P ₈₀ +10 t/ha manure	9.43	133.3	+2.36
b. Maize (W-M)			
N ₀ P ₀ (Control)	7.26	100	-
N ₁₂₀ P ₈₀	10.83	149.2	+3.57
N ₁₂₀ P ₈₀ +10 t/ha manure	11.79	162.4	+4.53
c. Pea (P-W-M)			
N ₀ P ₀ (Control)	9.72	100	-
N ₁₂₀ P ₈₀	12.17	125.2	+2,45
N ₁₂₀ P ₈₀ +10 t/ha manure	15.84	163.1	+6.12
d. Pea (P-W-M-M)			
N ₀ P ₀ (Control)	7.62	100	-
N ₁₂₀ P ₈₀	12.43	163.1	+4.81
N ₁₂₀ P ₈₀ +10 t/ha manure	13.65	179.1	+6.03
	LSD 5% = 0.66 g/100 g.d.w. LSD 1% = 2.25 g/100 g.d.w. LSD 0.1 % = 4.35 g/100 g.d.w.		

Note: Non-significant=under 0.66; * Significant =0.66-2.25; ** = Significantly different =2.55 – 4.35; ***very significant = over 4.35

Regarding the total content of phosphorus in the wheat seeds, in *Table 5* and *Table 6* we note that neither crop rotation, regime of nutrition level, nor their interaction led to significant differences, regardless of the quality of the crop rotation or organo-mineral fertilisation, except the pea (3 year crop rotation) when the mineral or organo-mineral

fertilisation determined more than 10 % increase of the total content of phosphorus.

Regarding the total content of potassium in the wheat seeds, in *Table 7 and 8* under the individual influence of both the observed factors and their interactions, we could notice significant difference.

Table 5

Influence of the crop rotation and regime of nutrition level on the content of phosphorus of seeds in wheat cultivated on preluvosoils, Oradea 2019-2022

Investigated factors	Total P, g/100 g.d.w.	Phosphorus %	Difference +/-
a. Crop rotation			
Wheat – Monoculture (Control)	0.36	100	-
Maize (W-M)	0.36	100	-
Pea (P-W-M)	0.40	111.0	+0.04
Pea (P-W-M-M)	0.36	100	-
b. Regime of nutrition level			
N ₀ P ₀ (Control)	0.36	100	-
N ₁₂₀ P ₈₀	0.37	102.8	+0.01
N ₁₂₀ P ₈₀ +10 t/ha manure	0.38	105.5	+0.02
	LSD 5% = 0.165 g/100 g d.w. LSD 1% = 0.219 g/100 g d.w. LSD 0.1 % = 0.281 g/100 g d.w.		

Note: Non-significant=under 0.165; * Significant =0.165-0.219; ** = Significantly different =0.219 – 0.281; ***very significant = over 0.281

Table 6

Influence of the factors interaction: crop rotation x regime of nutrition level on the content of P (*phosphorus*) of the seeds in wheat cultivated on preluvosols, Oradea 2019-2022

Investigated factors	Total P g/100 g.d.w.	Phosphorus %	Difference +/-
a. Wheat – Monoculture (M_t)			
N ₀ P ₀	0.36	100	-
N ₁₂₀ P ₈₀	0.37	102.8	+0.01
N ₁₂₀ P ₈₀ +10 t/ha manure	0.36	100	-
b. Maize (W-M)			
N ₀ P ₀	0.36	100	-
N ₁₂₀ P ₈₀	0.36	100	-
N ₁₂₀ P ₈₀ +10 t/ha manure	0.37	102.8	+0.01
c. Maize (P-W-M)			
N ₀ P ₀	0.36	100	-
N ₁₂₀ P ₈₀	0.40	111.1	+0.04
N ₁₂₀ P ₈₀ +10 t/ha manure	0.44	122.2	+0.01
d. Pea (P-W-M-M)			
N ₀ P ₀	0.35	100	-
N ₁₂₀ P ₈₀	0.36	102.8	+0.01
N ₁₂₀ P ₈₀ +10 t/ha manure	0.37	105.7	+0.02
	LSD 5% = 0.165 g/100 g d.w. LSD 1% = 0.219 g/100 g d.w. LSD 0.1 % = 0.281 g/100 g d.w.		

Note: Non-significant=under 0.165; * Significant =0.165-0.219; ** = Significantly different =0.219 – 0.281; ***very significant = over 0.281

Table 7

Influence of the crop rotation and regime of nutrition level on the content of K (*potassium*) of the seeds in wheat cultivated on preluvosols, Oradea 2019-2022

Investigated factors	Total K g/100 g.d.w.	Potassium %	Difference +/-
a. Crop rotation			
Wheat – Monoculture (M _t)	0.64	100	-
Maize (W-M)	0.67	104,7	+0.03
Maize (P-W-M)	0.64	100	-
Pea (P-W-M-M)	0.63	98,0	+0.01
b. Regime of nutrition level			
N ₀ P ₀	0.67	100	-
N ₁₂₀ P ₈₀	0.63	94.0	-0.04
N ₁₂₀ P ₈₀ +10 t/ha manure	0.63	94.0	-0.04
	LSD 5% = 0.165 g/10 plants s.u. LSD 1% = 0.219 g/10 plants s.u. LSD 0.1 % = 0.281 g/10 plants s.u.		

Note: Non-significant=under 0.165; * Significant =0.165-0.219; ** = Significantly different =0.219 – 0.281; ***very significant = over 0.281

Table 8

Influence of the factors interaction:crop rotation x regime of nutrition level on the content of K (*potassium*) of the seeds in wheat cultivated on preluvosols, Oradea 2019-2022

Investigated factors	Total K, g/100 g.d.w.	Potassium %	Difference +/-
a. Wheat – Monoculture (M_t)			
N ₀ P ₀	0.62	100	-
N ₁₂₀ P ₈₀	0.65	104.8	+0.03
N ₁₂₀ P ₈₀ +10 t/ha manure	0.65	104.8	+0.03
b. Maize (W-M)			
N ₀ P ₀	0.75	100	-
N ₁₂₀ P ₈₀	0.65	86.7	-0.10
N ₁₂₀ P ₈₀ +10 t/ha manure	0.65	80.0	-0.15
c. Maize (P-W-M)			
N ₀ P ₀	0.65	100	-
N ₁₂₀ P ₈₀	0.65	100	-
N ₁₂₀ P ₈₀ +10 t/ha manure	0.63	96.9	-0.02
d. Pea (P-W-M-M)			
N ₀ P ₀	0.66	100	-
N ₁₂₀ P ₈₀	0.64	97.0	-0.02
N ₁₂₀ P ₈₀ +10 t/ha manure	0.58	87.9	+0.08
	LSD 5% = 0.165 g/100 g d.w. LSD 1% = 0.219 g/100 g d.w. LSD 0.1 % = 0.281 g/100 g d.w.		

Note: Non-significant=under 0.165; * Significant =0.165-0.219; ** = Significantly different =0.219 – 0.281; ***very significant = over 0.281

CONCLUSIONS

A more intense accumulation of the phytomass which determines an intensification of the photosynthesis positively influences the chemical composition of the final product - the grains.

The total content of N in the winter wheat grains was influenced by the crop rotation and the nutrition level. The raw protein content follows the natural way similarly to nitrogen total content being influenced mainly by the crop rotation and the regime of nutrition level

There weren't observed any essential changes of the total P and K content under the influence of the crop rotation and the regime of nutrition level.

REFERENCES

- Ileana Ardelean, Ioana Maria Borza, Cristian Gabriel Domuța (2022), *Agrotechnics*. (Book) Primus Publishing House, Oradea, p. 390, ISBN 978-606-707-476-5.
- Bandici G.E., 1997, *Contributions to establishing the influence of the forerunner and fertilization on the dynamics of biomass accumulation, in autumn wheat, cultivated on soils with temporary excess of moisture, in the center of the Western Plain of Romania*. Doctoral thesis. University of Agriculture Sciences and Veterinary Medicine Cluj- Napoca, Romania [in Romanian].
- Bandici G.E., P. Gus, 2001, *Dynamics of biomass accumulation in autumn wheat*. University of Oradea Press, Oradea, pp. 55-61.
- Bandici G., E., C., Domuța, Ileana, Ardelean, 2003, *The influence of the forerunner plant, fertilisation level and climatic conditions on the total wet and dry gluten content of winter wheat seeds cultivated on brown luvisc soils in the Western Plain of Romania*, *Lucrări științifice USAMVB., Seria B*, vol. XLV, București p. 281-284, p.300.
- Bandici G., E., 2018, *Plant physiology* University of Oradea Publishing House, pp.483
- Bîlteanu G., 1993, *Phytotechny*, Ceres Publishing House, Bucharest, pp. 457.
- Boldea, Elena, 1986, *The bakery qualities of some varieties of wheat raionated and lines of perspective*, *Agricultural Problems*, Nb.7, p.27-32, p.50.
- Domuta Cornel coord., 2007, *Crops rotation in Crisurilor Plain*, *University of Oradea Publishing House.*, 255 pp.
- Domuta Cornel coord, 2008, *Crops rotation in Agriculture systems*, *University of Oradea Publishing House*, 297 pp.
- Domuta C., 2012, *Agrotechnics*. *University of Oradea Publishing House*,
- Hera, C., 1986a, *The influence of fertilization on qualitative indices of wheat crops*, *Theoretical and Applied Agrotechnology Problems*, Nb.2, vol.VIII, p.71-76, p.100.
- Hera, C., 1986b, *Influence of technological factors on wheat, Cereals and technical plants* Nb.7, p.47-52, p.88.
- Ionescu N, 1985, *The efficiency of the crop rotation and fertilization of wheat and maize on the acidic soils in the south of the country*. *Theoretical and applied agrotechnology problems*, nr. 2, vol. VII: pp.107.
- Lazany J., 2003, *Differences in soil carbon content in the treatments of Westik's crop rotation experiment*. *Natural resources and sustainable development*. International scientific session and reviewed papers. Oradea-Debrecen, pp. 119- 120.
- Muntean, L.S., S., Cernea, G., Morar, et al., 2008, *Phytotechny*, Academic Pres Publishing House, Cluj-Napoca, p.83-135, p.224.
- Salisbury F.B., C.W. Ross, - *Fisiologia vegetale*. Seconda edizione italiana condota sulla quarta edizione americana. Editura Zanichelli, 1995.
- Soltner D., 1990, *Phytotechnie speciale*, *Collection sciences et Techniques Agricoles*, Angers,
- Zahan P., R. Zahan, 1989a, *Research on the influence of the pre-planting plant and fertilization on the dynamics of accumulation of vegetable mass in wheat grown on podzolic soils with temporary excess of moisture in the Western Plain of the country (I)*. *Theoretical and applied agrotechnology problems* Nb. 1, vol. XI: 97-102.
- Zahan, P., R. Zahan, 1989b, *Research on the accumulation of root vegetable biomass and the quality of the harvest obtained, under the influence of the pre-walker plant and the fertilization of wheat grown on podzolic soils with temporary excess of moisture in the Western Plain of the country (II)*. *Theoretical and applied agrotechnology problems*, Nb. 1, vol. XI: 237-240.

RESEARCH ON THE OIL CONTENT PERCENTAGE OF SOME FLAX VARIETIES CULTIVATED IN THE WESTERN PLAIN OF ROMANIA

Raluca CHILBA^{1#}, Nicu Cornel SABĂU², Ciprian CHILBA¹, Ioana BORZA², Radu BREJEA²

¹ National Institute for Variety Testing and Registration, Bucharest 61 Marasti Blvd. Romania, Inand Variety Testing Center, Inand no. 304, Bihor County.

² University of Oradea, Faculty of Environmental Protection, 26 General Magheru St., 410048 Oradea, Romania

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

This study analyses the oil content of some varieties of flax for oil grown in regions of the Western Plain of Romania. We studied 3 varieties of flax for oil in 3 regions of the Western Plain of Romania, Inand, Bihor County, Arad, Arad County, Peciu Nou, Timișoara County: Lirina, Paltin and Simbol.

Keywords: oil content, flax varieties

#Corresponding author: inand@istis.ro

INTRODUCTION

Flax for oil is considered an important oleaginous plant because almost every part of the plant is used (stems, seeds, the oil extracted from them and the secondary products obtained) having a commercial, food, therapeutic, industrial, fodder, agronomic, pre-processing use (SINHG et al 2011). From flax, for food, dietary or therapeutic purposes, the fully mature seeds (Semen lini) are used, as such or in the form of flour (Farina lini), the oil extracted from them (Oleum lini) or flat cakes (Placenta lini) (Bâlțeanu, 2001), the recommendation of doctors and dieticians for all categories of consumers is to use it in the form of oil or powder (flour).

Flax seeds are rich in oil and protein. The seeds of flax varieties for fibre contain 30-36% oil and flax varieties for oil up to 44%, after pressing it results in 60-70 kg flat cakes rich in protein, carbohydrates and fats, which constitute a high-quality concentrated fodder in animal nutrition.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

In 2020, we studied 3 varieties of flax for oil in 3 regions of the Western Plain of Romania, Inand, Bihor County, Arad, Arad County, Peciu Nou, Timișoara County: Lirina, Paltin and Simbol. We sowed an experiment in

3 repetitions, the surface of the experimental plot being 10 m² harvestable, at a distance of 12.5 cm between rows, at a density of 1000 germinable grains per m² to determine the oil content percentage of the flax varieties.

The types of soil on which the experiments were carried out are: Inand - soft clay illuvial soil, Arad - leached chernozem soil and Peciu Nou cambic chernozem soil.

To prepare the land, a ploughing of 30 cm was carried out in the autumn of the previous year, and in the spring, we carried out a harrow pass with discs at a depth of 8-10 cm. In order to have the quality of the germinal bed before sowing, we carried out a work with the combiner.

Sowing was done at a depth of 2-3 cm with the Wintersteiger TC 2700 seed drill.

Fertilization was carried out with complex fertilizers 20.20.20, 250 kg/ha in the dose of 50.50.50. active substance, ammonium nitrate 150 kg/ha in a dose of 50.0.0 active substance and a foliar fertilization with cropmax 0.5l/ha was carried out in the vegetation.

The maintenance of the crop was carried out with dual gold EC 1.5 l/ha

The harvest was done with a combine of experiences.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

After harvesting, samples of 2 kilograms of seeds from each flax variety were taken, which were cold-pressed and then the percentage of oil content was determined.

Table 1 shows the productions/hectare and the oil content recorded in Inand, Bihor County, thus, in the Lirina variety there was obtained a production of 2220 kg/ha and an oil

content of 41.2%, in the Paltin variety there was obtained a production of 1863 kg/ha and a percentage content of 42.4% with 1.2% higher than in the Lirina variety and in the Simbol variety there was a production of 2155 kg/ha with an oil content percentage of 42.7% with 1.5 % higher than Lirina and 0.3% higher than the Paltin variety.

Table 1

Productions and oil content recorded in Inand, Bihor County

No	Variety	Production/plot/ha (kg)			Productions average/ha in kg	Oil content in percentage
		R ₁	R ₂	R ₃		
1	LIRINA	2150	2240	2270	2220	41.2%
2	PALTIN	1810	1830	1950	1863	42.4%
3	SIMBOL	2100	2070	2175	2115	42.7%

Table 2 shows the productions/hectare and the oil content recorded in Arad, Arad county, on a leached chernozem soil type, thus the Lirina variety obtained a production of 2300 kg/ha and an oil content of 41.3%, in the Paltin variety was obtained a

production of 2016 kg/ha and an oil content of 42.6%, 1.3% higher than in the Lirina variety and in the Simbol variety a production of 2156 kg/ha and an oil content of 42,7% was obtained, 1.5% higher than the Lirina variety and 0.2% higher than the Paltin variety

Table 2

Table with productions and oil content recorded in Arad, county

No.	Variety	Production/plot/ha (kg)			Productions average/ha (kg)	Oil content in percentage
		R ₁	R ₂	R ₃		
1	LIRINA	2230	2320	2350	2300	41.3%
2	PALTIN	1980	2060	2010	2016	42.6%
3	SIMBOL	2160	2090	2220	2156	42.8%

Table 3 shows the productions/hectare and the oil content of the flax varieties for oil in Peciu Nou, Timisoara county on a cambic chernozem soil type, thus the Lirina variety obtained a production of 2306 kg/ha and an oil content of 41.5%, in the Paltin variety a production of 2055 was obtained with an oil

content of 42.7%, 1.2% higher than in the Lirina variety, and in the Simbol variety a production of 2223 kg/ha was obtained with an oil content of 42.9%, 1.4% higher than the Lirina variety and 0.2% higher than the Paltin variety.

Table 3

Productions and oil content recorded in Peciu Nou, Timișoara county

Crt No.	Variety	Production/plot/ha (kg)			Productions average/ha (kg)	Oil content in percentage
		R ₁	R ₂	R ₃		
1	LIRINA	2250	2310	2360	2306	41.5%
2	PALTIN	2030	2120	2200	2055	42.7%
3	SIMBOL	2270	2190	2210	2223	42.9%

Figure 1 shows the oil content of the flax varieties on the 3 soil types. The soil on which the highest percentage of oil was obtained is the cambic chernozem soil from Peciu Nou, Timișoara county. In this location, in the Simbol variety, the oil content was 0.1% higher than that obtained on the leached chernozem type soil from Arad and 0.2% higher than the content obtained on the clay illuvial soil from

Inand. In the Paltin variety, an oil content of 42.7% was obtained on cambic chernozem, 0.1% higher than on the leached chernozem soil type and 0.3% higher than on the clay illuvial soil from Inand. In the Lirina variety, the highest oil content was also obtained on the cambic chernozem soil, 41.5%, 0.2% higher than on the leached chernozem soil and 0.3% higher than on the clay illuvial soil.

Figure 1 The oil content of the flax varieties on the 3 types of soil

CONCLUSIONS

The variety with the highest percentage of oil content is the Simbol variety 42.9% on cambic chernozem type soil and the variety with the lowest oil content is the Lirina variety on clay illuvial soil. The type of soil on which the highest oil content was obtained in all 3 varieties is the cambic chernozem type soil, thus in the variety Lirina 42.7%, Paltin 42.8% and Simbol 42.9%.

The clay-alluvial soil type from Inand is the one where the lowest oil percentage contents were obtained: Lirina 41.2%, Paltin 42.4% and Simbol 42.7%.

REFERENCES

- Bogdan I., Guş P., Rusu T., 2003. Differentiated agrotechnics. Risoprint Publishing House, Cluj-Napoca
- Borza I.M., A,Ş Stanciu 2010. Phytotechnics, University of Oradea Publishing House
- Brejea R., 2010. Soil science – guide of practical works, University of Oradea Publishing House
- Brejea R., 2011. Practicum of paedology, University of Oradea Publishing House
- Ciobanu Gh., Domuţa C., 2003. Agricultural research in Crişana. University of Oradea Publishing House
- Constantinescu M., Sinulescu G., Plant crop for oil, M.A.S.T.Publishing House
- David Gh., Pârşan P., Imbrea F., 2006. Technology of field plants, Cereals, legumes for grains and technical plants, EUROBIT Publishing House, Timişoara.
- Domuţa C., 2006. Differentiated agrotechnics. University of Orade Publishing House
- Domuţa C., Sabău N.C., 2001. Agrotechnics part I, part II, Publisher. University of Oradea Publishing House
- Doucet I., Doucet M., 2007. Genetics and plant breeding, Results of breeding research on oil flax and fibre flax, in Romania, Annals I.N.C.D.A, Fundulea, vol.
- Gradila M. 1998. The crop of technical and medicinal plants, M.A.S.T. Publishing House.
- Roman G. V., Duda M. Marcel, Imbrea F., Matei Gh., Timar A.V., 2012. Conditioning and preservation of agricultural products, Bucharest University Publishing House.
- Suciu Zaharia, Berar Viorel, Lăcătuşu Nichit 1988 – Experimental technique guide
- State Institute for the Testing and Registration of Varieties Bucharest 2008- Methodology of examining the agronomic value and use.

SOME ASPECTS OF DECARBONISATION AND MACHINES IN AGRICULTURE

Gheorghe DONCA

University of Oradea, Faculty of Environmental Protection, 26 General Magheru St., 410048 Oradea, Romania

REVIEW ARTICLE

Abstract

Sustainability and environmental protection have become key concepts in EU agriculture mainly due to the regulations of the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP). As a key component of the Green Deal, in December 2021, the European Commission adopted a Communication on Sustainable Carbon Cycles (European Commission, 2021) in which it promotes the upscaling of carbon farming as a green business model and sets out a series of short to medium-term actions to address current challenges to achieve this. This paper presents some aspects related to decarbonisation and agricultural machinery.

Keywords: decarbonisation, sustainability, eco-schemes, agricultural machines

Corresponding author: gdonca@uoradea.ro

INTRODUCTION

The Department of Economic and Social Affairs, Population Division, of the United Nations, (United Nations, 2019) has predicted that the global population will reach 8.55 billion people by 2030 and almost 10 billion people by 2050. In order to feed this growing population, according to FAO, food production must increase with 70 percent by 2050 and a 60 percent increase in demand for high quality protein such as milk, meat and eggs.

Agriculture is energy intensive and the pressure to produce more food requires more energy, an increasingly costly input to the production process. At the same time, the requirements for the use of sustainable methods and environmental protection for energy products have increased.

The European Climate Law (European Parliament) requires that greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions and removals are balanced within the European Union at the latest by 2050 with the aim to achieve negative emissions thereafter.

The agriculture sector accounts for 10% of the total EU27 greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions (from crops, livestock and soils), and an additional ~1% of total EU27 GHG emissions can be attributed to agriculture from the combustion of fossil fuels during the normal course of operating agricultural machinery. At EU level, methane (CH₄) represents 56 % and nitrous oxide (N₂O) 39 % of greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions in agricultural production, while carbon dioxide (CO₂) represents a minor

proportion of GHG emissions.

One of the projects that studies the solutions needed to achieve sustainable energy without pollution is RES4LIVE (<https://res4live.eu/>). This H2020 EU funded project, 2020-2024, with an overall budget € 5815206, have 17 partners from 8 countries. The strategic objective of RES4LIVE is to develop and bring into the market integrated, cost-effective and case-sensitive RES (Renewable Energy Systems) solutions towards achieving fossil-free livestock farming.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The agricultural machinery industry was the first one to introduce the international sustainability standard ISO 17989 (Tractors and machinery for agriculture and forestry - Sustainability - Part 1: Principles). This industry initiated various developments with the intention to increase the eco-friendliness of machines and production. Examples are machine connectivity with ISOBUS, precision farming, alternative fuel technology, automated machinery operation, and International and European standards for the protection of the environment during the use of sprayers and fertilizer application equipment.

Agricultural machinery have very long life cycles. Agricultural mechanization can contribute in the short term to the EU climate targets as alternative fuels burned in combustion engines may be used as well in the existing fleet, depending on the fuel, the engine type/stage and engine conformity requirements. Also, they can

be mixed in various portions with conventional diesel. Hydrogen could be used directly in combustion engines (30 % efficiency compared to 35 % H₂ - fuel cell) providing a zero-emissions option for specific use cases, while supporting the growth of hydrogen infrastructure. On-farm produced alternative fuels (i.e. bio-methane, plant oil or H₂) would be the best solution from an economic point of view. A 2020 JEC study (European Commission Joint Research Centre, 2020) concluded that overall for the alternative fuels they investigated, almost all offer a better Well-To-Wheel performance than conventional diesel when used in Internal Combustion

Engines.

EKoTech project (Götz, 2019) stands for efficient agricultural machinery fuel utilisation. In this large-scale research project funded by the German Federal Ministry of Agriculture, a highly qualified consortium of industry, scientific and association experts has succeeded in providing cross-manufacturer evidence that innovative machinery, intelligent process control and modern operating concepts can achieve considerably reduced yield-related fuel consumption in comparison with conventional processes.

Figure 1 Reaching CO₂ neutrality while keeping a proper balance results in an industry vision oriented toward optimisation of process and operations, possibly combined with usage of alternative energy sources

For reaching the target of CO₂ neutrality, all aspects must be dealt comprehensively as presented in Figure 1 (CEMA, 2022). The outcome should be the optimisation of agricultural processes, which will preserve the balance between the necessary environment protection and agricultural production notwithstanding social responsibility.

Achieving sustainability in agriculture requires achieving carbon neutrality. Besides the reduction of fossil fuel consumption and the use of renewable energy, an important step would be the introduction of carbon farming. A good example is Carbon Action (<https://carbonaction.org/en/carbon-action/>) which is a Finnish platform that develops and researches ways of accelerating soil carbon sequestration and how to verify the results scientifically. It also introduces climate-friendly, regenerative farming practices to Finnish farms.

At the EU level, there is a lot of concern related to carbon farming, probably due to the global advance in this field. Themes like “Carbon farming” (European Parliament, Policy Department for Economic, Scientific and Quality

of Life Policies, 2021) and “Agricultural potential in carbon sequestration” (European Parliament, Policy Department for Structural and Cohesion Policies Directorate - General for Internal Policies, 2022) are on the European Parliament table.

The main factors that limit carbon farming are:

- farmers’ knowledge of the carbon farming and soil health,
- measurability and verifiability of carbon sequestration,
- profitability and incentives of carbon farming.

Farmers’ knowledge of the carbon farming and soil health can be deepened with advisory and education, trials and pilots on farms level.

Measurability and verifiability of carbon sequestration can be improved by including farmers in scientific research carried out on their farms.

Profitability of carbon farming can be achieved at the current stage, only through support based on subsidies from CAP eco-schemes. In the future, it is likely that the

regulation of carbon certificates produced in agriculture will constitute the main engine of development.

The set of relationships related to carbon farming are presented in Figure 2 (Joona, 2021).

Figure 2 Relationships related for carbon farming

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

In order for everyone to understand the processes related to carbon farming, several suggestive posters were made, such as the one in

Figure 3 (Coopman, 2021).

For the study of carbon farming processes, many projects were financed, such as FiON (Nevalainen et al, 2022).

Figure 3 Illustration of carbon farming models

CONCLUSIONS

All civilized countries have understood that sustainable development is impossible without strong environmental protection, especially in agriculture.

The governing bodies of the EU have

started and will continue with taking decisions to implement several environmental protection measures in agriculture.

In addition to using renewable energies and supporting biodiversity, technologies related to carbon farming will have an important

role.

Private companies also understood the role of carbon farming, for example, BASF Agricultural Solutions launch Global Carbon Farming Program enabling farmers to reduce their CO₂ emissions.

REFERENCES

- CEMA, 2022, The role of agricultural machinery in decarbonising agriculture, https://www.cema-agri.org/images/publications/position-papers/CEMA_decarbonising_agriculture_27-04-22.pdf. Accessed on 16.10.2022
- Coopman F., 2021, Carbon Farming, https://ec.europa.eu/eip/agriculture/sites/default/files/20210325_eip-agri-ws_carbonneutral_franky_coopman.pdf. Accessed on 16.10.2022
- COWI, Ecologic Institute and IEEP, 2021, Technical Guidance Handbook - setting up and implementing result-based carbon farming mechanisms in the EU, Report to the European Commission, DG Climate Action, under Contract No. CLIMA/C.3/ETU/2018/007. COWI, Kongens Lyngby. <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/10acfd66-a740-11eb-9585-01aa75ed71a1/language-en>. Accessed on 16.10.2022
- Council of the European Union, 2022, Council conclusions on the Commission communication on sustainable carbon cycles in the agricultural and forestry sectors, Brussels, <https://data.consilium.europa.eu/doc/document/ST-7728-2022-INIT/en/pdf>. Accessed on 16.10.2022
- EIP-AGRI, 2021, Towards carbon neutral agriculture, Workshop Report, 24-25 March 2021, https://ec.europa.eu/eip/agriculture/sites/default/files/eip-agri_ws_carbon_neutral_agriculture_final_report_2021_en_lr.pdf. Accessed on 16.10.2022
- European Commission, 2019, The European Green Deal, https://ec.europa.eu/info/strategy/priorities-2019-2024/european-green-deal_en. Accessed on 16.10.2022
- European Commission, 2021, Sustainable Carbon Cycles, Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament and the Council, Brussels. Accessed on 16.10.2022
- European Commission Joint Research Centre (JRC), EUCAR and Concawe, 2020, Well-To-Wheels report v5 - Well-to-Wheels analysis of future automotive fuels and powertrains in the European context, <https://publications.jrc.ec.europa.eu/repository/handle/JRC121213>. Accessed on 16.10.2022
- European Environment Agency, 2021, Greenhouse gas emissions from agriculture in Europe, <https://www.eea.europa.eu/ims/greenhouse-gas-emissions-from-agriculture>. Accessed on 16.10.2022
- European Parliament, 2021, Regulation (EU) 2021/1119 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 30 June 2021 establishing the framework for achieving climate neutrality and amending Regulations (EC) No 401/2009 and (EU) 2018/1999 ('European Climate Law'), <http://data.europa.eu/eli/reg/2021/1119/oj>. Accessed on 16.10.2022
- European Parliament, Policy Department for Economic, Scientific and Quality of Life Policies, 2021, Carbon farming - Making agriculture fit for 2030, [https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/STUD/2021/695482/IPOL_STU\(2021\)695482_EN.pdf](https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/STUD/2021/695482/IPOL_STU(2021)695482_EN.pdf). Accessed on 16.10.2022
- European Parliament, Policy Department for Structural and Cohesion Policies Directorate-General for Internal Policies, 2022, Agricultural potential in carbon sequestration, [https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/STUD/2022/699655/IPOL_STU\(2022\)699655_EN.pdf](https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/STUD/2022/699655/IPOL_STU(2022)699655_EN.pdf). Accessed on 16.10.2022
- FAO, IFAD, UNICEF, WFP and WHO, 2018, The State of Food Security and Nutrition in the World 2018. Building climate resilience for food security and nutrition, Rome. Accessed on 16.10.2022
- FAO, IFAD, UNICEF, WFP and WHO. 2022, The State of Food Security and Nutrition in the World 2022. Repurposing food and agricultural policies to make healthy diets more affordable. Rome, FAO, <https://www.fao.org/3/cc0639en/online/cc0639en.html>. Accessed on 16.10.2022
- Fasihi M., Efimova O., Breyer C., 2019, Techno-economic assessment of CO₂ direct air capture plants, *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 224, pp. 957-980, <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0959652619307772>. Accessed on 16.10.2022
- Götz C., Köber-Fleck B., (VDMA Agricultural Machinery), 2019, More output, less CO₂ – Saving Fuel with Innovative Agricultural Machinery, https://cema-agri.org/images/publications/brochures/2019_EkoT ech_More_output_less_CO2.pdf. Accessed on 16.10.2022
- Heid B., Martens C., Orthofer A., 2021, How hydrogen combustion engines can contribute to zero emissions, <https://www.mckinsey.com/industries/automotive-and-assembly/our-insights/how-hydrogen-combustion-engines-can-contribute-to-zero-emissions>. Accessed on 16.10.2022
- IRENA, 2019, Renewable Energy Statistics 2019, <https://www.irena.org/publications/2019/Jul/Renewable-energy-statistics-2019>. Accessed 16.10.2022
- Joona J., 2021, Enabling carbon farming on the carbon action platform, https://ec.europa.eu/eip/agriculture/sites/default/files/20210325_eip-agri-ws_carbonneutral_juuso_joona.pdf. Accessed on 16.10.2022
- Nevalainen O., Niemitalo O., Fer I., Juntunen A., Mattila T., Koskela O., Kukkamäki J., Höckerstedt L., Mäkelä L., Jarva P., Heimsch L., Vekuri H., Kulmala L., Stam Å., Kuusela O., Gerin S., Viskari T., Vira J., Hyväluoma J., Tuovinen J-P., Lohila A., Laurila T., Heinonsalo J., Aalto T., Kuntu I., and Liski J., 2022, Towards agricultural soil carbon monitoring, reporting, and verification through the Field Observatory Network (FION), *Geosci. Instrum. Method. Data Syst.*, 11, 93–109, <https://doi.org/10.5194/gi-11-93-2022>. Accessed on 16.10.2022
- United Nations, Department of Economic and Social Affairs, Population Division, 2022, World Population Prospects 2022, Summary of Results, https://www.un.org/development/desa/pd/sites/www.un.org.development.desa.pd/files/wpp2022_summary_of_results.pdf. Accessed on 16.10.2022
- United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP) and UNEP DTU Partnership, 2021, Emissions Gap Report 2021: The Heat Is On – A World of Climate Promises Not Yet Delivered, ISBN: 978-92-807-3890-2, <https://wedocs.unep.org/handle/20.500.11822/36990>. Accessed on 16.10.2022.

BLACK SCURF (*RHIZOCTONIA SOLANI*) INFLUENCE ON POTATO YIELD USING DIFFERENT AGRICULTURAL PRACTICES

Manuela HERMEZIU ¹

¹National Institute of Research and Development for Potato and Sugar Beet Brasov, 2 Fundaturii, Brasov, Romania, e-mail: hermezium@gmail.com

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

Black scurf and stem canker on potato caused by *Rhizoctonia solani* Kuhn is a seed and soil born disease of potato with high level of survival. Managing it is a difficult task. Field experiments (using crop rotation and monoculture) were conducted with various fungicides along with treated and untreated checks at NIRDPSB Brasov, Romania.. Two different varieties, Brasovia and Cezarina, were planted in 19, respectively 25 April 2018.

Field experiments conducted to evaluate the efficacy of various fungicides showed that Sercadis (300 g/l fluxapiraxad), Serenade (1015.1 g/l *Bacillus subtilis* strain QST 713), Prestige Extra 370 FS (pencicuron 250 g/l + imidacloprid 120 g/l), Amistar (250 g/l azoxistrobin) and Ortiva (200 g/l azoxistrobin + 125 g/l difenoconazol) provide control of the disease.

The tubers were harvested 9 September, graded and placed into storage at 4-10°C.

Total yield with different black scurf degree of attack was between 12.48 t/ha to the untreated variant and 20.32 t/ha to Prestige variant on monoculture field and between 12.00 t/ha to the untreated variant and 12.38 t/ha to Serenade 8.0 l/ha variant.

On 25 October, 100 tubers from the 35-55 mm and >55 mm size category were selected and assessed for presence of sclerotia.

High prevalence of black scurf is due to the favorable climatic condition for the inoculum, monocropping and poor cultural practices. Low soil temperature and high moisture level was the major factors favoring the development of disease in the monoculture.

The results confirm that black scurf reduces progeny tuber quality and marketable yields.

Keywords: potato, black scurf (*Rhizoctonia solani*), fungicides, control, production

#Corresponding author: hermezium@gmail.com

INTRODUCTION

Black scurf and stem canker on potato caused by *Rhizoctonia solani* Kuhn (teleomorph: *Thanatephorus cucumeris* Frank Donk) is one of the most common and oldest diseases of potato affecting stem, stolons and tubers. Is a serious and commonly observed disease with the characteristic symptoms of black scurf (dark brown to black colored hard masses of sclerotia, irregularly shaped and superficial, varying from small, flat, barely detectable blotches to large and raised lumps adhering tightly to the skin) on tubers and stem canker (Tsrer, 2010). The two main pathosystems, stem canker and black scurf are clearly separated in term of symptomatology. Stem canker results in quantitative losses by sprout, stolon and root infection, mainly early in the season, affecting tuber size and number, whereas black scurf develops during plant senescence and is associated with the formation of sclerotia on progeny tubers and their malformation (Das et

al, 2014). *Rhizoctonia* potato disease accounts for significant marketable yield losses of up to 30% (Carling et al., 1989, Kanetis et al., 2016).

After the plants emerge, the frequency and intensity of the attack decrease. Sometimes a white-gray collar appears at the base of the stems, made up of the mycelial hyphae of the perfect stage *Thanatephorus cucumeris* (Frank) Donk. on which basidiospores are formed. At this stage the fungus is saprophytic (Plămădeală, 1987).

Black scurf disease increases gradually as level of inoculum increases and sclerotia may develop on tuber surface even under primary low inoculum level, resultantly the control through fungicidal chemistries is not always useful especially when levels of initial inoculum are high (Kyritsis & Wale, 2002).

Currently, the disease is managed by cultural practices, such as crop rotation with grains, and methods that minimize prolonged contact of the plant or tubers with the pathogen, such as planting in warmer, drier conditions to promote rapid sprout emergence and promptly removing

tubers from the field (Secor and Gudmestad, 1999).

The incidence and severity of the disease are substantially reduced in the case of rotations application as against planting potato in monoculture. The previous crop of colza, barley or sweet corn substantially reduces the level of rhizoctoniosis and also ensures a high quality of potato production (Larkin and Honeycutt, 2006).

Chemical fungicides are often used when losses from *R. solani* are great (Parry, 1990). However, current cultural and chemical controls are not completely effective and black scurf disease remains a persistent problem. Management through fungicidal chemistries is only effective when the levels of initial inoculum were not high as the quantity of *Rhizoctonia solani* on tubers increases, the effectiveness of fungicides decreases (Tsrer and Peretz, 2005).

Sprouts from seed tubers are attacked before emergence resulting in the subsequent killing of sprout tips, a symptom called 'nipping off'. Sprout 'nipping off' affects plant emergence and results in production of weak plants with few stems of uneven height and thickness (El Bakali and Martin, 2006).

Before being planted, seed potatoes are commonly treated with fungicides either by dusting, spraying or dipping in fungicide solutions (Welsh, 1996). Fungicides can also be applied in-furrow at the time of planting (Wicks et al., 1995). Seed tuber and in-furrow treatments can each be used alone, but enhanced disease control can be obtained when both types of treatments are applied (Atkinson et al., 2011).

MATERIAL AND METHOD

Two field experiment were conducted in 2018 to the NIRDPSB Brasov on a cambic chernoseum soil. The study included a trial in monoculture (potato after potato) and a trial in rotation (potato after wheat). Two different varieties were planted in April, 19, Brasovia variety (with yellow skin) and in April, 25, Cezarina variety (with red skin). Trials were carried out in 4 replicates plots in a randomized complete block, 4 rows each with 29 plants (75 cm between rows and 30 cm between plants on row).

Five fungicides (Ortiva - 1 l/ha, Sercadis - 0,3 l/ha, Amistar -3 l/ha, Serenade in three different doses - 8 l/ha, 5 l/ha and 2,5 l/ha and Prestige - 0,5 l/ha) were applied in furrow at the planting time.

Two weeks after plantation the first symptoms of the disease were observed, first of all the delayed in plants growth.

The tubers from two central rows of each four row plot were lifted in September 18 and the samples were separated into three categories (<35 mm, 35-55 and >55 mm). After, 100 tubers are placed into storage at 4-10°C. On October 24, 2018, the tubers from the 35-55 mm size category Brasovia variety and tubers >55 mm size category Cezarina variety were selected from each plot and assessed for presence of sclerotia. Both size of the tubers were examined and the disease level was estimated using the below scale (Table 1).

Table 1

Scale for sclerotia assessment

Disease level	Percentage Coverage
Trace	0% - 1%
Light	>1% - 5%
Moderate	>5% - 10%
Severe	>10%

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

During the vegetation period (April - August) the air temperature was higher by 2.7 °C, compared to the MAA. Between April 1st and

August 31st, the total rainfall exceeded the MAA value by 16.6 mm, noting that the distribution of rainfall was very uneven.

Table 2

Air temperature and rainfalls during the experiment

Year	Month					Average
	May	June	July	August	September	
	Air temperature (°C)					
2018	16.3	18.1	18.8	20.2	14.7	17.6
MMA	13.6	16.5	18.1	17.5	13.6	15.9
	Amount of rainfall (mm)					
2018	34.8	204.8	133.6	46.6	43.4	463.2
MMA	82.0	96.7	99.8	76.4	52.5	407.4

Since the month of May with 34.8 mm (42.4% compared to the MAA), the start up of potato crops was difficult, also the vegetation started with difficulty. In June and July, the thermo-hydric conditions were favorable for potato crops. The water necessary for the development of plants and for potato production accumulation was provided even in the unirrigated regime, from the abundant precipitations of 204.8 mm realized in June (211.8% compared to MAA) and 133.6 mm in July (133.9% versus MAA). In August, the air temperature was 2.7°C higher than MAA and less precipitation (46.6 mm, only 61.0% compared to MAA) hastened the drying of the

foliage and the tubers maturation. Slightly higher temperatures by 1.1°C and lower precipitation (43.4 mm, 82.7% compared to MAA) in September allowed potato to be harvested in good conditions (Table 2).

Plants emergence was measured in the two central rows. When any visible green portion of the potato plant was seen was counted as emerged. The number of emerged plants was converted to a percentage based on the number of seed planted per plot and was established the density in thousands hills (Table 3).

Table 3

Plants emergence % and density to cv. Brasovia and cv. Cezarina

No.	Product	Brasovia		Cezarina	
		Emergence %	Thousands hills /ha	Emergence %	Thousands hills /ha
1	Untreated(control)	98,7a	45,8a	50,2 de	23,3 de
2	Sercadis	98,3a	45,6a	23,9f	11,1f
3	Ortiva	96,1a	44,6a	38,6ef	17,9ef
4	Serenade (8 l/ha)	99,1a	46,0a	61,0bcd	28,3bcd
5	Serenade (5 l/ha)	93,1a	43,2a	73,1b	33,9b
6	Serenade (2,5 l/ha)	97,8a	45,4a	67,2 bc	31,2bc
7	Prestige	96,1a	44,6a	53,2 cde	24,7 cde
8	Amistar	98,7a	45,8a	44,4 e	20,6e
	Mean	97,3	45,1	51,5°	23,9°
	LSD 5% (variant*loc)			15,0%	6,9

Differences among treatments for emergence were not observed to Brasovia variety, but to Cezarina variety the differences between variants was high. To the Sercadis variant, there were fewer plants that emergence from the control. Also to the Ortiva variant the number of emerge plants was low, the highest number of plant being to all variants where Serenade were applied.

To Brasovia variety the average number of stems were not significant different but between plants height there were difference,

the tallest been retested to Serenade product (8 l/ha and and 2,5 l/ha) and the smallest to Ortiva and Sercadis products. To Cezarina variety the plants height was uniform, no difference except Sercadis variant at which the plants were at half the height of the others. Regarding the stem number, the difference was higher, most stem being to Serenade – 8l/ha and the fewest to variant with Sercadis (Table 4).

Table 4

Plants height and average number of stems

No.	Product	Brasovia		Cezarina	
		Plant height (cm)	Stem no.	Plant height (cm)	Stem no.
1	Untreated (control)	29.1bc	6.3a	26.7a	2.9ab
2	Sercadis	28.7c	5.8a	11.8b	1.7c
3	Ortiva	28.2c	5.6a	25.3a	2.8ab
4	Serenade (8 l/ha)	30.9a	5.9a	28.2a	3.3a
5	Serenade (5 l/ha)	28.5c	5.8a	27.9a	3.0ab
6	Serenade (2,5 l/ha)	30.9a	5.8a	26.1a	3.0ab
7	Prestige	29.7abc	5.9a	26.2a	2.7ab
8	Amistar	30.4ab	5.9a	25.5a	2.4b
	Mean	29.6	5.9	26.3	2.9
	LSD 5% (variant*loc)	1.1	0.44	2.9	0.46

Table 5

Correlations of products value with potato stems

	Brasovia		Cezarina	
	IPL	NRV	IPL	NRV
IPL Pearson correlation Sig. (2-tailed)	1.000	.130**	1.000	.370**
NRVPearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed)	.130**	1.000	.370**	1.000
	.000		.000	

** correlation is significant at the 0.01 level

A significant positive correlation is observed in both varieties at the level of the number of stems, 0.130** in the Brasovia variety and 0.370** in the Cezarina variety (Table 5).

Tuber number with attack did not vary much in the Brasovia variety, attacked tubers being recorded in all variants. The lowest number of attacked tubes was recorded to Ortiva variant (5 tubers) compared to the control one (8 tubers). In the Cezarina variety, the lowest number of attacked tubers was in the Sercadis variant (5 tubers) compared to the control (9 tubers), while in the Serenade (5 l/ha) variant was recorded. the highest number of attacked tubers.

Figure 1. Brasovia (tub. 30-55mm)

Figure 2. Cezarina (tub.>55 mm)

The lowest reduction in yield is evident by treatment withand Serenade (8 l/ha) (Fig. 6). Treatment Serenade (2,5 l/ha) and Prestige were rated the second best in inhibiting yield reduction.

Figure 3. Brasovia variety

Figure 4. Cezarina variety

Figure 5. Brasovia variety

Figure 6. Cezarina variety

To the Brasov variety, the yield were around 12 tons in most variants. The weakest results were obtained in treatment with Ortiva and to the treatment with Prestige was observed the inability of the product to cope with other diseases during the vegetation period (especially with potato late blight attack) (Figure 5).

To the Cezarina variety the lowest reduction in yield is evident by treatment with Prestige. Treatment with Amistar was rated the second best in inhibiting yield reduction. The worst results were obtained in treatment with Secadis (Figure 6).

CONCLUSIONS

High prevalence of black scurf of potato is due to the favorable climatic condition for the inoculum, monocropping and poor cultural practices. Low soil temperature and high moisture level was the major factors favoring the development of disease in the second location. Potato crop cultivated without proper rotation tactics may lead to the encouragement of soil-borne diseases.

REFERENCES

- Atkinson, D., Thornton, M.K., Miller, J.S., 2011. Development of *Rhizoctonia solani* on stems, stolons and tubers of potato II. efficacy of chemical applications. *American Journal of Potato Research* 88, 96-103.
- Brewer, M.T. & Larkin, R.P., 2005. *Crop Protection*, 24, 939-950.
- Carling, D.E., Leiner, R.H., Westphale, P.C., 1989. Symptoms, signs and yield reduction associated with *Rhizoctonia* disease of potato induced by tuber born inoculum of *Rhizoctonia solani* AG3. *Am Potato J.* 66, 693-701.
- Das, S., Shah, F.A., Butler, R.E., Fallon, R.E., Stewart, A., Raikar, S., Pitman, A.R., 2014. Genetic variability and pathogenicity of *Rhizoctonia solani* associated with black scurf of potato in New Zealand. *Plant Pathol.* 63, 651-666.,
- El Bakali, A.M. & Martín, M.P., 2006. Black scurf of potato. *Mycologist* 20, 130-132.,
- Kyritsis, P. &Wale, S. J., 2002. Effect of mycelial inoculum level and cultivar susceptibility on *Rhizoctonia solani* development on potato stems and seed tubers. *The-BCPC Conference Pests and disease (volumes 1 and 2, 761-764)*. Proceedings of an international conference, Brighton UK, 18-21.
- Larkin, R.P. & Honeycutt, C.W., 2006. Effects of different 3-year cropping systems on soil microbial communities and *Rhizoctonia* diseases of potato. *Phytopathology* 96, 68-79.
- Owais, M., Chohan, S., Naqvi S., 2014. Occurrence of black scurf disease of potato in Multan (Punjab) aslong with its in vitro chemical and biotic elicitor mediated management. *Journal of Agricultural Science*; Vol. 6, No. 9, 134-143.
- Tsrar, L. & Peretz-Alon, I., 2005. The influence of the inoculum source of *Rhizoctonia solani* on development of black scurf on potato. *Journal of Phytopathology*, 153(4), 240-244. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1111/j.1439-0434.2005.00962.x>
- Parry, D.W., 1990. Diseases of potato. In: *Plant Pathology in Agriculture*. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, UK, 276-280.
- Plămădeală, B.,1987. *Protecția cartofului. Boli, dăunători, buruieni*. Ed. Ceres.

Secor, G.A. & Gudmestad, N.C., 1999. Managing fungal diseases of potato. *Can. J. Plant Pathol.* 21, 213–221.

Welsh, R.D., 1996. Evaluation of fenpiclonil as a potato seed tuber treatment for the control of *Rhizoctonia solani* and *Helminthosporium*

solani. Proceedings of the Forty Ninth New Zealand Plant Protection Conference, 152-156.

Wicks, T.J., Morgan, B., Hall, B., 1995. Chemical and biological-control of *Rhizoctonia solani* on potato seed tubers. *Australian Journal of Experimental Agriculture* 35, 661-4.

PRELIMINARY LIST OF THE SPIDERS (ARACHNIDA) FROM NORTHWESTERN ROMANIA (TINCA AREA, BIHOR COUNTY)

Aurelian Leonardo ILIE^{1#}, Mariana MARINESCU²

¹"Nicolae Jiga" Highschool, Republicii Street, 36A, Tinca, Bihor, Romania

²Teacher Training Department, University of Oradea, Universitatii Street, 1, Oradea, Bihor, Romania

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

In this paper there were presented preliminary research on spiders (Arachnida) from northwestern Romania (Tinca area, Bihor county) during October 2020 – October 2022. There were recorded 59 species belonging to 18 families and 47 genera. Some phenological data unpublished in the scientific literature were obtained.

Keywords: spiders, Tinca, area, Bihor, county.

#Corresponding author

INTRODUCTION

Bihor county is located in Crişana region, in the north – western part of Romania. Tinca area is located in the south – western part of Bihor county, with a surface of 454 Km², at the confluence of the Miersigului Plain and the Holodului Depression. The average altitude is 110 m, the climate is temperate – continental moderate, the drainage is represented by Crişul Negru river. The vegetation belongs to the oak stage (Berindei and Pop, 1972). Tinca village includes: Tinca, Gurbediu, Râpa, Belfir and Girişu – Negru villages.

This paper is a synthesis of data regarding the spiders from Tinca area during October 2020 – October 2022, the results contributing to the completion of the information on spider diversity and distribution in the Romanian fauna. Data on the spider fauna in the Tinca area have not been published to date.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

During October 2020 – October 2022, there were identified the following species:

Class Arachnida

Order Araneae

Family Araneidae

Argiope bruennichi Scopoli, 1722

Araneus diadematus Clerck, 1757

Araneus circe Audouin, 1826

Araneus angulatus Clerck, 1757

Gibbaranea omoeda Thorell, 1879

Nuctenea umbratica Clerck, 1757

Zilla diodia Walckenaer, 1802

Larinioides ixobolus Thorell, 1873

Leviellus thorelli Ausserer, 1871

Family Phalangiidae

Opilio saxatilis Koch, 1839

Opilio parietinus De Geer, 1778

Family Liniphiidae

Tallusia vindobonensis Kulcznski, 1989

Microlinyphia pusilla Sundevall, 1830

Nerienne radiata Walckenaer, 1842

Nerienne clathrata Sundevall, 1830

Family Lycosidae

Lycosa singoriensis Laxmann, 1770

Trochosa terricola Thorell, 1856

Trochosa ruricola De Geer, 1778

Alopecosa pulverulenta Clerck, 1757

Pardosa agrestis Westring, 1861

Pardosa wagleri Hahn, 1822

Pardosa amentata Clerck, 1757

Pardosa monticola Clerck, 1757

Arctosa leopardus Sundevall, 1833

Hogna radiata Latreille, 1817

Family Philodromidae

Tibellus oblongus Walckenaer, 1802

Philodromus poecilus Thorell, 1872

Philodromus cespitum Walckenaer, 1802

Philodromus rufus Walckenaer, 1802

Thanatus vulgaris Thorell, 1870

Family Dictynidae

Dictyna civica Lucas, 1850

Dictyna uncinata Thorell, 1856
Brigittea latens Fabricius, 1775
Argyroneta aquatica Clerck, 1757
Family Theridiidae
Latrodectus mactans Fabricius, 1775
Parasteatoda tepidariorum Koch, 1841
Asagena phalerata Panzer, 1894
Enoplognatha thoracica Hahn, 1833
Steatoda albomaculata De Geer, 1778
Family Corinidae
Phrurolithus festivus Koch, 1835
Family Salticidae
Ballus chalybeius Walckenaer, 1802
Heliophanus cupreus Walckenaer, 1802
Phlegra fasciata Hahn, 1826
Pseudicius picaceus Simon, 1868
Family Anyphaenidae
Anyphaena accentuata Walckenaer, 1802
Family Amaurobiidae
Amaurobius ferox Walckenaer, 1830
Family Agelenidae
Tegenaria agrestis Walckenaer, 1802
Family Thomisidae
Misumena vatia Clerck, 1757
Synema globosum Fabricius, 1775
Xysticus bifasciatus Koch, 1837
Family Pholcidae
Pholcus phalangioides Fuesslin, 1775
Holocnemus pluchei Scopoli, 1763
Family Gnaphosidae
Drassodes lapidosus Walckenaer, 1802
Scotophaeus blackwalli Thorell, 1871
Family Miturgidae
Cheiracanthium mildei Koch, 1864
Zora spinimana Sundevall, 1833
Family Pisauridae
Pisaura mirabilis Clerck, 1757
Pisaura novicia Koch, 1878

Family Sparassidae

Micrommata virescens Clerck, 1757

There were identified 203 specimens, 59 species belonging to 18 families and 47 genera. The most represented families are Lycosidae – 10 species (16.94 %) and Araneidae – 9 species (15.25 %), followed by Theridiidae, Philodromidae – 5 species (8.47 %), Liniphiidae, Salticidae, Dictynidae – 4 species (6.77 %), Thomisidae – 3 species (5.08 %), Gnaphosidae, Pholcidae, Miturgidae, Pisauridae, Phalangidae – 2 species (3.38 %), Corinidae, Anyphaenidae, Amaurobiidae, Agelenidae and Sparassidae – 1 species (1.69 %).

In Romania, 973 species of spiders belonging to 34 families were reported (Weiss & Petrișor, 1999). The number of species identified in the Tinca area represents 6.06 % of the total species identified in Romania. From the point of view of species protection, no threatened species were identified. From the point of view of the phenology of the species, some changes were observed. Due to the positive temperatures, some even higher than normal for the period, recorded between December 2021 - February 2022, some species remained active in nature. Example: - *Leviellus thorelli* Ausserer, 1871 - one specimen, Tinca, December 20, 2021. According to araneae.nmbe.ch the activity period is August – September.

- *Pisaura novicia* Koch, 1878 - one specimen, Tinca, February 9, 2022. The activity period is April – October (araneae.nmbe.ch).
 - *Asagena phalerata* Panzer, 1894 - one specimen, Tinca, February 19, 2022. The activity period is May – October (araneae.nmbe.ch).

CONCLUSIONS

During October 2020 – October 2022, there were identified 59 species belonging to 18 families and 47 genera. Some phenological data unpublished in the scientific literature were obtained.

REFERENCES

- Fuhn I.E.; Niculescu – Burlacu Fl., (1971), *Fauna Republicii Socialiste România. Arachnida. Familia Lycosidae*, Romanian Academy Publishing House, Bucharest, 5(3), 256 p. (in Romanian)
- Fuhn I.E.; Gherasim F.V., (1995), *Fauna României. Arachnida. Familia Salticidae*, Romanian Academy Publishing House, Bucharest, 5(5), 300 p. (in Romanian)
- Ilie A.L.; Marinescu M., (2021), *New data about the invertebrates from Bihor county (Romania) during 2020. Human education today for tomorrow world* revue (editor Mariana Marinescu), Universul Academic Publishing House, Bucharest, No. 18, pp. 121 – 137.
- Ilie A.L.; Marinescu M., (2021), *New researches about the invertebrates from Tinca area, Bihor county, Romania, during 2021. Human education today for tomorrow world* revue (editor Mariana Marinescu), Universul Academic Publishing House, Bucharest, No. 18, pp. 138 – 155.
- Roberts M.J., (1995), *Spiders of Britain and Northern Europe*, Harper Collins Publishing House, London, 296 p.
- Weiss I; Petrișor A., (1999), *List of the spiders (Arachnida: Araneae) from Romania*, Travaux du Museum National d Histoire Naturelle Grigore Antipa, Bucharest, XLI, pp. 79 – 107.
- <http://research.amnh.org/entomology/spiders/catalog/index.html>
- www.araneae.nmbe.ch
- wiki.arages.de/index.php

Spiders from the Tinca area (photos by ILIE A. L.)

Araneus diadematus Clerck

Misumena vatia Clerck

Phlegra fasciata Hahn

Parasteatoda tepidariorum Koch

Hogna radiata ,Latr

THE ORGANIC FARMING PERSPECTIVES IN ROMANIA AND POLAND, AS A GLOBAL REGULATORY PHENOMENON OF EU POLICY

Gabriela A. POPOVICIU ^{1#}, Tomasz LACHOWSKI²

¹University of Oradea, Faculty of Environmental Protection, Romania

²Doctoral School of the University of Rzeszów, Poland

REVIEW ARTICLE

Abstract

A notable trend in recent regulations on the nature of the EU (EU) and its democratic legitimacy focuses, from our paper's subject, on the concept of ecological agriculture. In this sense, the EU has issued throughout its existence, a multitude of acts and norms, regulations, through which this field - ecological agriculture - can be practiced in the safest and cleanest conditions. From this perspective, the current paper proposes an overview of what organic means and the quality of organic from the point of view of farms classified as producing organic, bio products. Studying the European legislation on the matter, we came to the conclusion that doing ecological agriculture in the current times is perhaps the most important argument for life, its assurance and protection and human health. In the research carried out, we found that the EU cooperates with other countries through the United Nations (UN), Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) and other international bodies to promote global solutions to the problems of ecological agriculture. Global situations, such as climate change, depletion of the ozone layer, tropical forests, biodiversity, are elements that can intervene in the way organic agriculture can ensure, at a high level, the food and products that humanity needs so much, in the days ours, to be healthy. For this, based on the vast bibliography studied in the field, we will focus our research on the study of the latest European - but also national, Romanian and Polish regulations - in the matter of ecological agriculture.

Keywords: modern agriculture, European legislation, production progress, safety food products.

#Corresponding author: Popoviciu Gabriela A., gpopoviciu@uoradea.ro

INTRODUCTION

With regard to organic farming, the applicable legislation from 1 January 2022 is Regulation (EU) 2018/848 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 30 May 2018. This regulation includes the rules on organic production and labeling of organic products and repeals Regulation (EC) no. 834/2007 of the Council of 28 June 2007. This regulation provides for transitional periods for the implementation of certain new provisions for a limited period.

Considering the regulations of the EU Regulation mentioned above, we will say that organic production is considered a general management system of a farm, in which the production of healthy food must combine the best environmental practices and climate actions, a high level of biodiversity, the conservation of natural resources and the application of high animal welfare standards and high production standards in accordance with the demand of a growing number of consumers for products manufactured using

natural substances and processes (Regulation (EU) 2018/848, art.1). By this we must understand that organic production offers a specific market that responds to consumer demand for organic products but also that, on the other hand, it provides goods accessible to the public that contribute to environmental protection and animal welfare, as well as rural development (Regulation (EU) 2018/848, art.1).

Modern agriculture, especially in economically developed countries, has achieved enormous production progress thanks to the widespread use of chemical means aimed at maximum yield increase and the advancement of biotechnology (new, more efficient animal breeds or better-yielding plants) (Government Ordinance no. 10/2021). However, it has contributed too many negative effects that are being felt more and more. Agriculture should be one of those sectors that most clearly shapes and emphasizes the essence of sustainable development, because it is a sector on which all humanity depends directly and, at the same time, the natural environment indirectly (Directive 2011/92/EU). Agriculture is the most

important sector of the economy ensuring food security, alleviating the effects of poverty and preserving basic natural resources (Mancia et al, 2021). However, modern agriculture does not fulfill these basic assumptions and, moreover, is the source of further problems. Production progress in conventional agriculture causes a local surplus of food products, which leads to a decline in their prices and profitability of production (Regulation (EU) 2017/625). Today we are dealing with the largest food production in the entire history of man. It can meet the needs of a much larger number of the world's population than today. However, the surplus of food in most cases, due to the lack of communication and cooperation between countries, does not reach the needy. This leads to losses and a huge amount of food waste. It can therefore be said that agriculture is a sector on which we are completely dependent. Not only has our well-being depended on it, but also the survival of present and future generations. Acid rain, deforestation, car exhaust fumes and industrial pollution, soil degradation, depletion of the ozone layer, discharge of toxic sewage into rivers and oceans are just some of the problems affecting the environment in which we live. The dangers also arise from unsustainable, intensive and ill-considered agricultural production.

The intensive use of mineral fertilizers and pesticides remains an important tool in agricultural production to increase yields. The intensification of agriculture in the last few decades has led to harmful effects, such as: the appearance of nitrates in groundwater, contamination of food products, eutrophication of water reservoirs, changes in the lower layers of the atmosphere. As long as food is not considered in qualitative rather than purely quantitative terms, modern agriculture is unlikely to be sustainable (Staniak, 2014). The growing and increasingly poignant problem of the harmful effects of intensive farming contributed to the introduction of the concept of organic farming in 1981 at the Atlanta conference. It was there that organic production was recognized as the appropriate form of agriculture, conducive to sustainable development and the sustainable use of natural and environmental resources.

The largest number of farms (mostly family-run) in the EU is in Romania (about 3.5 million), but this does not seem to help us even when it comes to organic products, which are usually obtained on small plantations.

With only 2,9% ecological surface of the total agricultural surface, Romania ranks last in agricultural products with high added value. The European average is 8,5% of the area - and the performers are Switzerland (25%), Sweden and Estonia with 20%, Italy and the Czech Republic with 15%. Germany and France each have 7,7%, Poland have 3,5 % of the ecological surface of the total agricultural surface.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

In recent years, many incidents have contributed to a decline in consumer confidence in the quality of food products (Government Ordinance no. 10/2021). BSE (bovine spongiform encephalopathy), contamination of food products with dioxins, the foot-and-mouth disease epidemic, avian flu and pesticide residues in food - these are the main threats affecting the food sector. As a result, the society began to pay more and more attention to the quality and safety of purchased products, and to appreciate food produced using organic methods. Due to the fact that organic farming is more labor-intensive and time-consuming, requires a lot of dedication and enormous knowledge and skills, these products are more expensive than those from conventional production. Thus, the demand for organic food is effectively held back by its prices. At present, ecological products (Government Ordinance no. 10/2021) are still a luxury commodity, available only to selected social groups. Another reason limiting the development of organic farming is the availability of its products (Zegar, 2018). The number of places where such food can be purchased is still small. This is a problem not only for Poland and Romania, but also for other EU countries. Public opinion polls in England have shown that 60% of the population would choose organic food if it were more readily available and did not cost more than conventional food. At the same time, one of the House of Lords reports that health is the main factor why society is willing to pay a higher price for organic food (Staniak, 2014). The belief that organic food is healthier than that produced conventionally emerged on the basis of general public awareness. This knowledge is based primarily on the perception of "healthy food" as having higher nutritional values, containing more vitamins, with better taste, and free from pesticides and chemicals derived from chemical fertilizers. Many studies confirm these beliefs, indicating that organic vegetables they

contain no pesticide residues or contain only a small amount of them. In addition, it has been shown that vegetables and fruits from organic production contain more vitamin C and β -carotene. Moreover, numerous studies and conducted experiments show that organic food has higher taste and organoleptic values. The meta-analysis of data shows that organic crops contain on average 48% less cadmium and four times less pesticide residues. However, when it comes to nutritional value, there is still some debate among scientists dealing with this issue. Do organic products really have a higher nutritional value and do they really contain more macro- and micronutrients? Some authors show that vegetables grown organically do not differ or differ slightly in nutritional value from vegetables grown conventionally. In addition, some publications highlighted the risk of contamination of ecological crops with pathogenic microorganisms and toxic products of their life processes, derived from animal natural fertilizers commonly used in organic farming.

So far, many definitions of organic farming have been formulated. Each of them contains important elements that make up the whole issue. Zimny (2007) defines organic farming as a type of agriculture used in a non-degraded environment, favoring the preservation and enhancement of soil fertility, favoring plant and animal species resistant to diseases. This system is subject to the rhythm of natural processes; therefore it does not disturb the ecological balance or pollute the environment. The World Health Organization (WHO) and also the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO, 2021) on the other hand, characterizes organic farming "as a holistic management system that supports biodiversity, ecological cycles and soil fertility" (Reeve et al, 2016; Wesołowska et al, 2022; Smriti et al, 2022). This definition also takes into account the fact that regional conditions require the creation of local systems. In addition, WHO emphasizes that organic farming ensures that no agrochemical treatments are used in production, but cannot guarantee the complete absence of chemical residues due to global pollution of the environment. On the other hand, the legislation of EU defines organic farming as a system of sustainable management of plant and animal production within a farm, based on technologically unprocessed biological and mineral substances (Therond et al, 2017).

The basic rule is to reject agricultural, veterinary and food chemicals in the food production process. It is a sustainable, self-sufficient, ecologically, economically and socially sustainable system. By activating the natural production mechanisms on the farm, this system ensures sustainable soil fertility and animal health, as well as high quality of agricultural products (Therond et al, 2017; Luty et al, 2021). In addition, by excluding the production of industrially processed pesticides and fertilizers, as well as through sustainable animal husbandry, it does not cause soil, groundwater or air pollution, and additionally reduces the leaching of minerals from the soil and at the same time promotes the biodiversity of ecosystems. It is the most extensive and officially accepted definition of organic farming recognized in Europe. Organic farming is based on a few basic complexes. The most important of them is the production of high-quality food for human health. Another equally important goal of organic farming is environmental protection. In order for these goals to be realized, such a farm must be run in accordance with a few very important rules. The natural environment provides agriculture with all the necessary resources to produce high-quality food.

Activities within the organic farm are therefore aimed at maintaining and, if possible, increasing the natural value of these resources. It has been confirmed that organic farming improves landscape values (Popoviciu, 2019), contributes to the preservation and enhancement of biodiversity, as well as to the protection of wildlife. It prevents contamination of waters and soils, and also contributes to the improvement of their quality.

The ecological system of soil management and maintenance of soil health aims to increase its fertility and improve its condition by providing appropriate nutrients, improving the soil structure and efficient management of water resources. The most important measures used by organic farmers to maintain or improve the condition of the soil include:

*The use of multi-annual, varied crop rotation helps to reduce weed infestation and the occurrence of diseases and pests, helps to maintain soil fertility and ensures the supply of nutrients. Plants, such as clover, faba bean and lupine fix atmospheric nitrogen and enrich the soil with this element.

*The use of natural fertilizers, in addition to being a source of nutrients for

plants, helps to improve the structure of the soil and prevent erosion. In addition, organic fertilizers favor the biodiversity of soil microorganisms, which are responsible for the circulation of elements and the biodegradation processes of organic matter (Reeve et al, 2016).

*Prohibition of the use of synthetic mineral fertilizers and chemical plant protection products - the prohibition of any agricultural chemicals is primarily related to the quality of food products, but also allows avoiding long-term changes in the chemical composition of the soil.

*Sowing catch crops to cover the soil surface after harvesting - catch crops are not only the basis of animal feed, but also important from the point of view of soil protection, as it prevents soil erosion and leaching of nutrients.

In organic farming, water is treated not only as an indispensable element in the production process, but also as a necessary substrate for life on Earth, which must be protected and supported by rational management. One of the assumptions of organic farming is to preserve the natural resources of water, actively counteracting its run-off. Another is improving the soil structure and increasing its water capacity through the use of proper crop rotation and plant selection, as well as through the use of organic fertilizers. Proper soil cultivation is also of great importance (Reeve et al, 2016). Soil cultivated inappropriately has a lower capacity to accumulate water and also a low hold on to it, which may result in lowering the groundwater level. Mechanical tending treatments, by destroying the crust and too high concentration of soil particles on the surface of the field, regulate the water balance. In addition, the establishment and maintenance of mid-field trees, meadows and natural vegetation is very important as it prevents soil erosion and allows retaining rainwater. In addition, the ecological management system helps to maintain and even improve water quality by reducing the amount of agricultural chemicals used, which may enter lakes, rivers, streams and other water bodies and lead to its contamination.

Organically farmed lands have around 30% more biodiversity than conventionally farmed lands (Caprile et al, 2021).

The main source of gaseous emissions in agriculture is animal production (Smriti et al, 2022). The increasing amount of scientific data confirms that large-scale farms with intensive livestock production and Concentrated Animal

Feeding Operations (CAFO) contribute to the increased emission of chemical compounds to the atmosphere. The most troublesome of them are fragrances (e.g. organic acids) and greenhouse gases such as carbon dioxide (CO₂), methane (CH₄), nitrous oxide (N₂O), nitrogen oxides (NO_x), ammonia (NH₃), as well as reduced compounds sulfuric (H₂S). Moreover, intensive livestock production contributes to significant emissions of volatile organic compounds (Smriti et al, 2022). These are various compounds, e.g. (acids, alcohols, aldehydes, aromatic compounds, esters, etc.) responsible for unpleasant odors and negatively affecting the comfort, health and production efficiency of both animals and humans. In addition, the inappropriate use of mineral fertilizers significantly contributes to air pollution with various types of compounds. These compounds include, first of all, nitrogen oxides (NO, N₂O, NO₂), which have a much greater potential to cause the greenhouse effect than carbon dioxide.

The problem of air pollution is much less of organic farming. This is mainly due to the fact that organic farms do not use synthetic mineral fertilizers and livestock production is usually limited. It is connected with legal regulations defining the area of the enclosure for a specific number of animals. In organic farming there is no intensive livestock farming, which is the main source of gas emissions.

Organic agriculture in Romania is developing hard and more than half of the area of over 270.000 hectares, certified as such, is intended for crops to which no value is added through processing, such as cereals (33% of the organic area), in the higher exported. In Poland total area of organic farms was 509.000 hectares (Łączyński, 2021).

On the other hand, organic agriculture in Romania covers only 2,9% of Romania's agricultural area, the fifth smallest in the EU, after Malta (0,5%), Ireland (1,6%), Bulgaria (2,3%) and the United Kingdom (2,6% each), according to Eurostat data. For Poland the number of farms using organic agricultural production methods was around 18.600 and cover 3,5% agricultural total area (Łączyński, 2021). For Romania the number of organic farms in 2020 was around 10.000 (Willer et al, 2022).

The European Commission's target by 2030 is for the EU to use 25% of its agricultural land for organic farming.

In 2019, according to a SWOT analysis of MADR for the National Strategic Plan in the sector, from the total area of 395.576 ha cultivated in the ecological system, the largest share is held by cereals (32%), followed by:

- permanent pasture and hay crops 24%,
- industrial crops 19%,
- harvested green plants (forage) 8.46%,
- permanent crops (orchards, vines, fruit bushes) 4,85%,
- dry and proteinaceous legumes for the production of grains (including seeds and mixtures of cereals and legumes) 1,82%,
- fresh vegetables 0,17%,
- tuberous and root crops 0,13%.

Even a lot has been invested, post-crisis, in agriculture domain, in 2020 an investment differential is maintained in Romanian agriculture and investment in agriculture in Poland, for example, which represents for Romania an example of medium-term convergence.

I hope that by the end of this decade we will be above Poland.

The yield per hectare, for certain crops such as wheat, corn, sunflower, is above that in Poland even now, where the potential is very high.

Subsidies must be increased and agricultural areas consolidated because Romania is facing a high degree of fragmentation.

Agriculture has an important share in GDP, three times higher than the EU average and twice as high as in Poland.

CONCLUSIONS

There is no doubt that management in the ecological system has a positive effect on the environment and contributes to the improvement of the quality of soil, water and landscape. Moreover, the system promotes biodiversity and does not contribute to the emission of greenhouse gases and chemicals that pollute the air, which is often the case in intensive agricultural production. Undoubtedly, agricultural production consistent with the assumptions of organic production meets the basic goals of sustainable development, especially in the area of environmental governance. Even though the productivity is significantly lower compared to conventional production, organic products are of higher

quality, both in terms of nutritional value, taste and safety. Taking into account the overproduction of food and the enormous waste that is currently observed on the food market, it should be considered whether this is the right way to meet the objectives of sustainable development. Is it not better to replace the intensive and environmentally destructive conventional production and the huge amount of low-quality agricultural products with products produced with respect for the environment of higher quality.

Even, for example, Romania was positioned above the level of Poland in terms of production per hectare, in 2019 there was a difference of over two billion Euros between Romania and Poland in terms of investments in agriculture.

Romania provides 7% of the EU's wheat production, 24% of the corn production and a third of the sunflower production. It is basically about an increasingly intensive agriculture. And that's why the governors and the authorities in the field should pay more attention to effective investments even if short-term in agriculture; we also consider that both countries - through specific national programs - should encourage their own population to consume local products.

The set of measures required for this sector of agriculture must be different from the regulations in commercial relations.

The legislative framework in this area of marketing local products should be much simpler to apply. Or, what we see today, any solution that aims to over regulate market mechanisms only succeeds in leading to an upheaval, to a confused, ambiguous situation of commercial relations, with negative effects on the market.

The European directive to combat unfair commercial practices and the package for the consumer, which are to be transposed, will certainly represent an opportunity for the farmers of the two countries, but also for the local consumers of the products of these farmers.

REFERENCES

- Caprile A., McEldowney J., 2021. Development of organic production in the EU: 2021-2027 action plan. European Parliamentary Research Service [https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/BRIE/2021/696182/EPRS_BRI\(2021\)696182_EN.pdf](https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/BRIE/2021/696182/EPRS_BRI(2021)696182_EN.pdf)
- Directive 2011/92/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 13 December 2011 on the

- assessment of the effects of certain public and private projects on the environment (OJ L 26, 28.1.2012, p. 1).
- Government Ordinance no. 10 of August 30, 2021 for the amendment and completion of GEO 34/2000 on ecological agri-food products.
- Łaczyński A., 2021. Statistical analyses. Agriculture in 2020. Statistics Poland (Główny Urząd Statystyczny) Agriculture Department. 106-107. <https://stat.gov.pl/obszary-tematyczne/rolnictwo-lesnictwo/rolnictwo/rolnictwo-w-2020-roku,3,17.html>
- Luty Lidia, Musiał Kamila, Ziolo Monika, 2021. The Role of Selected Ecosystem Services in Different Farming Systems in Poland Regarding the Differentiation of Agricultural Land Structure; in MDPI volume Sustainability 2021, 13, 6673. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13126673>.
- Order of the Minister of Agriculture and Rural Development no. 312 of November 5, 2021 regarding the organization of the control and certification system, approval of control bodies and supervision of their activity in organic agriculture.
- Mancia Mircea Sebastian, Popoviciu Gabriela A., Herman Grigore-Vasile, Paina Liliana, 2021 - Elements of Food Security in Romania in the Current Geopolitical Context; in The 16th International Scientific Conference "DEFENSE RESOURCES MANAGEMENT IN THE 21st CENTURY", Braşov, October 28th-29th 2021, pp.150-154, ISSN: 2248 - 2245 (CD-ROM) ISSN: 2248 - 2385 (online), http://www.codrm.eu/conferences/2021/00_CoDRM_2021_Carte.pdf.
- Popoviciu G.A., 2019 – The influence of the Land use Change; in University of Oradea, Faculty of Construction, Cadastre and Architecture's Conference volume, „Modern Technologies for the 3rd Millenium”, 04-05.04.2019, Oradea, vol. 18, p. 369-372, ISBN: 978-88-7587-724-8, editat de Editografica S.R.L. Bologna, Italy, <https://cloud.uoradea.ro/index.php/s/ARDn5PeSxsoC6qD#pdfviewer>, https://docs.google.com/viewer?url=http%3A%2F%2Fwww.edlearning.it%2Fproceedings%2Fmoreinfo%2F20190405_index.pdf; https://apps-websiteofknowledge-com.am.e-information.ro/full_record.do?product=WOS&search_mode=SourceByDais&qid=8&SID=D5jki8TutPgiUfgszyA&page=1&doc=2.
- Regulation (EU) 2018/848 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 30 May 2018 on organic production and labeling of organic products and repealing Council Regulation (EC) No 834/2007.
- Regulation (EU) 2017/625 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 15 March 2017 on official controls and other official activities carried out to ensure the application of food and feed legislation, animal health and welfare rules, plant health and animal protection products plant.
- Reeve J.R., Hoagland L.A., Villalba J.J., Carr P.M., Atucha A., Cambardella C., Davis D.R., Delate K. (2016) Organic farming, soil health, and food quality: considering possible links. *Adv Agron* 137:319–367. DOI: [10.1016/bs.agron.2015.12.003](https://doi.org/10.1016/bs.agron.2015.12.003).
- Smriti Nautiyal, Chaman Lal, 2022. Product knowledge as a facilitator of organic purchase intention in emerging markets: Empirical evidence from India. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, vol. 372, 20.oct.2022, 133782, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2022.133782>.
- Staniak S., 2014. Characteristics of food produced in organic farming (in Polish). *Polish J. Agron.*, 19, 25-35.
- Therond O., Duru M., Roger-Estrade J., Richard G., 2017. A new analytical framework of farming system and agriculture model diversities. *A review. Agron. Sustain. Dev.*, 37(3), 1-24, DOI: [10.1007/s13593-017-0429-7](https://doi.org/10.1007/s13593-017-0429-7).
- Wesołowska Sylwia, Futa Barbara, Myszura Magdalena, Kobyłka Agata, 2022. Residual Effects of Different Cropping Systems on Physicochemical Properties and the Activity of Phosphatases of Soil; in MDPI volume Agriculture 2022, 12, 693. <https://doi.org/10.3390/agriculture12050693>.
- Willer H., Travnicek J., Meier C., Schlatter B., 2022. The World of Organic Agriculture Statistics and Emerging Trends 2022. Research Institute of Organic Agriculture FIBL. <https://www.fibl.org/fileadmin/documents/shop/1344-organic-world-2022.pdf>
- Zegar J.S., 2018. Agriculture and Rural Development (in Polish). *Wież i Rolnictwo*, 2(179), 31-48, <https://doi.org/10.53098/wir022018/02>.
- Zimny L., 2007. Definitions and divisions of farming systems (in Polish). *Acta Agroph.*, 10(2), 507-518. https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/100335/0/Free_trade_agreement_between_UK-Northern_Ireland_and_Liechtenstein_Iceland_and_Norway_volume_2.pdf, viewed at September 14th, 2022. [https://ec.europa.eu/transparency/documents-register/detail?ref=COM\(2020\)857&lang=en](https://ec.europa.eu/transparency/documents-register/detail?ref=COM(2020)857&lang=en), viewed at September 14th, 2022. https://electricScotland.com/independence/sip/EU-UK_Trade_and_Cooperation_Agreement_24.12.2020.pdf, viewed at September 14th, 2022. https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?toc=OJ%3AL%3A2021%3A149%3A&uri=uriserv%3AOJ.L_2021.149.01.0010.01_ENG, viewed at September 14th, 2022.

INCREASING BIOMASS IN LOLIUM PERENNE SPECIES ACORDING TO CLIMATIC CONDITIONS AND FERTILIZATION

Alina-Ștefania STANCIU^{1#}, Octavian BERCHEZ¹, Olimpia MINTAȘ¹,
Andra Nicoleta LAZĂR¹, Carmen IANCU¹, Ioana-Teodora STANCIU¹, Mihaela Lavinia
Cărbunar², Teodora Iuliana VIDICAN¹

¹ University of Oradea, Faculty of Environmental Protection, Gen.Magheru st., no.26, 410048, Oradea, Romania

² Student of the University of Oradea, Faculty of Environmental Protection, Gen.Magheru st., no.26, 410048, Oradea, Romania

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

An objective of great importance in achieving a rational fodder base is the continuous provision of green fodder, in sufficient quantities and of superior quality, throughout the vegetation period. The research carried out was oriented towards improving productivity and crude protein content, knowing that these present different values depending on the harvest phenophase, the moment of grazing and the mowing technique, or different technological factors. White clover mixed with grasses (Lolium perenne) forms the traditional mixture, which cooperates very well in terms of the sustainable use of nitrogen, many researchers confirm the strong connection between the two species (Trifolium pratense and Lolium perenne). Through the participation of white clover in the mixtures, it makes available to the perennial, partner grasses, symbiotically fixed nitrogen, so that at the production level of 5-10 t/ha SU, the amount of crude protein obtained in mixtures with white clover is between 710-850 kg/ha at N0 – N180 and only 305-906 kg/ha in the case of mixtures without clover, values that were also influenced by the weather. Regarding the green mass harvest for the simple mixture consisting of Trifolium repens with Lolium perenne, in 2018 green mass harvests between 42.70 t/ha for the non-fertilized version and 67.62 t/ha for the fertilized version were obtained with N180P80K50 (table 12.). The increase in yield obtained with the version with maximum fertilization is 6.35 t/ha of green mass.

Keywords: crude protein, perennial grasses, white clover, green fodder

#Corresponding author: as1stanciu@yahoo.com

INTRODUCTION

Animal husbandry can be considered the agricultural industry, which transforms primary agricultural products into foods with a particularly high biological value, essential in human nutrition; animal husbandry also has an essential economic role, contributing to the profitability of agriculture, and to the significant increase of its contribution to the achievement of the gross domestic product on the economy (Moga et al., 2005). Thus, the expansion of sown meadows is linked to the intensification of animal husbandry systems. Along with the improvement and specialization of animal breeds for meat or milk, the need to cultivate some plant species appeared, in order to ensure higher quality fodder. In general, in Western European countries, countries with a highly

developed animal husbandry sector, the area occupied by sown meadows is constantly increasing (Rotar, 2010, 2011). By establishing the sown meadows, a floristic composition established according to scientific criteria is achieved with an optimal balance between fabaceae and poaceae, and superior fodder is obtained from a qualitative point of view. It also restores the structure of the soil, capillarity and microbiological activity in the soil and improves the mineral nutrition of the plants, through the annual fixation of 100-150 kg/ha/year of nitrogen by the fabaceae in the mixture (Dragomir, 2005). The productivity and utilization coefficient of sown meadows, as a rule, are higher than natural meadows (Dragomir et al. 2004, Rotar and Vidican, 2005). From the data entered in Table 1, it follows that the net primary production of sown meadows is

three times higher than that of natural meadows, meadows that were initially cleared and sown.

The consumption coefficient of net primary production calculated at the trophic level of herbivores (sheep) was made according to the formula:

$$Ec = Cn / Pn^{-1}$$

in which:

Ec - consumption efficiency

Cn - consumption (c) at the level (n) of herbivores

Pn-1 - production at the lower trophic level (in our case at the level of primary producers, so PPN).

According to the data in Table 1., the production at the lower trophic level was 0.26 (ie 26%) relative to the entire PPN and 0.33 (33%) relative to the above-ground PPN in the case of the natural meadow. In the sown meadow, the corresponding values were 0.54 (54%) compared to PPN and 0.68 (68%) if the ratio is made to aboveground PPN. It is obvious that in the case of the sown meadow the coefficient of use, expressed in our example by the efficiency of the consumption made by the sheep, is much higher than in the case of the natural meadow.

I calculated the accumulation efficiency (Ea) according to the relationship:

$$Ea = Pn^{-1} - Cn$$

in which the meaning of the symbols Pn-1 and Cn is the same as in the relationship expressing consumption efficiency. The values for the accumulation efficiency were 80% of the PPN (ie 1895 kcal m² year⁻¹) in the natural meadow and 57% of the PPN (ie 3990 kcal m⁻² year⁻¹) in the sown meadow. If we proceed to convert the above figures into kg/ha SU, estimating the energy value of SU at 4400 kcal/kg, then we can note the particularly significant fact that in the case of the natural meadow made available to wild herbivores and decomposers, it remains, annually, a quantity of 4300 kg/ha SU, while in the case of the sown meadow made available to the same wild consumers and decomposers, a quantity more than double remains: 9068 kg/SU. This, in the case of the sown meadow, means a much greater biodiversity and a more intense microbial activity in the soil (Şuteu, 1997).

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The experiences were established in 2017 in an experimental field in Sălard commune.

From a climatic point of view, the area is characterized by a multiannual average temperature of 12.60C. In spring, as a result of the increase in solar radiation, the average air temperature rises, the multiannual average of this season being 11.5°C, i.e. 8.95°C higher than in winter. In summer, compared to the previous season, the temperature rises by 12.1°C, the average air temperature being 23.6°C (Table 2). The change in the degree of cloudiness and, in general, the weather conditions during the summer, determines, in a multiannual profile, important variations in the average temperature of this season. The multiannual precipitation average (2017-2021) is 582 mm with decreasing trends (Table 3).

Interpretation of analytical data - the texture is medium; the soil reaction is neutral at a depth of 0-48 cm and slightly alkaline at a depth of 78-100 cm; the nitrogen content is small at a depth of 0-25 cm and very low at a depth of 25-48 cm; the potassium content is low; sum of exchange bases: is small, degree of saturation in bases: indicates a eubasic soil (Table 4).

The experience is bifactorial, of the 3 x 3 type, placed according to the block method in subdivided plots comprising variants in 3 repetitions. The surface of a plot is 10 m².

The factors of the experience were the following: - factor D (the main factor) - the doses of chemical fertilizers with the following graduations:

d₁ - N₀P₀K₀

d₂ - N₈₀P₈₀K₅₀

d₃ - N₁₈₀P₈₀K₅₀

- factor C - culture with 3 gradations:

c₁ - *Lolium perenne* (Mara, 25kg)

c₂ - *Lolium perenne*50% + *Trifolium repens* 50%

c₃ - *Trifolium repens* (Miorița, 10kg)

During the growing season, a series of observations were made regarding the emergence, growth and development of the plants, the dates of the start of vegetation in the spring, the degree of weediness, the entry and exit from the winter, the persistence of some species sown in the vegetal carpet and their degree of dominance. The harvests were done at the plot level, in the first year at the full flowering of the legumes, and in the following years at the budding of the legumes and the sprouting of the grasses. The green mass harvest was transformed into SU and processed statistically according to the analysis of variance method.

The objectives of this research are the following: the influence of differentiated fertilization with nitrogen on the evolution of the vegetal carpet and the determination of the productive potential of the simple mixture of *Lolium perenne* and *Trifolium repens* and of monocultures in order to ensure an economic use.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

In the conditions of our country, it is necessary to establish sown meadows, by cultivating mixtures made up of perennial poaceae and fabaceae. These mixtures are artificially composed phytocenoses and are far from having a behavior similar to climax communities. According to their complexity, mixtures can be simple or complex. The most important advantage of using mixtures consists in reducing the doses of chemical fertilizers with nitrogen, in order to stimulate the symbiotic fixation of nitrogen by fabaceae and in this way to complete the nitrogen requirement of the mixture. The productivity and profitability of mixtures of perennial poaceae and fabaceae also depends on the system of their use. In the first year, it is recommended to use them by mowing at the full flowering of the fabaceae, a fact that allows the good establishment of the fabaceae, taking into account their high sensitivity to frequent mowing at this stage of vegetation.

Most of the experiments carried out in our country used nitrogen doses between 200-300 kg/ha/year, there are also some experiments where the nitrogen dose reached 400 kg/ha/year. The response of different species to the doses of fertilizer applied is greatly influenced by the seasonal conditions in which they are cultivated, the variety and the applied technology. Thus, the same varieties under the same fertilization conditions, but cultivated in different seasonal conditions, achieve very different SU productions, the difference of which can exceed 6 t/ha SU (Simtea, 1990).

At the beginning of the 19th century Mitscherlich (1874) cited by Razec 1995 illustrated how agricultural systems respond to the increase in the intensity of a production factor (Figure 1.).

Figure. 1. Diagram illustrating the non-linear relationship dose-response (Razec, 1995)

The specialized agronomic literature records numerous reactions of this kind of agricultural crops to various treatments. Unlike non-living systems, a linear dose-response relationship never appears in living systems. A uniform intensification of a factor does not lead to a uniform reaction of the body. However, there are tolerance limits everywhere, exceeding which can instantly lead to lethal effects. Some authors consider this as the fundamental theory of autoecology (Remmert, 1978, cited by RAZEC, 1994). Thus, when used for grazing, the *Lolium perenne* species is rich in basal leaves, resists trampling very well and regenerates easily after grazing, for this reason it dominates in the first year all the mixtures in which it participates, while also having a very high nutritional value. Under the conditions of exploitation by mowing, all species of poaceae behave well, less so the species *Lolium perenne*, however, even in this species there are varieties suitable for exploitation by mowing.

Depending on the floristic composition, the maximum production is achieved in pure fabaceae crop (13.08 t/U.S.ha), followed by complex mixtures in which at least one of the perennial fabaceae species is present (12.07-12.43 t/ha US).

Regarding the floristic composition in the case of the monoculture of *Lolium perenne*, the influence of nitrogen fertilizers can be noted, thus, in the second year of use, the participation of this species in the vegetal carpet is maintained at a level between 85-89% in the variants fertilized with N₈₀ and N₁₈₀, plants from other botanical families occupying between 10-12% (Figure 3). On the other hand, from the third year of use, the *Lolium perenne* species almost disappears from the vegetation (12-20%) being replaced by species from other botanical families whose weight increases up to 93% in the unfertilized version and 87% in the fertilized version with the dose maximum nitrogen.

The species *Trifolium repens* in pure culture has a better behavior towards the administration of nitrogen, reacting especially to moderate doses of nitrogen (N_{80}) with values between 78-98%, and in the case of the maximum dose, participation in the vegetal carpet was 57-78 %. The maintenance of white clover in the vegetal carpet in a large proportion, both in the non-fertilized version (80%) and in the fertilized versions (N_{80} , N_{180}), we consider it to be a result of the high installation capacity of the species, as well as the climatic conditions of the years experimental.

In the culture associated with *L.perenne* and *T. repens*, the evolution of the floristic composition shows us a maintenance of the two species at a similar level in the experimental years with the maximum fertilized variant, respectively *Lolium perenne* has a weight of 52% and *Trifolium repens* with 38% which emphasizes both the influence of nitrogen on the two species and their capacity for protocoperation. Different situation with the variant with moderate doses of nitrogen (N_{80}), especially in the third year of use, when the species *Lolium perenne* (11%) is replaced in a mixture of species from other botanical families (55%)

In the simple mixture made up of *Trifolium repens* with *Lolium perenne*, in 2018 green mass harvests were obtained between 42.70 t/ha in the unfertilized version and 67.62 t/ha in the version fertilized with $N_{180}P_{80}K_{50}$ (Table 12.). The increase in yield obtained with the version with maximum fertilization is 6.35 t/ha of green mass. With the same mixture, the application of nitrogen in doses between 80-180 kg/ha determines statistically very significant yield increases of 8.50 t/ha of green

mass, for $N_{80}P_{80}K_{50}$, and of 6.35 t/ha for the variants fertilized with $N_{180}P_{80}K_{50}$ (table 11).

In the next two experimental years, a maintenance of green mass yield increases between 4.75 and 10.50 t/ha is observed in the variant fertilized with moderate doses of nitrogen, and in the $N_{180}P_{80}K_{50}$ variant the yield increase is 6.35 t/ha of green mass. Increases that are statistically assured as highly significantly positive.

The quality of the fodder is influenced mainly by the structure of the mixture, and only second by fertilization. For the meadow white clover based mixture, we have registers a slight decrease of the protein percentage following fertilization, from 18.68% (N_{80}) to 17.53% (N_{180}) for the *Trifolium repens* and *Lolium perenne* mixture, or from 19.05% (N_{80}) to 18.58% (N_{180}) for *Trifolium repens* (Table 14).

Nitrogen applied recovered by harvest is greater as the amount of nitrogen is lower, both monocultures and mixtures. Thus, in 2019, the largest amount of nitrogen is recovered *Lolium perenne* where monoculture of 62%, the application $N_{80}P_{80}K_{50}$ dose.

Table 1

Energy relations in natural and sown grassland ecosystems (kcal m² year⁻¹) after PUIA *et al.*

Energy transformation	Grasslands	
	Natural grasslands	Seeded grassland
Net primary production (NPP):		
- plant (aerial part)	1880	5600
- roots	500	1400
TOTAL	2380	7000
Consumption (by sheep):		
- food (weight gain)	300	1880
- excreta	130	790
- breath	180	1090
- wool production	5	40
TOTAL	615	3800
Available (for other wild primary consumers and decomposers):		
- plant (aerial part)	1265	1800
- roots	500	1400
- excreta	130	790
TOTAL	1895 (80% din PPN)	3990 (57% din PPN)

Table 2

The average temperature (°C) monthly and annual weather of Săcuieni station

Month/ Year	I	II	III	IV	V	VI	VII	VIII	IX	X	XI	XII	A
2017	-6.1	2.3	9.0	10.5	16.8	21.6	23.0	23.9	16.6	11.2	6.1	3.3	11.5
2018	3.2	1.3	3.8	15.7	19.7	21.2	22.0	24.1	17.8	13.7	8.0	1.2	12.6
2019	-0.9	3.6	8.4	13.3	14.8	23.0	21.8	24.0	17.8	13.2	10.9	4.2	12.8
2020	-1.5	4.4	6.9	11.0	14.5	20.0	21.6	23.2	18.9	12.7	5.1	4.9	11.8
2021	1.8	3.6	4.7	8.7	14.7	22.2	25.0	21.8	17.1	10.5	6.4	2.1	11.6

Table 3

Monthly and annual precipitations in Săcuieni

Month/ Year	I	II	III	IV	V	VI	VII	VIII	IX	X	XI	XII	A
2017	14.7	39.2	39.5	46.5	138.3	76.9	35.0	60.9	95.4	38.2	56.4	84.9	725.9
2018	32.2	58.6	65.8	38.3	57.6	83.6	127.6	36.9	22.1	12.7	39.8	61.0	636.2
2019	46.8	8.7	12.0	46.0	105.8	119.3	21.9	11.5	33.0	10.9	35.3	46.4	497.6
2020	13.5	45.2	43.8	15.4	60.0	101.5	133.2	29.0	31.0	62.7	14.1	45.2	594.6
2021	56.8	46.4	18.6	36.5	80.8	5.4	43.5	24.8	9.1	4.7	75.9	57.1	459.6

Table 4

Soil - Chernozem, cambic subtype, on clays, sandy-clayey clay on medium clay (SRTS), Haplic Chernozems (WBR-SR-1998), Typic Haplustosolls (USDA-ST-1999) - Succession of horizons: Am – Bv – C- Analytical data

Horizons	Am ₁	Am ₂	Bv	C
Coarse sand % (2-0,2mm)	0-25	25-48	48-78	78-100
Fine sand % (0,2-0,02mm)	0.50	0.50	0.40	0.20
Dust % (0,02-0,002mm)	61.7	51.70	60.10	56.10
Physical clay % (sub 0,01 mm)	13.1	18.00	12.10	19.40
Texture	LN	LL	LN	LL
Carbonates	-	-	-	-
Ph in water	7.1	7.25	6.75	7.85
Humus	2.13	1.40	-	-
Total nitrogen %	0.105	0.070	-	-
Mobile phosphorus (ppm)	12	3	-	-
Mobile Potassium (ppm)	120	130	-	-
Amount of exchange bases (me./100 g. sol)	18.3	-	-	-
Exchangeable hydrogen	3.0	-	-	-
Degree of saturation in bases	96	-	-	-

Table 5

Influence of fertilization on green mass yield of the culture *Trifolium perenne* (2018) (t/ha)

Dosing of fertilization	Yield (t/ha)	Percent %	Differences t/ha	Significance
d1 (control)	35.35	100,0	0,00	Mt.
d2 (N ₈₀ P ₈₀ K ₅₀)	35.35	153,5	0,00	-
d3 (N ₁₈₀ P ₈₀ K ₅₀)	38.30	108,40	0,59	-
LSD (5%)			1.85	
LSD (1%)			2.54	
LSD (0.1%)			3.32	

Table 6

Influence of fertilization on green mass yield of the culture *Trifolium perenne* (2019) (t/ha)

Dosing of fertilization	Yield (t/ha)	Percent %	Differences t/ha	Significance
d1 (control)	25.65	100.0	0,00	Mt.
d2 (N ₈₀ P ₈₀ K ₅₀)	35.75	139.37	10.10	***
d3 (N ₁₈₀ P ₈₀ K ₅₀)	39.15	152.63	13.50	***
LSD (5%)			1.80	
LSD (1%)			2.60	
LSD (0.1%)			3.85	

Table 7

Influence of fertilization on green mass yield of the culture *Trifolium perenne* (2020) (t/ha)

Dosing of fertilization	Yield (t/ha)	Percent %	Differences t/ha	Significance
d1 (control)	18.70	100,0	0,00	Mt.
d2 (N ₈₀ P ₈₀ K ₅₀)	26.75	143.04	8.05	***
d3 (N ₁₈₀ P ₈₀ K ₅₀)	22.00	117.64	3.30	**
LSD (5%)			2.10	
LSD (1%)			3.03	
LSD (0.1%)			4.63	

Table 8

Influence of fertilization on green mass yield of the culture *Lolium perenne* (2018) (t/ha)

Dosing of fertilization	Yield (t/ha)	Percent %	Differences t/ha	Significance
d1 (control)	30.75	100.0	0.00	Mt.
d2 (N ₈₀ P ₈₀ K ₅₀)	38.75	243.00	8.00	***
d3 (N ₁₈₀ P ₈₀ K ₅₀)	39.45	259.70	8.70	***
LSD (5%)			1.85	
LSD (1%)			2.54	
LSD (0.1%)			3.32	

Table 9

Influence of fertilization on green mass yield of the culture *Lolium perenne* (2019) (t/ha)

Dosing of fertilization	Yield (t/ha)	Percent %	Differences t/ha	Significance
d1 (control)	26,25	100.0	0.00	Mt.
d2 (N ₈₀ P ₈₀ K ₅₀)	35.25	134.28	9.00	***
d3 (N ₁₈₀ P ₈₀ K ₅₀)	40.15	152.95	13.90	***
LSD (5%)			1.72	
LSD (1%)			2.48	
LSD (0.1%)			3.65	

Table 10

Influence of fertilization on green mass yield of the culture *Lolium perenne* (2020) (t/ha)

Dosing of fertilization	Yield (t/ha)	Percent %	Differences t/ha	Significance
d1 (control)	12.50	100.0	0.00	Mt.
d2 (N ₈₀ P ₈₀ K ₅₀)	24.75	198.0	1.80	*
d3 (N ₁₈₀ P ₈₀ K ₅₀)	26.80	214.40	2.78	**
LSD (5%)			1.65	
LSD (1%)			2.40	
LSD (0.1%)			3.71	

Table 11

Influence of fertilization on green mass yield of the mixture *Trifolium repens* + *Lolium perenne* in 2018 (t/ha)

Dosing of fertilization	Yield (t/ha)	Percent %	Differences t/ha	Significance
d1 (control)	42.70	100.0	0,00	Mt.
d2 (N ₈₀ P ₈₀ K ₅₀)	51.20	119.90	8,50	***
d3 (N ₁₈₀ P ₈₀ K ₅₀)	49.05	114.87	6,35	***
LSD (5%)			1.86	
LSD (1%)			2.55	
LSD (0.1%)			3.33	

Table 12

Influence of fertilization on green mass yield of the mixture *Trifolium repens* + *Lolium perenne* in 2019 (t/ha)

Dosing of fertilization	Yield (t/ha)	Percent %	Differences t/ha	Significance
d1 (control)	32.70	100.0	0.00	Mt.
d2 (N ₈₀ P ₈₀ K ₅₀)	43.20		10.50	***
d3 (N ₁₈₀ P ₈₀ K ₅₀)	39.05		6.35	***
LSD (5%)			1.76	
LSD (1%)			2.45	
LSD (0.1%)			3.23	

Table 13

Influence of fertilization on green mass yield of the mixture *Trifolium repens* + *Lolium perenne* in 2020 (t/ha)

Dosing of fertilization	Yield (t/ha)	Percent %	Diferența t/ ha Differences t/ha	Semnificația Significance
d1 (control)	18.55	100.0	0.00	Mt.
d2 (N ₈₀ P ₈₀ K ₅₀)	23.30		4.75	***
d3 (N ₁₈₀ P ₈₀ K ₅₀)	24.25		5.70	***
LSD (5%)			1.65	
LSD (1%)			2.40	
LSD (0.1%)			3.71	

Table 14

The influence of nitrogen on the chemical composition of SU in the studied crops

Dose N	Variants	BP %	BP kg/ha	CA	A %	P %	K %	Ca %	Mg %
N ₀		17.06	638.04	27.56	13.88	0.23	2.41	2.20	0.41
N ₈₀	<i>T.repens</i>	19.05	1019.17	23.78	15.45	0.31	3.58	2.19	0.47
N ₁₈₀		18.58	817.52	28.58	12.04	0.28	3.06	1.87	0.31
N ₀		15.36	305.60	25.61	17.19	0.32	3.18	1.55	0.30
N ₈₀	<i>L. perenne</i>	17.72	855.80	28.62	14.02	0.30	3.54	1.40	0.31
N ₁₈₀		17.56	906.00	26.47	15.13	0.32	3.46	1.58	0.36
N ₀		19.14	710	21.53	15.03	0.30	3.23	2.53	0.48
N ₈₀	<i>L.perenne+T.repens</i>	18.68	870	26.58	14.03	0.34	3.32	2.15	0.45
N ₁₈₀		17.53	850	23.42	18.72	0.33	3.35	1.86	0.43

CONCLUSIONS

Analyzing the dry mass production of the experimental field, we can state that seeded grasslands are an extremely advantageous option for producing the necessary hay for the housing period or for grazing.

Generally, by nitrogen fertilization favor Poaceae growth in disfavor to Fabaceae. As the fertilizer doses increase, so does the participation rate of Poaceae.

We recommend for the Săcuieni area, Bihor county, (the area where the experiment took place) a mixture of *Trifolium repens* and *Lolium perenne* and pure culture of *Lolium perenne*.

Starting its second year of seeding, the *Trifolium pratense* and *Lolium multiflorum* mixture yields results between 23.30 to 51.20 t/ha of green mass on N80P80K50 and between 24.25 to 49.05 t/ha of green mass on N180P80K5 fertilization. This mixture displays a good perennity in the third year of cultivation, with the chosen cultivars maintaining an elevated proportion, *Lolium perenne* with 52% and *Trifolium repens* with 38% in N180P80N50 fertilization version.

The quality of the fodder is influenced mainly by the structure of the mixture, and only second by fertilization. For the meadow white clover based mixture, we have registers a slight decrease of the protein percentage following fertilization, from 18.68% (N80) to 17.53% (N180) for the *Trifolium repens* and *Lolium perenne* mixture, or from 19.05% (N80) to 18.58% (N180) for *Trifolium repens*.

Nitrogen applied recovered by harvest is greater as the amount of nitrogen is lower, both monocultures and mixtures. Thus, in 2019, the largest amount of nitrogen is recovered *Lolium perenne* where monoculture of 62%, the application N80P80K50 dose.

REFERENCES

- Alina Ștefania Șuteu, 1995, Partial experimental results on associated Poaceae and Fabaceae perennial forage crops, Bibliographic reference, USAMV Cluj-Napoca
- Alina Ștefania Șuteu, 1997, Research on the cultivation technology of perennial Poaceae and Fabaceae species, with special focus on associated crops, nitrogen fertilization system, density and competitive ability of the species, PhD thesis, USAMV Cluj-Napoca
- Cardașol V., Gh. Motcă, C. Bărbulescu, C. Pavel, N. Simtea, A. Ionel, A. Lăpușan, I. Țucra, N. Dragomir, Constantina Chiper, I. Capșa, Stela Capșa, I. Razec, V. Panait, T. Iacob, N. Petcu, Fl. Dincă, D. Ștefan, 1998, Effect of chemical fertilizer application on the production and quality of permanent and temporary grasslands in Romania, Scientific Papers ale ICPCP Măgurele-Brașov, vol.XIII, pp. 1-13
- Carlier L., I. Puia, I. Rotar, (1998). For a better grass production, Ed. Risoprint, Cluj Napoca
- Frame J., 2000, Improved grassland management, Farming press. Miller Freeman House, U.K.
- Deak D., I. Rotar, Roxana Vidican, Anca Bogdan, 2012, The study of the behaviour of *Trifolium pratense*+*Lolium multiflorum* in the conditions of the depression Odorheiul Secuiesc, Bulletin USAMV Cluj.
- Nagy Miklos, I. Rotar, Roxana Vidican, Gliga A., Anamaria Malinas 2014. The behaviour of *Dactylis glomerata* and *Medicago sativa* species under mineral fertilization in pure culture. Romanian Journal of Grasslands and Forage Crops. RJGFC NO 10, Cluj-Napoca, pp.59-66.
- Olar M.V., Olar M., Duda M.M., Vârban D.I., Moldovan Cristina, Bărbieru V., Ghețe A.B., Olar V.M., (2018), Tall fescue variety (*Festuca arundinacea* SCHREBER) NAPOCA 2, RFGFC NR.17/2018, pp.27-32
- Popovici D., M. Pop, C. Ciubotariu, N. Simtea, C. Constantinide, V. Văsui, 1979, Contributions to the determination of the optimal proportion of Poaceae and Fabaceae in simple mixtures for the establishment of temporary grassland in different conditions in RS Romania, Scientific Papers of SCPCP Măgurele Brașov, vol. V, pp. 21-32
- Razec I., 1995, Productivity of Poaceae and Fabaceae perennial associations at different vegetation stages. Dry matter yields. Scientific papers of I.C.P.C.P. Brașov, vol. XVII, 125-140
- Rotar I., 1993, Investigations of competitive constraints in pure and associated crops of *Medicago sativa* and *Dactylis glomerata* under differentiated nitrogen fertilization, PhD Thesis, USAMV Cluj Napoca
- Rotar I. Și Carlier L. 2005. Meadow Culture, Ed. Risoprint, Cluj-Napoca, Cod ISBN 973-656-8112-1

Rotar I., Carlier L., 2010, Meadow Culture, Ed.
Risoprint, Cluj-Napoca
Samuil, C., Vîntu, V., Iacob, T., Saghin, Trofin, A.
2009 - Management of permanent
grasslands in North- Eastern Romania,
Alternative Functions of Grassland,

European Grassland Federation, vol. 14,
ISBN:978-80- 86908-15-1, pg. 236
Samuil, C., V. Vîntu, Gabriela Mihaela Surmei, A.
Ionel,2010, Research on the behaviour of
simple habelical.

THE FUNCTIONAL NUTRITIONAL VALUE AND THE HEALTH BENEFITS OF CONSUMING EGGPLANT

Andrada IENCIU¹, Mariana BEI^{1#}, Mihai CĂRBUNAR¹, Mihaela CĂRBUNAR¹, Oana VIDICAN¹

¹University of Oradea, Faculty of Environmental Protection, Oradea City, Maghru 26, 410087, Romania Institution

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

Eggplants, due to their multiple functional properties and metabolic benefits on several pathologies, proven by repeated research, are also considered medicinal plants or foods. They have a low caloric content but an increased content of mineral elements, representing a complete food through the content of vitamins, fibers, and phytochemical nutrients with antioxidant activity. The positive metabolic effects of eggplants are given by the content of anthocyanins, present in the purple skin, of glycoalkaloids with anticancer effect and of solasodine, an aglycol with an effect on lung cancer.

The pharmacological properties of eggplants, due to functional nutrients, have the effect of reducing LDL-c, triglycerides and blood sugar, contributing significantly to weight reduction.

Eggplants are important plants from an agronomic and economic point of view but also from a nutritional point of view, representing a significant base source for various pharmaceutical products and essential nutraceutical compounds.

Keywords: eggplant, *Solanum melongena*, functional components, metabolic effect

#Corresponding author: marianaf.bei@gmail.com

INTRODUCTION

The consumption of vegetables, as safe sources of vitamins and minerals, due to their functional nature, contributes to the improvement of metabolic disorders, protecting the body from various diseases and illnesses (Apahidean et al., 2000).

Eggplants are grown mainly as vegetables but are also grown for medicinal purposes. The analysis of the content in phytochemical compounds of eggplant shows that these vegetables are a rich source of some essential compounds such as: aspartic acid, tropane, flavonoids, lanosterol, gramisterol, steroid alkaloids, glycoalkaloids, histidine, nasunin, oxalic acid, solasodine, ascorbic acid and tryptophan (Nishimura, et al. 2019). Added to these functional nutrients are significant amounts of choline and acetylcholine esters with antihypertensive and stress-reducing effects, suppressing sympathetic nervous activity (Yamaguchi et al, 2019). They are also low in calories and high in water. These compounds show functional properties on cancer, with anti-inflammatory, anti-asthmatic, hypolipidemic and hypocholesterolemic, antiplatelet and hypotensive effects and improving glycemic levels in type II diabetes (Naeem and Ugur, 2019; Yarmohammadi et al, 2021).

Tropical species of eggplant, such as *Solanum kumba*, *Solanum aethiopicum* and *Solanum gilo*, had positive metabolic effects following daily consumption over a period of 12 weeks in various forms, prepared or raw (Nwanna et al, 2018).

Solanum melongena extract has a significant beneficial effect on the treatment of Bowen's disease. The extract could inhibit cell cycle progression into S phase, inducing progressive cell apoptosis and ultimately cell death (Sarah and Misbahuddin, 2018).

Amides (n-trans-p-coumaroyltyramine, feruloyldopamine) have been shown to inhibit bacteria (Zacares et al., 2007). N-trans-coumaroyltyramine, n-trans-feruloyltyramine and n-trans-feruloyloctopamine have demonstrated effective free radical scavenging activity (Li et al., 2012). Neochlorogenic acid, a phenylpropanoid compound showed antioxidant activity, in vitro, analyzed by three methods (ABTS, DPPH and FRAP) (Zielinski et al., 2020). A variety of alkaloids can inhibit anticholinesterase activity related to the treatment of Alzheimer's disease (Lelario et al., 2019).

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The so varied and rich nutritional components of eggplants, presented in the specialized literature, depend on numerous

factors, such as the variety, harvest period, storage and preservation conditions, processing and cooking conditions, and the environment in which they grow.

Starting from these factors, in our study we analyzed the quality of eggplant varieties of different colors, cultivated in an ecological system, in the western part of Romania. The ecological system of eggplant cultivation ensures superior quality products, without pesticide residues, being requested by consumers in ever-increasing quantities.

The biological material was represented by the varieties Violetta di Firenze, Carina, Black Beauty, Dourga, Jilo Tingua Verde, Japanese Pickling, Orange de Turquie (Fig. 1).

1.1. Violetta di Firenze

1.2. Carina

1.3. Black Beauty

1.4. Dourga

1.5. Jilo Tingua Verde

1.6. Japanese Pickling

1.7. Orange de Turquie
Figure 1. Eggplant variety

The nutri-functional quality was evaluated based on the content of bioactive compounds: polyphenols (TPC), flavonoids (TF), monomeric anthocyanins from the fresh peel and pulp, and the antioxidant activity by the FRAP method.

The analyzes were performed on the fresh sample without heat treatment.

-Total phenol content (TPC) – was analyzed by the Folin-Ciocalteu spectrophotometric method, with absorbance measurement at 765 nm, using gallic acid as a standard.

-The total content of flavonoids (TF) – was analyzed by the AlCl₃ spectrophotometric method (Atanassova et al., 2011). Absorbance was measured at 510 nm after 30 minutes. As a standard quercetin was used.

-FRAP antioxidant activity - The reducing capacity of the samples was tested with the original method of Benzie and Strain. The expression was made by correspondence with the FeSO₄ activity for the sample extract, the concentration was calculated using the calibration curve (0-1000pM FeSO₄).

-Monomeric anthocyanins - the difference in absorption of the pigments at 520 nm is proportional to the concentration of the pigment. Results are expressed on the basis of cyanidin-3-glucoside (AOAC method).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Eggplant is the third most important crop in the genus *Solanum* after potatoes and tomatoes (Zhang, 2013). Being a thermophilic species, the cultivation area is limited by the climatic conditions, and the rather high requirements regarding the quality of the soil, but the high requirements regarding the soil moisture, consider eggplants to be the most demanding Solanoaceae vegetables in terms of pedoclimatic factors.

For all the samples, 3 repetitions were made, from fruits coming from organic culture, and the results presented in figures 2., 3., 4., 5., 6., represent the average values.

The highest amount of anthocyanins in fresh eggplant peel (figure 2) was recorded in the cultivar Japanese Pickling (39.49 mg/100g) and the lowest value was recorded in the cultivar Carina (10.42 mg/100g).

Figure 2. Content of Anthocyanins from the peel of the eggplant fruit (fresh product)

Anthocyanins have been associated with both the prevention and management of type 2 diabetes in both animal and human studies (Xiao and Hogger, 2015). The metabolic benefits correlate faithfully with the polyphenolic compound, with protective actions on pancreatic beta cells, improving glucose tolerance and insulin sensitivity through the antioxidant and anti-inflammatory effect (Xiao and Hogger, 2015).

The data presented in figure 2 indicate a null content in anthocyanins in the Dourga, Orange de Turquie and Jilo Tingua Verde cultivars, which led to the determination of the content in other compounds with antioxidant activity such as lycopene and carotene. The data are presented in figure 3.

In the cultivar Dourga, it was not possible to determine the content in carotene and lycopene, due to the white color of the peel.

Figure 3. Content of carotene and lycopene from the peel of the Orange de Turquie and Jilo Tingua Verde variety

In the cultivar Jilo Tingua Verde, the lycopene content was approximately three times higher (152.01 µg/g) compared to Orange de Turquie (53.29 µg/g). The lycopene content was also much higher in the cultivar Jilo Tingua Verde, being 40.76 µg/g compared

to Orange de Turquie, which recorded a content of 20.42 µg/g (figure 3).

Both the lycopene content and the carotene content recorded significant values, so these two eggplant cultivars can represent functional foods with an effect on some metabolic disorders.

Figure 4. Content of Polyphenols from the peel of the eggplant fruit (fresh product)

The amount of polyphenols (figure 4), determined from the eggplant skin, recorded values between 189.28 mg GAE / 100g for Orange de Turquie and 369.16 mg GAE / 100g for Black Beauty.

Polyphenols have become an emerging area of interest in nutrition in recent decades

due to their vital role in health through their putative protective effect on acute and chronic diseases, including obesity, neurodegenerative diseases, type 2 diabetes and cardiovascular diseases (Cory, et al, 2018).

Figure 5. Content of Flavonoids from the peel of the eggplant fruit (fresh product)

The total flavonoids in the eggplant skin (figure 5) varied within very wide limits, between 10.62 mg quercitin/100 mg in the cultivar Jilo Tingua Verde 100g and 931.51 mg quercitin/100g in the cultivar Violetta di Firenze, and in cultivar Orange de Turquie flavonoids were not identified.

Culinary preparation plays a significant role on the content of polyphenols. Quercetin content can be reduced by up to 80% by boiling, 65% by microwaving and 30% by frying (Pandey and, 2009).

In general, the relationship between cooking method and polyphenol availability is complex and depends on the food, polyphenolic compound, cooking method, and other factors, often showing a U-shaped relationship (Cory, et al, 2018).

The antioxidant activity determined by the FRAP method (figures 6) varied between 26.22 mM FeSO₄/g in the cultivar Orange de Turquie and 58.87 mM FeSO₄/g in Violetta di Firenze and Black Beauty.

Figure 6. Antioxidant activity from the peel of the eggplant fruit (fresh product)

Anthocyanins from vegetables and fruits show strong antioxidant and anti-inflammatory action, to which are also added hepatoprotective, chemo-protective and cardio-protective effects important from the perspective of optimal health.

The dose of 12 mg/kg body administered for 30 days can reduce markers of oxidative

stress and lipid peroxidation and doses of 320 mg/day lead to the decrease of IL-6 in obesity and in cardiovascular diseases where oxidative stress causes vascular inflammation. Anthocyanin extracts from berries at a dose of 160 mg twice daily for a period of 12 weeks lead to significant increases in serum HDL-C and decreases in LDL-C. A dose of 150 ml/day

of anthocyanin-rich pomegranate juice consumed between lunch and dinner for 14 days has been shown to significantly reduce both systolic and diastolic BP.

The recommended daily intake of anthocyanins and associated flavonoids according to WHO-FAO, is 200–250 mg/day, while the intake of anthocyanins extracted from grape skin has been established at 2.5 mg/kg. In the United States, according to the US-FDA Flavonoid Nutritional Database the recommended intake of anthocyanins is 12.5 mg/day/person, a dose supported by the US-NHANES (United States National Health and Nutrition Examination Survey).

CONCLUSIONS

The anthocyanin content of the fresh peel was between 10.42 mg/100g in Carina and 39.49 mg/100g in Japanese Pickling. This amount correlated with the degree of damage to the body has a significant effect on the disorders caused by oxidative stress, leading to a decrease in IL-6, a significant increase in HDL-c and a decrease in LDL-c.

Anthocyanins and related flavonoids, even though they are not considered essential components of the human diet, their functional effects and increased content in many fruits and vegetables could reduce morbidity from heart failure, ischemic heart disease and cancers by 9-14%, respectively.

A quantity of 100 g of eggplant consumed per day provides 22.5% of the RDI of health-enhancing anthocyanins.

The eggplant cultivar Violetta di Firenze recorded the highest amount of total flavonoids, determined from the peel, being 931.51 mg quercetin/100g, being one of the most important phenolic protectors on human health. This amount per 100 g of product provides 53.67% of the RDA.

The highest value of the total amount of polyphenols in the eggplant skin was recorded in the Black Beauty variety, namely 359.16 mg GAE/100g, which would provide 143.66% of the RDA with the expected functional effect on the atherosclerotic risk.

The antioxidant activity determined by the FRAP method was the highest in Violetta di Firenze and Black Beauty varieties, 58.87 mM FeSO₄/g.

REFERENCES

- Apahidean Al. S., 2000, General vegetable cultivation, Ed. Risoprint, Cluj-Napoca
- Gürbüz N, Uluişik S, Frary A, Frary A, Doğanlar S. 2018. Health benefits and bioactive compounds of eggplant. *Food Chem.* 2018 Dec 1;268:602-610. DOI: 10.1016/j.foodchem.2018.06.093. Epub 2018 Jun 20. PMID: 30064803.
- Nishimura M, Suzuki M, Takahashi R, Yamaguchi S, Tsubaki K, Fujita T, Nishihira J, Nakamura K. 2019. Daily Ingestion of Eggplant Powder Improves Blood Pressure and Psychological State in Stressed Individuals: A Randomized Placebo-Controlled Study. *Nutrients.* 2019 Nov 16;11(11):2797. doi: 10.3390/nu11112797. PMID: 31744060; PMCID: PMC6893753.
- Yamaguchi S., Matsumoto K., Koyama M., Tian S., Watanabe M., Takahashi A., Miyatake K., Nakamura K. 2019. Antihypertensive effects of orally administered eggplant (*Solanum melongena*) rich in acetylcholine on spontaneously hypertensive rats. *Food Chem.* 2019;276:376–382. DOI: 10.1016/j.foodchem.2018.10.017. [PubMed] [CrossRef] [Google Scholar]
- Muhammad Yasir Naeem, Senay Ugur. 2019. Nutritional Content and Health Benefits of Eggplant. *urkish Journal of Agriculture - Food Science and Technology*, 7(sp3): 31-36, 2019 DOI: <https://doi.org/10.24925/turjaf.v7isp3.31-36.3146>
- Yarmohammadi F, Ghasemzadeh Rahbardar M, Hosseinzadeh H. 2021. Effect of eggplant (*Solanum melongena*) on the metabolic syndrome: A review. *Iran J Basic Med Sci.* 2021 Apr;24(4):420-427. doi: 10.22038/ijbms.2021.50276.11452. PMID: 34094022; PMCID: PMC8143715.
- Nwanna EE, Ibukun EO, Oboh G. 2018. Nutritional content of selected species of tropical eggplant fruit (*Solanum* spp) diet Attenuates hepatic inflammation in high-fat fed male Wistar rats induced with streptozotocin. *Food Sci Nutr.* 2018 Nov 19;7(11):109-119. doi: 10.1002/fsn3.811. PMID: 30680164; PMCID: PMC6341174.
- Sarah Q. S., Misbahuddin M. 2018. Effect of *Solanum Melongena* Peel Extract in the Treatment of Arsenic-Induced Bowen's Disease. *Bangladesh J. Pharmacol.* 13, 309–315. 10.3329/bjp.v13i4.38273 [CrossRef] [Google Scholar]
- Zacarés L., López-Gresa M. P., Fayos J., Primo J., Bellés J. M., Conejero V. 2007. Induction of P-Coumaroyldopamine and Feruloyldopamine, Two Novel Metabolites, in Tomato by the Bacterial Pathogen *Pseudomonas syringae*. *Mpmi* 20, 1439–1448. 10.1094/mpmi-20-11-1439 [PubMed] [CrossRef] [Google Scholar]
- Zielinski A. A. F., Alberti A., Bona E., on so. 2020. A Multivariate Approach to Differentiate Yerba Mate (*Ilex Paraguariensis*) Commercialized in the Southern Brazil on the Basis of Phenolics, Methylxanthines and In Vitro Antioxidant Activity. *Food Sci. Technol.* 40, 644–652. 10.1590/fst.15919 [CrossRef] [Google Scholar]

-
- Lelario F., De Maria S., Rivelli A. R., Russo D., Milella L., Bufo S. A., et al. 2019. A Complete Survey of Glycoalkaloids Using LC-FTICR-MS and IRMPD in a Commercial Variety and a Local Landrace of Eggplant (*Solanum Melongena* L.) and Their Anticholinesterase and Antioxidant Activities. *Toxins* 11, 230. 10.3390/toxins11040230 [PMC free article] [PubMed] [CrossRef] [Google Scholar]
- Li W. J., Cheng X. L., Liu J., Lin R. C., Wang G. L., Du S. S., et al. 2012. Phenolic Compounds and Antioxidant Activities of *Liriope Muscari*. *Molecules* 17, 1797–1808. 10.3390/molecules17021797 [PMC free article] [PubMed] [CrossRef] [Google Scholar]
- Cory H, Passarelli S, Szeto J, Tamez M, Mattei J. The Role of Polyphenols in Human Health and Food Systems: A Mini-Review. *Front Nutr.* 2018 Sep 21;5:87. doi: 10.3389/fnut.2018.00087. PMID: 30298133; PMCID: PMC6160559.
- Xiao JB, Hogger P. Dietary polyphenols and type 2 diabetes: current insights and future perspectives. *Curr Med Chem.* (2015) 22:23–38. 10.2174/0929867321666140706130807 [PubMed] [CrossRef] [Google Scholar]
- Pandey KB, Rizvi SI. Plant polyphenols as dietary antioxidants in human health and disease. *Oxid Med Cell Longev.* (2009) 2:270–8. 10.4161/oxim.2.5.9498 [PMC free article] [PubMed] [CrossRef] [Google Scholar]
- Mohammed HA, Khan RA. Anthocyanins: Traditional Uses, Structural and Functional Variations, Approaches to Increase Yields and Products' Quality, Hepatoprotection, Liver Longevity, and Commercial Products. *Int J Mol Sci.* 2022 Feb 15;23(4):2149. doi: 10.3390/ijms23042149. PMID: 35216263; PMCID: PMC8875224.

RESEARCH REGARDING THE EFFECT OF IRRIGATION ON THE LEAF SURFACE OF PLUM SEEDLINGS IN THE SECOND FIELD

Adelina VENIG¹, Aurora VENIG¹, Nicu Cornel SABĂU¹

¹University of Oradea, Faculty of Environmental Protection, Oradea

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

The growth of horticultural plants is affected by high temperatures and drought, through the inhibitory effects they have on cell division and extension, as well as on some morphological changes regarding the increase in thickness of the leaves and the cuticle, the reduction of the number of stomata, wilting, change in position of the leaves on the plant and the change in the number of aquaporins. The current work is a research on the influence of irrigation in the nursery, on plum seedlings. Plum rootstocks are demanding in terms of water, their culture being extended over larger areas in areas with a richer pluviometric regime. From the large amount of water absorbed from the soil by the roots, for the synthesis of organic substances, the rootstock uses only a small part, the rest being eliminated through the phenomenon of transpiration. Two varieties of plum were studied, namely Cacanska Lepotica and Stanley. Four irrigation norms were used in the research. The leaf surface of the seedlings, under the effect of different watering norms, the average leaf surface, the effect of irrigation and the variety on the leaf surface were analyzed.

Keywords: irrigation rate, seedlings, leaf surface, Cacanska Lepotica, Stanley
#Corresponding author: adelina_venig@yahoo.com

INTRODUCTION

Water is indispensable for plants, being a basic component of living cells and tissues. Only in the presence of water can the processes of assimilation and disassimilation and gas exchange take place. Once inside the plant, water keeps the cell walls stretched and gives the cells and tissues turgidity, which ensures the mechanical balance of the various organs (Sela, 2020). Together with dissolved substances, water determines the osmotic pressure of cells and tissues, ensuring intercellular exchanges. As a participant in plant metabolism, water is involved in the fundamental processes of the living world, photosynthesis, respiration, transpiration. The importance of water as a vegetation factor in the life of plants is known and appreciated as such from the moment when man began to practice agriculture and horticulture. With the deepening of agronomic and horticultural knowledge and with the progress made in the related fields (plant physiology, pedology, climatology, biophysics, etc.), some clarifications and differentiations of water requirements for agricultural and

horticultural crops could be made. The water in plants is found in different states: a part of the water enters the structure of all the chemical compounds of the organic matter, another part is represented by water very tightly bound osmotically and by biocolloids and another part of the water that is found in the vessels and cells plants, being very weakly retained, is mobile and moves from cell to cell or from one organism to another, under the effect of forces acting inside or outside the plant organism (Panigrahi, 2020). For a normal development of plants, a high water content in their tissues is necessary, which is achieved by continuously maintaining a high humidity in the soil (Goyal, 2021). Corresponding to the interaction of influencing factors, the water consumption requirements specific to fruit plants vary within relatively wide limits according to the species and variety, parent stocks, the age period of the plants and the vegetation phase, the climatic factors through the precipitation regime, the thermal and wind regime, the factors pedological through the orography of the land, the state of fertility and the technological factors through the culture system and the technical level

practiced. Through irrigation, an optimal water supply level of 65-75% of the soil's total retention capacity must be ensured, by no means creating excess moisture (>80%). Our country, due to its geographical location at the confluence of continental and Mediterranean climates, generally offers favourable climate and soil conditions for a large number of fruit nurseries. Numerous autochthonous varieties attest to the presence of fruit growing on the lands of our country since ancient times. Initially, the fruit nurseries were concentrated in the areas with a richer rainfall regime, so that the rootstock capture depended to a greater extent on the rainfall regime, the human intervention at the beginning being modest in this regard (Steele, 2015)

A shortcoming characteristic of the climatic regime of our country, which is reflected quite significantly in fruit growing, is the defective distribution of precipitation during the year, resulting in prolonged periods of drought in some areas (periods of time longer than 10 days during the vegetation and 14 days during rest, in which no rains greater than 5 mm fall) (Twoney, 2016). Taking into account these aspects, associated with the tendency to develop important fruit-growing centres in typically dry areas, on zonal soils and on sands, it is found that irrigation must be a concern of prime importance for the fruit-growing sector in our country, but which must manifest itself differently, depending on the pedoclimatic zone, type of rootstock, etc. Plum rootstocks are demanding in terms of water, their culture being extended over larger areas in areas with a richer pluviometric regime (Novelli, 2022). From the large amount of water absorbed from the soil by the roots, for the synthesis of organic substances, the rootstock uses only a small part, the rest being eliminated through the phenomenon of transpiration. In the case of planting rootstocks on wet and poor soils where the soil solution has a lower concentration of fertilizing elements, the transpiration coefficient is higher than in the case of rootstocks planted on more fertile soils (Kun, 2022). By applying fertilizers and ensuring sufficient amounts of water in the soil, the transpiration coefficient decreases so that water is used more economically by the rootstock (Faulkner, 2022). Irrigation represents both an important technological sequence in the agrotechnology of

crop plants, as well as the most important means of eliminating the water deficit in the soil, constituting the infrastructure of sustainable development (Zai, 2022). Irrigation also means the controlled supply of soil and plants with additional amounts of water compared to those received naturally, in order to ensure the constancy of agricultural production at a high level. Finally, the aim is to create the conditions for the practice of efficient, sustainable agriculture, under the conditions of protecting the environmental factors. Among these factors, a primary role belongs to the soil, whose fertility must be maintained at a high level and even improved. The use of this radical method of fighting drought, which is irrigation, is indicated to be associated in the complex with other technical-agricultural measures, including drying works (where applicable), fertilizing, selection of the most valuable plants and varieties, etc. At the same time, irrigation can also be defined as the set of works and measures that compete for the controlled supply of water to plants in order to obtain high, constant and quality productions. In our country, the development of irrigation at the moment is characterized by the following two main features: very intense pace in the development of new lands and the use of modern solutions in the construction of irrigation systems. In this way, fruit growing will cease to be tributary to the biggest enemy of agriculture, the drought. However, the action to remove the moisture deficit does not stop at landscaping. The creation of the irrigation system constitutes a first stage, after which an equally important stage follows, that of exploitation, of putting the respective facilities into maximum efficiency. This second, long-lasting stage, involves the application of irrigation in such a way that once the expected results are achieved in the production of trees, the maintenance of the soil in a state of permanent fertility and the irrigation system in a perfect state is ensured operation. In the climatic conditions of our country, irrigation is a measure to supplement the quantities of water that come naturally, from precipitation, in periods when they are insufficient compared to the requirements of crops. It is, in fact, a means used to correct a natural factor, which, as it is presented, has the effect of large fluctuations in the harvest from one year to another. Through

the use of irrigation, the aim is to obtain the most stable productions, close to the productive potential of the plants in the given pedo-climatic conditions. This, of course, all the more since, during the research carried out in our country, it was found that there are years in which, due to insufficient rainfall in certain periods, harvests are greatly reduced, going up to total compromise.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The key research methods employed were analysis and synthesis and analogy to resemble the results.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

According to the results of the analysis of variance, it can be observed that only irrigation and fertilization showed considerable, statistically guaranteed influences on the leaf surface of seedlings in field II. Irrigation had the highest contribution to this character (30.75 %), compared to fertilization treatments (22.07 %), against the background of a very small influence of the variety (0.11 %). Also, the combined effects of the three factors showed significant influences on the leaf surface, but considerably less than their separate effects. The interaction between variety and irrigation was highlighted by a major effect of 3.64%, followed by the fertilization x variety interaction.

Table 1

Variance Analysis Regarding the Effect of Irrigation, Variety and Fertilization on the Leaf Surface of Seedlings from the Second Field

The source of variation	SP	GL	S ²	Test F
Total	43868124	159		
Repetition	216761	4	54190	0,59
Irrigation	8493021	3	2831007	30,75**
Irrigation error	1104856	12	92071	
Variety	9986	1	9986	0,12
Irrigation x Variety	970711	3	323570	3,84*
Type error	1349748	16	84359	
Fertilization	9982917	3	3327639	22,07**
Irrigation x Fertilization	3044252	9	338250	2,24*
Variety x Fertilization	1398818	3	466273	3,09*
Irrigation x Variety x Fertilization	2819710	9	313301	2,08*
Fertilization error	14477344	96	150806	

Taking into account the unilateral effect of irrigation, it is observed that the leaf surface recorded an amplitude of 610 cm² with values between 4275 cm² in the non-irrigated version and 4885 cm² in the case of using the 30 mm watering norm. As such, the three watering norms showed major and strongly statistically assured influences, determining progressive increases of this character between 4.42 and 14.27%. Changing the watering rate from 10 to 20 mm had a significant effect associated with an increase in leaf area of 5.17%, while the addition of irrigation from 20 to 30 mm determined a significant increase of this character of 4.05 %.

Table 2

The Average Leaf Area of Seedlings in the Second Field under the Effect of Different Irrigation Rate

Irrigation rate	Leaf surface (cm ²)		Relative values (%)	Difference/Significance
10 mm – 0 mm	4464	4275	104,42	189*
20 mm – 0 mm	4695	4275	109,82	420***
30 mm – 0 mm	4885	4275	114,27	610***
20 mm – 10 mm	4695	4464	105,17	231**
30 mm – 10 mm	4885	4464	109,43	421***
30 mm – 20 mm	4885	4695	104,05	190*

Regarding the individual effect of the varieties, the leaf surface recorded an amplitude of 15 cm²) and very low variability, with limits from 4572 cm² in the case of Stanley seedlings to 4587 cm² in the case of Cacanska Lepotica. Thus, at the level of the entire experience, it is confirmed that, against the background of the climatic conditions in field II, the variety did not significantly influence the development of the leaf apparatus in the seedlings.

Table 3

The Average Leaf Surface of the Seedlings of the Two Varieties in the Second Field – Individual Effect

Variety	Leaf surface (cm ²)		Relative values (%)	Difference/Significance
Cacanska Lepotica				
Stanley	4587	4572	100,33	15

Considering the effect of the interaction between the varieties and irrigation on the leaf surface of the seedlings in field II, it follows that in the case of the Cacanska Lepotica variety, the three watering norms generated significant variations compared to the non-irrigated variant. against the background of statistically ensured differences and between watering rules.

The seedlings of the Stanley variety efficiently utilized only the norms of 20 and 30 mm which determined significant increases of this character compared to the control variant, while the effect of the norm of 10 mm was insignificant and less than in the Cacanska Lepotica variety.

Considering the interaction between irrigation and leaf surface in the seedlings of the Stanley variety, it is observed that only irrigations with 20-30 mm allowed a significant variation of 7.76-11.7%, while the effect of the watering rate of 10 mm was smaller and insignificant. Also, only increasing the watering rate from 10 to 30 mm determined a significant increase of 7.18% of this character.

Under the effect of different watering norms, the seedlings of the Cacanska Lepotica variety recorded a leaf surface with limits from 4234 cm² in the case of the non-irrigated variant, to 4821 cm² in the 30 mm variant, against the background of a variability between treatments of 9.5%. Compared to the non-irrigated agrofund, in the seedlings of this variety, the three watering norms generated significant increases of 4.61-16.86%. The progressive modification of the watering norm by 10 mm determined significant variations of this character of 210-309 cm².

Table 4
The Effect of Irrigation and Variety on the Leaf Surface in the Second Field

Variety	Irrigation rate				S%
	0 mm	10 mm	20 mm	30 mm	
Stanley	z 4316 a	yz 4498 a	xy 4651 a	x 4821 a	4572±41
Cacanska Lepotica	u 4234 a	z 4429 a	y 4738 a	x 4948 a	4587±49
	4275±44	4464±46	4695±54	4885±62	4580±32
S%	6,46	6,52	7,32	8,06	8,73

The relationship between the watering rate and the variation of the leaf surface in the Cacanska Lepotica seedlings is highlighted with a precision of approximately 99.25% by means of an exponential function. Thus, against the background of average values of 4226 cm² in the absence of irrigation, the average growth rate of this character was 16.83 cm²/mm of watering, with small variations from one norm to another (15.3-18.2 cm²/mm of watering).

CONCLUSIONS

In the seedlings of the Cacanska Lepotica variety, irrigation had a higher effect on the leaf surface. Regarding the individual effect of the

varieties, the leaf surface recorded an amplitude of 15 cm²) and very low variability, with limits from 4572 cm² in the case of Stanley seedlings to 4587 cm² in the case of Cacanska Lepotica. Considering the effect of the interaction between the varieties and irrigation on the leaf surface of the seedlings in field II, it follows that in the case of the Cacanska Lepotica variety, the three watering norms generated significant variations compared to the non-irrigated variant. against the background of statistically ensured differences and between watering rules. The seedlings of the Stanley variety efficiently utilized only the norms of 20 and 30 mm which determined significant increases of this character compared to the control variant, while the effect of the norm of 10 mm was insignificant and less than in the Cacanska Lepotica variety. Under the effect of different watering norms, the seedlings of the Cacanska Lepotica variety recorded a leaf surface with limits from 4234 cm² in the case of the non-irrigated variant, to 4821 cm² in the 30 mm variant, against the background of a variability between treatments of 9.5%. Compared to the non-irrigated agrofund, in the seedlings of this variety, the three watering norms generated significant increases of 4.61-16.86%. The progressive modification of the watering norm by 10 mm determined significant variations of this character of 210-309 cm².

REFERENCES

- Faulkner N., 2022. Principles of Irrigation, Syrawood Publishing House, 97-98
- Goyal M., 2021. Closed Circuit Trickle Irrigation Design: Theory and Applications- Research Advances in Sustainable Micro Irrigation, Apple Academic Press, 90-91
- Kun A. & co., 2022. Root Yield and Sugar Accumulation in Sugarbeet and Fodder Beet According to Irrigation Water Quality, MDPI article, Agronomy, 123-125
- Novelli S., 2022. External Benefits of Irrigation in Mountain Areas: Stakeholder Perceptions and Water Policy Implications, MDPI article, Agriculture, 74-76
- Panigrahi B., 2020. Handbook on Irrigation and Drinage, NIPA Press, 37-39
- Sela G, 2020. Fertilization and irrigation, Cropaia Press, 23-25
- Steele A., 2015. Drip Irrigation: Technology, Management and Efficiency, NOVA Press, 167-168
- Twomey D., 2016. Irrigation Engineering, Apple Academic Press, 74-75
- Zai S., Feng X., Wang D., 2022. Influence of Micro-Furrow Depth and Bottom Width on Surface Water Flow and Irrigation Performance in the North China Plain, MDPI Article, 245-246

COMPARATIVE RESEARCH ON THE REGENERATION AND ORGANOGENIC CAPACITY OF IN VITRO CULTURES OF *Opuntia fragilis* var. *fragilis*, IN THE PRESENCE IN THE CULTURE MEDIUM OF AUXIN - DICHLORPHENOXYACETIC ACID - 2.4 D (2.5 mg/l) AND OF CYTOQUININE - BENZYLADENINE - BA (2 mg/l)

Iuliana Teodora VIDICAN^{1#}, Alina Ștefania Stanciu¹, Carmen Violeta IANCU¹, Mihai Marcel CĂRBUNAR¹, Andrada-Iulia IENCIU¹, Oana Maria VIDICAN², Ioana Teodora STANCIU²

¹University of Oradea, Faculty of Environmental Protection, Oradea City, Maghru 26, 410087, Romania Institution

²Student of the University of Oradea, Faculty of Environmental Protection, Oradea City, Maghru 26, 410087, Romania Institution

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

Among the 130 genera of the Cactaceae family, the genus *Opuntia* is one of the most studied in the world (Griffith, 2001a, b, 2004; Pinkava, 2002). The species of this genus of cactus are, from an economic point of view, the most widespread and important of the Cactaceae family, the fruits and plant mass are edible (Nobel, 2002; Nobel et al., 2002), they are extremely efficient in transforming water into biomass (Kluge et al., 1978, Griffith, 2004a), being also recognized as an indicator of some noxes (Nobel, 1994). Due to their great adaptability to harsh environmental conditions, cacti belonging to the genus *Opuntia* are found in arid and semi-arid areas used to combat desertification (Le Houérou, 2000; Juárez et al., 2002). There is evidence that *Opuntia* plants (fig.1) have been used by humans for at least 9000 years (Kiesling, 1998).

For the initiation of in vitro cultures of *Opuntia fragilis* var. *fragilis* we sampled stem fragments sectioned into portions approximately 1 cm long and 0.5 cm thick with at least 2-3 areoles. The portions thus taken were deposited on the sterilized culture medium consisting of macroelements and Fe EDTA Murashige-Skoog (1962) microelements Heller (1953), supplemented with 2.5 mg/l 2,4-dichlorophenoxyacetic acid (V_1) and 2 mg/l benzyladenine (V_2).

The evolution of the in vitro cultures was monitored for 90 days. Their response was different, the presence of auxin, respectively, 2.5 mg/l 2,4-D (V_1) in the culture medium determined the formation of new roots 2.3/variant, respectively an increase of 35.29% with a length average of the largest generated root of 4.7 cm, an increase of 38.23%, also being the only variant on which callus formation was observed, with 1.4 calluses/variant and an average diameter of 2, 4 cm. The favorable effect of cytokinin was noted by the formation of new strains in the medium supplemented with 2 mg/l BA (V_2) where we recorded 3.7 newly formed strains/variant, so an increase of 64.28% with an average length of 6.5 cm, respectively an increase of 91.17, all data were reported to the control group lacking growth regulators (V_0).

Keywords: Rhizogenesis, caulogenesis, callus, phytoinoculation.

#Corresponding author: iuliateodora68@yahoo.com

INTRODUCTION

Auxins, along with cytokinins, belong to the category of growth regulators or phyto regulators, organic compounds with mimetic phytohormonal effects (Cachiță, 1987; Cachiță et al., 2004).

Fig.1. Image representing the cactus *Opuntia fragilis* var. *fragilis*, where: a-stems; b-flower; c-fruit; d-areoles; e-thorns.

Auxins have a rhizogenic action (Cachiță et al., 2004), according to Sandra Aparecida et

al., 1996, the addition of dichlorophenoxyacetic acid (2,4-D) to the culture medium is highly effective in rhizogenesis and callus formation, which subsequently it can be detached, cut and then transferred to a fresh culture medium to obtain seedlings, but in higher concentrations it becomes toxic.

The addition of benzyladenine (BA) boosts the formation of buds at the inoculum level, from which new stems will be generated (Mauseth, 1976), exerting an antagonistic effect on auxins, inhibiting rhizogenesis (Cachiță et al., 2004). In in vitro cactus cultures, it is considered that, in order to multiply plant material, the most effective growth regulator to generate new stems is BA (Escobar et al., 1986).

The aim of this research is to study how the presence in the culture medium of an amount of 2.5 mg/l 2,4 dichlorophenoxyacetic acid (2,4 D) and 2 mg/l benzyladenine (BA) influences the regenerative capacity and organogen of vitroplants of *Opuntia fragilis* var. *fragilis*, knowing that it is believed that cacti invariably induce organogenesis processes when they are grown on media supplemented with growth regulators (Copăceacu, 2001).

MATERIAL AND METHOD

To initiate *in vitro* cultures of *Opuntia fragilis* var. *fragilis* i keep prelevet strains with mature areolas but with less thorns trainers, shorts and white. The material so obtained was sectioned transverse operation which resulted in sliced washers that were divided so that eventually fragments were inoculated following dimensions: about 1 cm long and 0,5 cm thick, yet have minimum 2-3 areola. After these operations we obtain the explants from mid dial and lateral (Fig. 2).

Fig.2. Schematic representation of *Opuntia fragilis* var. *fragilis* young stems (a, b), and how slicing it into rings ellipsoid (c) and lateral explants inoculated on media centers and aseptic (d), where: ar - areola.

Knowing that *in vitro* cultures of naturally occurring cacti - the areola - some long hairs and bristles, host parties for a variety of organisms (Garcia-Saucedo et al., 2005), sanitized of plant material was achieved by submersare for one minute at 96 ° alcohol, followed by the coating process it with a solution of 0.8% sodium hypochlorite mixed with water in a ratio of 1:2, which were added three drops of Tween 20 as surfactant (Cachiță et al., 2004). Sanitized lasted 20 minutes, during which the plant material was continuously stirred. After decanting disinfectant plant material was washed with sterile distilled water to remove chlorine, achieving five consecutive rinses, of five minutes each.

After sterilization, the plant material was deposited in Petri capsules on filter paper discs (previously sterilized in the oven) in a laminar

flow hood, horizontal air sterile operation, followed by sizing operation and future inocula removal of necrotic parts thereof.

The culture medium used for the growth of explants consisted of: macro Murashige-Skoog EDTA and Fe (1962), trace elements Heller (1953), mineral mixture to which vitamins were added: pyridoxine HCl, thiamine HCl and nicotinic acid (containing 1 mg/l each), m-inositol - 100 mg/l, sucrose - 20 g/l and agar 7 g/l the pH of the medium was adjusted to a value of 5.8, its first autoclaving. In the basic medium (MB) shown, we added 2.5 mg/l 2,4-D and 2 mg/l BA, obtaining the following variants: V_0 - control, medium without growth regulators and V_1 - supplemented medium with 2.5 mg/l 2,4-D and V_2 - medium supplemented with 2 mg/l BA.

The culture medium was placed in a glass vial with a capacity of 15 ml (each container was placed 5 ml of medium). Medium vials were sterilized for 30 minutes, by autoclaving at a temperature of 121°C. After cooling media proceeded to inoculate explants, aseptic room operation performed in a laminar flow hood with sterile air. To obstruction fitoinoculi containers we used polyethylene, immobilized with elastic.

Containers inocula were transferred to room for growth, under the following conditions: temperature ranged from 24°C in peroadă light and 20° during the phase of darkness and light was the regime fotoperiodic 16 hours lumină/24h, lighting cultures achieving is the white light emitted by fluorescent lamps, the intensity of 1700 lux.

Reaction and evolution of explants was monitored for 90 days. In this time period were conducted periodic observations and readings every 30 days. Values recorded biometric control group (V_0 , fitoinoculi grown on basic medium, without growth regulators) were considered the reference as 100% being reported - every trait - all readings averaged every experimental variant part.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Comparing the results obtained on this date, it is found that the average length of the main stem both at the level of the phytoinocula of the variant V_1 (medium supplemented with 2.5 mg/l 2,4-D) and V_2 (medium supplemented with 2 mg/l BA) was located 0.3 cm (Fig. 4A) above the value of the same parameter recorded in the control group V_0 (medium without growth regulators), which represented

an increase of 18.75% (Fig. 5A). Values that, statistically, are considered to be distinctly significant (Table 1).

It is noted that the addition of BA in the culture medium exerted a stimulating effect on the caulogenesis of vitro cultures of *Opuntia fragilis* var. *fragilis*, the average number of cauline neoformations exceeded the values of the similar biometric parameter in the control variant V_0 (medium without growth regulators) which with 1.4 new stems/variant is 35.72%

below the value of this parameter in the explants of the V_2 variant (medium supplemented with 2 mg/l BA) with 3.7 kaolin neoformations/variant (Fig. 4B), while in the experimental variant V_1 (medium supplemented with 2.5 mg/l 2,4-D) an average number of 0.9 cauline neoformations/variant (Fig. 4B), thus registering a deficit of 35.72% (Fig. 5B), in relation to the values of the same parameter recorded in the control group V_0 .

Fig.3. Inoculi de *Opuntia* (Tournef.) Mill. *fragilis* var. *fragilis*, la 90 de zile de la inocularea explantului „in vitro”, unde: A-mediul de bază modificat de noi și lipsit de regulatori de creștere (V_0); B-mediul de bază cu adaos de 2,5 mg/l 2,4-D (V_1); C-mediul de bază cu adaos de 2 mg/l BA (V_2); (iiv–inocul inițial viabil; mc–mediu de cultură; nc–tulpini noi; rd–rădăcini; ar–areole; sp–spini; cl–calus; mg–mugurași).

And regarding the average length of the largest newly formed stem, the addition of auxin, 2.5 mg/l 2,4-D (V_1) determined a minus of 0.2 cm (Fig. 4C) in relation to those 3.2 cm recorded in the control V_0 (medium without growth regulators), which represents a deficit of 5.89% (Fig. 40C), while the presence in the

culture medium of 2 mg/l BA (V_2) also stimulated the increase in the length of the newly formed stems up to an average value of this parameter of 6.5 cm (Fig. 4C), recording an increase of 91.17 (Fig. 5C), These results are considered, from the point of view of statistically, as being very significant (Table 1).

Table 1. The results of the biometric evaluations of the in vitro seedlings from 90 days after the inoculation of the explants on basic aseptic media (V_0) with the addition of 2.5 mg/l 2.4 D (V_1) and 2 mg/l BA (V_2)

Parameter	The average length of the main stem		Average number of newly formed stems +/- Standard deviation		Average length of the largest newly formed stem +/- Standard deviation		Average number of new roots +/- Standard deviation		Average length of the largest newly formed root +/- Standard deviation		Average number of calluses +/- Standard deviation		The average diameter of calluses +/- Standard deviation	
	Standard deviation	Significance	Standard deviation	Significance	Standard deviation	Significance	Standard deviation	Significance	Standard deviation	Significance	Standard deviation	Significance	Standard deviation	Significance
Alternative														
90 days														
V_0	1,60±0,15	0,0211 ***	1,40±0,45	0,2042 **	3,40±0,32	0,1053 ***	1,70±0,29	0,0800 ***	3,40±0,29	0,0863 ***	0	0	0	0
V_1	1,90±0,40	0,1537 **	0,90±0,33	0,1079 *	3,20±0,84	0,7084 **	2,30±0,53	0,2763 **	4,70±0,75	0,5631 ***	1,40±0,25	0,0632 **	2,40±0,30	0,0895 ***
V_2	1,90±0,36	0,1305 **	3,70±0,60	0,3505 ***	6,50±0,61	0,3684 ***	2,60±0,62	0,3790 **	3,40±0,68	0,4558 **	0	0	0	0

Legend: *** very significant ** distinctly significant * significant NS insignificant

Fig.4. The graphic presentation of the average values, in absolute values, corresponding to the biometric parameters at the level of vitro cultures of *Opuntia* (Tournef.) Mill. *fragilis* var. *fragilis*, on a base aseptic medium modified by us - (variant V0), with the addition of 2.5 mg/l 2,4-D (variant V1) and 2 mg/l BA (variant V2), data expressed in absolute values; (where: A-average length of the main stem; B-average number of new stems; C-average length of the largest new stem; D-average number of roots; E-average length of the largest root; F-number callus average; G-average callus diameter.

Following the results obtained, it can be said that the presence of cytokinin in the culture medium - in the case of this experiment of benzyladenine (BA) added in concentrations of 2 mg/l (V2) - a greater number of new strains/variant is also obtained, and the length of the shoots on the explant is considerably longer, results similar to those reported by Vidican et al., 2010, also, the results obtained allow us to consider that we are in agreement with the reports made by Khalafalla et al., 2007, which reached the conclusion that the most effective culture medium in terms of the number and length of shoots in vitro cultures of *Cactacaea*, is the medium supplemented with benzyladenine (BA), these parameters reaching the maximum value at a concentration of 5.0 mg/l BA. I also noted that the presence of BA in the culture medium represented a favorable stimulus that determined the swelling of 100% of the areoles, differentiating a variable number of buds from them, an aspect also noted by Juárezi et al., (2002).

The newly formed stems from the explants grown on mediums lacking growth regulators as well as those supplemented with BA cytokinin or 2,4 D auxin maintain their

intense green color, and the areoles are well developed, the long, white spikes that keep the same fluffy appearance (Fig.3). However, it was found that, in the control group without growth regulators (V0) and in the one supplemented with 2 mg/l BA (V2), the stems have a much higher number of thorns (Fig.3) compared to the stems regenerated from the explants cultivated on medium with 2.5 mg/l 2,4-D (V1) in which the thorns - modified leaves - were much rarer, but quite long, a fact that could be a consequence of the "defoliation" action that auxin 2,4-D - a herbicide with a defoliating effect - to have exercised it in this case (Fig. 3), also, the presence of a large number of buds can be found at their level. It should be noted that in the explants grown on medium supplemented with 2 mg/l BA (V2), first-order ramifications were generated at the neostem level.

Regarding rhizogenesis, at this time it was noted that this phenomenon was manifested in all the experimental variants studied. The average number of roots generated at the level of explants grown on medium supplemented with 2.5 mg/l 2,4-D (V1), was 0.6 roots/variant above the value of the same parameter recorded in the control

group V_0 (medium without growth regulators) Fig. 4D), which represents an increase of 35.29% (Fig. 5D), while at the level of explants of *Opuntia fragilis* var. *fragilis* grown on medium supplemented with 2 mg/l BA (V_2) was 2.6 roots/variant, respectively an increase of 52.94% (Fig.5D). These differences, from a statistical point of view, are considered to be distinctly significant (Table 1).

The presence of 2,4-D auxin in a concentration of 2.5 mg/l (V_1) in the culture medium also positively influenced the growth in length of the newly formed roots, thus the average length of the largest root - in absolute values - exceeded the value recorded by this parameter in the control group by 1.3 cm (Fig. 4E), marking an increase of 38.23% (Fig. 5E); these differences are considered, from a statistical point of view, to be very significant (Table 1). It is found that this parameter had an average absolute value of 3.4 cm in the case of explants of *Opuntia fragilis* var. *fragilis*

inoculated and grown on culture media supplemented with 2.0 mg/l BA (V_2) so they managed to equal the control V_0 (Fig.4E).

In the phytoinoculi grown on culture medium supplemented with 2.0 mg/l BA (V_2) but also in the control sample V_0 (medium without growth regulators) (Fig.3), callus formation was not observed. In the explants of *Opuntia fragilis* var. *Fragile*. The presence in the acid culture medium of 2.5 mg/l 2,4-D (V_1) had a stimulatory effect on callusogenesis which was manifested only at the level of explants grown on this medium where 1.4 callus/variant were generated, a 140% increase compared to the control group V_0 (medium without growth regulators) (Fig. 4F); this growing until they reached an average diameter of 2.4 cm, respectively an increase of 240% (Fig. 5G). These results are considered, from a statistical point of view, to be very significant (Table 1).

In the case of our experiment, the callus generated at the explant level of *Opuntia fragilis* var. *fragilis* inoculated and grown on culture medium supplemented with 2.5 mg/l 2,4-D (V_1) either due to the abundance it covered the entire surface of the nutrient substrate (Fig. 41B), in which case it shows signs of early semiescence - fact highlighted by the cream

color - it was located at the base of the neostems in the form of opalescent, friable, pale green tissue (Fig.3).

CONCLUSIONS

From the data monitored and examined for 90 days, we found the particularly favorable effect of benzyladenine (BA) on caulogenesis in vitro cultures of *Opuntia fragilis* var. *fragile*. The

explants inoculated and grown on culture medium supplemented with 2 mg/l BA (V₂), were distinguished by the most new strains/variant, respectively by 164.28% above the values recorded in the control lot compared to the phytoinocula belonging to the V₁ variant (culture medium supplemented with 2.5 mg/l 2,4-D) where an increase of 64.28% was marked.

The average length of the largest newly formed shoot is also found in the explants grown on culture medium supplemented with 2 mg/l BA (V₂) which, with 6.5 cm, registered an increase of 91.17% compared to the control group without of growth regulators (V₀) compared to 3.2 cm the value of the same parameter in the phytoinocula belonging to the V₁ variant (culture medium supplemented with 2.5 mg/l 2,4-D), which represents a deficit of 5.89%.

Rhizogenesis is a phenomenon manifested in all the experimental variants studied, thus with an average number of 2.3 roots/variant, the explants grown on culture medium supplemented with 2.5 mg/l 2,4-D (V₁) exceeded the control by 35.29% compared to 2.6 roots/variant in the explants on culture medium supplemented with 2 mg/l BA (V₂) which represents an increase of 52.94%. The presence of auxin in the culture medium positively influenced the length of the largest root, so in the explants of variant V₁ (culture medium supplemented with 2.5 mg/l 2,4-D) it was 4.7 cm, an increase of 38.23%, compared to 3.4 cm in V₂ (culture medium supplemented with 2 mg/l BA) which equaled the control.

The presence in the culture medium of 2,4-dichlorophenoxyacetic acid (2,4-D) had a stimulating effect on callusogenesis, only at the level of the explants grown on this medium (V₁) 1.4 calluses/variant were generated, which grew until they reached an average diameter of 2.4 cm.

REFERENCES

- Cachiță C.D., C.Deliu, R.L. Tican., A. Ardelean, 2004. Plant biotechnology treated vol.I, Editura Dacia, Cluj-Napoca, p. 29-154;
- Copăcescu V.S., 2001, *Cactus, monography*; Ceres Publishing House, Bucuresti, p. 11-517;
- Escobar H.A., V.M. Villalobos, A. Villegas, 1986, *Opuntia* micropropagation by axillary proliferation. Plant Cell Tissue Org. Cult., vol. 7, p. 269-277;
- Griffith M. P., 2001a, A new Chihuahuan Desert prickly pear, *Opuntia x rooneyi*. Cactus and Succulent Journal (U.S.A.), vol. 73, p. 307-310;
- Griffith M. P., 2001b, Experimental hybridization in northern Chihuahuan desert region *Opuntia*. Aliso, vol. 20, p. 37-42;
- Griffith M.P., 2004a, The origins of an important cactus crop, *Opuntia ficus-indica* (Cactaceae): new molecular evidence. American Journal of Botany, vol. 91, p. 1915-1921;
- Griffith M.P., 2004b, What did the first cactus look like? An attempt to reconcile the morphological and molecular evidence. Taxon, vol. 53, p. 493-499;
- Heller R., 1953, Recherches sur la nutrition minérale des tissus végétaux cultivés *in vitro*. Ann.Sci. Nat. Bot. Veg. Ser., vol. II, p. 1-5 ;
- Juarezi, M.C., Passera C.B., 2002, In vitro propagation of *Opuntia ellisiana* Griff. and acclimatization to field conditions. Biocell, vol. 26, p. 319-324;
- Khalafalla, M.M., Abdellatef, E., Mohameed Ahmed M.M., Osman, M.G., 2007, Micropropagation of cactus (*Opuntia ficus-indica*) as strategic tool to combat desertification in arid and semi arid regions. Commission for Biotechnology and Genetic Engineering, National Centre for Research, Khartoum, Sudan, Int. J. Sustain. Crop Prod., vol. 2, nr. 4, p. 1-8;
- Kiesling R., 1998, Origen, domesticación y distribución de *Opuntia ficus-indica*. Jurnal of the Professional Association for Cactus Development, Instituto de Botánica Darwinion C. C., San Isidro – Argentina, vol. 22, nr. 1642 p. 1-9;
- Kluge M., I.P. Ting, 1978, Crassulacean acid metabolism: an ecological analysis, Springer-Verlag, Berlin, Germany, *Ecological studies*, vol. 114, p. 324-335;
- Kluge M., Ting I.P., 1978, Crassulacean acid metabolism: an ecological analysis, Springer-Verlag, Berlin, Germany, *Ecological studies*, vol. 114, p. 324-335;
- Le Houérou H.N., 2000, Utilization of fodder trees and shrubs in the arid and semiarid zones of west Asia and north. Africa, Arid soil Res. and Rehabilitation, vol. 14, p. 101-135;
- Mauseth J.D., 1976, Cytokinin and gibberellic acid-induced effects on the structure and metabolism of shoot apical meristems in *Opuntia polyacantha* (Cactaceae). American Journal of Botany, vol. 63, p. 1295-1301;
- Murashige T., F. Skoog, 1962, A revised medium for rapid growth and bioassays with tobacco tissue cultures. *Physiologia Plantarum*, vol. 15, p. 473 – 497;
- Nobel P.S., 1994, Remarkable agaves and cacti. Oxford University Press, New York Environmental biology, p. 36-48.
- Nobel P.S., 2002, *Cacti: biology and uses*. University of California, Berkeley, California, USA , p. 57-74;
- Nobel P.S., De la Barrera E., Beilman D.W., Doherty J.H., Zutta B.R., 2002, Temperature limitations for cultivation of edible cacti in California. Madroño, vol. 49, p. 228-236;
- Pinkava D.J., 2002, On the evolution of continental North American *Opuntioideae*. Succulent Plant Research, vol. 6, p. 59-98;
- Sandra Aparecida O., Silva Machado M.F.P., Claudete Aparecida M.A. J.P., 1996, Micropropagation of *Cereus peruvianus* mill. (Cactaceae) by areole activation. In Vitro Cellular & Developmental Biology – Plant, Springer Berlin/ Heidelberg, vol. 32, nr. 3, p. 47-50;
- Vidican I.T., Cachiță C.D., 2010, Initiation of *Opuntia fragilis* var. *fragilis*, „*in vitro*” cultures. Studia Universitatis „Vasile Goldiș” Arad. Ser. Științele Vieții, vol 20, Ed. „Vasile Goldiș” University Press Arad, nr.3, 35-40

THE MARKET OF EDIBLE MUSHROOMS FROM THE SPONTANEOUS FLORA OF ROMANIA

Ruben BUDĂU^{1#}

^{1#} University of Oradea, Faculty of Environmental Protection, 26 General Magheru St., 410048 Oradea, Romania

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

Edible mushrooms from the spontaneous flora of Romania are characterized by special attention on the internal and European market. This attention is due primarily to the nutritional qualities that they contain, but also because they are harvested from an environment of a natural nature, free of pollutants. In general, edible mushrooms derived from spontaneous flora, are seasonal mushrooms, which by their nutritional value contribute both to the economic circuit and to the diversity of natural products rich in nutrients. The main objective of this work was to identify the main edible mushrooms harvested from the spontaneous flora of Romania, mushrooms that are of major interest for the Romanian market, as well as for the European market, followed by the average purchase value, the areas of provenance, packaging, and the delivery market. The data present in this study are data taken between 2019 and 2022. The value of non-wood forest products such as mushrooms is a dynamic of interest for the most harvested and marketed edible mushrooms by private entrepreneurs, as well as average purchase prices, identified areas with high harvest potential and packaging and delivery preferences.

Keywords: spontaneous flora, non-wood forest products, edible mushrooms, truffles, boletus
#Corresponding author: rubenbudau2014@gmail.com

INTRODUCTION

Due to the high nutritional value of edible mushrooms, their use in human food nutrition is of increased interest both for cultivated mushrooms and especially for mushrooms that come from spontaneous flora. The food consumption of edible mushrooms is quite widespread in Romania (Łuczaj Ł et al, 2015., Nicola S et al, 2021), the mycological background in the flora of our country is rich and varied, of about 1600 spontaneous species, of which only 400 are edible (Şesan T. E., Tănase C., 2004). Among those mentioned above in Romania was issued in 2019, Order no. 768/2019 on the amendment of the annex to the Order of the Minister of Agriculture, Forests and Rural Development no. 246/2006 for the establishment of the List of edible mushrooms from spontaneous flora whose harvesting or acquisition and marketing are premises (Romania 2019).

The final list officially lists 43 edible mushrooms which can be harvested from spontaneous flora and marketed to the final consumer. According to the Products and Services Catalog of the National Forest Administration, edible mushrooms are among the most appreciated natural products from the spontaneous flora of the Romanian forest fund.

Mushrooms from spontaneous flora are among the most important non-wood forest products, over 3000 species being consumed worldwide and over 100 being of great importance in medicine and the fight against several diseases (VASILE D., DINCĂ L., ENESCU C.M., 2017)

The main objective of this work was to identify which are the most appreciated, consumed, and marketed mushrooms in the current context of the market of edible mushrooms from the spontaneous flora of Romania, as well as their commercial value, starting with the average purchase prices in the last four years, respectively the main areas in Romania from which mushrooms are collected.

At European level, Romania is known for its organic products such as mushrooms and berries. Romania must develop policies that benefit these products, the EU being a free trade area, stimulating economic growth and promoting trade (Dehousse, 2005 quoted by Timofte, 2016).

MATERIAL AND METHOD

For the current study, data have been taken in the form of a questionnaire, for the period 2019-2022, to the main entrepreneurs who purchase the edible mushrooms and sell them to the final consumer in Romania and the European Union.

The questionnaire was attended by 18 companies, which purchase, sort, process and deliver in different forms, edible mushrooms harvested from the spontaneous flora of Romania.

The questionnaire included:

- the official list of the 43 edible mushrooms whose harvesting or acquisition and marketing are prerequisites, according to Order no. 768/2019 on the amendment of the annex to the Order of the Minister of Agriculture, Forests and Rural Development no. 246/2006.
- a grid of the average purchase price in the period 2019-2022.
- a grid of the final form in which the edible mushrooms are delivered to the consumer.
- a grid of edible mushroom harvesting areas
- a grid of the main delivery areas
- a grid about the packaging and storage of edible mushrooms

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Following the interpretation of the results in Figure 1, the main edible mushrooms harvested from spontaneous flora, mushrooms that are of interest for the Romanian local market and especially for the European one, are presented. This graph is based on the information provided by the purchasers and is correlated with the requirements of the consumer market.

At the top of the list of edible mushrooms are mushrooms known locally and under names such as buckwheat, hribi or porcini, (*Boletus sp.*).

This is also affirmed by Kovalčík M., 2014, who stated that the harvest rate at the mushroom picking is mainly related to *Boletus sp.*

The mushrooms of the *Boletus sp.* category are the most appreciated and marketed mushrooms being thus on the first place, we can also say that these mushrooms have a tradition, highly appreciated among gourmets, due to their taste, nutritional values and especially the form of presentation.

Also, in the first category of edible mushrooms of high interest we mention the mushrooms *Amanita cesarela* and *Craterellus cibarius* but compared to that of mushrooms of the *Boletus sp.* category, the interest for these mushrooms is at least 30% below its value.

The authors of Cioacă L., Enescu C.M., 2018 state that in the period 2012-2017 the three fungi *Craterellus cibarius*, *Amanita cesarela* and *Boletus edulis* had the highest quantities recorded in terms of volume harvested from the spontaneous flora of edible mushrooms.

Truffles (*Tuber sp.*) are also of medium to high interest to the market, being considered luxury culinary mushrooms. The specific legislation in Romania provides clear notions of harvesting and valorization, but requires high knowledge about this fungus, requiring trained dogs for their identification, as well as special tools for harvesting them. Now we could only identify medium interest for this type of fungus, but without statistical data indicating the quantity harvested and officially marketed, however, the most significant signals are from the eastern part of Romania where it seems that the willing companies assign on a contractual basis the areas where these mushrooms can be harvested with the help of specialized dogs and based on the authorizations and legislation in force.

Figure 1. The main edible mushrooms that are of interest to the Romanian market and the EU.

The average purchase price, it is directly influenced by the season in which we can have the harvest of edible mushrooms from spontaneous flora. This season does not have a precise date, but it is included in the spring-autumn period of a calendar year between May

and November, being directly influenced by atmospheric precipitation, heat, woody plant species, relief, etc.

Unequivocally the highest price we have identified in the fungi of the *Tuber sp. category*. The low production of edible mushrooms, as happened in the 2021 season, has put a huge pressure on the purchase price of the main edible mushrooms coming from the spontaneous flora *Boletus sp.* as evidenced by Figure No. 2. which can be easily explained, the poorer the season is in the mushroom harvest, the purchase price increases in relation to the market requirement.

The average purchase price for *Boletus sp.* was 18 €/kg in the 2021 season, a price that remains a record for this category. In the year 2022, the average minimum price is a price is influenced by the abundant harvest in the season between August and September, so it had the average value of € 3 / kg, being the lowest price compared to all other seasons taken in the current study.

The harvesting of the *Boletus sp.* takes place in late spring until late autumn (Beldeanu E.C., 2004) in dry weather. The pedo-climatic conditions that are quite favorable, but also the diversity of forest species known to be the symbiosis between fungi and trees, allow to achieve impressive amounts of buckwheat annually, when the temperature and humidity conditions are met.

Figure 2. Average purchase price for the most appreciated mushrooms (2019-2022)

The category of mushrooms of medium interest as shown in Figure 3 reconfirms the 2021 season when the production of mushrooms was very low, which is why the price in some cases such as that of *Armillaria mellea* and *Morchella conica* mushroom, the purchase price has doubled thus reaching an average price between 4.5 and 5 €/kg, compared to the 2019, 2020 seasons, and the overproduction in 2022 practically significantly

reduces this price, thus reaching average prices between 1.4 and 2 €/kg.

The average purchase price for traditionally sun-dried mushrooms in the category *Boletus sp. mushrooms* in the case of purchase from peasant households in Romania, at the level of 2022 it is around 45 – 55 €/kg.

Mauro R.F., et al.,2022 in the study on the labelling and content of products of the *Boletus sp. category* states that the buying-in price for dried mushrooms in Spain was between €30/kg and €295/kg.

Figure 3. Average purchase price for mushrooms of medium interest (2019-2022)

For mushrooms in the category of low market interest, the average purchase price does not exceed the value of € 2 / kg, but it has not fallen below the value of € 1 / kg, which allows us to state that in the case of these edible mushrooms the price keeps a constant, a slight increase being influenced in this category in the 2021 season, as shown in Figure No 4.

Figure 4. Average purchase price for mushrooms of low interest (2019-2022)

About the areas where edible mushrooms grow, Enescu C.M., 2022 states that superior mushrooms grow in deciduous, resinous, or mixed forests, through meadows, pastures, and orchards, being found from the lowlands to the

mountain hollows, at different altitudes and latitudes, where they find favorable conditions of humidity and heat.

In the case of truffles, the author of Romanian origin, Duck N., 2015 states that the main forest species where he found truffles were: hazelnut, Tartar maple, hornbeam, edible chestnut, sky, wild cherry, horn, beech, common ash, sessile oak, jugaster, birch, hawthorn, black pine, white poplar, trembling poplar, pedunculated oak, linden with large leaf, generally truffles being found much easier in mixed forests.

Following the centralized data on the areas of origin of the edible mushrooms, it emerged that the main areas from which the edible mushrooms are harvested are in the counties of Arad, Argeş, Bihor, Cluj, Bistrița Năsăud, Sălaj, Braşov, Hunedoara, Satu Mare, Harghita, Covasna, Dolj, Gorj, Vâlcea, Suceava, Botoşani, Piatra Neamţ and Bacău.

In the case of truffles (*Tuber sp.*) the region with a high impact is represented by the eastern part of Romania, especially in the counties of Piatra Neamţ, Suceava, Iaşi, Bacau, press sources report annually that this valuable fungus is illicitly marketed, but also in Bihor as concluded by Timiş-Gânsac Voichița et al, 2018.

Figure 5. Mushrooms marketed fresh on the shelf (a. - *Craterellus cibarius*; b- *Armillaria mellea.*) and cleaned according to customer requests (c- *Craterellus cibarius.*)

After the purchase of fresh mushrooms, they are marketed to consumers in several forms:

- chilled (kept immediately after harvesting at a temperature of 2-4°C and delivered under these temperature conditions), it is worth mentioning that the mushrooms must be stored as short a period as possible after harvesting in a cold space, and the storage space must also have useful ventilation for the storage period.

- in some cases such as that of the marigolds (*Craterellus cibarius*) for delivery in their fresh form (Figure No 5), the mushrooms are cleaned and washed, thus reaching the recipient in the cleanest possible form;

- in the case of gherkins (*Boletus sp.*) they are in most cases supplied as they are harvested or according to customer preferences are easily cleaned from the humus part (Figure no.6) or are cleaned and cut in cubic form (Figure no.7).

Figure 6. *Boletus sp.* in wooden crates prepared for the expedition

Figure 7. Delivery method of *Boletus sp.* wash and cut into cubic forms

- another way the mushrooms are delivered is to cut into slices and dry them. The drying process can be carried out in special furnaces for this process but also naturally, in the sun (figure no.8), the local communities in most of the areas where buckwheat is harvested, put into practice this process, being known the ratio of 10 kg of fresh mushrooms from *Boletus sp.* quality II and III ultimately equate to 1 kg of dry product.

Figure 8. Drying in the sun of the mushrooms from the *Boletus sp.* group in the Codru Moma Mountains region of Arad County

- the freezing of edible mushrooms (Figure 9) shows another process by which they are stored and transported in different periods of time in different forms (whole, cubes, slices). In the first phase, freezing is carried out at a temperature of -30°C , and for the storage period the temperature of -20°C is used.

Figure 9. Mushrooms (*Boletus sp.*) cleaned and frozen in full form

As far as mushroom packaging is concerned, wooden crates are the most widely used form of packaging for fresh mushrooms refrigerated in a proportion of 75%, and for frozen ones, plastic crates and bags are used (Figure 10).

Figure 10. Sorting and packaging center for edible mushrooms, Beiuș Bihor County.

Local communities (Figure 11) are the first beneficiaries of edible mushrooms, firstly because they are an alternative to food inside a household, and secondly because, from an economic point of view, the harvesting of edible mushrooms is a source of income.

This income resource is welcome for communities in areas where edible mushrooms can be harvested, because in the current context, jobs in rural areas are very few, the migration of young people to large urban areas also has a major impact in terms of potential mushroom pickers, while the population is increasingly ageing.

It is also worth mentioning the average amount that a picker can harvest in a day, in a good season, the quantity harvested can reach 80-100 kg / day, mushrooms from the *Boletus sp.* category, this value is influenced by several factors, such as: knowledge of the areas, the distance from the point of harvest to the reception and season.

Figure 11. Mushroom pickers happy with the harvest.

Non-wood forest products are essential for many industrial branches, as well as for the creation of culinary products and handicraft products (Dincă L., Timiș G.V., 2020), the same authors describing some traditional recipes in which edible mushrooms can be used as a main culinary element.

Regarding the risks regarding the serious intoxications that can occur due to the consumption of fungi, Gawlikowski T, et al., 2015 are of the opinion that the only way to avoid poisoning is to avoid the consumption of toxic species, for this reason the initiation in the recognition of edible mushroom species is good to be carried out both on the basis of specialized guidelines but especially in the presence of people who know this field very well.

Figure 12. Thematic courses on the recognition of edible mushrooms. ([Http:// incredibleromania.com](http://incredibleromania.com)*)

Certainly lately, initiation courses in harvesting and valorization of edible mushrooms are on an upward trend (Figure 12.) as well as the organization of groups of tourists who can stay in rural areas specifically to participate in the identification and harvesting of edible mushrooms from spontaneous flora.

CONCLUSIONS

The dynamics of the edible mushroom market in Romania is influenced by each season depending on the harvest that can be obtained in a certain period.

The most appreciated and marketed edible mushrooms from the forest fund are *Boletus sp.* but without differences between the eight species of *Boletus* being followed by *Craterellus cibarius*, *Armillaria mellea* and obviously those of the truffle group (*Tuber sp.*) mushrooms which fall under the category of luxury products and for which both legislation and harvesting arrangements are more restrictive and knowledge also plays a decisive role in obtaining significant harvests.

Edible mushrooms of medium commercial interest *Armillaria mellea*, *Morchella conica* and *Craterellus cibarius* can also make a significant contribution to the economic circuit, followed by mushrooms in the low interest category that we have identified, but which have a correlation between supply and demand.

The lack of knowledge regarding the identification of these mushrooms is one of the reasons why they are classified in this category, and the purchase price influences in a negative sense most of the time the harvesting of these mushrooms.

Regarding the most favorable areas where edible mushrooms from the spontaneous flora of Romania are harvested and capitalized, these areas are also situated in the counties: Arad, Arges, Bihor, Cluj, Bistrița Năsăud, Sălaj, Brașov, Hunedoara, Satu Mare, Harghita, Covasna, Dolj,

Gorj, Vâlcea, Suceava, Botoșani, Piatra Neamț and Bacău.

In addition to the domestic consumption of edible mushrooms from spontaneous flora, an estimated consumption of 17%, the largest quantity being exported to Italy 37%, Germany 13%, Spain 18%, Austria 8%, and a percentage of 7% to other countries, sometimes even Japan or Canada.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

I would like to thank the Romanian companies, which responded favourably in completing the questionnaires regarding the market for edible mushrooms harvested from spontaneous flora.

REFERENCES

- Beldeanu E. C., 2004. Species of Sanogenous Interest from the Forest Fund. Rîyuts Transilvania University of Brasov.
- Cioacă L., Enescu C.M., 2018. Trends in the evolution of harvesting of non-wood forest products in Romania.
- Dincă L., Timiș Gânsac-Voichița., 2020. The Usage of Non-Wood Forest Products - Culinary and Artisanal Traditions in Romania. Sustainable Development Research; Vol. 2, No. 1; pp.50-57
- Enescu C. M., 2022. Non-wood forest products: course support. Ex Terra Aurum. Bucharest.
- Gawlikowski T, Romek M, Satora L. Poisoning related to edible mushrooms: a study on the circumstances of the collection, transport, and storage of mushrooms. Human and experimental toxicology. 2015;34(7): 93-104. doi:10.1177/0960327114557901
- Kovalčík M., 2014. Value of forest berries and mushrooms picking in Slovakia's forests. Beskydy, 7 (1): 39–46
- Mauro R.F., Alberto O., Paloma M., 2022. It's what's inside those counts: DNA-barcoding of porcini (*Boletus sp.*, Basidiomycota) commercial products reveals product mislabelling. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.foodcont.2022.109346>
- Nicola S., Paolo D., Marco F., Edoardo S., 2021. Motioned leading on edibility of mushrooms.
- Șesan Tatiana Eugenia., Tănase C., 2004. Guide to the recognition of edible and toxic mushrooms. GEEA Bucharest Publishing House.
- Łuczaj Ł., Stawarczyk K., Kosiek T., Pietras M. & Kujawa A. (2015) – Wild food plants and fungi used by Ukrainians in the western part of the Maramureș region in Romania. Acta Societatis Botanicorum Poloniae 84 (3): 339-346.
- Vasile D., Dincă I., Enescu C.M., 2017. Impact of collecting mushrooms from the spontaneous flora on forest ecosystems in Romania.
- Racolța Nicolae., 2015. The truffle picker's guide. Topography OF TECHNO-PRINT Zalău.
- Romania Products and Services Catalogue., National Forest Administration – Romsilva. [chrome-extension://efaidnbmnnnibpcajpcglclefindmkaj/http://www.romsilva.ro/files/content/bucuresti/Catalog-General.pdf](http://www.romsilva.ro/files/content/bucuresti/Catalog-General.pdf)
- Romania (2019): Order no. 768/2019 amending the annex to the Order of the Minister of Agriculture, Forests and Rural Development no. Regulation (EC) No 246/2006 for the establishment of the List of edible mushrooms in spontaneous flora whose harvesting or acquisition and marketing are permitted.
- Timiș-Gânsac Voichița., Enescu C.M., Dincă L., Oneț Aurelia. 2018 The Management Of Non-Wood Forest Products In Bihor County. Natural Resources and Sustainable Development, Vol. 8, No 1 pp.27-34
- Timofte, C.S., 2016. Democracy at the European level. The democratization of the decision-making process in the institutional system of the EU. Editura Scoala Ardeleana Eikon, Cluj-Napoca-București

*<https://incredibleromania.com/curs-de-cuiperce-salbatice-comestibile/>

CONTRIBUTIONS TO THE STUDY OF BEECH STANDS DEVELOPED BY *FAGUS SYLVATICA* AND *FESTUCA DRYMEJA* IN THE WESTERN CARPATHIANS, THE BIHARIA MASSIF, AND THE GAINA MOUNTAIN

Ana-Maria BUIA^{1#}, Petru BURESCU²

¹ University of Oradea Faculty of Medicine and Pharmacy, Doctoral School of Biomedical Sciences, "Piața 1 Decembrie" Square, no 10, Bihor County, Oradea, Romania

² University of Oradea, Faculty of Environmental Protection, Oradea City, Maghru 26, 410087, Romania Institution

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

Phytocoenoses of the *Festuco drymejae-Fagetum* association develop in all the Romanian Carpathians, throughout sites at altitudes between 800 and 1,300 m, peaks with medium to steep slopes ranging from 16° to 36°, with varied exposures. The lithological substrate consists mainly of crystalline shales on which moderately to weakly acidic and slightly moist oligobasic districambosols, formed. The floristic index of the association includes a number of 73 species, which shows a high biodiversity.

The phytocoenoses of this association are dominated by hemicryptophytes (47.94%), followed by geophytes (28.76%) and phanerophytes (15.06%), and with regard the geographical area of the association, Eurasian species are dominant (38.35%), followed by European (20.54%), Central European (13.69%) and Circumpolar (12.32%) species. Regarding the ecological factors, in terms of soil moisture, mesophilic species are dominant (72.59%), with regard the temperature, micro-mesothermic species predominate (56.15%), and as far as the chemical reaction of the soil is concerned, acid-neutrophils (35.61%) are dominant. The karyological spectrum shows that polyploid species are dominant (56.16%), followed by diploids (30.13%). These meadows have a high ecological value since they shelter four rare, endangered species included on the red lists.

The study of this association founded in the surveyed territory - alongside the analysis of bioforms, floristic elements, ecological indices, the economic analysis and the interpretation of cytogenetic character - provides some important information regarding the habitat conditions, and the economic, ecological and scientific relevance of the phytotaxa found in the field.

Keywords: phytocenoses, bioforms, floristic elements, ecological indices, karyotype

#Corresponding author: anamariabuia@yahoo.com

INTRODUCTION

Research on beech stands subordinated to the *Festuco drymejae-Fagetum* association was carried out in the Biharia Massif, the part included in Bihor county and Mount Gaina in Arad county.

From the literature we reviewed, in-depth research papers on beech forests with *Festuca drymeja* were relatively few in Romania namely in: Sinca Noua, Tarcu, Godeanu and Cerna Mountains, Plopis Mountains, Zarandului Mountains, Somesul Cald Valley, Iadului Valley, Transylvania, Piatra Craiului, Cluj County, Bucegi Mountains, Oituz Valley, Tasnad Hills, Codru-Moma Mountains, Orastie Valley river basin, and northern part of Bihor Mountains.

This association spreads widely throughout the surveyed territory, being described in Vartop, Baita, Cristior Valley, Runcului Hills, Lespedioara Peak, Paraul Mare,

the upper basin of Halmagel Valley, Gaina Valley and Leucii Valley.

Research on the flora and vegetation of the forests growing in the areas adjacent to the surveyed territory was carried out on the occasion of incursions and trips made in the territory by the great botanists Marossy (1973, 1975), Boscaiu et Marossy (1979), Ursu et Olaru (), Ursu (2013), the last two paper works being founded on the research conducted in the basin of the Ariesul Mare river and Ariesul Mic river valleys.

The aim of the research was to carry out a phytocenological, ecological and bioeconomic study of the beech stands in the Apuseni Mountains, and in order to achieve this goal we aim to attain several objectives as follows:

- Revealing the floristic composition of the phytocoenoses of the *Festuco drymejae-Fagetum* association,

- Making the ecological characterization of the phytocenoses of the cenose from the perspective of the share of bioforms, floristic elements, ecological indices (soil moisture, air temperature, and chemical reaction of the soil), and genetic karyotype,
- Economic relevance of beech stands and the protective role of the habitat.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The material subjected to research consists of moderately to weakly acidic and slightly moist oligobasic districambosols, formed mainly on crystalline on slopes with predominantly southern exposure, with slopes ranging from 16° to 36°.

We carried out in total 20 phytocenological surveys in the most representative phytocenoses, over the years 2018-2021, and we gathered 10 of them in the association table. In this table (see Table 1) we inputted all the species we found, by corresponding coenotaxonomic units, suballiance, alliance, order, and class according to (Sanda et al., 2008), according to their consistency (K), in accordance with the indications of some famous authors (Borza et Boşcaiu, 1965), (Cristea et al., 2004), while having the ecological-floristic systems criteria elaborated by (Tüxen, 1955), (Braun-Blanquet, 1964), and based on the information from some works published more recently according to the authors (Coldea et al., 1997), (Oberdorfer, 1992), (Borhidi, 2003), (Sanda et al., 2008), (Chifu et al., 2014). The quantitative criterion we pursued in the research of phytocenoses is the abundance and dominance of individuals, according to the system developed by (Braun-Blanquet et Pavillard, 1928), with a grading scale from +,1,2,3,4,5, quantified in percentages ranging from 5 to 100%. We analyzed, and characterized ecologically, phytocenologically and cytogenetically the phytocenosis of the *Festuco drymejae-Fagetum* association based on the association table (see Table 1), and histograms with reference to the distribution of bioforms, floristic elements, ecological indices, and genetic karyotypes.

We found and described the association based on the floristic criterion, with the help of the characteristic, indicator, dominant and differential species. The name of the associations is in accordance with the provisions established by the Code of Phytosociological Nomenclature elaborated by (Weber et al., 2000).

Information on the value of ecological indices, bioforms and phytogeographic elements are presented according to (Sanda et al, 2003), (Meusel et Jäger, 1992), (Cristea et al., 2004), (Burescu et Toma, 2005). Data regarding the karyotype of the species were taken over from (Majovsky et Murin, 1987), (Sanda et al., 2003), (Ciocârlan, 2009), (Moore, 2009).

To assess the economic relevance of plants, we used the information from "Flora României" magazine (1952-1976) as well as information from the work (Ciocârlan, 2009), to which we added our observations and findings regarding the use of plants by the local people, but also the protection role that these beech stands provide.

To establish the status of rare, vulnerable, endangered, endemic species we used the "Red Lists" prepared by (Boşcaiu et al., 1994), (Oltean et al., 1994), (Dihoru et Negrean, 2009), and the "European red list of vascular plants" (Bilz et al., 2011).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The floristic composition of the beech stands with *Carex pilosa* with counts 73 species, showing a high biodiversity. The species developing the phytocenosis are *Fagus sylvatica* and *Festuca drymeja* in a codominance relationship. The remaining species are subordinated to the suballiance *Symphyto Fagenion*, the alliance ***Symphyto Fagenion***, the alliance ***Symphyto cordati-Fagion*** (*Polystichum aculeatum*, *Gymnocarpium dryopteris*, *Euphorbia carniolica*, *Cephalanthera longifolia*, *Epipactis atrorubens*, *Veronica urticifolia*, *Dentaria glandulosa*, *Pulmonaria rubra*), the order ***Fagetalia sylvaticae*** (*Lamium galeobdolon*, *Oxalis acetosella*, *Galium odoratum*, *Dentaria bulbifera*, *Mercurialis perennis*, *Lathraea squamaria*, *Galeopsis speciosa*) and the class ***Quercio-Fagetea*** (*Mycelis muralis*, *Athyrium filix-femina*, *Viola reichenbachiana*, *Scrophularia nodosa*, *Veronica officinalis*, *Brachypodium sylvaticum*). In the association there are found transgressive species from the classes ***Epilobietea angustifolii*** (*Rubus idaeus*, *Solidago virgaurea*, *Atropa belladonna*, *Hypericum perforatum*), ***Betulo-Adenostyletea*** (*Luzula luzuloides*, *Gentiana asclepiadea*, *Petasites albus*, *Doronicum columnae*, *Veratum album*, *Doronicum austriacum*) and ***Vaccinio-Piceetea*** (*Picea abies*, *Dryopteris cristata*, *Luzula sylvatica*, *Vaccinium myrtillus*, *Polytricum commune*).

Table 1

Festuco drymejae-Fagetum Morariu et al. 196

Lifeform	Floristic elements	M	T	R	G	Survey no.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	K	ADm
							Altitude (mamsl)	800	1170	900	980	1130	1190	800	1270	870		
						Exposure	V	SE	SV	S	S	S	SE	E	E	E		
						Slope (°)	30	28	26	18	16	20	70	24	22	36		
						Tree layer density	0.7	0.8	0.7	0.7	0.8	0.7	0.7	0.8	0.7	0.7		
						Tree height (m)	24	20	28	20	24	28	20	20	30	22		
						Tree diameter (cm)	60	40	36	24	28	40	28	24	54	40		
						Tree layer coverage (%)	-	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-		
						Grass layer coverage (%)	20	40	90	80	60	70	30	40	50	70		
						Area (mpx10)	80	120	80	40	80	40	40	80	40	80		
G-H	Ec	4	2	3	D	<i>As. Festuca drimeja</i>	+	4	5	4	2	4	3	1	5	5	V	51.05
MPh	E	3	3	0	D	<i>As. Fagus sylvatica</i>	4	4	4	4	5	4	4	5	5	5	V	72.5
Symphyto fagenion- Symphyto cordati- Fagion																		
H	Eua	3.5	3.5	3.5	P	<i>Polystichum aculeatum</i>	+	.	+	.	+	.	+	.	+	+	III	0.3
MPh	Ec	3.5	3	3	P	<i>Acer pseudoplatanus</i>	.	+	+	.	.	+	.	.	+	.	II	0.2
G	Cp	3	2.5	2	P	<i>Gymnocarpium dryopteris</i>	+	+	.	+	+	.	II	0.2
MPh	Ec	4	3	0	D	<i>Abies alba</i>	.	1	+	I	0.55
H	Alp-Carp-B	3	4	4	DP	<i>Euphorbia carniolica</i>	.	+	I	0.05
G	E	2.5	3	4	P	<i>Cephalantera longifolia</i>	.	+	+	I	0.1
G	Eua	2	0	4.5	P	<i>Epipactis atrorubens</i>	.	.	+	I	0.05
H	Ec	3	2.5	4	D	<i>Veronica uticifolia</i>	+	I	0.05
Fagetalia sylvaticae																		
nPh	E	3	2.5	3	P	<i>Rubus hyrtus</i>	+	.	+	+	+	1	+	+	.	+	IV	0.85
H-Ch	Ec	3	0	4	D	<i>Lamium galeobdolon</i>	+	+	+	.	+	.	+	+	+	+	IV	0.35
G	Eua	3	3	3	P	<i>Galium odoratum</i>	.	+	+	+	+	+	.	.	+	+	IV	0.35
H-G	Cp	4	3	3	D	<i>Oxalis acetosella</i>	+	.	+	.	+	.	.	+	+	+	III	0.3
Th	Eua	3	2	0	D	<i>Galeopsis speciosa</i>	+	+	.	+	.	II	0.15
G	Ec	3	3	4	P	<i>Dentaria bulbifera</i>	.	.	+	+	+	.	.	+	.	.	II	0.2
H-G	E	3.5	3	5	P	<i>Mercurialis perenis</i>	.	+	+	+	+	II	0.2
G	Eua	3	3	3	P	<i>Lathraea squamaria</i>	.	.	.	+	I	0.05

Table 1 Continuation

H	Eua	4	3	0	P	<i>Dryopteris filix- mas</i>	.	.	+	.	.	.	+	.	+	.	II	0.15
H	Eua	3.5	3	3	P	<i>Senecio nemorensis ssp.jacquinianus</i>	+	.	+	+	.	II	0.15
G	Eua	3.5	3	4	D	<i>Circea lutetiana</i>	+	.	+	+	+	.	.	.	+	.	II	0.25
H-Hh	Cp	3.5	3	4	P	<i>Carex sylvatica</i>	+	+	.	.	+	.	.	.	+	.	II	0.2
H	Eua	3.5	3	4	D	<i>Salvia glutinosa</i>	.	+	+	.	.	.	+	.	.	.	II	0.15
Ch	Ec-SM	3	3.5	4	DP	<i>Euphorbia amigdaloides</i>	.	.	+	+	I	0.1
H	Eua	3.5	3	4	DP	<i>Asarum europaeum</i>	.	+	+	I	0.1
G	Eua	3	2.5	2.5	P	<i>Polygonatum verticilatum</i>	.	.	.	+	.	.	.	+	.	.	I	0.1
H	Eua	3	0	3.5	P	<i>Epilobium montanum</i>	.	+	+	.	.	I	0.1
H	Eua	3.5	0	0	P	<i>Stachys sylvatica</i>	+	.	I	0.05
nPh	Eua	3.5	3	3	D	<i>Daphne mezereum</i>	.	+	I	0.05
H	Eua	3	3	3	D	<i>Lathyrus vernus</i>	.	+	I	0.05
Th-TH	Cosm	3.5	3	3	P	<i>Geranium robertianum</i>	.	.	+	I	0.05
H	E	4.5	3	3	P	<i>Carex remota</i>	.	.	+	I	0.05
H	Atl-M	3.5	3	4	D	<i>Sanicula europaea</i>	.	.	+	I	0.05
G	Eua	3	0	4	D	<i>Lilium martagon</i>	+	I	0.05
nPh	E	3	3	4	P	<i>Euonimus latifolium</i>	+	I	0.05
H	Eua	3,5	0	4	P	<i>Paris quadrifolia</i>	+	.	I	0.05
Quercio- Fagetea																		
H	E	3	3	3	D	<i>Mycelis muralis</i>	+	+	+	.	+	+	+	.	.	.	IV	0.3
H	Cosm	4	2.5	0	P	<i>Athyrium filix- femina</i>	+	.	.	+	+	+	.	.	+	.	III	0.25
H	Eua	3	2.5	3	P	<i>Viola reichembachiana</i>	.	.	.	+	I	0.05
H	Eua	3.5	3	0	P	<i>Scrophularia nodosa</i>	.	.	+	+	.	+	.	.	+	.	II	0.2
Ch	Eua	2	2	2	P	<i>Veronica officinalis</i>	.	+	I	0.05
H	Eua-M	3	3	4	DP	<i>Brachypodium sylvaticum</i>	.	+	I	0.05
H	Eua	3	2.5	0	D	<i>Fragaria vesca</i>	.	+	I	0.05
I-nPh	Atl-M	3	3	3	P	<i>Hedera helix</i>	.	.	+	I	0.05
MPh	E	3	3	0	DP	<i>Acer platanoides</i>	+	I	0.5
mPh	E	3	3	3	D	<i>Corylus avellana</i>	.	.	+	+	I	0.1
G	Eua	3.5	0	3	P	<i>Platanthera bifolia</i>	+	.	.	.	I	0.05
G	Cosm	3	3	0	P	<i>Pteridium aquilinum</i>	.	.	.	+	I	0.05
H	Cp	2	0	1	P	<i>Deschampsia flexuosa</i>	.	.	.	+	I	0.05
G	E	3.5	4	0	P	<i>Anemone nemorosa</i>	+	I	0.05
G	E	3.5	3	4	P	<i>Anemone ranunculoides</i>	+	I	0.05
H-Ch	MP	2.5	3	4	P	<i>Glechoma hirsuta</i>	+	I	0.05
G	Eua	2	3	4	D	<i>Polygonatum odoratum ssp.odoratum</i>	+	+	I	0.1
G	Ec	2.5	3	3	P	<i>Galium schultesi</i>	+	I	0.05
mPh	E	3	3	3	P	<i>Euonymus europaeus</i>	+	I	0.05
Epilobietea angustifolii																		
nPh	Cp	3	3	3	DP	<i>Rubus idaeus</i>	.	+	+	+	II	0.15
H	Cp	2.5	2	3	D	<i>Solidago virgaurea</i>	.	+	+	.	+	+	II	0.2
H	Atl-M	3	3	3	P	<i>Atropa bella- dona</i>	.	.	.	+	I	0.05
H	Eua	3	3	0	P	<i>Hypericum perforatum</i>	.	.	+	I	0.05
Betulo- Adenostyletea																		
H	E	2.5	2.5	2	DP	<i>Luzula luzuloides</i>	+	.	.	+	+	+	+	+	+	.	IV	0.35
H	Ec	4	2	4	P	<i>Gentiana asclepiadea</i>	.	.	+	.	.	.	+	.	+	.	II	0.15
G	E	3.5	2	3	P	<i>Doronicum austriacum</i>	+	.	+	+	II	0.15
G	Eua	4	0	0	P	<i>Petasites albus</i>	+	I	0.05
G	Alp-Carp-B	3.5	2	3.5	P	<i>Doronicum columnae</i>	.	+	I	0.05
G	Eua	4	2.5	4	DP	<i>Veratrum album</i>	.	.	+	.	.	.	+	.	.	.	I	0.1
Vaccinio- Piceetea																		
MPh	E	0	0	0	D	<i>Picea abies</i>	1	+	+	.	.	.	1	.	.	.	II	1.1
H	Cp	3.5	2	3	P	<i>Dryopteris cristata</i>	+	+	+	II	0.15
H	Ec	3.5	2.5	2	DP	<i>Luzula sylvatica</i>	+	I	0.05
Ch-nPh	Cp	0	2	1	D	<i>Vaccinium myrthillus</i>	+	.	I	0.05
Variae Syntaxa																		
H	M	3	2	5	D	<i>Primula veris ssp.columnae</i>	.	+	I	0.05
H	Eua	3	3	0	D	<i>Stachys officinalis</i>	.	.	.	+	I	0.05
G	Cp-Bo	3.5	3	4	P	<i>Polypodium vulgare</i>	+	.	.	+	I	0.1
H	Cosm	3	3	4	DPI	<i>Urtica dioica</i>	+	I	0.05

Location and date of surveys: 1 Piatra Grăitoare , 15.09.2018 GPS 462906, 223916; 2 Vârtope 16.09.2018 GPS 463036, 223936; 3 Băița 23.07.2019 GPS 463027, 223756,5; 4 Valea Criștior 26.07.2019 GPS 462513, 223713,9; 5 Dealul Runcului 26.07.2019 GPS 462537,7, 223757,9; 6 Vf. Lespedioara 27.09.2019 GPS 462053,2, 224158; 7 Pârâul Mare 27.07.2019 GPS 462156,9, 224044,7; 8 Valea Hălmăgel 27.07.2019 GPS 462125,8, 224301; 9 Valea Găina 07.08.2019 GPS 462013,2, 224219,6; 10 Valea Leucii 08.08.2019 GPS 462328,3, 223848,3.

The analysis of the association from the point of view of lifeforms (see Figure 1) highlights the fact that hemicryptophytes are in majority (47.19%), followed by geophytes (28.76%), phanerophytes (15.06%), camephytes (4.1%), therophytes (2.73%), and climbing plants (1.36%).

The spectrum of floristic elements (see Figure 2) highlights that the most representative species are Eurasian (38.35%), followed by European (20.54%), Central-European (13.69%), circumpolar (12.32%), cosmopolitan (5.47%), Atlantic-Mediterranean (4.1%), Alpine-Carpatho-Balkan (2.73%), Mediterranean (1.36%) and Pontic Mediterranean (1.36) species.

Regarding the ecological factors (see Figure 3), one may notice that in relation to moisture, the majority species are mesophilic (72.29%), followed at great distance by mesohygrophilic and xeromesophilic species (with 12.31% each); in relation to air temperature, micro-mesothermals (56.15%), are followed by microthermals (27.38%) and eurythermic species (13.69%); with regard the chemical

reaction of the soil, most species are acidoneutrophilic (35.61%), weakly acidoneutrophilic (31.50%), euriionic (20.54%), acidophilic (6.84%), strongly acidophilic and neutro-basiphilic (with 2.73% each).

Within the karyological spectrum (see Figure 4) the polyploid species are dominant (56.16%), followed by the diploid (30.13%) and diplo-polyploid (13.69%) species. The diploidy index has a value of 0.52.

Beech stands with *Festuca drymeja* are of economic importance, providing raw material and accessory products for the wood industry, the pulp and paper industry, the hospitality and food industry, but also for local communities. These forests are ecologically important in that they provide critical environmental services, anti-erosion, anchoring the soil through the root system, regulating watercourse flows and reducing surface runoff. One can find a small number of species of scientific value within this association, namely: *Lilium martagon*, *Cephalanthera longifolia*, *Platanthera bifolia*, *Sanicula europaea*.

Figure 1. The spectrum of bioforms in the association *Festuco drymejae* – *Fagetum*

Legend: MPh= Megaphanerophytes; mPh= Mesophanerophytes; nPh= Nanophanerophytes; l-nPh= Climbing plants; Ch= Camephytes; H= Hemicryptophytes; Th= Annual therophytes; G= Geophytes

Figure 2. The spectrum of floristic elements in the association *Festuco drymejae – Fagetum*
 Legend: Cp= Circumpolar; Eua= Eurasian; E= European; Ec= Central European; Atl-M= Atlantic-Mediterranean; Alp-Carp-B=Alpino-Carpatho-Balkan; Cosm= Cosmopolitan, M= Mediterranean; M-P= Mediterranean-Pontic

Figure 3. Diagram of ecological indices for the association *Festuco drymejae – Fagetum*

Figure 4. The karyological spectrum of the association *Festuca drymejae* – *Fagetum*
Legend: D= Diploid; P= Polyploids; DP= Diplo-polyploids

CONCLUSIONS

1. The phytocenoses of these beech forests (*Fagus sylvatica*) with *Festuca drymeja* have a high conservation value, forming rare communities in sparsely distributed habitats.

2. In the spectrum of lifeforms, hemicryptophytes predominate (47.94%), followed at a distance by geophytes (28.76%), and phanerophytes (4.84%).

3. In terms of geographic area, the Eurasian species (38.35%) are predominant, followed by the European (20.54%), Central European (13.69%), and circumpolar (12.32%) species.

4. With regard the ecological indices, the most numerous elements, in relation to soil moisture are the mesophils (72.29%), in relation to the air temperature, the micro-mesothermals are predominant (56.15%), and in relation to the chemical reaction of the soil, the acid-neutrophils (31.50%) are dominant.

5. Analysis of chromosomal karyotypes highlights the dominance of polyploid species (56.16%), compared to diploid (30.13%) and diplo-polyploid (13.69%) ones.

REFERENCES

- Bilz, M., Kell, SP., Maxted, N., Lansdown, RV., 2011. European Red List of Vascular Plants. Publication Office of the European Union, Luxembourg.
- Borhidi, A., 2003. Magyarország növénytársulásai, Akadémiai Kiadó, Budapest.
- Borza, Al., Boşcaiu, N., 1965. Introduction to the study of the living soil cover. Romanian Academy Publishing House, 340 p.
- Boşcaiu, N., Marossy, A., 1979. Aspects of vegetation from Cepelur Valley (Biharia Massif), Nymphaea, "Țării Crișurilor" Museum, Oradea. pp. 301-302.
- Boşcaiu, N., Coldea, Gh., Horeanu, C., 1994. Red list of extinct, endangered, vulnerable and rare vascular plants from the flora of Romania. Ocrot. Nat. Med. Inconj., Bucharest, 38, 1:45-56.

- Braun-Blanquet, J., Pavillard, G., 1928. Vocabulaire de sociologie végétale, ed.II, Imprimerie Roumegous & Dehan, Montpellier
- Braun-Blanquet, J., 1964. Pflanzensoziologie, ed.III Springer-Verlag, Wien-New York.
- Burescu, P., Toma, I., 2005. Manual of practical works of botany, Oradea University Press, Oradea, 590 p.
- Chifu, T., (ed.), Irimia, I., Zamfirescu, O., 2014. The phytosociological diversity of Romania's vegetation, The European Institute, Iasi, vol. I+II+III.
- Ciocârlan, V., 2009. Illustrated flora of Romania: Pteridophyta et Spermatophyta, Ceres Publishing House, Bucharest, 1141 p.
- Coldea, Gh., Sanda, V., Popescu, A., Ștefan, N., 1997. Les associations végétales de Roumanie. Tome I: Les associations herbacées naturelles, Edit. Presa Universitară Clujeană, Cluj-Napoca, 261 p.
- Cristea, V., Gafta, D., Pedrotti, F., 2004. Phytosociology. Cluj University Press, Cluj-Napoca, 396 p.
- Dihoru, Gh., Negrean, G., 2009. Red Book of vascular plants from Romania. Romanian Academy, Publishing House, Bucharest, 630 p.
- Majovszky, J., Murin, A., 1987. Karyotaxonomický prehľad flóry Slovenska, Veda, Bratislava, 436 p.
- Marossy, A., 1973. Contributions to the knowledge of the flora of the Biharia I Massif, Nymphaea, "Țării Crișurilor" Museum, Oradea. p.p. 17-20.
- Marossy, A., 1975. Contributions to the knowledge of the flora of the Biharia II Massif, Nymphaea, "Țării Crișurilor" Museum, Oradea. p.p. 83-86.
- Meusel, H., Jäger, E.J., 1992. Vergleichende Chorologie der Zentraleuropäischen Flora. III, Gustav Fischer Verlag, Jena, 333 p.
- Moore, D.M., 2009. Flora Europaea checklist and chromosome index, Cambridge Univ. Press., New York, 423 p.
- Oberdorfer, E., 1992. Süddeutsche Pflanzengesellschaften, Teil IV: Wälder und Gebüsche 2, Stark bearbeitete Auflage Textband, Gustav Fischer Verlag Viena, New York.
- Oltean, M., Negrean, G., Popescu, A., Roman, N., Dihoru G., Sanda V., Mihăilescu, S., 1994. Red list of higher plants in Romania, Stud. Sint. Doc. Ecol., Romanian Academy, Bucharest, 1:1-52.

ABOUT NUMERICAL SIMULATION OF THE INDUCTION HEAT TREATMENT APPLIED TO REVERSIBLE CLAW OF SCARIFIER

Gabriel CHEREGI^{1#}, Mihaela Codruța LUCACI¹ Laura Melinda DERECHICHEI¹, Adrian Gabriel CHEREGI², Teodora Anca CODĂU³

¹ University of Oradea, Faculty of Environmental Protection, Forestry Department, 26 Gen. Magheru Str, 410059 Oradea, Romania

² C.C. ALUGARD L.T.D. 407 A, Sântandrei, Romania

³ "Dimitrie Cantemir" Secondary School, 2A, Sextil Pușcariu St., Oradea, Romania,

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

This paper proposes an analysis of the induction hardening method of the reversible claw of Scarifier. In the case of the reversible claw of Scarifier the heating analysis needs solution in the thermal diffusion problems coupled with eddy currents case. We make the known simulation to be sure that the requirements parameter is the same in practice.

Keywords: Numerical simulation, Electromagnetic field, Electromagnetic field coupled with thermal, reversible claw of Scarifier.

#Corresponding author: grcheregi@yahoo.com

INTRODUCTION

The reversible claw of Scarifier is used for scarification process.

The cutting area of the reversible claw must have optimal linear and angular parameters, depending on the terrain conditions in which it is worked.

In scarifiers, the claw-type loosening active organs are mounted on rigid or elastic supports. The elastic supports ensure the vibration of the active organs during work, in the longitudinal and transverse direction, so that the effect of loosening and crushing the soil is more pronounced, and the advance of the aggregate is easier and at the same time the energy consumption is reduced. For this active organ, the application of heat treatment in the electromagnetic field implies a high durability in the technological process of scarification.

In general, the reversible claw must be had a homogeneous structure to respond of imposed requirements.

We know that the induction hardening simulation method is used for all kinds of geometry types of metal piece. This method considers the change of both parameters like the

electromagnetic and thermal parameters. Both parameters are according with the temperature.

We must verify that the B-H relation is depended on temperature, passing from iron-magnetic environment form to air. In this case, we observe that the eddy's current problems and thermal diffusion are strongly coupled in the Curie point zone.

As we know the B-H relation is linear and the magnetic permeability is adjusting according to the highest effective value of the magnetic induction (T. Leuca, 2007).

We adopt linear pattern (FLUX 2D - tutorial) and the B-H relation.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

For the simulation we use FLUX 2D software package.

In the analysis of this case, we must solve the electromagnetic problem with a parallel - plane structure.

The magnetic field problem can be solved by reduced to the determination of a potential vector with a single component, which verifies a similar equation of the scalar potential.

The coupled of thermal diffusion problems with eddy currents is the main problem of every hardening method.

For a better analysis of the results, we need to find the result of eddy currents problem

(power density) and temperature (thermal capacity and thermal conductivity) (T. Leuca, 2002, T. Leuca 1997).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The numerical simulation with FLUX 2D software (FLUX 2D - tutorial) allows to be

determining accurately the relationship between the used frequencies, the desired treatment depth, and the power density.

The desired treatment depth is very important to make a complete map of the hardening process.

Figure 1. The reversible claw

Figure 2. Positioning of points A and B where the temperature field is analyzed

Figure 3. The temperature in point A

Figure 4. The temperature in point B

CONCLUSIONS

The thermal transfer to the surface of the workpiece is characterized by a convection coefficient with the value $\alpha = 20 \text{ W/m}^2/\text{°C}$ and by a radiation coefficient (characteristic of the thermal transfer by radiation) $\varepsilon = 0,75$ by which the dependence of the thermal transfer coefficient α_e it's a function of temperature

The numeric simulation of the hardening process is a complex problem because the non-linear problems of eddy currents is provided from non-linear relation of B-H.

The non-linear of thermal problem provide from dependence with temperature of thermal parameters (T. Leuca, 2007, 2009, M. Arion, 2008, M. Marincaru, P Minciunescu, 2011, F.I. Hantilă 2012, A. Burcă 2012, 2013, 2014).

After the simulation process we observe that the coupled of two problems result from strong dependence of relation B-H with temperature. Through proposed heat treatment we get a homogenous structure for the reversible claw of Scarifier.

REFERENCES

- . Arion M, G. Cheregi "About the analisis of simultaneous induction hardening method of pinions with rectangular coil" Journal of electrical and electronics engineering, University of Oradea, 2008.
- Arion M., T. Leuca, F.I. hathazi, V.D. soproni, C. Molnar, G. Cheregi, 2012. Aspects Regarding the Numerical Computation of the Eddy Current Problem within the Electromagnetic Induction Processes of Thin Planes" Journal of electrical and electronics engineering, Vol. 5 nr. 2. University of Oradea.
- Burca A., 2014. Contributions to analyze electro-inductive systems equipped with high frequency inverters" doctoral thesis. University of Oradea.
- Burca A., Stanciu Bogdan, Mich-Vancea Claudiu.,2012. Aided Design Elements of Induction Heating Process for Hardening. Journal of Electrical and Electronics Engineering Oradea.
- Burca Adrian, Leuca Teodor, Cheregi Gabriel, 2013. Study on Using Concentrators in the Induction-Hardening Process of a Cylindrical Part. Journal of Electrical and Electronics Engineering Oradea.
- Cheregi G. R., 2006. Contributions on the numerical analysis of the heating process through induction in the thermal treatments' issues. doctoral thesis. University of Oradea
- Cheregi G., Burca Adrian, Lucaci Mihaela Codruța, Derecichei Laura Melinda, Codău Anca Teodora, 2016..About Using Elta Software in Simulation of the Induction Hardening Method – Annals of Oradea University, Environmental Protection Fascicula, Vol. XXVII, pp. 365-370.
- Cheregi G., M. Arion, 2008. About the analisis of simultaneous induction hardening method of pinions with circular coil" Journal of electrical and electronics engineering, University of Oradea.
- Cheregi G., M. Arion, 2010. About the analisis of simultaneous induction hardening method of disk used at suspense harrow in agriculture with rectangular coil" Journal of electrical and electronics engineering, Vol. 3 nr. 2, University of Oradea, ,
- Cheregi, G. T. Leuca, M. Arion, 2008. About numerical analisis of electromagnetic field induce in gear wheels during hardening process. Journal of electrical and electronics engineering, University of Oradea.
- Cingoski V., 1996. Analysis of magneto-thermal coupled problems involving moving eddy-current conductors. IEEE Transactions on Magnetics. (vol.32, p.1042-1046)
- Doppel K., 1996. Finite element method for calculating power frequency 2D electromagnetic field distributions in ferromagnetic materials. IEEE Transactions on Magnetics (vol.32, p.792-796)
- Florea I. Hantilă, Mihai Maricaru, Radu Mircea Ciuceanu, Lilica Corlan, 2012. Harmonic analysis of circuits with nonlinear resistive elements. Rev. Roum. Sci. Techn. – Électrotechn. et Énerg., 57, 4, Bucarest,

-
- Hantila F. et al, "The numeric computation of eddy currents", Ed. ICPE, Bucharest, 2001 (in Romanian).
- Leuca T., 1997. Numerical modelling energy optimization of the electromagnetic and thermal coupled fields in the induction heating process of the cylindrical half-finished products. International symposium on non-linear electromagnetic systems, Braunschweig.
- Leuca T., B. Cranganu-Cretu, M. Arion, G. Tarcau, 2002. Numerical modelling of industrial processing by electromagnetic induction of ferromagnetic parts. 10th International IGTE Symposium on Numerical Field Calculation in Electrical Engineering, Graz, Austria.
- Leuca T., G. Cheregi, 2009. A simultaneous induction hardening method of pinions. Rev. Roum. Sci. Techn. – Électrotechn. et Énerg., 54, 2, Bucarest
- Leuca T., M. Arion, G. Cheregi 2005. Dual Frequency Simulation of the Electromagnetic Induction Process in Gear Wheels. Annals of Oradea University, pp.36-39, Oradea.
- Leuca T., M. Arion, G. Cheregi, I. Horge, 2007. About numerical computation of electromagnetic field in ferromagnetic bodies. Annals of Oradea University.
- Maricar M., P. Minciunescu, I. R. Ciric, G-M. Vasilescu, 2011. A new vector boundary elements procedure for inductance computation. Rev. Roum. Sci. Techn. – Électrotechn. et Énerg., 56, 2, Bucarest
- FLUX 2D – tutorial.

ASPECTS REGARDING THE PROCESSING OF COMPLEX SURFACES FROM WOOD

Laura DERECICHEI^{1#}, Codruța LUCACI¹, Gabriel Adrian CHEREGI¹, Marius OROS²

¹ University of Oradea, Faculty of Environmental Protection, Forestry Department, 26 Gen. Magheru Str, 410059 Oradea, Romania

² C.C. ALUGARD L.T.D. 407 A, Sântandrei, Romania

³ "Dimitrie Cantemir" Secondary School, 2A, Sextil Pușcariu St., Oradea, Romania,

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

CNC machines have gradually replaced the classic, manually operated ones, allowing the performance of various operations, specific to industrial production processes. The CNC machine interface is easy to learn and use, providing the ability to simulate machine operation. Through advanced software programs, CNC machine tools enable the creation of products that are difficult to design using traditional methods.

Keywords: : CNC, wood, 5 axis milling

#Corresponding author: derecichei.laura@gmail.com

INTRODUCTION

Every CNC machine has two or more directions of motion, called axes. These axes can be precisely moved and precisely positioned throughout the travel range.

The most common types of axes are linear and rotary. Instead of producing these movements with the help of an operator, through the use of cranks and discs, as required by classic machining machines, CNC machines are driven by computer-controlled servomotors and guided by a memorized program. In general, the movement type, axes, movement distances and machining speeds are programmable.

CNC machine tools can be used continuously, increasing productivity and providing greater control over industrial processes (meproutilaje.ro).

Unlike classic lathes or milling centers, CNC machine tools do not require a high degree of operator expertise. The research for this paper was carried out at a company in the field of wood processing in Sighetu Marmăției, between January 2022 and May 2022.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

Wood in general allows fairly easy processing on CNC machines, so it is widely used for milling, cutting and turning. In addition, it is a relatively cheap and abundant material. On the other hand, it is usually one of the most used

materials also for home CNC machines used by some DIY makers and hobbyists.

Classification of CNC by their axes.

Due to the higher number of axes, CNC machines have more freedom of movement and more variable part processing complexity. (hwlibre.com, Derecichei L. et al., 2013, Derecichei L. et al., 2017, Derecichei L. et al., 2018).

CNC machines with more than 5 axes

In addition to 3, 4 and 5 axes, there are types of CNC machines with more axes, even up to 12.

These are more advanced and expensive machines, although not as common. Some examples are:

7 axes: Long, thin parts with many details can be made. These types of CNC machines have axes for right-left, up-down, back-forward, tool rotation, workpiece rotation, tool head rotation, and work clamp movement.

9-axis: This type combines a lathe with 5-axis machining. The result is that it turns and mills along multiple planes with a single setup and with high precision. In addition, it does not need secondary accessories or manual charging.

12 Axis: They have two VMC and HMC heads, each of which allows movements in the X, Y, Z, A, B and C axes. These types of machines offer improved productivity and precision. The way these machines work is shown in figure 1.

Figure 1 Working CNC with 12 axes (hwlibre.com)

NX CAM shown in figure 2 allows for simplified CNC programming and the execution of work instructions together with the CNC program, the document being automatically generated by pressing a button (Derecichei L., 2020, Lucaci C., et al., 2013, Lucaci C., et al., 2015, <http://www.digitaltwin.ro>).

The advantages of this way of working are:

- the work instructions are created as an integral part of the CNC program in the NX CAM file, thus simplifying their management and making unnecessary the use of additional text editing software (such as Microsoft Office);

- updating the work instructions is done 90% faster thanks to the associativity with the CAD reference and the CAM program;
- both the steps performed on the CNC and the additional steps can be documented;
- publication can be done in PDF or HTML format;
- the creation of new work instructions can be done quickly and consistently through configurable templates;
- a procedural and unitary way of working is established.

Figure 2 Programming with NX CAM (digitaltwin.ro)

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Processing of complex wooden surfaces is done on CNC machines.

In addition to the programming of CNC machine tools, the execution of the reference by G/ISO program described above also involves knowing the operating functions on the control panel of the CNC machine and a series of preparations before starting the automatic machining processes for example:

- manual, automatic operation;
- the system for clamping elements to be processed;
- zero set – setting the zero point;
- setting the tools;
- the collision avoidance system.

Some CNC machines allow simulation of the machining process at high speed, thus

avoiding possible problems that can interrupt the cutting and later changes can be made in the program lines (Derecichei L. et al., 2018, Derecichei L. et al., 2020).

The processing of complex surfaces can be done through a first work phase, or through a previous roughing or pre-drilling phase, because the differences are too large differences between the raw part and the part we want to make, or processing with a single pass would affect the quality of the final part (tehdno-design.ro). An example of roughing of the part to be subsequently passed through a final finishing phase is shown in figure 3.

Figure 3 Machining with CNC 5 axes (tehno-design.ro)

When processing several parts from a piece of material, you can opt, as in this example from figure 4., for some neutral portions called "bridge portions", some connecting portions

that remain for fixing the parts until the processing is completed, after which they detach from each other (<http://www.cnc-3d.ro>, Ganea, M., 2010).

Figure 4 CNC milling (bridge finishing) (<http://www.cnc-3d.ro>)

On this machine, 2 motors are mounted, shown in figure 5., on a single arm controlled on axes A and C, each with 2 heads for tools which gives a very high speed when changing

operations. The two motors have a power of 7.5 kw each, with the help of the two inverters (<http://directindustry.com>).

Figure 5 Chuck motors (directindustry.com)

Fixing the landmarks can be done both with the help of pneumatic and vacuum clamps.

Figure 6 shows vacuum clamping on special templates.

Figure 6 Fixing the landmarks through the vacuum system (directindustry.com)

The position of the X-axis above the work tables gives a very high flexibility because the CNC arm can work in front of the table, to the side of the table, behind the table, above the table and under the table.

The clamping tables can move on the X and Y axes, which gives it an asset for series production and small milestones.

The circular cloth has the characteristics of outer diameter 230 mm, Z=40, n= 6000 rpm.

For cutting speed:

$$v = \frac{\pi \times D \times n}{1000 \times 60} = \frac{\pi \times 230 \times 6000}{60000} = 72.22 \text{ m/min}$$

So we will be able to use a maximum cutting speed of 72 m/min.

The main program that Velox duet CA works with is E-lab.

E-Lab is a program of the newest generation and is updated every day to the requirements of customers and their needs.

In the E-lab program when we work, we must forget about those ISO codes made in notepad or generated in other programs without any graphic interface and imported into the machine program.

The realization of a new project is presented in figure 7 and figure 8.

Figure 7 Select slot (woodworking company)

Figure 8 Choosing the area to work on (woodworking company)

You can choose to work with both tables at the same time (it is used for large landmarks like table tops) and work on each table with a different landmark (on table 1A with the front-left leg and on table 2A with the back-right leg).

A 3D design program (eg Solidworks) can be used for the model and a program for creating operations with the help of the machine's post-processor (eg AlphaCam) can be used to process these landmarks. Example of a completed program figure 9.

Figure 9 Program made on CNC Velox (woodworking company)

CONCLUSIONS

The programming of CNC machines is often done manually or assisted by a graphical conversational interface, in the case of the present work, "E-lab", an interface that is much easier to use for defining and modifying the

processing parameters of complex wooden surfaces.

Modular milling cutters can be used to make marks with complex surfaces, which brings an advantage for the time of making marks much shorter, a very important thing to which we have contributed to increase production in the production hall.

REFERENCES

- Derecichei L., Lucaci C., Ganea M., –2013-”Issues concerning the simulation of finishing wooden sculptural surfaces in the concept of 5 simultaneous CNC axes” - Natural Resources and Sustainable Development Oradea- 2013, pp.261- 270, ISBN 978-3-902938-02-2;
- Derecichei L., Lucaci C., – 2013 - CAD-CAM software problem when drawing three-dimensional sculptures surfaces - International Symposium “Risk Factors for Environment and Food Safety”, Annals of University of Oradea, Fascicle Environmental Protection, vol.XX, Oradea University Publishing House 2013;
- Derecichei L., Lucaci C., Cheregi G., Lustun L.- 2017- Simulation of Sculptural Surface Processing in Wood in 5 Axis CNC With Sprutcam Program-International Symposium “Risk Factors for Environment and Food Safety”, Annals of University of Oradea, Fascicle Environmental Protection vol.XXVIII, Publishing House of the University of Oradea 2017, pp.165-172, ISSN 1224 – 6255;
- Derecichei L., Lucaci C., Cheregi G., – 2018- Issues Related to the Use of SPRUTCAM in Wood Processing - International Symposium “Risk Factors for Environment and Food Safety”, Annals of University of Oradea, Fascicle Environmental Protection, vol.XXXI, Publishing House of the University of Oradea 2018, pp.133-140, ISSN 1224 – 6255;
- Derecichei L., Lucaci C., Cheregi G., – 2019- Study on circumferential processing on milling machines in 5 axis CNC - International Symposium “Risk Factors for Environment and Food Safety”, Annals of University of Oradea, Fascicle Environmental Protection, vol.XXXIII, anul 24, Publishing House of the University of Oradea 2019, pp. 123 -133, ISSN 1224 – 6255;
- Derecichei L., Lucaci C., Cheregi G., 2020. Aspects Regarding the Process of Wooden Surfaces on 3-Axis CNC Milling Machines with Spherical Tool - International Symposium “Risk Factors for Environment and Food Safety”, Annals of University of Oradea, Fascicle Environmental Protection, vol.XXXIV, anul 25, Publishing House of the University of Oradea 2020, pp.165-171, ISSN 1224 – 6255;
- Ganea, M., 2010. Machinery and Technology for Processing Surface Echipamenre 4 and 5 Axis CNC, ISBN 978-606-10-0041-8, University of Oradea Publishing House;
- Lucaci, C., Derecichei L., Cheregi, G. -Aspects concerning the simulation of roughing sculptural wooden surfaces in the concept of 5- CNC axes - Natural Resources and Sustainable Development Oradea- 2013, ISBN 978-3-902938-02-2;
- Lucaci C., Lustun L., Cheregi G., Derecichei L., 2015. About Using the Solidworks in the Woodworking Engineering - International Symposium “Risk Factors for Environment and Food Safety”, Annals of University of Oradea, Fascicle Environmental Protection vol.XXV, University of Oradea in 2015, pp. 367-372, ISSN 1224-6255
- www.pro-cnc.ro,
www.hwlibre.com,
www.digitaltwin.ro,
www.greenbau.ro,
www.tehno-design.ro,
www.cnc-3D

COMPARATIVE STATIC ANALYSIS OF LATTICES BEAMS MADE OF WOODEN AND METAL MATERIAL TO ESTABLISH THE LIMITS OF USE FOR THE SAME LOAD VALUES

Marius Serban FETEA¹

¹Technical University of Cluj-Napoca, Faculty of Building Services, 128-130 B-dul 21 Decembrie, Cluj-Napoca 400604, Romania

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

Considering the wide field of use of lattice beams, starting from the roofs of houses to bridges and electricity transmission systems, the current work is intended to be and present a comparative static analysis of a structure made of wood material - oak, and steel. This follows the stability of some limits of use of these types of structure depending on the elastic and mechanical properties of the materials. It is also known that the realization of metal structures involves a higher energy consumption than those made of wooden material. Thus, from an economic, as well as energetic point of view, the analysis carried out by the author allows the stabilization of the values of external loads until the use of wood material ensures the safe operation of the structures. From the dimensional point of view, of the adopted geometry and the method of loading the structure with lattices, the similarity is maintained both for the wooden material and for the steel.

Keywords: lattice beam; nodes; displacements; tensile forces.

#Corresponding author: Marius.Fetea@insta.utcluj.ro

INTRODUCTION

In the vast majority of scientific works up to now, the topic related to the analysis of beams with lattices has been a challenge mainly from the point of view of adapting their geometry according to the position in the final structure, the way of loading and supporting. It is known that at the present time the studies have presented and solved extensively all the previously mentioned challenges.

In the current conditions, the analysis on these landings is no longer relevant except for certain specific cases of loading and ensuring geometric non-deformability. The current work is based on the static analysis of the same beam-type structure with lattices, taking into account the geometry, its loading method and the supporting method (Soare, 1999). The difference in terms of obtaining these data obtained by the two types of materials from which the beam is considered to be made, namely: wooden material and steel.

Taking into account the daily realities, the problem of comparative analysis that was addressed and that was wanted to be solved by the author, constitutes a challenge that needs to be solved on several levels.

One of the plans is strictly related to the determination of the mechanical characteristics that are determined from the calculations for each type of material - stresses, displacements, efforts, reactions (Bors, 2003) - and the second level on which the analysis is aimed is the energetic one. In the current conditions related to the energy crisis, the problem of saving energy in all industrial branches is of almost importance. The mechanical analysis carried out with the data presented is in close correlation with the energetic one because, through the results obtained by the author in the current paper, certain limits of using a less energy-consuming material such as wood compared to steel are presented.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

In the present work, the materials that were taken into account for the lattice beam studied are: the wooden material is called oak beam and steel. From the beginning, the same geometry and the same dimensional values were considered for the beam elements with lattices (Martian, 1999). It was also considered the simultaneous action of three forces concentrated on nodes 1, 3 and 5, having modules of 300 [KN] - nodes 1 and 3 and 200 [KN] on node 2.

For the case of the wooden material, the following physical-mechanical characteristics were considered

$\rho = 700$ [Kg/mc]- oak density;

$E = 11500$ [N/mm²]- longitudinal modulus of elasticity;

$\nu = 0.372$ - Poisson's ratio.

For the steel material, they considered the following physical-mechanical characteristics

$\rho = 7860$ [Kg/mc] - oak density;

$E = 210000$ [N/mm²]-longitudinal modulus of elasticity;

$\nu = 0.3$ - Poisson's ratio

Analytical mechanical calculation of lattice beams is based on the known methods - the method of sections or the method of isolation of nodes (Martian, 1999), (Ille, 1983). By applying these known analytical methods, the sectional stresses in the system bars and the stresses are determined. The displacements of the points in the transverse sections of the beam bars are determined using one of the known methods - the direct integration method (Fetea, 2021), Mohr's method or the initial parameters method (Barsan, 1979).

The method used is not a classic analytical one that involves a laborious mathematical calculation, but is by applying one of the aforementioned, by using calculation programs dedicated to mechanical calculations using the LISA educational software (Ghinea, 2004) . The use of the mentioned program leads to the idea of the fact that in the present work the mathematical apparatus used is not of interest, but its application to establish, based on the results obtained, the limits of use of the two dimensionally equal structures and having the same loads, but different materials.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Next, based on the modeled structure with the help of Lisa educational software, the geometry of the structure and the mechanical parameters for each of the materials considered separately are presented. Taking into account the similar way of geometric, two-dimensional conception and loading of the structure, the following values were obtained.

Figure.1 Wood lattice beam

Figure. 2 Steel lattice beam

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

1. For the structure made of wooden material.

Figure. 3 Displacements along X axes for wood lattice beam

Figure. 4 Displacements along Y axes for wood lattice beam

Figure. 5 Tensile force for wood lattice beam

Figure. 6 Displacements magnitude for wood lattice beam

Figure. 7 Reactions forces for wood lattice beam

kinematic and static parameters for the wooden structure

Table 1

Node	Displacement in X	Displacement in Y	Tensile Force	Displacement Magnitude
1	0	0	-50000.0000000003	0
2	-1.16229248448008E-18	-0.00561500063678498	46269.5264839553	0.00561500063678498
3	0.000679347826086957	-0.00953163170835257	158769.526483956	0.00955581061409659
4	0.00203804347826087	-0.00561500063678499	78730.4735160451	0.00597342894578796
5	0.00271739130434783	0	-11692.7019786072	0.00271739130434783
6	0.00271739130434783	-0.000434782608695654	-21640.6313547263	0.00275195410895048
7	0.00203804347826087	-0.00604978324548064	-78730.473516045	0.00638384668805415
8	0.000679347826086956	-0.00909684909965691	-108769.526483956	0.00912218049650071
9	-3.425043973191E-18	-0.00518021802808933	-46269.5264839555	0.00518021802808933
10	-3.425043973191E-18	0	0	3.425043973191E-18

2. For steel structure.

Figure 8 Displacements along X axes for steel lattice beam

Figure. 9 Displacements along Y axes for steel lattice beam

Figure. 10 Tensile forces axes for steel lattice beam

Figure. 11. Displacements magnitude for steel lattice beam

kinematic and static parameters for the steel structure

Table 2

Node	Displacement in X	Displacement in Y	Tensile Force	Displacement Magnitude
1	0	0	-125000	0
2	6.82321593405864E-20	-0.000698965860988417	153173.816209888	0.000698965860988417
3	9.30059523809523E-05	-0.000983202503002831	252519.526483955	0.000987591650981983
4	0.000223214285714285	-0.000698965860988417	209980.473516044	0.000733742388154192
5	0.000316220238095238	0	-29231.7549465176	0.000316220238095238
6	0.000316220238095238	-5.95238095238094E-05	-54101.5783868155	0.000321773713782272
7	0.000223214285714286	-0.000722775384797941	-172480.473516045	0.000756458111343087
8	9.30059523809525E-05	-0.000959392979193307	-202519.526483955	0.000963890551724467
9	1.45257473603225E-19	-0.000639442051464607	-115673.816209888	0.000639442051464607
10	1.45257473603225E-19	0	0	1.45257473603225E-19

CONCLUSIONS

Following the results obtained from the application of the Lisa numerical calculation program, one can proceed to a precise interpretation of them (Ghinea, 2004). From tables 1 and 2 presented in the previous sub-chapter, it is noted that the static analysis of the two types of structures, which are geometrically identical and different in terms of materials, allows the interpretation of the kinematic parameters (the displacements along the X and Y axes, the maximum displacement and the static parameter given by the axial force that appears in the transverse sections of the bars.

The Lisa program allows the interpretation of the results both in the nodes of the structure and in the elements, depending on the calculation method used to create the program. The results that were presented in the paper are those from the application of the node isolation method.

The following are noted:

1. Due to the load symmetry of the structures, the displacement values along the X and Y axes for both studied structures are mirrored from node 3 to node 8.

2. Regarding their maximum values, it is noted that they are recorded in nodes 5 and 6 for both the wooden and the metal structure. For the metal structure, the displacement value along the X axis is 0.3 [mm], and the wooden one is approximately 2.7 [mm]. Therefore, the displacement in the wooden structure for the same load is approximately 9 times greater. In the end nodes, the displacements on both structures can be considered as zero.
3. The displacements along the Y axis for both structures are larger. The maximum values are recorded in nodes 3 and 8. For the wooden structure it is about 9.5 [mm], and for the metal structure about 1 [mm]. Taking into account the maximum permissible displacement values for both structures, for the wooden structure we are at the acceptable upper limit
4. Regarding the maximum values of the axial forces, they are recorded in nodes 3 of each structure, being approximately 159[KN] for the wooden structure and 252{KN} for the metal one. It is noted that the static parameters do not have the same kinematics. Therefore, the metal structure can take an axial force only 63% higher than the wooden one because the static parameters do not have the same kinematics. Therefore, the metal structure can take an axial force only 63% higher than the wooden one.

From the comparative static analysis carried out in this work, it is noted that from a mechanical point of view certain limits can be established for the safe use of wooden structures. Of course, the external load values will always be taken into account as well as the location where the structure will be operated and incorporated.

Analyzing from the energy point of view, it was found that more and more countries aim to gradually replace metal and concrete constructions with wooden structures because, beyond the thermal and ecological advantages, the production of wood for construction consumes tens of times less energy than the manufacture of concrete, steel or bricks. Due to the multiple advantages they have, the production of wooden beams worldwide has seen a permanent increase in the last 40 years.

REFERENCES

- Bârsan, G: Dynamics and stability of structures (Dinamica și stabilitatea construcțiilor), Editura Didactică și Pedagogică București, 1979.
- Bors I, Mechanics, theoretical compendium and applications of kinematics, dynamics and analytical mechanics, UTpres, Cluj-Napoca 2003;
- Marius Fetea, Anuța Abrudan., Mechanical Study Regarding The Limits Of Use Of Polypropylene Pipes, Acta Technica Napocensis-Series: Applied Mathematics, Mechanics, And Engineering, Volumul 63, Numărul 4, 2020/12/24.
- Ille V, Bia C, Soare M., Mechanics, theoretical compendium and applications of kinematics, dynamics and analytical mechanics 1983
- Ghinea M., Fireteanu V., Matlab, Calcul numeric, grafica, aplicatii. Editura Teora. Bucuresti 2004;
- Martian I.: Theory of Plasticity and Elasticity (Teoria Elasticitatii si Plasticitatii). LITO UTCN, 1999.
- Soare, M.: Differential equations with applications in mechanical construction (Ecuatii diferențiale cu aplicații în mecanica construcțiilor), Editura Tehnică, București. 1999.

ASPECTS REGARDING FUNCTIONAL STABILITY OF DEMOUNTABLE JOINTS USED IN SOLID WOOD CHAIRS

Codruța LUCACI^{1#}, Gabriel CHEREGI¹, Laura DERECHICHEI¹, Adrian Gabriel CHEREGI², Anca RAKOS³

¹University of Oradea, Faculty of Environmental Protection, Oradea City, Magheru 26, 410087, Romania Institution,
²C.C. ALUGARD L.T.D. 407 A, Sântandrei, Romania

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

The objective of the present study was to optimise and streamline the assembly process of solid wood chairs by applying more efficient ironmongerys to demountable joints

Industrial tests were realized and implemented on solid wood chairs and took place at a company in Sighetul Marmației.

The test results showed the advantages of the application of these ironmongerys, namely: reduction of assembly time, reduction of the number of machining operations per parts, high resistance to the stresses to which they are subjected.

Based on tests, it was found that such ironmongery can be successfully implemented in the wood industry when assembling solid wood chairs or various wooden structures.

This substantially reduces the assembly time and the machining time of the parts, resulting in increased production.

Keywords: Chair, mortise and tenon, assembly, ironmongery
#Corresponding author: codruta.mihaela.cl@gmail.com

INTRODUCTION

The chair is made of solid wood.

The component parts are machined from hardwood lumber by cutting, and the frame assembly is based on mortise and tenon jointed, either with applied straight or round tenon

Mortise and tenon jointed is simple and very strong and is mainly used for joining elements at 90°.

This is a tenon made at the end of a piece of wood that fits perfectly with a mortise in another piece of wood.

There are several variations of the joint, each of them having an added strength or esthetics or resolves some more complicated problems.

The assembly between the two elements must be made a little forced, without play, but without forcing too much.

A joint where the tenon enters very difficult risked to give in at the slightest expansion of the wood.

(<https://woodenmagazine.ro/2019/01/10/mortise-and-tenon-the-most-used-traditional-joint-for-furniture/>)

The benefits of lag screw joints include less loosening and slippage when a load is first applied than bolted timber joints; however, they also require more caution, making construction management an important consideration [Inoue-Shoin Co. Ltd., 2012.].

For example, screwing in a lag screw without first drilling a pilot hole can cause the timber member to crack, or driven in using a hammer. In addition, overtightening beyond a lag screw's pullout strength risks damaging the joint, weakening it compared with its original performance.

One potential solution to prevent the latter scenario is to apply a torque control method to provide suitable torque by means of a torque wrench or other tool. (Matsubara D. et al. 2018)

MATERIAL AND METHOD

Joints of elements, panels, sub-assemblies and their assemblies are used to produce various mechanical structures in the construction of different types of furniture as well as finished wooden products.

The solid wood chairs under test are made at a company in Sighetul Marmației.

In the case of round-tenon joints made by clamping, a circumferential pressure p_f arises between them and the joined parts in the radial direction, the expression of which is [Curtu I et al. 1981]:

$$p_f = \frac{\delta}{c(s_{11}^{(1)} + s_{12}^{(2)}) + \frac{(bc)^{1+e_2}}{b^{2e_2} - c^{2e_2}} \cdot \frac{c^{e_2}}{b^{2+e_2}} \left[(s_{11}^{(2)} + s_{12}^{(2)}) - \frac{b^{e_2-1}}{c^{e_2}} (s_{12}^{(2)} - s_{11}^{(2)}) \right]} \quad (1.1)$$

or by entering the notation $b = \alpha c$ it is obtained

$$p_f = \frac{\delta}{c \left\{ s_{11}^{(1)} + s_{12}^{(1)} + \frac{\alpha^{1+e_2}}{\alpha^{2e_2-1}} \left[\frac{s_{11}^{(1)} + s_{12}^{(2)}}{\alpha^{1+e_2}} - \frac{s_{12}^{(2)} - s_{11}^{(2)}}{\alpha^{1-e_2}} \right] \right\}} \quad (1.2)$$

where the meaning of the terms is as follows

- for tenon

$$s_{11}^{(1)} = \frac{1}{E_T^{(1)}}; s_{12}^{(1)} = -\frac{\nu_{TR}^{(1)}}{E_R^{(1)}}$$

- for mortise

$$s_{11}^{(2)} = \frac{1}{E_T^{(2)}}; s_{12}^{(2)} = -\frac{\nu_{TR}^{(2)}}{E_R^{(2)}}; s_{22}^{(2)} = \frac{1}{E_R^{(2)}}; e_2 = \sqrt{\frac{s_{22}^{(2)}}{s_{11}^{(2)}}} = \sqrt{\frac{E_T^{(2)}}{E_R^{(2)}}}$$

$$k_{1,2} = -1 + e^2; \alpha = 1,5; 2,0; 2,5; 2\delta = \text{tightening}$$

Note that in relation (1.1) determined pressure has not been taken into account and swelling of the tenon due to moisture variation in the adhesive film, as well as elastic relaxation.

By following the deformation mode of the round tenon joints (fig. 1 a) and with eccentric (fig. 1 b) determined with the method *moiré-urilor*, areas of maximum deformation can be observed (tensile or compression). From Fig. 1 a and b it can be observed that joints with tenons are less rigid than those with bolts or eccentrics.

Figure 1 Deformation mode of round tenon and eccentric joints [Curtu I et al. 1981]

For 90° joints with round tenon (fig. 2) tensions are generated by shear forces $T = Q$ and bents moments $M_t = Ql_0$. In the case of strength calculation the following assumptions are allowed: the tenon is made of a stronger

material than the material of the joining pieces; the strength of the glue is at least equal to that of wood; between the pieces there are no games.

Figure 2 90° joints with rounded tenons [Curtu I et al. 1981]

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

On the basis of the tests performed when assembling the chairs by mortise and tenon jointed, a jointed well-known, a considerable difference was observed between their bolt

assembly which requires more processing of the part and eccentric assembly which is more accessible, easier to mount.

Figure 3 a) Bolt assembly crosspiece

b) Eccentric assembly crosspiece

In the image below it can be seen glued parts between mortise and tenon. To join the parts on the crosspiece channel, insert the bolt.

Mortise and tenon it is joined with glue or wood glue, but the excess glue will go

into that bolt channel. To the technological process in the gluing phase is necessary the intervention of a worker to ensure the cleaning of the hole for the bolt after the gluing operation.

Figure 4 The crosspiece channel

In case of eccentric assembly highlighted in the images below, some processing on parts is no longer necessary. It can be noted those two tenons of 10 mm x 20 mm long without mortise and without bolt

channel. Through tenons in the middle of the crosspiece, it can be mounted in any position, thus choosing the most aesthetically favorable way.

Figure 5 **Eccentric assembly without mortises and without bolt channel**

Versus bolt assembly, eccentric assembly has the advantage of eliminating some processing on the part that is more difficult to realize and offers the possibility to choose how to mount the assembly

In the bolt assembly where the crosspiece with mortise is used, on the

crosspiece 3 holes of 30 mm are processed next to each other while are processed to eccentric assembly just a hole where the eccentric is inserted. This eliminates the processing of the three holes on automatic machines thus reducing assembly processing time and increasing the production of chairs.

Figure 6 a) **Crosspiece with 3 holes to bolt assembly**

b) **Crosspiece with 1 hole to eccentric assembly**

Figure 7 a) **Fixing the bolt**

b) **Eccentric assembly without bolt**

Bolt assembly it is mounted using a screwdriver to fix the bolt. In the case of eccentric assembly, the mounting of the bolt is eliminated

The disadvantage in the case of bolt assembly is the threading of the screw which requires a certain number of threads as well as the insertion of the crescent in the 3 holes.

Figure 8 a) threading of the screw

b) threading of the eccentric

With bolt assembly the threading time is longer than with eccentric assembly,

threading time is reduced using eccentric assembly

Figure 9 a) End of bolt assembly

b) End of eccentric assembly

CONCLUSIONS

After the tests it was concluded that:

- Eccentric assembly helps in processing the pieces by eliminating some processed on the parts
- There is no glue left in the holes after the parts are assembled
- A hole is easier to make than a mortise
- Versus bolt assembly, eccentric assembly has the advantage of eliminating some processing on the part that is more difficult to realize and

offers the possibility to choose how to mount the assembly

- Due to less processing, production costs decrease
- Increase production
- Eccentric assembly compared to conventional structures have a higher resistance to all types of stresses to which they are generally subjected.
- Practically, such a structure becomes indestructible regardless of the type of request to which the structure is subjected.

REFERENCES

- Catarig A, Kopenetz L., 2001, Construction Statics – Statically Indeterminate Structures: Matrix publishing house Rom, Bucharest, pp 56-78.;
- Cismaru, M., 2003. Wooden structures for furniture and finished products
- Curtu I.T. Mihaiescu, V. Nastase, D. Mihai, O. Stoian, 1988. Joints in wood, Structure, technology, reliability, Technical publishing house, Bucharest,
- Curtu I, Șerbu A.D., Sperchez Fl., Gonciar M., Florea R., Tudor E., 1981. Strength calculation in the wood industry, Technical publishing house,
- Curtu I., 1976, 1977. Material resistance, vol. I și II, Reprography of the University of Brașov,.
- Curtu I., 1978. The study of the torsion of wooden bars of rectangular section in the wood industry 29. nr. 3
- Fetea M. S. 2016, Study regarding the Wood Beams Response to Static and Dynamic Loading - Annals of the University of Oradea, Fascicle: Environmental Protection vol. XXVI -year 21 Publishing house of the University of Oradea pp 195 – 203
- Fetea M. S. 2017. Free vibrations study of wooden rectangular plate having a free edge - Annals of the University of Oradea, Fascicle: Environmental Protection vol. XXIX – year 22 Publishing house of the University of Oradea pp 173 – 181
- Fetea M. S, 2018. Theoretical and comparative study regarding the mechanical response under the static loading for different rectangular plates- Annals of the University of Oradea, Fascicle: Environmental Protection vol. XXXI – year 23 Publishing house of the University of Oradea pp 141 – 147
- Fetea M. S., 2019. Modal Analysis Study of Rectangular Wood Plates - Annals of the University of Oradea, Fascicle: Environmental Protection vol. XXXII – year 24 Publishing house of the University of Oradea pp 119 – 127
- Fetea M. S. 2019 - Dynamic analysis of vibrations modes for rectangular wood plates - Annals of the University of Oradea, Fascicle: Environmental Protection vol. XXXIII – year 24 Publishing house of the University of Oradea pp 133 – 141
- Fetea M. S., 2021. Analytical study of displacements and deformations of wooden beams using the method of initial parameters - Annals of the University of Oradea, Fascicle: Environmental Protection vol. XXXVI – year 26 Publishing house of the University of Oradea pp 169 – 177
- Goia I 2000. Material resistance, Transilvania Express Publishing House Brasov, pp. 38- 46
- Japan Timber Engineering Society 2012 ISBN 978-4-7530-1856-7 C3052. Inoue-shoin Co. Ltd., Tokyo, pp. 173–175
- Matsubara, D., Wakashima, Y., Fujisawa, Y. et al. 2018. Effects of tightening speed on torque coefficient in lag screw timber joints with steel side plates - [Journal of Wood Science](#) 64 ,112–118
- Missir-Vlad Ioana, 2002, Strength of Materials, Combined Static of Loading, Technical Publishing House-Info, Chișinău.
- <https://woodenmagazine.ro/2019/01/10/mortise-and-tenon-the-most-used-traditional-joint-for-furniture/>

THE VEGETATION OF THE SUBALPINE MEADOWS DEVELOPED BY *VIOLA DECLINATA* AND *NARDUS STRICTA* IN THE GILAU MOUNTAINS, CLUJ COUNTY.

Iosif-Constantin MATEȘ¹, Petru BURESCU²

¹ University of Oradea Faculty of Medicine and Pharmacy, Doctoral School of Biomedical Sciences, "Piața 1 Decembrie" Square, no 10, Bihor County, Oradea, Romania

² University of Oradea, Faculty of Environmental Protection, Oradea City, Magheru 26, 410087, Romania Institution

RESEARCH ARTICLE (REVIEW ARTICLE)

Abstract

The lifeforms (see Figure 1) show the dominance of hemicryptophytes (74.19%), followed at a great distance by phanerophytes (11.28%), chamaephytes (9.67%), geophytes (3.22%) and therophytes (1.61 %).

In the spectrum of floristic elements (see Figure 2), we may notice the high share of Eurasian species (29.03%), followed by circumpolar (22.58%), European (16.20%), Carpatho-Balkan (12.9%), central European (9.67%), cosmopolitan (6.45%), and Mediterranean (3.22%) species.

The ecological indices diagram (see Figure 3) highlights the predominance of mesophilic species (43.54%), followed by euryhydra (22.58%), xeromesophilic (20.96%) and mezzo-hygrophilic species with (11.28%). With regard air temperature, the majority species are microthermal (38.70%), closely followed by eurythermal (33.88%), micro-mesothermal (17.74%), cryophilic (6.44%) and moderately thermophilic (3.22%) species. As far as the chemical reaction of the soil is concerned, euriionic species are dominant (40.32%), followed by acidophilic (24.19%), acid-neutrophilic (17.74%), strongly acidophilic (11.29%), and weakly acid neutrophils (6.45%) species.

The karyological spectrum (see Figure 4) highlights the predominance of polyploids (46.77%) followed by diploids (30.46%), diplo-polyploids (20.96%), and species of unknown karyotype (1.61%). The diploidy index has a value of 0.65.

Keywords: phytocenoses, lifeforms, floristic elements, ecological indices, karyotype.

#Corresponding author: constantinmates@parcapuseni.ro

INTRODUCTION

Populations of *Nardus stricta* together with *Viola declinata* occupy large areas on plateaus or on slightly inclined slopes (2-10°) and with different exposures, growing on siliceous soils, short-profile spodosols, acidic and poorly aerated soils.

Phytocenoses developed by *Nardus stricta* are quite widespread in the mountain, subalpine and alpine floors, the *Viola declinatae-Nardetum strictae* association being described from the entire Carpathian chain as follows: Penteleu Massif (Serbănescu, 1939), Parang Mountains (Safta, 1943; Buia, 1959), Sebes Valley (Al.Borza, 1959), Bihor Mountains (Simon, 1966), Padis Plateau (Kovács et al., 1966), Rarau Mountains (Raclaru, 1967), Bucegi Mountains (Beldie, 1967), Ceahlau Mountains (Zanoschi, 1971), Siriu Mountain (Dihoru, 1975), Bodoc Mountains (Kovács, 1981), Retezat Mountains (Coldea, 1993), Fagaras Mountains (Stancu, 2005), Suhard Mountains (Costica et al., 2010), Orastie river basin (Vintan, 2014), the northern part of Bihor

Mountains (Togor, 2016). The phytocenoses of the association were found in some places within the the Bihor Mountains, Somesul Cald - Somesul Rece rivers interfluvial area: Petreasa, Salha Peak, Pietroasa, Fleiu, Bortita, Marsoaia, Somesul Rece river flood land, Racatau-Dorna Valley.

Type of habitat: R3609 - Southeastern Carpathian pastures with *Nardus stricta* and *Viola declinata*. Correspondences: NATURA 2000: 6230* Species-rich *Nardus* grasslands, on siliceous substrates in mountain areas; CORINE: Alpic mat-grass swards; EUNIS: E4.31 Alpic *Nardus stricta* swards and related communities; E4.3172 Eastern Carpathian mat-grass swards. Natural habitat of community interest, whose conservation requires the designation of special conservation areas (Donita et al., 2005).

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The material subjected to research consists of the meadows developed by *Nardus stricta* and *Viola declinata*, studied during the years 2018-2019, by surveying within the Western Carpathians (i.e. Apuseni) Mountains, Somesul Cald-Somesul Rece rivers interfluvial.

We carried out 10 phytocoenological surveys on the most representative phytocoenoses. All plant species found, with the assessment of abundance and dominance (AD) for each species according to the Braun-Blanquet scale (Braun-Blanquet et Pavillard 1928), were enclosed in the association table (see Table 1). The *Viola declinatae-Nardetum strictae* association was analyzed and characterized ecologically, phytocenologically, cytogenetically based on the association table and histograms with reference to the distribution of lifeforms, floristic elements, ecological indices, and genetic karyotypes.

Finding and description of the association were made based on the floristic criterion, with the help of characteristic, indicator, dominant and differential species. The name of the association is in accordance with the provisions established by the International Code of Phytosociological Nomenclature (Weber et al., 2000). Classification of species by corresponding coeno-taxonomic units (i.e. sub-alliances, alliances, orders, classes) was made in accordance with the ecological-floristic systems elaborated by Tüxen (Tüxen, 1955), and Braun-Blanquet (Braun-Blanquet, 1964), and on the basis of more recent works (Coldea et al., 1997 and Sanda et al., 2003, 2008).

The ecological and phytocoenological characterization of the species within the surveyed territory was made according to dedicated literature (Sanda et al., 2003), (Ciocarlan, 2009), (Sarbu et al., 2013).

The information on the value of ecological indices, lifeforms, floristic elements, and number of chromosomes are presented according to synthesis works elaborated by various researchers (Pop, 1977, 1982), (Sanda et al., 2003, 2008), (Cristea et al., 2004), (Ciocarlan, 2009), (Burescu et Toma, 2005), (Donita et al., 2005).

We carried out the analysis of phytocoenoses with regard the influence of ecological factors moisture (M), temperature (T) and soil chemical reaction (R) according to a previous paper works (Sanda et al., 2003), which adapted the ecological indices values for the plants in Central Europe on a 1 to 9 scale (Ellenberg, 1974) to the pedoclimatic conditions specific to Romania, by making use of scale ranging between 1 and 6. We made the classification of the species by the corresponding coenotaxa according to the

works of other authors (Borza et Boscaiu, 1965).

Cytogenetic analysis of species by karyotype thereof was done according to the works of Sanda et al., 2003.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The herbaceous layer (see Table 1) includes 62 phytotaxa, showing a high biodiversity.

The dominant and characteristic basic species is *Nardus stricta*, with a coverage of 70.83% ADm and maximum consistency (K=V), and the differential and characteristic species *Viola declinata* has a small coverage of only 0.5%, but a maximum consistency (K=V).

There are highlighted 13 species belonging to the alliance **Potentillo-Nardion** (i.e. *Arnica montana*, *Campanula abietina*, *Hieracium aurantiacum*, *Gnaphalium sylvaticum*, *Carex leporina*, *Antennaria dioica*, *Campanula rotundifolia* ssp. *polimorfa*, *Potentilla ternata*, *Danthonia decumbens*, *Campanula serrate*, *Scorzonera rosea*, *Hieracium officinarum*, *Hieracium umbellatum*), two species belonging to the alliance **Genistion pillosae** (i.e. *Vaccinium myrtillus*, *Vaccinium vitis-idaea*), and four species (i.e. *Potentilla erecta*, *Hypericum macullatum*, *Luzula sudetica*, *Festuca nigrescens*) belong to the order NARDETALIA and class **NARDO-CALLUNETEA**. A significant number of species migrated from the neighboring associations, where euriionic species are found, and they belong to the following classes: **MOLINIO-ARRHENATHERETEA** (*Festuca rubra*, *Agrostis capillaris*, *Cerastium holosteoides*, *Orchis ustulata*, *Trifolium repens*, *Leontodon hispidus*, etc.), **QUERCO-FAGETEA** (*Veronica officinalis*, *Hieracium transylvanicum*, *Trifolium medium*, *Aconitum lycoctonum* ssp. *vulparia*, etc.) and **VACCINIO-PICEETEA** (*Deschampsia flexuosa*, *Picea abies*, *Laserpitium krapfii*, *Calluna vulgaris*, *Bruckenthalia spiculifolia*, *Homogine alpine*, etc.).

From the lifeforms' perspective (see Figure 1), the species analysis shows the dominance of hemicryptophytes (74.19%), followed at a great distance by phanerophytes (11.28%), chamaephytes (9.67%), geophytes (3.22%), and therophytes (1.61%).

Regarding the share of floristic elements (see Figure 2), one can notice a high percentage of Eurasian species (29.03%), followed by circumpolar (22.58%), European (16.20%), Carpatho-Balkan (12.9%), Central European

(9.67%), Cosmopolitan (6.45%) and Mediterranean (3.22%) species.

The diagram of ecological indices (see Figure 3) shows the dominance of mesophilic species (43.54%), followed by eurihydric (22.58%), xeromesophilic (20.96%), and mezzo-hygrophilic (11.28%) species. Regarding the air temperature, the majority species are microthermal (38.70%), closely followed by eurythermal (33.88%), micro-mesothermal (17.74%), cryophilic (6.44%) and moderately thermophilic (3.22%) species. Following the analysis of the chemical reaction of the soil, euriionic species are dominant (40.32%), followed by acidophilic (24.19%), acid-neutrophilic (17.74%), strongly acidophilic (11.29%), and weakly acidic neutrophils (6.45%) species.

The karyological spectrum (see Figure 4) highlights the predominance of polyploids (46.77%) followed by diploids (30.46%) and

diplo-polyploids (20.96%). The diploidy index has a value of 0.65. The economic value of the mat-grass is low, and as far as the pastoral potential of these meadows is concerned, it is small due to the floristic composition encompassing few fodder species. This is due to the unfavorable climatic and vegetation conditions in which coenoses develop and overgrazing in these areas. The meadows have a low conservation value consisting of habitats of priority conservation interest at European level, sheltering several species of protected, endemic, vulnerable and rare plants placed on the Red List (i.e. *Viola declinata*, *Arnica montana*, *Campanula rotundifolia* ssp. *polymorpha*, *Scorzonella rosea*, *Campanula serrata*, *Orchis ustulata*). Through the strong development of the root system, they completely cover the soil, thus preventing its erosion. Figure 1 Spectrum of bioforms in the *Violo declinatae-Nardetum strictae* association

Figure 1 Spectrum of bioforms in the *Violo declinatae-Nardetum strictae* association

Legend: MPh = Megaphanerophytes; mPh = Mesophanerophytes; nPh = Nanophanerophytes; Ch = Chamaephytes; H = Hemicriptophytes; G = Geophytes Th = Annual terophytes.

Figure 2 The spectrum of floristic elements from the *Violo declinatae-Nardetum strictae* association

Legend: Cp= Circumpolar; Eua= Eurasian; E= European; Ec= Central European; Carp-B = Carpatho-Balkan; Arct-Alp = Arctic-Alpine; Cosm= Cosmopolitan; M= Mediterranean.

Figure 3. Ecological indices diagram for the *Viola declinatae-Nardetum strictae* association

Figure 4. The karyological spectrum for the *Viola declinatae-Nardetum strictae* association
 Legend: D = Diploids; P = Polyploids; DP = Dipopoliploids; N = Unknown karyotype.

Table 1

Viola declinata-*Nardetum strictae* Simon, 1966

Lifeforms	Floristic elements	M	T	R	G	Survey no.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	K	ADm
						Altitudine (mamsl)	1641	1668	1663	1546	1260	1315	1345	1363	1310	1369		
						Exposure	V	-	E	S	S	V	-	E	-	V		
						Slope (°)	2	-	6	2	10	8	-	4	-	10		
						Grass layer coverage (%)	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100		
						Area (sq.m.)	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	200	100	100		
H	Carp-B	3.5	2	2	DP	<i>As. Viola declinata</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	V	0.5
H	Eua	0	0	1.5	D	<i>As. Nardus stricta</i>	5	5	5	5	4	5	5	5	4	4	V	80
Potentillo - Nardion																		
H	E	3	2.5	3	P	<i>Arnica montana</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+	.	+	.	.	IV	0.35
H	Carp-B	3.5	2	2	P	<i>Campanula abietina</i>	.	.	+	.	.	+	+	+	+	+	III	0.3
H	Cp	3	3	3	P	<i>Gnaphalium sylvaticum</i>	.	+	+	.	+	.	+	+	.	.	III	0.25
H	E	3.5	2	4	P	<i>Hieracium aurantiacum</i>	+	+	+	II	0.15
H	M	0	3	2	P	<i>Danthonia decumbens</i>	+	+	+	.	.	.	II	0.15
H	E	2.5	0	0	DP	<i>Hieracium officinarum</i>	+	+	+	.	.	II	0.15
H	Cp	4	2.5	3	P	<i>Carex leporina</i>	.	+	+	.	.	I	0.1
H	Cp	3	1	2.5	P	<i>Antennaria dioica</i>	.	+	I	0.05
H	Cp	2	0	3	DP	<i>Campanula rotundifolia ssp. polymorpha</i>	.	.	+	I	0.05
H	Carp-B	0	1.5	2	N	<i>Potentilla ternata</i>	+	.	.	I	0.05
G	Alp-Carp-B	2	0	4	D	<i>Scorzonera rosea</i>	+	I	0.05
H	Carp-B	0	2.5	0	DP	<i>Campanula serrata</i>	+	I	0.05
H	Cp	2.5	3	0	DP	<i>Hieracium umbellatum</i>	+	I	0.05
Genistion pillosae																		
Ch-nPh	Cp-Bo	0	2	1	D	<i>Vaccinium myrtillus</i>	+	+	+	+	1	+	+	+	.	2	V	2.6
Ch-nPh	Cp-Bo	3	2	1	D	<i>Vaccinium vitis idaea</i>	+	.	1	1	+	+	.	+	+	+	V	1.35
Nardetalia et Nardo - Callunetea																		
H	Eua	0	0	0	P	<i>Potentilla erecta</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+	1	+	+	+	V	0.95

H	Eua	4	3	2	DP	<i>Hypericum maculatum</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	V	0.5	
H	Eua	0	2	2	P	<i>Luzula sudetica</i>	.	+	+	.	.	I	0.1	
H	E	3	1	2	P	<i>Festuca nigrescens</i>	1	.	.	I	0.5	
Molinio - Arrhenatheretea																			
H	Cp-Bo	3	0	0	DP	<i>Festuca rubra</i>	+	+	1	+	+	+	2	.	1	1	V	3.5	
H	Cp	0	0	0	P	<i>Agrostis capillaris</i>	+	+	.	+	+	.	+	.	.	.	III	0.25	
H-Ch	Cosm	3	0	0	P	<i>Cerastium holosteoides</i>	.	+	.	+	.	.	+	+	+	.	III	0.25	
H	Eua	2.5	2	3	D	<i>Stellaria graminea</i>	.	.	.	+	+	.	+	+	+	.	III	0.25	
H	Eua	3.5	3	3	D	<i>Agrostis canina</i>	+	+	+	II	0.15	
H	Eua	3.5	0	0	P	<i>Trifolium repens</i>	.	.	.	+	.	.	+	.	+	+	II	0.2	
G	E	2.5	3	0	DP	<i>Orchis ustulata</i>	+	+	+	I	0.15	
H	Eua	2.5	0	0	DP	<i>Leontodon hispidus</i>	.	.	+	+	.	I	0.1	
H-Ch	E	3	3	3	P	<i>Polygala vulgaris</i>	+	.	.	.	I	0.05	
H	Cosm	4	0	0	DP	<i>Deschampsia cespitosa</i>	+	.	I	0.05	
H	Cosm	3	0	0	P	<i>Poa platensis</i>	+	.	I	0.05	
H	Cosm	4.5	3	3	P	<i>Juncus effusus</i>	+	I	0.05	
H	Ec	3	2.5	3	D	<i>Centaurea phrygia</i>	+	+	I	0.1	
H	Eua	0	0	0	P	<i>Anthoxanthum odoratum</i>	+	+	I	0.1	
Th	E	3	3	0	P	<i>Euphrasia stricta</i>	+	.	I	0.05	
H	Eua	0	3	0	DP	<i>Briza media</i>	+	I	0.05	
H-Ch	Eua	3	0	0	P	<i>Veronica chamaedrys</i>	+	.	.	I	0.05	
H	Eua	0	0	0	D	<i>Plantago lanceolata</i>	+	.	I	0.05	
Quercio - Fagetea																			
Ch	Eua	2	2	2	P	<i>Veronica officinalis</i>	.	+	+	.	+	.	+	+	+	+	IV	0.35	
H	Carp-B	3	0	0	D	<i>Hieracium transylvanicum</i>	+	+	+	.	+	+	III	0.25	
H	Eua	3	3	0	P	<i>Trifolium medium</i>	+	.	+	.	.	.	I	0.1	
H	Ec	4	2.5	4	D	<i>Aconitum lycoctonum ssp.vulparia</i>	I	0.05	
H	Ec-M	3	2.5	3	P	<i>Senecio ovatus</i>	.	.	.	+	I	0.05	
MPh	Eua	3	2	2	P	<i>Betula pendula</i>	+	I	0.05	
MPh	Eua	3	2	2	DP	<i>Populus tremula</i>	+	I	0.05	
Fragaria vesca																			
H	Eua	3	2.5	0	D	<i>Fragaria vesca</i>	+	.	.	I	0.05	
Vaccinio - Piceetea																			
H	Cp	2	0	1	P	<i>Deschampsia flexuosa</i>	+	+	+	1	1	+	+	1	1	1	V	2.75	
MPh	E	0	0	0	D	<i>Picea abies</i>	+	.	.	.	+	+	+	+	.	+	III	0.25	
H	Ec	0	0	3	D	<i>Laserpitium krapfii</i>	+	.	1	+	+	+	III	0.7	
Ch	Atl-Ec	0	0	1	D	<i>Calluna vulgaris</i>	+	.	.	+	+	II	0.1	
nPh	Carp-B-Anat	2.5	2.5	1.5	P	<i>Bruckenthalia spiculifolia</i>	+	.	.	+	I	0.1	
H	E	3.5	2.5	2.5	P	<i>Homogyne alpina</i>	.	+	I	0.05	
mPh	Cp-Bo	2	0	0	D	<i>Juniperus communis</i>	+	+	.	I	0.1	
MPh	E	3	2.5	2	D	<i>Sorbus aucuparia</i>	+	I	0.05	
H-G	Cp	3	2	2.5	D	<i>Moneses uniflora</i>	+	I	0.05	
Ch	Cp-Bo	5	2.5	1	P	<i>Lycopodium annotinum</i>	+	.	I	0.05	
Variae syntaxa																			
Ch	MP	2	4	0	DP	<i>Thymus glabrescens</i>	+	+	+	.	.	.	II	0.15	
mPh	Carp-B-Sudet	4	2	2	D	<i>Salix silesiaca</i>	+	.	+	I	0.1
H	Eua	2	4	4	D	<i>Scabiosa ochroleuca</i>	+	I	0.05	
H	Ec	3.5	2.5	0	P	<i>Knautia dipsacifolia</i>	+	.	+	I	0.1	
H	Cp	4	1.5	0	P	<i>Epilobium anagallidifolium</i>	.	+	I	0.05	

Location and date of surveys: 1. Petreasa (Franturi), 06.08.2018, GPS 463257,6, 225847,5; 2-3. Salha Peak, 06.08.2018, GPS 463309,2, 230000, 463303,2, 230009,3; 4. Pi 06.08.2018, GPS 463251,1, 225807, 463259, 225742,9; 5-6. Fleiu, 07.08.2018, GPS 463109,7, 225207,9, 463126,2, 225210,5; 7. Marsoaia, 14.09.2018, GPS 463220,4, 2251 Somesul Rece river flood land, 22.07.2019, GPS 463220,1, 230351,3,; 9-10. Racatau-Dorna Valley, 10.08.2019, GPS 463342,6, 230245,1, 463346,9, 230315,5.

CONCLUSIONS

1. Formation of the association encompasses 62 phytotaxa which, considering the difficult development conditions, proves a high biodiversity.
2. Analysis of lifeforms shows the dominance of hemicryptophytes (74.19%).
3. With regard the share of floristic elements, one can notice a high percentage of Eurasian species (29.03%).
4. The diagram of ecological indices highlights the predominance of mesophils (43.54%), euryhydric (22.58%), microthermal (38.70%), eurythermic (33.88%), euryionic (40.32%) and acidophilic (24.19%) species.
5. The association shelters six plant species considered to be protected, endemic, vulnerable and rare, being included on the Red List (i.e. *Viola declinata*, *Arnica montana*, *Campanula rotundifolia* ssp. *polymorpha*, *Scorzonella rosea*, *Campanula serrata*, *Orchis ustulata*).

REFERENCES

- Beldie, A., 1967. Endemisms and Dacian elements in the flora of the Romanian Carpathians, *Comunicări Botanice* magazine, SSNG, 113-130;
- Borza, Al., 1959. The flora and vegetation of the Sebeş valley, Romanian Academy Publishing House, Bucharest, 326 p.;
- Borza, Al., Boşcaiu, N., 1965. Introduction in the study of the living soil cover, Romania Edit. Acad. R.P.R., Bucharest, 340 p.;
- Borhidi, A., 1971. *Die Zönologie der Fichtenwälder von Ost-und Südcarpateen*, Acta Bot. Hung., 17, Budapest, 3-4:287-319;
- Braun-Blanquet, J., 1964. *Pflanzensoziologie*, ed.III Springer-Verlag, Wien-New York.
- Braun-Blanquet, J., Pavillard, G., 1928. *Vocabulaire de sociologie végétale*, ed.II, Imprimerie Roumegous & Dehan, Montpellier;
- Buia, Al., Păun, M., Safta, I., Pop, M., 1959. Geobotanical contributions on the pastures and hayfields of Oltenia. Scientific papers of Agricultural Institute "Tudor Vladimirescu", Craiova, 93-183;
- Burescu, P., Toma, I., 2005. Manual of practical works in botany, Oradea University Press, Oradea, 590 p.;
- Ciocârlan, V., 2009. Illustrated flora of Romania: Pteridophyta et Spermatophyta, Ceres Publishing House, Bucharest, 1141 p.;
- Coldea, Gh., Plămadă, E., 1970. Contributions to the study of the class Scheuchzerio-Caricetea fuscae Nordh. 1936, in Romania (I), Hydrobiology, Bucharest, 11:105-116;
- Coldea, Gh., 1991. Prodrôme des associations végétales des Carpates du Sud-Est (Carpates Roumaines), Documents Phytosociologiques, N.S., XIII, Camerino, 317-539;
- Coldea, Gh., 1993. Cormophytes. Syntaxonomy and description of plant associations in Retezat National Park. Ecological studies, Editor I. Popovici, Brasov, 1992, 31-48;
- Coldea, Gh., Sanda, V., Popescu, A., Ştefan, N., 1997. Les associations végétales de Roumanie. Tome I: Les associations herbacées naturelles, Edit. Presa Universitară Clujeană, Cluj-Napoca, 261 p.;
- Costică, M., Ştefan, N., Sârbu, I., 2010. Contribution to the study of the wood vegetation from the Suhard Mountain, *Analele Univ. „Al.I.Cuza”*, s.II Biologie Vegetală, Iaşi, 56, 1:65-81;
- Cristea, V., Gafta, D., Pedrotti, F., 2004. *Fitosociologie (Phytosociology)*, Cluj Napoca University Press, Cluj-Napoca, 396 p.;
- Dihoru, Gh., 1975. Living soil cover in Siriu Mountain, Romanian Academy Publishing House, Bucharest, 216 p.;
- Doniţă, N., Popescu, A., Paucă-Comănescu, M., Mihăilescu, M., Biriş, I.A., 2005. Habitats in Romania, Editura Tehnică Silvică Publishing House, Bucharest, 496 p.;
- Kovács, A., Coman, N., Peterfi, Şt., 1966. Phytocenological research on the Padiş Plateau *Studia Univ. „Babeş-Bolyai”*, Biololy series, f.1, Cluj-Napoca, 33-41;
- Kovács, A., 1981. Flora and vegetation of the Bodoc Mountains, Aluta. Studies and Communications Covasna County Museum, Sfântu Gheorghe, 11-13:363-405;
- Ellenberg, H., 1974. Zeigerwerte der Gefässpflanzen Mitteleuropas, *Scripta Geobotanica*, Göttingen, 9:1-97;
- Pop, I., 1977. Ecological biogeography, vol. I. Dacia Publishing House, Cluj-Napoca;
- Pop, I., Hodişan, I., Raţiu, O., Cristea, V., Marcu, A., 1984. The study of spruce-beech and mountain spruces along the course of the Somesul Rece river valley (Cluj county), *Botanical contributions*, Cluj-Napoca, 75-83;
- Raclaru, P., 1967. The vegetation of the meadows of the Rarău Massif, *Communications on Botany*, 5th Conference on Geobotany, Bucharest, 143-178;
- Safta, I., 1943. Geobotanical research on Transylvanian pastures, *Bulletin of Faculty of Agronomy of Cluj, Timisoara*, 10:3-107;
- Sanda, V., Biţă-Nicolae, C., Barabaş, N., 2003. The flora of spontaneous and cultivated cormophytes from Romania, „Ion Borcea” Publishing House, Bacau, 316 p.;
- Sanda, V., Öllerer, K., Burescu, P., 2008. Phytocoenoses from Romania. Syntaxonomy, structure, dynamics and evolution. „Ars Docendi” Publishing House, Bucharest, 570 p.;
- Simon, T., 1966. Beiträge zur kenntnis der vegetation des Bihar (Bihor)-Gebirges, *Annales Univ. Scient. Budapest., sect. Biol.*, Budapest, 8, 253-273;
- Stancu, I.D., 2005. The flora and vegetation of the Raiosu and Buda Mountains, the Fagaraş Massif Pitesti University Press;

Sârbu, I., Ștefan, N., Oprea, A., 2013. Vascular plants from Romania: Illustrated determinants collected in the field, Victor B Victor Publishing House, Bucharest, 1320 p.;

Togor ,G.C., 2016. The flora and vegetation of the northern part of the Bihor Mountains, PhD thesis, University of Oradea, 496 p.;

Tüxen, R., 1955. Das System der nordwestdeutschen Pflanzengesellschaften, Mitt. Florist.-Soz. Arbeitsgem. N. F., 5:155-176;

Vințan, V. I., 2014. The flora and vegetation of the Orastie river basin PhD Thesis, University of Oradea, Oradea, 627p.;

Weber, H.E., Moravec, J., Theurillat, J.P., 2000. International Code of Phytosociological Nomenclature, 3 ed., Journal of Vegetation Science, Uppsala, 739-768;

Zanoschi, V., 1971. A contribution to the knowledge of the vegetation of the Ceahlău Massif, Biological research and studies, Botanical Series, Bucharest, 23, 4:347-3.

EVALUATION OF THE PRODUCTIVITY OF PERMANENT GRASSLANDS FROM THE BELIȘ-FÂNTÂNELE RESERVOIR AREA (CLUJ COUNTY)

Călin Gheorghe PĂȘCUȚ¹, Alina Emilia Maria GHERDAN¹, Valeriu Adrian ȘTEF¹,
Andrea-Maria PĂȘCUȚ²

¹ University of Oradea, Faculty of Environmental Protection, 26 Gen. Magheru St., 410048 Oradea, Romania

² Partenie Cosma Economic College, 1F Calea Armatei Române St., 410087 Oradea, Romania

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

This paper represents a case study regarding the evaluation of the productivity of permanent grasslands in the Beliș-Fântânele reservoir area based on the floristic relevés. The main types of grasslands studied in the area are *Festuca rubra*-*Agrostis capillaris* and *Nardus stricta*-*Festuca rubra*, located on lithological substrates formed by acidic rocks. Following the floristic study and the assessment of the participation weight of the component species in each type of grassland green mass production of 12.63 t/ha was determined, with an animal load of 0.98 livestock units UVM/ha in the case of *Festuca rubra*-*Agrostis capillaris* grasslands and a green mass production of 1.41 t/ha with a load of 0.16 livestock units UVM/ha in the case of *Nardus stricta*-*Festuca rubra* grasslands. The very poor productivity of grasslands consisting of *Nardus stricta* and *Festuca rubra* it is mostly due to the fact that they are not grazed by animals, being invaded by woody subshrub and shrub species. The data provided by the present study are useful in characterizing the pastoral quality of these grasslands in the context of the improvement and rational use of the pastoral fund.

Keywords: grasslands, green mass production, pastoral value, cargo with animals, floristic relevés

Corresponding author: pascutcalin@yahoo.com

INTRODUCTION

Considering the fact that determining the production of green mass of pastures by the classical method is quite difficult, a new method based on the floristic relevés with the percentage assessment of the species in the grass carpet was proposed (Marușca, 2019).

The studies and researches regarding the vegetation of the grasslands in our country generally contain little information regarding their green mass production. These grasslands productivity studies are useful in determining the optimal grazing capacity, improvement and rational management of the pastoral fund.

At the present time, animal breeding systems based on the utilization of grasslands, have to cope with the growing needs of food. The production of fodder obtained from these areas must be consistent with the increasing demands for meat and milk, as well as with climate change (Marușca et al., 2014).

The grasslands that are the subject of this study are located near the Beliș-Fântânele reservoir in Cluj county. Beliș-Fântânele lake is located in the western part of Cluj county, in the

northern area of the Apuseni Mountains, at the confluence of the Gilău Mountains to the east, the Vlădeasa Mountains to the west and the Mare Mountain to the south. The grasslands in the vicinity of the reservoir cover an area of 1450 ha, being generally formed by *Festuca rubra*, *Agrostis capillaris* and *Nardus stricta*.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

For the percentage assessment of the species in the grassy carpet (AD-abundance-dominance) the Braun-Blanquet scale was used, which has the following values: +0.5%; 1-5.0%; 2-17.5%; 3-37.5%; 4-62.5%; 5-87.5% (Cristea et al., 2004). The botanical nomenclature used for the identified species is in accordance with the works elaborated by Ciocârlan (2009) and Sârbu et al. (2013). Considering the fact that large differences occur between abundance-dominance appreciation grades, which can be 25% between grades 4 to 5, 3 to 4, and 20% between grades 2 to 3, a new formula was adopted to transform AD intervals into participation percentages, taking into account the general frequency (K) of the respective species, presented in the works developed by

Marușca, 2019; Marușca et al., 2020; Pășcuț & Marușca, 2020.

The floristic relevées were carried out in the most representative points, the GPS coordinates, altitude, exposition, slope, relief form, grass vegetation cover and woody vegetation cover being reproduced for each separate survey. The ordering of species in the table which shows the floristic composition for each type of grassland begins with *Poaceae*, *Fabaceae* and other families. Relevées with an area of 400 m² were used in the study of the floristic composition of these grasslands.

After transforming the phytocoenological ratings into appreciation percentages, next to each species in the floristic survey, the fodder quality index (F) and useful phytomass index (M) are written (Păcurar & Rotar, 2014; Marușca, 2019; Marușca et al., 2019; Marușca et al., 2020; Pășcuț & Pantea, 2021). The fodder quality index (F) has the following values: F1-F3 (harmful species), F4-F9 (species with fodder value). Values for the forage phytomass index (M) range from M1-M9 for useful phytomass species and M0 for F1-F3 values.

In order to determine the pastoral value (PV) and the production of green forage (GM), we used the method proposed by Marușca (2019) and applied in the previous manuscripts submitted and published by this journal (Marușca et al., 2019; Marușca, 2021; Marușca & Pășcuț, 2022), which we won't detail anymore. Based on these data, the optimal animal loading or grazing capacity (GC) expressed in large cattle unit (UL) per hectare is further determined according to the formula:

$$GC \text{ (UL/ha)} = \frac{GM \text{ (kg/ha)}}{Rd \times Gd}$$

where: Rd - daily requirements for grass for 1 UL, 65 kg, respectively 50 kg + 15 kg (30%

- season climatic fluctuations and unconsumed remains); Gd - number of grazing days (season).

For the grasslands in the area of the Beliș-Fântânele reservoir, the duration of the grazing season is 130 days.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

As a result of the study of the grasslands in the Beliș-Fântânele reservoir area, two main types of meadows were identified, namely *Festuca rubra-Agrostis capillaris* and *Nardus stricta-Festuca rubra*.

The floristic study of these grasslands was carried out in 2022, with a total of 16 relevées carried out, 9 relevées in *Festuca rubra* meadows with *Agrostis capillaris* and 7 relevées in *Nardus stricta* meadows with *Festuca rubra*.

The *Festuca rubra-Agrostis capillaris* grasslands type is present on slopes with generally sunny exposures (S, SE, SW), at altitudes of 1015-1265 m and terrain inclination of 0-15 degrees (table 1). In this type of grassland, the grassy vegetation has a high coverage (87-93%), being built up by *Festuca rubra* (50%) and in a smaller percentage by *Agrostis capillaris* (21.3%). In these grasslands there are also other species from the *Poaceae* family, *Nardus stricta* (11.3%), *Holcus lanatus* (2%), *Deshampsia flexuosa* (1.4%), with low fodder quality, the rest having an insignificant weight. The *Fabaceae* family is represented by *Trifolium repens*, *Trifolium montanum*, *Trifolium pratense*, *Lotus corniculatus*, with good fodder value but with a low percentage weight. Some toxic and harmful species for animals are also present in these meadows: *Hypericum maculatum*, *Ranunculus acris*, *Rumex conglomeratus*, *Pteridium aquilinum*, *Veratrum album*, *Carduus acanthoides*, *Colchicum autumnale*, *Rumex alpinus*.

Table 1

Floristic composition of the *Festuca rubra-Agrostis capillaris* grasslands

No. relevées	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	K	Participation P (%)	Indices		
Altitude (m.s.m.)	1145	1100	1125	1150	1240	1265	1040	1050	1015					
Exposition	SV, V	E	V, SV	S, SE	S	S	-	V	N					
Slope (°)	5	8	12	10	8	15	-	10	5					
Area	400	400	400	400	400	400	400	400	400					
GPS coordonates	Lat. N	46.68113	46.67664	46.67543	46.66844	46.67378	46.67886	46.64168	46.64689	46.65815				
	Long. E	23.05864	23.03060	22.99784	22.96795	22.95200	22.94407	22.85626	22.91456	22.93478				
General coverage (%)	100	100	97	98	97	99	100	100	100					
Grass vegetation cover (%)	89	89	89	88	87	91	93	92	91					
Woody vegetation cover (%)	11	11	11	12	13	9	7	8	9					
Molehills (%)	10	20	3	2	1	10	15	25	8					
Landform	side	side	side	side	side	side	plateau	side	side			F M		
	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13
Poaceae														
<i>Festuca rubra</i>	3	3	3	3	3	4	4	4	3	V	50	7	6	
<i>Agrostis capillaris</i>	2	3	2	2	3	1	1	1	3	V	21.3	7	5	
<i>Nardus stricta</i>	2	1	1	1	+	1	1	1	1	V	11.3	3	0	

0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13
<i>Holcus lanatus</i>	+	+	+	•	+	•	+	1	•	IV	2	6	6
<i>Anthoxanthum odoratum</i>	+	+	+	+	+	•	+	•	+	IV	0.4	5	3
<i>Deshampsia flexuosa</i>	•	•	1	•	+	1	•	•	•	III	1.4	4	3
<i>Poa pratensis</i>	•	+	•	•	+	•	•	+	+	III	0.3	8	6
<i>Cynosurus cristatus</i>	+	•	•	+	+	•	+	•	•	III	0.3	7	4
<i>Danthonia decumbens</i>	+	•	•	+	+	+	•	•	•	III	0.3	4	3
<i>Deschampsia cespitosa</i>	•	•	+	+	+	•	•	+	+	III	0.3	3	0
<i>Lolium perenne</i>	•	•	•	•	•	•	+	•	+	II	0.2	9	8
<i>Phleum montanum</i>	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	+	+	II	0.2	6	5
<i>Briza media</i>	•	•	+	•	•	•	•	+	•	II	0.2	5	2
Fabaceae													
<i>Trifolium repens</i>	+	+	+	+	+	•	+	+	+	V	0.5	8	5
<i>Trifolium montanum</i>	+	+	+	•	+	+	+	•	•	IV	0.4	7	4
<i>Trifolium pratense</i>	•	•	+	+	•	•	+	•	•	III	0.3	8	7
<i>Lotus corniculatus</i>	+	•	+	•	•	•	+	•	•	II	0.2	8	6
<i>Anthyllis vulneraria</i>	•	•	•	•	+	+	•	•	•	II	0.2	6	5
<i>Genista sagittalis</i>	+	•	•	•	•	+	+	•	•	II	0.2	3	0
Other families													
<i>Thymus pulegioides</i>	+	+	+	•	+	+	+	+	+	V	0.5	3	0
<i>Achillea millefolium</i>	+	+	•	1	+	•	+	+	+	IV	2	6	4
<i>Alchemilla vulgaris</i>	+	+	+	+	•	•	+	1	+	IV	2	6	4
<i>Juncus conglomeratus</i>	+	+	1	1	•	•	+	•	+	IV	2	3	0
<i>Luzula luzuloides</i>	•	•	+	1	•	+	+	•	•	IV	2	3	0
<i>Plantago lanceolata</i>	•	+	+	+	•	+	+	•	+	IV	0.4	6	1
<i>Leontodon autumnalis</i>	+	+	•	+	•	•	+	+	+	IV	0.4	5	3
<i>Potentilla erecta</i>	+	+	+	•	•	•	+	+	+	IV	0.4	5	2
<i>Fragaria vesca</i>	•	+	•	+	+	+	+	+	•	IV	0.4	5	1
<i>Hieracium pilosella</i>	•	+	+	•	+	+	•	+	+	IV	0.4	4	1
<i>Viola canina</i>	•	+	•	+	+	+	+	•	+	IV	0.4	4	1
<i>Gnaphalium sylvaticum</i>	+	•	+	+	+	+	•	•	•	IV	0.4	3	0
<i>Plantago media</i>	+	•	•	+	+	•	•	+	•	III	0.3	6	2
<i>Bellis perennis</i>	+	•	•	•	•	•	+	•	+	III	0.3	5	1
<i>Carex pallescens</i>	+	+	+	+	•	•	+	•	•	III	0.3	4	3
<i>Prunella vulgaris</i>	+	+	+	•	•	•	+	•	•	III	0.3	4	2
<i>Veronica chamaedrys</i>	•	•	+	•	+	•	•	+	+	III	0.3	4	2
<i>Cerastium holosteoides</i>	•	+	•	•	•	•	+	+	+	III	0.3	3	0
<i>Cruciata glabra</i>	•	•	+	+	•	•	+	+	•	III	0.3	3	0
<i>Juncus tenuis</i>	•	+	+	•	•	•	+	•	+	III	0.3	3	0
<i>Veronica officinalis</i>	+	+	•	•	•	+	+	+	•	III	0.3	3	0
<i>Urtica dioica</i>	+	•	+	•	•	•	+	•	•	II	0.2	5	7
<i>Cichorium intybus</i>	•	+	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	II	0.2	5	6
<i>Leucanthemum vulgare</i>	•	•	•	•	+	+	•	•	•	II	0.2	5	5
<i>Filipendula vulgaris</i>	•	•	+	•	+	•	•	•	•	II	0.2	5	4
<i>Polygala vulgaris</i>	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	+	+	II	0.2	4	1
<i>Achillea distans</i>	•	•	+	+	•	+	•	•	•	II	0.2	3	0
<i>Campanula abietina</i>	•	•	+	+	•	•	•	•	+	II	0.2	3	0
<i>Campanula serata</i>	•	•	•	•	+	+	•	•	•	II	0.2	3	0
<i>Carlina acaulis</i>	•	•	•	•	+	•	+	•	•	II	0.2	3	0
<i>Centaurea phrygia</i>	•	•	+	+	•	•	+	•	•	II	0.2	3	0
<i>Euphrasia rostkoviana</i>	+	•	•	•	+	•	•	•	+	II	0.2	3	0
<i>Hypochaeris radicata</i>	•	•	•	+	+	•	•	•	•	II	0.2	3	0
<i>Luzula sylvatica</i>	•	•	•	•	+	+	•	•	•	II	0.2	3	0
<i>Rumex acetosella</i>	•	+	•	•	•	•	+	•	•	II	0.2	3	0
<i>Epilobium palustre</i>	•	•	+	•	•	•	•	•	•	I	0.1	4	4
<i>Luzula campestris</i>	•	•	•	•	•	•	+	•	•	I	0.1	4	2
<i>Angelica sylvestris</i>	•	•	+	•	•	•	•	•	•	I	0.1	3	0
<i>Carex nigra</i>	•	•	+	•	•	•	•	•	•	I	0.1	3	0
<i>Centaureum erythraea</i>	•	+	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	I	0.1	3	0
<i>Cirsium canum</i>	•	•	+	•	•	•	•	•	•	I	0.1	3	0
<i>Cirsium erisithales</i>	•	•	+	•	•	•	•	•	•	I	0.1	3	0
<i>Filipendula ulmaria</i>	•	•	+	•	•	•	•	•	•	I	0.1	3	0
<i>Juncus inflexus</i>	•	•	•	•	•	•	+	•	•	I	0.1	3	0
<i>Succisa pratensis</i>	•	•	+	•	•	•	•	•	•	I	0.1	3	0
Shrubs, subshrubs and invasive young trees													
<i>Picea abies</i>	•	1	1	+	+	+	•	1	1	IV	2	3	0
<i>Salix cinerea</i>	•	•	1	+	+	+	•	+	+	IV	2	3	0
<i>Betula pendula</i>	•	•	+	•	+	+	•	•	+	III	0.3	3	0
<i>Sorbus aucuparia</i>	•	•	•	+	•	+	•	+	+	III	0.3	3	0
<i>Sambucus racemosa</i>	+	•	•	•	•	+	•	•	+	II	0.2	3	0
<i>Vaccinium myrtillus</i>	1	+	+	1	1	1	1	+	+	V	2.8	3	0
<i>Vaccinium vitis-idaea</i>	1	1	+	1	+	+	+	+	+	V	2.8	3	0
<i>Calluna vulgaris</i>	•	+	•	•	1	+	+	+	+	IV	2	3	0
<i>Rubus idaeus</i>	+	•	•	+	+	•	+	+	+	IV	2	3	0
Toxic and harmful plants													
<i>Hypericum maculatum</i>	1	+	+	•	+	+	+	+	•	IV	2	1	0
<i>Ranunculus acris</i>	+	+	+	•	+	•	+	•	+	IV	0.4	1	0
<i>Rumex conglomeratus</i>	•	•	+	+	•	•	+	•	•	III	0.3	2	0
<i>Pteridium aquilinum</i>	•	•	•	•	+	1	•	•	•	II	0.8	1	0
<i>Veratrum album</i>	•	•	+	•	•	+	•	•	•	II	0.2	1	0
<i>Carduus acanthoides</i>	•	•	+	+	•	•	+	•	•	II	0.2	2	0
<i>Colchicum autumnale</i>	•	•	+	+	•	•	•	•	•	II	0.2	1	0
<i>Rumex alpinus</i>	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	+	•	I	0.1	2	0

The localities and date where the relevées were carried out: 1-2 Beliș (12.10.2022); 3 – Bălcești (12.10.2022); 4-6 Dealul Botii (12.10.2022); 7 - Smida (12.10.2022); 8-9 Giurcuța de Sus (15.10.2022). Where: F – fodder quality indices; M – production indices; K – constancy; AD values (Abundance-Dominance): +-0.5%; 1-5.0%; 2-17.5%; 3-37.5%; 4-62.5%; 5-87.5%.

In these grasslands there are also some subshrub, shrubby and young invasive tree species (7-13%), of which the most representative are *Picea abies*, *Salix cinerea*, *Vaccinium myrtillus*, *Vaccinium vitis-idaea*,

Calluna vulgaris, *Rubus idaeus*. Some sub-shrub and shrub species are located on molehills, which have a high weight in some relevés (1-25%) (figure 1).

Figure 1 *Festuca rubra*-*Agrostis capillaris* grasslands, with molehills and woody shrubby vegetation (a - Smida, relevée No. 7, b - Dealul Botii, relevée No. 5)

Acidophilic grasslands of *Nardus stricta* and *Festuca rubra* were identified on slopes with different exposures (S, SE, SW, N, NE), at altitudes of 1100-1260 m on terrain with a gentle to strongly inclined slope (0-25 degrees) (table 2).

Grassy vegetation has a different coverage, ranging from 27-92%, the dominant species being *Nardus stricta* (40%), followed by *Festuca rubra* (9%). Among the species of the *Poaceae* family found in this type of meadow, we mention *Deschampsia flexuosa*, *Agrostis capillaris*, *Holcus lanatus*,

Anthoxanthum odoratum, *Danthonia decumbens*, *Deschampsia cespitosa* which have a low participation rate.

From the *Fabaceae* family, *Trifolium repens*, *Trifolium montanum*, *Genista sagittalis*, *Trifolium alpestre*, *Genista tinctoria* are present, which have a total participation percentage of 1.3%, insignificant for increasing the forage quality of these grasslands.

In these grasslands there are also some toxic and harmful species present in small numbers, namely: *Hypericum maculatum*, *Pteridium aquilinum*, *Rumex alpinus*.

Table 2

Floristic composition of the *Nardus stricta*-*Festuca rubra* grasslands

No. relevées	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	K	Participation P (%)	Indices	
Altitude (m.s.m.)	1130	1140	1260	1115	1180	1115	1100				
Exposition	-	S	S	S	S, SE	N, NE	V, SV				
Slope (°)	-	15	25	12	18	10	20				
Area	400	400	400	400	400	400	400				
GPS coordonates	Lat. N 46.6801546.6674346.6762746.6658146.6348246.6411346.64577										
	Long. E 23.0083523.0107022.9387122.9183922.9071122.9159122.92627										
General coverage (%)	100	100	100	100	98	100	100				
Grass vegetation cover (%)	79	27	54	31	92	88	30				
Woody vegetation cover (%)	21	73	46	69	8	12	70				
Molehills (%)	25	10	35	30	30	5	25				
Landform	plateau	side	side	side	side	side	side			F	M
Poaceae											
<i>Nardus stricta</i>	4	2	3	2	4	4	2	V	40	3	0
<i>Festuca rubra</i>	1	+	1	1	2	2	1	V	9	7	6
<i>Deschampsia flexuosa</i>	+	+	1	+	+	•	+	V	2.8	4	3
<i>Agrostis capillaris</i>	+	•	•	+	+	+	•	III	0.3	7	5
<i>Holcus lanatus</i>	•	•	•	+	+	+	•	III	0.3	6	6
<i>Anthoxanthum odoratum</i>	+	•	•	+	+	+	•	III	0.3	5	3
<i>Danthonia decumbens</i>	+	•	+	•	+	+	•	III	0.3	4	3
<i>Deschampsia cespitosa</i>	+	•	•	•	+	•	•	II	0.2	3	0
Fabaceae											
<i>Trifolium repens</i>	+	•	•	•	+	+	•	III	0.3	8	5
<i>Trifolium montanum</i>	•	+	+	+	+	•	•	III	0.3	7	4
<i>Genista sagittalis</i>	+	+	•	•	•	+	+	III	0.3	3	0
<i>Trifolium alpestre</i>	+	•	•	+	•	•	•	II	0.2	6	3
<i>Genista tinctoria</i>	+	•	•	•	+	•	•	II	0.2	3	0
Other families											
<i>Potentilla erecta</i>	+	+	•	+	+	+	+	V	0.5	5	2
<i>Luzula luzuloides</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	V	0.5	3	0

<i>Hieracium pilosella</i>	+	•	+	+	+	+	•	IV	0.4	4	1
<i>Thymus pulegioides</i>	•	+	+	+	+	•	+	IV	0.4	3	0
<i>Veronica officinalis</i>	+	+	+	+	+	•	•	IV	0.4	3	0
<i>Viola declinata</i>	+	+	•	+	+	•	+	IV	0.4	3	0
<i>Alchemilla vulgaris</i>	•	•	•	+	+	+	•	III	0.3	6	4
<i>Fragaria vesca</i>	+	•	+	•	+	+	•	III	0.3	5	1
<i>Luzula campestris</i>	+	•	+	+	+	•	•	III	0.3	4	2
<i>Achillea distans</i>	+	+	•	+	+	•	•	III	0.3	3	0
<i>Campanula abietina</i>	+	+	•	+	•	+	•	III	0.3	3	0
<i>Campanula serata</i>	•	•	+	•	+	•	+	III	0.3	3	0
<i>Cerastium holosteoides</i>	+	•	•	•	+	+	•	III	0.3	3	0
<i>Euphrasia rostkoviana</i>	+	•	+	•	•	•	+	III	0.3	3	0
<i>Gnaphalium sylvaticum</i>	+	+	•	+	•	•	+	III	0.3	3	0
<i>Juncus conglomeratus</i>	+	+	•	•	+	+	•	III	0.3	3	0
<i>Luzula sylvatica</i>	•	+	+	•	•	•	+	III	0.3	3	0
<i>Carex pallescens</i>	•	+	+	•	•	•	•	II	0.2	4	3
<i>Veronica chamaedrys</i>	•	+	•	•	•	•	+	II	0.2	4	2
<i>Lycopodium clavatum</i>	•	•	•	•	+	•	+	II	0.2	3	0
<i>Plantago lanceolata</i>	•	•	•	+	•	•	•	I	0.1	6	1
<i>Carex nigra</i>	+	•	•	•	•	•	•	I	0.1	3	0
<i>Succisa pratensis</i>	•	+	•	•	•	•	•	I	0.1	3	0
Shrubs, subshrubs and invasive young trees											
<i>Calluna vulgaris</i>	1	4	2	4	+	+	4	V	31.5	3	0
<i>Vaccinium myrtillus</i>	1	1	2	1	+	1	+	V	9	3	0
<i>Vaccinium vitis-idaea</i>	•	1	1	+	+	1	1	V	2.8	3	0
<i>Picea abies</i>	1	•	1	+	1	•	+	IV	2	3	0
<i>Betula pendula</i>	+	•	+	+	•	+	+	IV	0.4	3	0
<i>Salix cinerea</i>	1	+	•	•	+	•	+	III	1.4	3	0
<i>Juniperus communis</i>	•	•	•	•	+	+	•	II	0.2	3	0
<i>Rubus idaeus</i>	•	•	•	•	•	+	+	II	0.2	3	0
<i>Sorbus aucuparia</i>	+	•	+	•	•	•	•	II	0.2	3	0
Toxic and harmful plants											
<i>Hypericum maculatum</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	V	0.5	1	0
<i>Pteridium aquilinum</i>	+	•	+	•	•	•	•	II	0.2	1	0
<i>Rumex alpinus</i>	•	+	•	•	+	•	•	II	0.2	2	0

The localities and date where the relevées were carried out: 1-2 Bălcești (12.10.2022); 3-4 Dealul Botii (12.10.2022); 5-7 Giurcuța de Sus (15.10.2022). Where: F - fodder quality indices; M - production indices; K - constancy; AD values (Abundance-Dominance): +0.5%; 1-5.0%; 2-17.5%; 3-37.5%; 4-62.5%; 5-87.5%.

In these grasslands, the shrubby, sub-shrub woody vegetation and young trees are quite well highlighted, with a rather high share

in some cases (8-70%), in which *Calluna vulgaris* stands out (31.5%), which becomes dominant in some relevées (figure 2).

a.

b.

Figure 2 *Nardus stricta-Festuca rubra* grasslands, invaded by *Calluna vulgaris* (a. - Bălcești, relevée No. 2; b. - Dealul Botii, relevée No. 4)

As a result of the calculations performed at the grassland type level, for the grasslands with the greatest spread in the area of the Beliș-Fântânele reservoir, it turned out that the most productive are those of *Festuca rubra* and *Agrostis capillaris* with a pastoral value (VP) of 64.72 (good), with a forage green mass (MV) production rated at 12.63 t/ha, supporting an

animal load of 1.49 livestock units UVM/ha (table 3).

The least productive grasslands in the studied area are those of *Nardus stricta* and *Festuca rubra*, with a very poor pastoral value (VP) (10.68), a very low production of green mass (MV) (1.41 t/ha) and a livestock load rated at 0.16 livestock units UVM/ha.

Productivity of grasslands identified in the Belis-Fântânele reservoir area

Grassland type	Pastoral value (VP)	Useful phytomass index (IM)	Green mass production (MV) (t/ha)	Cargo with animals (UVM/ha)
<i>Festuca rubra</i> - <i>Agrostis capillaris</i>	64.72 (Good)	4.68	12.63 (Medium-Good)	1.49
<i>Nardus stricta</i> - <i>Festuca rubra</i>	10.68 (Very thin)	0.74	1.41 (Very thin)	0.16

CONCLUSIONS

The permanent grasslands from the studied area have a great variability from an agro-productive point of view, with mezophytes, micro-mesothermophilous and acid-neutrophilous vegetation.

The *Festuca rubra* and *Agrostis capillaris* grasslands have the highest productivity, with good pastoral value (VP), medium to good production of green mass per hectare and an optimal loading of 1.49 livestock units UVM/ha at 130 days of grazing. At the opposite pole are the de *Nardus stricta* with *Festuca rubra* grasslands with low productivity very poor pastoral value (VP), very poor green mass (MV) production which allow an animal load of only 0.16 livestock units UVM/ha.

The low productivity of *Nardus stricta* grasslands is mainly due to the fact that these grasslands are abandoned, ungrazed, which leads to the encroachment of woody transgressive species from the neighboring forests.

In order to increase the productivity of these permanent grasslands, it is necessary to adopt some measures, such as the clearing of sub-shrub woody vegetation, shrubs and invasive arboreal youth, combating toxic and harmful plants, destroying and leveling of molehills, correcting the chemical reaction of the soil (correcting acidity), over-seeding, fertilizing. In addition to these measures, it is necessary to introduce these grasslands into the productive circuit and ensure a minimum load of 0.3 livestock units UVM/ha.

REFERENCES

- Ciocârlan, V., 2009. Illustrated flora of Romania, *Pteridophyta* et *Spermatophyta*, Ceres Publishing House, București.
- Cristea, V., Gafta, D. & Pedrotti, F., 2004. Phytosociology, Presa Universitară Clujeană Publishing House, Cluj-Napoca.
- Marușca, T., 2019. Contributions to the evaluation of pasture productivity using the floristic releve, Romanian Journal of Grassland and Forage Crops, vol. 19, 33- 47.
- Marușca T. 2021. Contributions to the evaluation of the ecological productivity of Vlădeasa Massif grasslands (Apuseni Mountains). Academy of Agricultural and Forestry Sciences "Gheorghe Ionescu Șişesti", ACTA Agricola Romanica, Field plant culture series, Tom 3, 3:38-44.
- Marușca, T., 2021. Contributions to the assessment of Natura 2000 Habitat productivity of mountain pastures in Padurea Craiului (Southern-Eastern Carpathians). Romanian Journal of Grassland and Forage Crops, Cluj Napoca, 23:99-104.
- Marușca, T., Pășcuț, C., G., 2022. Studies concerning the productivity of permanent grasslands from Codru-Moma Mountains (Western Romanian Carpathians). Journal of Montology, 14:1-7.
- Marușca, T., Mocanu, V., Haș, C., E., Tod, A., M., Andreoiu, C., A., Dragoș, M., M., Blaj, A., V., Ene, A., T., Silistru, D., Ichim, E., Zevedei, M., P., Constantinescu, S., C. & Tod, V., S., 2014. Guide for drawing up pastoral planners. Capolavoro Publishing House, Brașov, 248 p.
- Marușca, T., Memedemin, D., Groza, A., Pop O.,G., Simion, I. & Taulescu, E., 2019. Comparative study of steppic grasslands productivity and grazing pressure in Babadag and Casimcea plateaus. Annals of the Academy of Romanian Scientists Series Agriculture, Silviculture and Veterinary Medicine Sciences Online ISSN 2344-2085, Volume 8, Number 2, 33-42.
- Marușca, T., Dihoru, G., Doniță, N., Memedemin, D. & Pășcuț C, G., 2020. Contributions to the evaluation of the productivity of permanent grasslands from the Babadag Plateau (Dobrogea). University of Oradea Annals, Series: Environmental Protection. I.S.S.N. 1224-6255, vol. XXXV, 85-94.
- Marușca, T., Ionescu, I., Simion, I., Taulescu, E. & Mălinaș, A., 2020. Contributions to the evaluation of the productivity of the permanent grasslands from North Oltenia. Romanian Journal of Grassland and Forage Crops, 21, Cluj-Napoca: 49- 59.
- Păcurar, F., Rotar I., 2014. Methods of study and interpretation of grassland vegetation. Risoprint Publishing House, Cluj-Napoca.
- Pășcuț C, G., Marușca T., 2020. Studies regarding the evolution of grassland productivity from Codru Moma Mountains (Western Carpathians). Annals of the Academy of Romanian Scientists, Series on Agriculture, Silviculture and Veterinary Medicine Sciences. I.S.S.N. Online 2344-2085, Volume 9, Number 2/2020, pp. 61-68.
- Pășcuț C,G. & Pantea S,D., 2021. Contributions to the evaluation of thr productivity of permanent grasslands from the Meziad Hills (Bihar County). University of Oradea Annals, Series: Environmental Protection, Vol. XXXVI, 203-210.
- Sârbu, I., Ștefan, N. & Oprea A., 2013. Vascular plants from Romania. Victor B Victor Publishing House, București.

VEGETATION OF SUBALPINE BUSHES DEVELOPED BY *PINUS MUGO* IN THE VLADEASA MOUNTAINS-WESTERN CARPATHIANS

Iulia-FLORINA POP^{1#}, Laviniu Ioan Nuțu BURESCU²

¹Doctoral School of Biomedical Sciences, University of Oradea, Piața 1 Decembrie no.10, Oradea, Bihor County, Romania

²Department of Forestry and Forest Engineering, University of Oradea, 26 Magheru Blvd, Oradea, Bihor County, Romania

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

The aim of the research consists in the development of a phytocenological, ecological, bioeconomic and ecoprotective study of the subalpine bushes developed by *Pinus mugo* in the Vlădeasa Mountains.

A total of 8 phytocenological surveys were conducted in the sampling areas, i.e. the most representative of the phytocenoses of the association *Calamagrostio villosae-Pinetum mugo*, Sanda et Popescu 2002.

A floristic inventory was carried out in which the species we found were filled in into a synthetical association table while observing the affinity criteria for the coenotaxa, alliance, suballiance, order, and vegetation class to which they are subordinated.

The phytocoenoses of the subalpine bushes were analyzed based on tables, histograms, diagrams regarding their share in ecological classification by categories of lifeforms, phytogeographical elements, affinity of the ecological behaviour with respect to soil moisture, air temperature, chemical reaction of the soil as well as belonging to the genetic karyotype. Scientific, economic, ecoprotective, and bioeconomic relevance were also subjected to study.

We draw seven conclusions in which the research results are synthesized.

Keywords: plant association, phytotaxa, bushes, *Pinus Mugo*, natural habitat

#Corresponding author: Popiulia03@yahoo.com

INTRODUCTION

The subalpine bushes developed by *Pinus mugo* have an exceptional protective role of the subalpine habitat preventing soil erosion.

From all the Western Carpathians, only the Boceasa and Vlădeasa Mountains are areas of forests and subalpine bushes included in the protected area, SCI ROSCI0016 sites including the plots 104C, 117E, 123C, 123D, 124D of Management Unit I Boceasa and ROSPA0081, encompassing natural habitats of community interest sheltering rare species of plants in endangered ecosystems as well as populations of birds of global conservation interest, such as: *Circaetus gallicus* (the Short-toed Snake Eagle), *Aquila chrysaetos* (the Golden Eagle), *Falco peregrinus* (the Peregrine Falcon), *Bonasa bonasia* (the Hazel Grouse), *Strix uralensis* (the Ural Owl), *Bubo bubo* (the Eagle Owl), *Aegolius funereus* (the Tengmalm's Owl or the Boreal Owl), *Glaucidium passerinum* (the Eurasian Pygmy Owl), *Dryocopus martius* (the Black Woodpecker), *Picoides tridactylus* (the Eurasian Three-toed Woodpecker), *Ficedula albicollis* (the Collared Flycatcher), *Ficedula parva* (the Red-breasted Flycatcher).

The bushes developed by *Pinus mugo* as well as the pure spruce or beech forests mixed with resinous forests represent the living and nesting place of protected bird species but also migration stops, while the rocky areas are the favorites places of predatory bird species.

Buteasa Mountain (Boceasa) including Buteasa Peak, and Gropoiu Glacier, is part of the Natura 2000 site, has an area of 372.6 ha and the specification ROSCI0016 and it shelters plant species with high conservation value such as *Pinus mugo*, *Alnus viridis*, *Gentiana punctata*, *Aconitum variegatum* ssp. *paniculatum*, *Juniperus sibirica*, *Soldanella montana*, *Arnica montana*, *Campanula rotundifolia* ssp. *kladniana*, *Vaccinium gaultherioides*, *Hypericum richeri* Vill. ssp. *grisebachii* (Bois.) Nyman.

The Vlădeasa Mountains provides an attractive tourist landscape thanks to their very varied landforms, the very rich vegetation and fauna in terms of species, natural resources, forest fruits, edible mushrooms, clearly marked and well-maintained tourist routes.

The goal of our research paper is to carry out a phytosociological, ecological, bioeconomic and eco-protective study of the

bushes developed by *Pinus mugo* in the Vladeasa Mountains.

To reach the proposed goal, we set the following objectives to achieve:

- Floristic inventory of phytocoenoses developed by *Pinus mugo*,
- Study of the living soil cover of the subalpine bushes and the classification of the species in the association table according to their affinity to the coenotaxa, suballiance, alliance, order, and vegetation class to which they are subordinated,
- Ecological characterization of the cormoflora of the subalpine bushes in terms of distribution by the type of lifeform, phytogeographical elements, belonging to the environmental indices categories, soil moisture, air temperature and chemical reaction of the soil as well as the belonging to the genetic element (karyotype).

So far, specific detailed research works on forest ecosystems-subalpine bushes of *Pinus mugo* within the Vladeasa Massif have not been done except for the ones carried out by Resmerita (1970), and Burescu L.I.N (2018), and those conducted in the neighboring areas i.e. Padis Plateau, by Togor (2016).

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The research work was carried out on Vladeasa Mountain and Buteasa Mountain.

The biological material consists in the phytocoenoses of the association *Calamagrostio villosae-Pinetum mugo*, Sanda et Popescu 2002, spread in the subalpine floor as wide strips of 350-450m on rough terrain with variable slopes (ranging between 4-34°), with surface rankers, gravels, rocks, boulders on skeletal soils but also on districambosols, acid brown soils.

To establish the structure of living soil cover of the bushes, we employed the phytocenological research methods of the Central European school developed by Braun-Blanquet (1964) adapted to Romania's vegetation characteristics by Borza et Boscaiu (1965).

We selected the plant association defined by Géhu et Rivas-Martinez (1981), as

the basic coenotaxa unit for the study of phytocoenoses.

The field research was carried out by traveling on the itinerary but also stationary, during the years 2021-2022, following the estimation of the thickness, and the degree of soil coverage with the estimation of the indices of abundance and dominance, according to the Braun-Blanquet et Pavillard system (1928) corroborated with the consistency indices (K=I-V) and highlighting the degree of fidelity of the species to the environment of the coenotaxa of the phytocoenoses in the case of the *Calamagrostio villosae-Pinetum mugo* association.

We carried out eight phytocenological surveys from the most representative communities of *Pinus mugo* bushes during their optimal vegetation period within areas of 400m², 600m², and 1200m². Among the eight surveys aforementioned, one phytocenological survey was carried out in the Gropoiu glacial caldera, at the altitude of 1,730m, three surveys were conducted on Buteasa Mountain, at altitudes of 1,795m, 1,753m, and 1,758m, and four surveys were carried out on Vladeasa Mountain, at altitudes of 1,822m, 1,836m, 1,823m, and 1,825m.

The surveys' results were inputted into the synthetic phytosociological table, being analyzed cenotaxonomically and in terms of consistency, and providing scientific information regarding the affiliation of the type of lifeforms, phytogeographic elements, ecological indices (moisture, temperature, chemical reaction of the soil), and the type of genetic karyotype.

In order to classify the phytocoenoses of the subalpine bushes by coenotaxa units, suballiance, alliance, and vegetation class, we reviewed the traditional floristic ecological systems of the authors Tüxen (1955), Braun-Blanquet (1964), Soó (1964-1980), Borza et Boscaiu (1965), Oberdorfer (1992), Mucina (1997), Rodwell et al. (2002), Pott (1995), Borhidi (1996), Sanda et al. (2008), Coldea et al. (2012), and Chifu et al. (2014).

To classify the cormoflora by categories of lifeforms we used the system developed by Raunkier (1937), and improved by Braun-Blanquet (1964), Sanda et al. (2003), Burescu et Toma (2005), and Ciocarlan (2009).

With regard the categories of phytogeographic elements, we studied the

works developed by Meusel et Jäger (1922) and Coldea et al. (2006).

Cormoflora of the subalpine bushes was then analyzed in terms of the ecological indices categories (soil moisture, air temperature, chemical reaction of the soil) according to Ellenberg (1979) for Central Europe on a scale

ranging from 1 to 9 and for Romania according to Sanda et al. (2003) using a 1 to 6 scale.

The research results were processed statistically and presented graphically in tables, histograms, and diagrams.

Table.1 *Calamagrostio villosae-Pinetum mugo* Sanda et Popescu 2002

Bio.	E.f.	M	T	R	2n	Survey no.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	K	ADm
						Altitude (mamsl)	1730	1795	1753	1758	1822	1836	1823	1825		
						Grass cover (%)	100	90	100	100	80	100	100	100		
						Exposure	-	SV	-	-	S	-	E	SE		
						Slope (°)	-	28-34	-	-	4-8	-	12-18	8-12		
						Surface (m ²)	1200	1200	1200	1200	400	1200	1200	1400		
H	Eua	4	2,5	1,5	P	<i>As. Calamagrostis villosa</i>	3	2	3	4	3	4	4	2	V	41,8
MPh	Alp-Ec	0	2	0	D	<i>As. Pinus mugo</i>	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	V	87,5
<i>Pinion mugii et Junipero-Pinetalia mugii</i>																
mPh	Arct-Alp	2,5	1,5	4	D	<i>Juniperus sibirica</i>	+	+	+	.	+	+	+	+	V	0,43
H	Alp-Carp-B	3,5	2	1,5	P	<i>Soldanella montana</i>	.	+	1	+	+	+	+	+	V	1
H	Cp	0	0	1	P	<i>Deschampsia flexuosa</i>	+	+	.	+	+	+	.	.	IV	0,43
H	E	2,5	2,5	2	DP	<i>Luzula luzuloides</i>	+	.	.	.	2	+	+	+	IV	2,43
H	Alp-Carp-B	0	0	3	D	<i>Laserpitium krapfii</i>	+	+	.	.	+	+	.	.	III	0,25
H	End	3,5	2	2	P	<i>Campanula abietina</i>	+	+	+	II	0,18
mPh	Alp-Carp-B	4	2	2	D	<i>Salix silesiaca</i>	+	+	.	II	0,12
<i>Vaccinio-Piceetea</i>																
H	Alp-E	3,5	2,5	2,5	P	<i>Homogyne alpina</i>	+	+	1	1	+	+	+	+	V	1,62
Ch(nPh)	Cp	0	2	1	D	<i>Vaccinium myrtillus</i>	2	2	2	2	1	1	2	2	V	14,37
Ch(nPh)	Cp	3	2	1	D	<i>Vaccinium vitis-idaea</i>	.	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	V	0,43
H	Ec	3,5	2,5	2	DP	<i>Luzula sylvatica</i>	+	.	+	+	.	+	+	.	IV	0,31
MPh	E	0	0	0	D	<i>Picea abies</i>	.	+	+	.	+	+	+	+	IV	0,37
H	End	0	2,5	0	P	<i>Campanula napuligera</i>	+	+	.	.	II	0,12
H(G)	Alp-E	3	2	0	P	<i>Gentiana punctata</i>	.	.	+	.	.	+	+	.	II	0,18
H	Arct-Alp	3	2	1	D	<i>Hieracium alpinum</i>	.	+	.	.	+	+	.	.	II	0,18
H(G)	Cp	4	3	3	D	<i>Oxalis acetosella</i>	.	.	+	+	.	+	.	.	II	0,18
H	Arct-Alp	2,5	1	2	DP	<i>Festuca supina</i>	+	+	.	.	+	.	.	.	II	0,18
<i>Juncetea trifidi</i>																
Ch(nPh)	Arct-Alp	3,5	0	1	D	<i>Vaccinium gaultherioides</i>	+	.	.	.	+	.	+	1	III	0,81
<i>Nardo-Callunetea</i>																
H	E	3	2,5	3	P	<i>Arnica montana</i>	+	+	+	.	+	+	.	+	IV	0,37
H	Cp-Bo	3	0	0	DP	<i>Festuca rubra</i>	+	+	.	.	II	0,12
H	Alp-Carp-B	2,5	2,5	3	N	<i>Hypericum richeri ssp. grisebachii</i>	+	+	+	.	II	0,18
H	E	0	0	1,5	D	<i>Nardus stricta</i>	+	+	.	II	0,12
<i>Betulo-Adenostyletea</i>																
H	Alp-Carp-B	3,5	3	4	P	<i>Achillea distans</i>	+	+	.	II	0,12
H	Alp-Carp-B	3,5	1,5	4	DP	<i>Aconitum variegatum ssp. paniculatum</i>	.	.	+	+	.	+	+	.	II	0,18
H	Ec	4	2	4	P	<i>Geantiana asclepiadea</i>	.	.	.	+	.	+	.	.	II	0,12
<i>Seslerietea albicantis</i>																
H	End	2,5	2	0	DP	<i>Campanula kladniana</i>	+	+	+	.	II	0,18
<i>Epilobietea angustifolii</i>																
nPh	Cp	3	3	3	DP	<i>Rubus idaeus</i>	+	.	.	+	.	+	.	.	II	0,18
H	Eua	3,5	3	3	P	<i>Senecio nemorensis</i>	+	+	II	0,12
<i>Variae syntaxa</i>																
						<i>Cetraria islandica</i>	+	1	+	+	III	0,81
						<i>Cladonia rangiferina</i>	+	+	.	.	II	0,12

Species found in a single survey: *Thymus glabrescens* (2) +; *Deschampsia caespitosa* (1) +; *Solidago virgaurea* (1) +; *Athyrium distentifolium* (1) +; *Doronicum austriacum* (1) +; *Dryopteris cristata* (3) +; *Veratrum album* (5) +; *Agrostis capillaris* (6) +; *Polytrichum juniperinum* (6) +. Location and date of surveying: 1-46°41'845"N, 022°42'903"E Gropoiu (27.08.2022), 2-46°42'005"N, 022°42'767"E, 3-46°41'760"N, 022°42'826"E, 4-46°41'678"N, 022°42'641"E, Boceasa Mountain (27.08.2022), 5-46°45'646"N, 022°47'723"E, 6-46°45'605"N, 022°47'689"E, 7-46°45'513"N, 022°47'771"E, 8-46°45'420"N, 022°47'786"E, Vladeasa Mountain (09.09.2022).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The phytocenosis, respectively the forest ecosystem gathers 33 species, of which two species belong to lichens, which means a high biodiversity, considering the altitude of the subalpine floor as well as the critical climatic conditions. (see Table 1)

The species that develop and instill the physiognomy of the phytocenosis are the *Calamagrostis villosa* from *Poaceae* family with a coverage of 41.8%, maximum consistency (K=V) and the *Pinus mugo* bush with a coverage of 87.5%, and a maximum consistency (K=V) found in relation of codominance (see Figure 1). Along with the characteristic species, there is a rich nucleus totaling seven species subordinated to the alliance and order **Pinion**

mugi et Junipero Pinetalia mugi (*Soldanella montana*, *Juniperus sibirica*, *Laserpitium krapfii*, *Campanula abietina*, *Salix silesiaca*), class **Vaccinio-Piceetea** (*Homogyne alpina*, *Vaccinium myrtillus*, *Vaccinium vitis-idaea*, *Luzula sylvatica*, *Picea abies*, *Hieracium alpinum*, *Campanula napuligera*, *Gentiana punctata*) totaling 11 species. A relatively large number of species (11) are transgressive, and belonging to classes **Juncetea trifidi** (*Vaccinium gaultherioides*), **Nardo-Callunetea** (*Festuca rubra*, *Arnica montana*, *Hypericum richeri ssp. grisebachii*), **Betulo-Adenostyletea** (*Aconitum variegatum ssp. paniculatum*, *Achillea distans*), **Seslerietea albicantis** (*Campanula kladniana*), **Epilobietea angustifolii** (*Rubus idaeus*, *Senecio nemorensis*).

Figure 1. **Calamagrostio villosae-Pinetum mugo**, Sanda et Popescu 2002 (original picture taken on 27.08.2022, on Boceasa Mountain)

The analysis of the spectrum of lifeforms shows the dominance of hemicryptophytes (74.1%), followed at a great distance by phanerophytes (16%) and camephytes (9.6%) (see Figure 2), since they adapt best to the subalpine environment.

A good knowledge of lifeforms is paramount because it highlights the adaptation of the plant corm to the living environment for the purpose of protecting regenerative buds during unfavorable seasonal conditions.

Figure 2. Spectrum of lifeforms from the *Calamagrostio villosae-Pinetum mugo* association

The spectrum of the phytogeographical elements that make up the flora of the subalpine scrubs in the Vladeasa Mountains highlights the share of circumpolar species (19.3%) on a par with the Alpine-Carpatho-Balkan ones (19.3%), followed by the Arctic-Alpine (12.9%) and European (12.9%) species, proving the close

ties with the boreal flora of the North Polar Circle, and with that of the Alps and the Balkan Mountains. Eurasian and Central European species have a low share of 9.6% followed by endemites, Alpine-European species i.e. 6.4% and Alpine-Central European species i.e. 3.2% (see Figure 3 below).

Figure 3. Spectrum of phytogeographical elements from the *Calamagrostio villosae-Pinetum mugo* association

The chart of the ecological indices shows the fact that depending on the soil moisture, the majority species are mesophilic (45.1%) followed by euryhydra (22.6%), xeromesophilic (16.1%), and mesohygrophilic species (i.e. 16.1%) (see Table 2).

In terms of air temperature, microthermal species predominate (58%), followed by eurythermal ones (19.3%),

micromesothermal species (12.9%) and cryophiles (9.6%).

Strongly acidophilic species (25.8%) are the ones predominating in phytocenoses, followed by euriionic ones (19.3%), acidophilic (19.3%), acid-neutrophilic (19.3%) and weak-acid-neutrophilic species with a share of 16.1% (see Figure 4).

Table 2

		Ecological indices for the <i>Calamagrostio villosae-Pinetum mugo</i> association								
Ecological indices		1	1.5	2	2.5	3	3.5	4	4.5	0
M	sp. no.	-	-	-	5	6	8	5	-	7
	%	-	-	-	16.1	19.3	25.8	16.1	-	22.6
T	sp. no.	1	2	11	7	4	-	-	-	6
	%	3.2	6.4	35.4	22.6	12.9	-	-	-	19.3
R	sp. no.	8	-	6	-	6	-	5	-	6
	%	25.8	-	19.3	-	19.3	-	16.1	-	19.3

M=Soil moisture
T=Air temperature

R=Chemical reaction of the soil

The karyological spectrum of subalpine *Pinus mugo* bushes is dominated by polyploid species (38.8%) capable of phytosociological competition, of colonizing the bare space in a habitats facing hostile living conditions, very low temperatures, strong winds, strongly acidic and acidic soils, poor in assimilable mineral substances.

Diploid species have a steady percentage of 35.5%, ensuring the gene pool necessary for the evolution of phytocenosis populations through allopolyploidy and autopolyploidy followed by diplo-polyploid species (22.6%) while those with unknown karyotype have an insignificant presence (i.e. (3.2%) (see Figure 5).

Figure 4. Diagram of ecological indices for the *Calamagrostis villosae-Pinetum mugo* association

Figure 5. Karyological spectrum of the *Calamagrostis villosae-Pinetum mugo* association

A significant number of rare, vulnerable, endemic species found shelter in the phytocenoses of the association *Calamagrostis villosae-Pinetum mugo* (Sanda et Popescu 2002) such as: *Pinus mugo*, *Soldanella montana*, *Juniperus sibirica*, *Arnica montana*, *Campanula kladniana*, *Campanula napuligera*, *Campanula abietina*, *Gentiana punctata*, *Hypericum richeri* ssp. *grisebachii*, *Vaccinium gaultherioides*, *Aconitum variegatum* ssp. *paniculatum*.

Economic relevance

The ecosystem developed by *Pinus mugo* bushes in the Vladeasa Mountains is the home to medicinal herbs (*Gentiana punctata*, *Arnica montana*, *Juniperus sibirica*, *Vaccinium myrtillus*, *Vaccinium vitis-idaea*, *Vaccinium gaultherioides*, *Picea abies*, *Aconitum variegatum* ssp.

paniculatum) as well as to fodder plants (*Festuca rubra*, *Agrostis capillaris*, *Nardus stricta*).

The thickets of *Pinus mugo* have no economic relevance for the forest mass; however, they have a pedological importance favoring the genesis of a thin layer of soil. These are included in the natural habitat of community interest NATURA 2000 4070* R3105 Southeast Carpathian bushes of mountain pine (*Pinus mugo*) with alpine rose whose conservation requires the designation of Special Areas of Conservation (ASC) - Habitats Directive, Annex I - in Romania, Donita et al. (2005). In terms of eco-management measures, the clearing of *Pinus mugo* thickets in order to exploit the meadows, as well as their burning, is prohibited.

CONCLUSIONS

The floristic inventory of the subalpine bushes gathered in the plant association *Calamagrostio villosae-Pinetum mugo*, Sanda et Popescu 2002, gathers a total number of 33 taxa of which 31 cormophyte species and two species of lichens, which shows the multitude of Arctic, Alpine, Arctic-Alpine, Arctic-Balkan elements, Carpathian endemic species.

The analysis of the ecological categories of lifeforms shows the majority share of hemicryptophyte species (74.1%) followed by phanerophytes (16%) and camephytes (9.6%).

The spectrum of phytogeographical elements with regard to the genetic center of origin as well as the geographical distribution area in which the speciation process took place shows us the share of circumpolar (19.3%) and Alpine-Carpatho-Balkan (19.3%) species followed by Arctic-Alpine and European species with the percentage of 12.9%.

The ecological indices of the phytocenosis of the *Pinus mugo* thickets suggest that they have a mesophilic (45.1%), microthermal (58%) and a strongly acidophilic (25.8%) nature.

Cytogenetic analysis shows the share of polyploid species (38.8%) followed by diploid (35.5%) and diplo-polyploid (22.6%) species.

The subalpine bushes of *Pinus mugo* in the Vlădeasa Mountains are not relevant from economic standpoint, but they represent the vegetation that provides the subalpine ecosystem with essential environmental services in critical situations, land stability and soil protection (prevention of soil erosion, landslides, and avalanches).

The bibliographic index encloses 32 references of the authors whose scientific works were consulted.

REFERENCES

- Borhidi, A., 1996. *Critical revision of the Hungarian plants communities*, Janus Pannonius University Press, Pécs, 43-94.
- Borza, A., Boşcaiu, N., 1965. *An introduction to the study of the living soil cover*. Publishing House of the Romanian Academy: Bucharest.
- Braun-Blanquet, J., & Pavillard, J., 1928. *Vocabulaire de Sociologie Végétale (Vocabulary of Plant Sociology)*. Edit. 3, Imprimerie Lemair Andres, 15-18.
- Braun-Blanquet, J., 1964. *Pflanzensoziologie (Plant sociology)*. Springer-Verlag, Wien-New York, 3, Aufl, 12-24.
- Burescu, L.I.N., 2018. *Cercetări privind pădurile cu valoare de coservare ridicată din Munții Pădurea Craiului și Vlădeasa în vederea stabilirii măsurilor de protejare (Research on forests with high conservation value in Pădurea Craiului and Vlădeasa Mountains to establish protection measures)*. University of Oradea Publishing House.
- Burescu, P., Toma, I., 2005. *Handbook of practical botany* York. Publishing House of the University of Oradea, Oradea.
- Chifu, T., Irimia, I., Zamfirescu O., 2014. *Diversitatea fitosociologică a vegetației României III, Vegetația pădurilor și tufărișurilor (The phytosociological diversity of Romania's vegetation III, Vegetation of forests and bushes)* European Institute, Iasi, pp. 498-510.
- Ciocărlan, V., 2009. *The illustrated flora of Romania. Pteridophyta and Spermatophyta*. Ceres Publishing House: Bucharest.
- Coldea, G., Oprea, A., Sârbu, I., Sârbu, C., Ștefan, N., 2012. *The vegetable association of Romania*. Cluj University, Press Publish House, Cluj-Napoca.
- Coldea, Gh., Fărcaș, S., Stoica, I.A., Ursu, T.M., 2006. *The biodiversity of postglacial forests and the dynamic of their evolution until present day, based on phytohistoric and coenologic data*. Studii și cercet., Biol., Bistrița, 11:41-47
- Coldea, Gh., Fărcaș, S., Ciobanu, M., Hurdu, B., Ursu, T., 2008. *Diversitatea floristică și fitocenologică a principalelor situri protejate din Parcul Natural Apuseni (The floristic and phytocenological diversity of the main protected sites in the Western Carpathians Natural Park)* Cluj University Press, Cluj-Napoca, 170p.
- Cristea, V., 1991. *Fitocenologie și vegetația României-îndrumător de lucrări practice (Phytocenology and vegetation of Romania -a practical courses guide-)*, Cluj-Napoca, pp.57-82-96.
- Doniță, N., Popescu, A., Pauca-Comănescu, M., Mihăilescu, S., Biriș, I.A., 2005. *Habitats in Romania*. "Editura Tehnică Silvică" Publishing House, Bucharest, 496p.
- Ellenberg, H., 1979. *Zeigerwerte der Gefässpflanzen Mitteleuropas (Indicative values of the vascular plants of Central Europe)*, Scripture Geobot., 9: 1-121.
- Gehu, J.M. & Rivas-Martinez, S., 1981. *Notions fondamentales de phytosociologie (Fundamentals of Phytosociology)*. In: Dierschke H. (ed.), *Syntaxonomy* pp5-33. Ber.Int.Symp.Int.Vereinigung Vegetationskunde. Cramer, Berlin.
- Meusel, H. et Jäger, E.J., 1992. *Comparative Chorology of Central European Flora*, Vol.3. „Gustav Fischer Verlag” Publishing House Jena
- Mucina, L., 1997. *Conspectus of classes of European vegetation*. Folia Geobot. Phytotax, Praha, 32: 117-172.
- Oberdorfer, E., 1992. *Süddeutsche Pflanzengesellschaften (South German plant communities)*, III-Walder und Gebüsche. Gustav Fischer Verlag, Jena.
- Pott, R., 1995. *Die Pflanzengesellschaften Deutschlands (Plant communities of Germany)*, 2 Aufl, Welmer Verlag, Stuttgart.
- Raunkier, C., 1937. *Plant life forms*. Clarendon Press, Oxford.
- Resmeriță, I., 1965. *Vegetația de pe Masivul Vlădeasa cu plante noi sau rare pentru Munții Apuseni*.

-
- (Vegetation on the Vlădeasa Massif with new or rare plants for the Apuseni Mountains). Stud. Cerc.Biol., Ser.Bot., Bucharest, 17 (1): 23-34.
- Resmeriță, I., 1970. *Flora, vegetația și potențialul productiv pe Masivul Vlădeasa (Flora, vegetation and productive potential on the Vlădeasa Massif)*, Romanian Academy Publishing House, Bucharest, PP.199-203.
- Resmeriță, I., 1970. *Cenotaxoni noi pentru știință pe Masivul Vlădeasa (New coenotaxa for science on the Vlădeasa Massif)*, Biological Research studies, Biological Series 2, Bucharest, 115-124.
- Rodwell, J.S, Schamèneé, J.H.J., Mucina, L., Pignatti, S., Dring, J. & Moss, D., 2002. *The diversity of European vegetation: An overview of phytosociological alliances and their relationships to EUNIS habitats*. National Center for Agriculture, Nature Management and Fisheries, Wageningen.
- Sanda, V., Biță, N.C., Barabaș, N., 2003. *Flora cormofitelor spontane și cultivate din România. (Flora of spontaneous and cultivated cormophytes in Romania)*. Ion Borcea Publishing House, Bacău.
- Sanda, V., Öllerer, K., Burescu, P., 2008. *Phytocoenoses in Romania. Syntax, structure, dynamics and evolution*. Ars Docendi Publishing House, University of Bucharest
- Soó, R., 1964-1980. *A magyar flora és vegetáció rendszertani, növényföldrajzi kézikönyve (A systematic and phytogeographical manual of the Hungarian flora and vegetation)*. Acad. Kiado, I-VI, Budapest.
- Togor, G.C., 2016. *Flora și vegetația din partea nordică a Munților Bihor*. Teză de doctorat. (Flora and vegetation in the northern Bihor Mountains. Doctoral thesis). University of Oradea, pp.470-473
- Tüxen, R., 1955. *Das System der nordwestdeutschen Pflanzengesellschaften (The system of Northwest German plant communities)*, Mitt.D.Flour. Soz. Arbeitsgem.m.n.Folge5, 155-156.
- ***European Commission 2003-Interpretation of European Union Habitats, EUR25 (ec.europa.eu/environment/nature/nature_conservation/eu_enlargement/2004/pdf/habitats_im_en.pdf)
- ***European Commission - Directive 92 (43) EEC on the conservation of natural habitats and of wild species
- ***Geografia României, III Carpații Românești și Depresiunea Transilvaniei (Geography of Romania, III Romanian Carpathians and the Transylvanian Depression), 1987, Publishing House of the Academy of the Socialist Republic of Romania, 430-453p.

TURKEY OAK (*QUERCUS CERRIS* L.) SMART FORESTS FROM ROMANIA'S WEST PLAIN

Voichița TIMIȘ-GÂNSAC¹, Lucian DINCĂ²

¹ Department of Forestry and Forest Engineering, University of Oradea, Gen. Magheru Street nr.26, 410048 Oradea, Romania

² "Marin Drăcea" National Institute for Research and Development in Forestry, 13 Closca Street, 500040 Brasov, Romania

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

The smart forest concept is relatively recent while some researchers search nowadays for methods to frame stands in this category. The present article proposes a new method of quantifying smart forests from a certain species (Turkey oak) on a certain habitat (Romania's West Plain), by taking into consideration and quantifying 13 site and stand characteristics. Based on this quantification it was established that Turkey oak smart forests occupy 6% of the areal and are represented by seed reservations and forests under extreme conservation regime, aged 60-70, with even aged or relatively even aged structures and diverse soil or station types. The proposed method can be applied in any condition and is especially useful for identifying these valuable forests.

Keywords: functional category, soil type, smart forests, Turkey oak, current growth.

Corresponding author: timisvoichita@yahoo.com

INTRODUCTION

West Plain is located in East Romania, at the border with Hungary (Cantar et al., 2021). With a length of 375 km, the area is characterized by annual average temperatures of 10-12°C and by phaeozem, luvisol and fluvisol soils (Dinca et al, 2019).

Turkey oak growth and productivity is linked to late spring-early summer hydrologic balance (Di Filippo et al, 2010), with low soil water content (Montagnoli et al, 2012), or roe deer activity (Cutini et al, 2011). This species has multiple ecological roles, like other forest species: red oak (Dinca et al., 2021); staghorn sumac (Timiș-Gânsac et al., 2020); white willow (Timiș-Gânsac et al., 2020); birch (Hapa et al., 2021).

Starting with the year 2000, only four articles mentioned the concept of "Climate-Smart Forestry" (Jandl et al, 2018; Nabuurs et al, 2017; Nabuurs et al, 2018; Yousefpour et, 2018). The most recent definition offered by specialists considers that "Climate Smart Forestry is sustainable adaptive forest management and governance to protect and enhance the potential of forests to adapt to and mitigate climate change.

The aim is to sustain ecosystem integrity and functions and to ensure the continuous delivery of ecosystem goods and services, while

minimizing the impact of climate-induced changes on forests well-being and nature's contribution to people." (Bowditch et al, 2020). In Romania, alder (Blaga et al, 2019), pubescent oak (Dincă et al, 2020), douglas fir (Dinca et al., 2021) and manna ash smart forests (Dinca et al., 2020) were identified and described in the Southern Carpathians.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The material for the present paper is represented by Turkey oak stand elements from Romania's West Plain, that were extracted from forest management plans realized during 1995-2008 for 13 forest districts (Forest management plans). The exceedingly large number of values (5074 stand elements) offers a good statistical insurance of the results obtained. Stands up to the age of 40 were not taken into consideration.

In total, 13 stands or site-specific parameters were taken into consideration (table 1). Each analysed parameter has obtained a grade from 1 to 5, where: 1 = very low; 2 = low; 3 = average; 4 = high; 5 = very high. The grade was given by taking into consideration the ecological requests of Turkey oak.

The addition of all these values has resulted in a hierarchy of Turkey oak stands, while the ones with very high values were situated in the smart forest category.

The meaning of some terms used in Table number 1 is rendered below:

Vitality: 1=very vigorous; 2= vigorous; 3= normal; 4 = weak; 5 = very weak.

Structure: 1= even aged stand; 2= relatively even aged stand; 3= relatively uneven aged stand; 4= uneven aged stand.

Production/protection subunits (SUP): A= Regular Forest, normal assortments; C= Conversion; K= Seed reservations; M= Forests under the extreme conservation regime.

Functional group (GF) and functional category (FCT): 1,2L= Forests located on fields

with lithological substratum, very vulnerable to erosion and landslides; 1,3A= Steppe forests from the limit between steppe and silvosteppe; 1,4B= Forests located near cities; 1,4J= Forests of game interest.

Soil type: 2201= preluvisol; 2401= luvisol; 2407= stagnic luvisol; 3101= eutric cambisol; 6401= stagnosol.

Station type (TS): 6142= Hill Turkey oak stand, Bi stagnic luvisol, subaverage edaphic with *Carex-Poa pratensis*; 7332= Hill Turkey oak stand with oak, Bm stagnic luvisol with *Poa pratensis-Carex carryophylla*.

Table 1.

Grade obtained based on the stand's and site's characteristics

Nr crt	Characteristic	Grade				
		1	2	3	4	5
1	Average diameter (cm)*	10-22	24-26	28-30	32-36	38-80
2	Average H (m)*	9-18	19-20	21-22	23-24	25-34
3	Production class	5	4	3	2	1
4	Current growth (m ³ /an/ha) *	0.1-0.6	0.7-1.1	1.2-1.8	1.9-3.1	3.2-9.5
5	Pruning	0.3	0.4	0.5	0.7	0.6
6	Vitality	5	4	3	2	1
7	Structure	1	2	3	4	
8	Crown density	0.2-0.4	0.5-0.6	0.9	0.7	0.8
9	SUP	O, C	A, Q	V	B, M	E, K
10	Functional group + Functional category	2,1C	1,3G; 1,4J; 2,1B	1,1A; 1,1B; 1,1C	1,2A; 1,2; 1,2I; 1,4B; 1,4I	1,3A; 1,4A; 1,5H
11	Litter	1	2	3	4	5
12	Soil type	2405	2108;2401; 6401	2101;2201; 2209	1307;3109	3101
13	Station type	5131	6131; 6142;	5132;6132; 6152;7332	5153;6143 6153;6253	7334

* The entire value range was divided in 5 categories for these characteristics, 1 = the smallest 5 = the highest. The category division was realized so that the analyzed biometric characteristics are respected. In addition, a balanced division was intended as number of values for each category.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The final grades obtained for the analysed stands vary between 54 and 22. We consider smart forests as those that have obtained

grades higher than 50, which amount to 29 stands (6% of the total number of stands).

The main characteristics of Turkey oak smart forests from Romania's West Plain are rendered in Table number 2.

Table 2.

The characteristics of smart Turkey oak forests from Romania's West Plain

Nr crt	Age (years)	Current growth (m ³ /year/ha)	SUP	Functional category	Structure	Flora	Soil type	Site type
1	70	6.0	E	5C	1	81	9501	9624
2	75	6.4	M	4A	1	81	2101	8430
3	80	1.8	M	4A	1	81	2101	8430
4	100	0.7	K	5H	3	63	2407	6143
5	120	0.2	K	5H	2	61	3101	6153
6	60	6.1	A	5B	2	81	9506	9641
7	60	3.8	V	4J	2	71	9501	9540
8	65	6.2	M	2I	1	71	2212	8511
9	65	4.3	K	5H	1	92	2201	6153
10	65	3.7	K	5H	1	92	2201	6153
11	70	6.7	V	4I	1	73	1301	9531
12	70	6.0	V	4J	1	73	1301	9531
13	70	4.7	V	4J	1	73	1301	9531
14	90	1.2	K	5H	2	63	2407	6143
15	100	0.7	K	5H	2	63	2407	6143
16	150	1.9	M	4F	3	91	2212	8336
17	60	8.5	M	4A	1	81	2101	8430
18	65	4.3	M	4C	2	51	2407	7333
19	70	6.0	M	2I	1	91	2108	8511
20	85	3.2	A	3A	2	73	2407	8321
21	85	1.8	K	5H	2	81	1210	8430
22	85	3.8	A	4B	1	91	2108	8511
23	90	3.6	K	5H	2	92	2101	8323
24	90	4.2	V	4J	1	91	2212	8336
25	90	1.5	M	4F	3	91	2212	8336
26	100	0.3	K	5H	2	63	2407	6143
27	105	0.3	K	5H	2	61	2201	6153
28	120	1.4	K	5H	2	71	2401	6143
29	120	1.6	M	2B	2	91	2407	6143

The smart Turkey oak forests from Romania's West Plain have advanced ages (between 60 and 150 years), with most of them ranging between 60 and 70 years (figure 1).

The current growth of these forests has a large variability gathered between 0.2 and 8.5 (m³/year/ha), (figure 2).

Figure 1 The distribution on age of Turkey oak smart forests from Romania's West Plain

Figure 2 The distribution on current growth of Turkey oak smart forests from Romania's West Plain

The stand belongs generally to K (Seed reservations) and M (Forests under the extreme conservation regime) production/protection subunits (figure 3) and to no less than 12 functional categories (figure 4), with the highest

percentage (38%) in the 5H category - Forests established as reservations for producing forest seeds and conserving the forest geno-fund.

Figure 3 The distribution on production/protection subunits Turkey oak smart forests from Romania's West Plain

Figure 4 The distribution on Functional category of oak smart forests from Romania's West Plain

The structure of these stands is even aged (45%), relatively even aged (45%) and less likely to be relatively uneven aged (10%). The characteristic flora for these stands is *Arum-Pulmonaria* and *Carex-Poa pratensis*. The most widespread soils are stagnic luvisol and rodic preluvisol. The soils from these stands are characterized by a good supply in nutritive elements (Edu et al., 2012; Crişan et al, 2020;

Chisăliță et al, 2015; Enescu et al, 2019), microorganisms (Enescu et al., 2017) and humidity (Constandache et al., 2021). The number of soils on which these stands vegetate is very high (11), as well as the number of forest stations (12), which indicates a high variability of stational conditions characteristic to the studied area and stands.

CONCLUSIONS

We can consider smart Turkey oak forests from Romania's West Plain as those that record a total higher than 50 by adding the grades obtained by their station and stand characteristics. From the total of Turkey oak stands located in this area, 6% can be framed in the smart forest category. These stands are characterised by ages of 60-70 years, are situated in seed reservations and forests under extreme conservation regimes, have an even aged or relatively even aged structure, an *Arum-Pulmonaria* and *Carex-Poa pratensis* flora as well as a high variability of current growth, soil or station types. The method proposed for identifying smart forests can also be applied in other regional or climatic conditions and is of great importance as it can establish (based on clear, quantifiable criteria) a special forest category over which specialists can then apply specific conservation measures.

REFERENCES

- Blaga T., Dinca L. & Pleșca I. M., 2019. How can smart alder forests (*Alnus glutinosa* (L.) Gaertn.) from the Southern Carpathians be identified and managed. Scientific papers series „Management, Economic Engineering in Agriculture and Rural Development”, 19(4), 29-35.
- Bowditch E., Santopuoli G., Binder F., Rio M. D., La Porta N., Kluvankova T., ... & Pretzsch H., 2020. What is Climate-Smart Forestry? A definition from a multinational collaborative process focused on mountain regions of Europe. *Ecosystem Services*, 43, 101113.
- Cântar I.C., Dinca L.C., 2021. The contribution of forests from counties located in Romania's West Plain to the area's long-lasting development. *Sustainable Development Research*, 3(2), 7-13.
- Crișan V. E., Dincă L. C., & Decă S. Ș., 2020. Analysis of chemical properties of forest soils from Bacau County. *Revista de Chimie*, 71(4), 81-86.
- Crișan V., Dincă L., 2017. The predominant forest soils from Timiș Forest Administration County. *JOURNAL of Horticulture, Forestry and Biotechnology*, 21(3), 137-141.
- Chisăliță I., Dincă L.C., Spârchez G., Crăciunescu A., & Vișoiu D., 2015. The influence of some stagnoluvosols characteristics on the productivity of *Quercus cerris* and *Quercus frainetto* stand from O.S. Făget, D.S. Timiș. *Research Journal of Agricultural Science*, 47(3), 23-28.
- Constandache C., Dinca L.C. & Tudor C., 2021. The chemical properties of soils from forest fields occupied by oil drills in Moinesti, Romania. *Revista de Chimie*, 72(3), 1-9.
- Cutini, A., Bongio P., Chianucci F., Pagon N., Grignolio S., Amorini E. & Apollonio M., 2011. Roe deer (*Capreolus capreolus* L.) browsing effects and use of chestnut and Turkey oak coppiced areas. *Annals of forest science*, 68(4), 667-674.
- Dinca L., Chisalita I. & Cantar I.C., 2019. Chemical properties of forest soils from Romania's West Plain. *Revista de Chimie*, 70(7), 2371-2374.
- Dincă L., Vechiu E. & Oneț A., 2020. Can we identify manna ash (*Fraxinus ornus* L.) "smart forests" in Banatul Mountains? *Natural Resources and Sustainable Development*, 10(1), 91-100.
- Dincă L. & Vechiu E., 2020. Intelligent pubescent oak forests (*Quercus pubescens* Wild.) from Dobroudja Plateau, Romania. *Sustainable Development Research*, 2(1), 1-9.
- Dinca L., 2021. Smart Douglas fir forests (*Pseudotsuga Menziesii* (Mirb.) Franco) from Apuseni Mountains, Romania, *International Research Journal of Advanced Engineering and Science*, 6(4), 16-20.
- Dincă L. & Dincă M., 2021. The Red Oak (*Quercus Rubra* L.) from Romania's West Plain. *Research Journal of Agricultural Science*, 53 (2), 102-107.
- Di Filippo A., Alessandrini A., Biondi F., Blasi S., Portoghesi L. & Piovesan G., 2010. Climate change and oak growth decline: Dendroecology and stand productivity of a Turkey oak (*Quercus cerris* L.) old, stored coppice in Central Italy. *Annals of Forest Science*, 67(7), 706-706.
- Edu E.M., Udrescu S., Mihalache M. & Dincă L., 2013. Physical and chemical characterization of dystric cambisol from Piatra Craiului National Park, *Scientific papers Serie A Agonomy*, 56, 37-39.
- Enescu R. E., Dincă L. & Lucaci D., 2017. The main characteristics of forest soils from Cluj and Harghita counties. *ProEnvironment*, 10(30), 57-61,
- Enescu, C. M & Dincă, L., 2019. Diversity and characteristics of forest soils from Sălaj County. *Current Trends in Natural Sciences*, 8(15), 114-119.
- Hapa M. & Dinca L., 2021. *Betula pendula* ssp. distribution and growth in the Sub-Carpathians curvature. *Romanian Journal of Ecology & Environmental Chemistry*, 3(2), 16-22.
- Jandl R., Ledermann T., Kindermann G., Freudenschuss A., Gschwantner T., & Weiss P., 2018. Strategies for climate-smart forest management in Austria. *Forests* 9, 1–15.
- Montagnoli A., Terzaghi M., Di Iorio A., Scippa G. S., & Chiantane D., 2012. Fine-root morphological and growth traits in a Turkey-oak stand in relation to seasonal changes in soil moisture in the Southern Apennines, Italy. *Ecological Research*, 27(6), 1015-1025.
- Nabuurs G.-J., Delacote P., Ellison D., Hanenwinkel M., Hetemaki L., Lindner M. & Ollikainen M., 2017. By 2050 the mitigation effects of EU forests could nearly double through climate smart forestry. *Forests* 8, 1–14.
- Nabuurs G.-J., Verkerk H., Schelhaas M., Ramon J., Trasobares A. & Cienciala E., 2018. Climate-Smart Forestry: quantification of mitigation impacts in three case regions in Europe Outline – Concept of Climate-Smart Forestry – Three cases regions in Europe. Brussels.
- Timiș-Gânsac V. & Dincă L., 2020. Staghorn sumac (*Rhus Typhina* L.) from Dobrogea's forests. *Annals of West University of Timișoara, ser. Biology*, 23 (2), 179-188.
- Timiș-Gânsac, V. & Dincă L., 2020. Salcia albă din pădurile dobrogene. *Buletin Științific. Revista de Etnografie, Științele Naturii și Muzeologie (Serie Nouă)*, 45(32), 19-27.

Yousefpour R., Augustynczik A.L.D., Reyer C.P.O., Lasch-Born P., Suckow F. & Hanewinkel M., 2018. Realizing mitigation efficiency of European commercial forests by climate smart forestry. Sci. Rep. 8, 1–11.

***Forest management plans: Carei (2008), Livada (2001), Satu Mare (2004), Oradea (2007), Sacuieni (2008), Tinca (2004), Ceala (2001), Chisinau Cris (2001), Radna (1995), Savarsin (2005), Lunca Timisului (2007), Timisoara (2007), Lugoj (1999).

IS THE SOMEȘ-TISA HYDROGRAPHIC AREA PRETABLE FOR PEDOLOGICAL STUDIES CARRIED OUT WITH MOBILE APPS?

Bogdan-Vasile CIORUȚA^{1-3#}, Kateryna RADLOVSKA⁴, Mirela COMAN^{1,5}

¹University of Agricultural Sciences and Veterinary Medicine in Cluj-Napoca, Doctoral School, 3-5 Calea Mănăştur, 400372, Cluj-Napoca, Romania; mail: bogdan-vasile.cioruta@usamvcluj.ro

²Technical University of Cluj-Napoca - North University Center of Baia Mare, Office of Informatics, 62A Victor Babeș Str., 430083, Baia Mare, Romania; mail: bogdan.cioruta@staff.utcluj.ro

³Technical University of Cluj-Napoca - North University Center of Baia Mare, Department of Specialty with Psychopedagogical Profile, 76 Victoriei Str., 430072, Baia Mare, Romania; mail: bogdan.cioruta@campus.utcluj.ro

⁴Ivano-Frankivsk National Technical University of Oil and Gas, Department of Ecology, 15 Karpatska Street, Kolomyia, Ivano-Frankivs'ka oblast 76008, Ukraine; mail: kateryna.radlovska@nung.edu.ua

⁵Technical University of Cluj-Napoca - North University Center of Baia Mare, Faculty of Engineering, 62A Victor Babeș Str., 430083, Baia Mare, Romania; mail: mirela.coman@irmmm.utcluj.ro

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

Monitoring and protection of soil resources are concerns of particular interest, which have more recently been achieved through the use of mobile devices that come bundled with a wide variety of applications. In order for such applications to be used to their full potential (to efficiently collect, process, store and disseminate information of interest to users), the space under study needs to be truly highly diversified. The diversification of the spatial configuration, as well as the dynamics of the field conditions, must be sufficiently well represented, in order to be able to support and validate the incursion of mobile applications in research. In these conditions, for this paper, we aimed to verify whether the hydrographic area Someș-Tisa is appropriate (suitable) to support the development of agro-pedological studies using mobile applications. The results, according to the literature consulted (especially the *Methodology for the Development of Pedological Studies*) and the functionalities of some applications created in the MIT App Inventor® environment, showed that in the considered area mobile applications can be used for agro-pedological studies. meet, for the most part, all the basic ecopedological indicators. Consequently, it can be stated that the Someș-Tisa hydrographic area corresponds to the requirements of the research undertaken and that the incursion of mobile applications is more than welcome.

Keywords: Someș-Tisa hydrographic space, water collection area, land use, application testing.

#Corresponding author: bogdan-vasile.cioruta@usamvcluj.ro

INTRODUCTION

The Someș-Tisa hydrographic area is located in the northern and northwestern parts of Romania (Fig. 1), occupying an area of 22380 km², ≈9.42% of the Romanian territory (ABAST, 2016-2021). It is bounded on the north by Ukraine - by the natural border of the river Tisza on a length of 61 km, on the west by the border with the Republic of Hungary, and on the territory of the country, it borders the Siret basins to the east, the Mureș basin to the south and Crișuri basin to the southwest.

From an administrative point of view, the Someș-Tisa hydrographic area extends over the territory of 7 counties: Maramureș (≈97%), Bistrița-Năsăud (≈94%), Sălaj (≈88%), Satu Mare (≈77%), Cluj (≈66%), Alba and Bihor; the share of the last two being insignificant, ≈0.06% and ≈0.7% (ABAST, 2016).

From the development regions (Covășnianu, 2011; CJ Maramureș, 2018) and implicitly from the hydrographic network of the country perspective, which is managed on basins (Fig. 2), the Someș-Tisa hydrographic space includes administrative territories from the North-West development region; together it has a share of ≈65.52% (ABAST, 2021; ADRNV, 2021). The total population of the Someș-Tisa hydrographic area was according to the data from the INS, at the level of 2011, 1835850 inhabitants, of which 1005310 inhabitants (≈54.76%) in the urban area and 830540 inhabitants (≈45.24%) in rural (ABST, 2016-2019). The main urban agglomerations are Cluj-Napoca, Baia Mare, Satu Mare, Bistrița, Zalău, Sighetul Marmăției, Dej, Borșa, Lăpuș, Jibou, Beclean, Năsăud. The degree of industrialization of the territory of the Someș-Tisa river basin is relatively high, represented by many economic

branches, of which the share is held by the extraction and preparation of minerals, building materials industry, chemical industry, textile industry, food industry, wood exploitation and processing (ABST, 2016-2021; CJ Maramureș, 2018). The distribution of the main economic activities in the Someș-Tisa hydrographic area represented by ranges of industrial and

agricultural products is as follows: industrial products - timber, processed PVC and polyethylene products, textiles and metals, furniture, etc., and agricultural products - bakery products, meat, and meat products, dairy products, etc. (CJ Maramureș, 2018; ABAST, 2019-2021; ADRNV, 2021).

Figure 1. Territorial water management subunits of Water Basin Administration Someș-Tisa (ABAST, 2019)

Figure 2. Romania's hydrographic network managed by river basins (Gâțescu, 2010)

The infrastructure in the Someș-Tisa hydrographic area is represented by the road with a length of 4540 km, the railway with non-electrified lines of around $\approx 90\%$, and the electrified lines and double lines representing the difference between the regional network and air transport through Avram Iancu International Airport in Cluj, Satu Mare International Airport and Baia Mare International Airport.

The area of the Someș-Tisa hydrographic area has a high tourist potential, among which

are listed only some of the tourist objectives that can be visited, namely: Rodna National Park located in Maramureș and Bistrița-Năsăud counties being included in the biosphere reserve and UNESCO Biosphere, Apuseni Natural Park on the Someș Cald and Beliș rivers, Maramureș Mountains Natural Park and Pietrosul Mare Scientific Reserve in Maramureș, Ocna Șugatag Spa (Maramureș), Alexandru Borza Botanical Garden (Cluj) (ABAST, 2019; CJ Maramureș, 2018).

In the Rodna Mountains National Park there are several natural areas of special scientific, geological, landscape, floristic, faunal, and speleological interest, among which we mention: Pietrosu Mare, Piatra Rea, Poiana cu Narcisse on the Sacă Massif, Izvorul Tăușoarelor Cave, Izvorul Bătrâna, Izvoarele Mihăieșei, Peștera și izbuluc Izvorul Albastru al Izei.

S.P.A. (areas for special protection) according to H.G. no. 1284/2007 are: The lower meadow of the Tour, the Nir Plain - Ierului Valley, the Lower Meadow of the Tour - on the Tur and Valea Rea rivers, etc.; S.C.I. (areas of Community importance) according to O.M. no. 776/2007 are: Valea Izei and Dealul Solovan - on the rivers Iza, Boicu, Ieud and Botiza, Câmpia Careiului, etc (ABAST, 2019; CJ Maramureș, 2018).

The cultural objectives on the territory of the Someș-Tisa hydro-graphic space are numerous; thus, the most interesting objectives can be enumerated, such as: "George Coșbuc" and "Liviu Rebreanu" Memorial House, Săpânța Merry Cemetery, Baia Mare County Museum of History and Archeology, Sighetu Marmăției Ethnography Museum and Bârsana Monastery, wooden churches (UNESCO monuments) from Rogoz, Poienile Izei, Surdești, Plopiș, Ieud and Budești, Ardud Fortress, etc (ABAST, 2019; Cioruța et. al, 2020). Based on the above information, and taking into account that the monitoring and protection of soil resources are concerns of particular interest (which has more recently been achieved through the use of mobile devices that come bundled with various applications), through this paper, we set out to analyze whether the Someș-Tisa hydrographic area can be a representative one for soil monitoring and protection, as well as for carrying out agro-pedological studies using mobile applications (Cioruța et. al, 2014; Cioruța and Coman, 2019; 2021).

MATERIAL AND METHOD

In order for mobile applications to be used to their full potential (to efficiently collect, process, store and disseminate information of interest to users) (Cioruța et. al, 2014), the space considered for research needs to be extremely diverse. The diversification of the spatial configuration, as well as the dynamics of the field conditions, must be sufficiently well represented, to be able to support and validate the incursion of mobile applications.

In these conditions, we set out to verify whether the Someș-Tisa hydrographic area is

suitable (suitable) to support the development of agro-pedological studies in accordance with the specifications of the literature, especially the Methodology of Elaboration of Pedological Studies (1987, with subsequent amendments and completions) (Florea et. al, 1987; Cioruța and Coman, 2022), to see which of the basic ecopedological indicators are needed in agro-pedological studies. The next step coincided with checking the functionality of applications created in the MIT App Inventor® (Cioruța and Coman, 2021-2022) to see if they can be adapted to the conditions of the Someș-Tisa watershed.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

On the Romanian territory, the Someș-Tisa hydrographic area includes the Tisa sub-basin (also the Tour) with 123 coded watercourses (surface 4540 km² and network density of 0.35 km/km²), Someș with 403 codified watercourses (surface 15740 km², network density of 0.35 km/km²) and Crasna with 54 coded watercourses (area 2100 km² and network density of 0.34 km/km²) (ABAST, 2016; ABAST, 2019; CJ Maramureș, 2018).

From a geological perspective, the Someș-Tisa hydrographic area includes the north and northwest of the Transylvanian Basin, the northern and eastern massifs of the Apuseni Mountains, as well as parts of the Eastern Carpathians and the Pannonian Depression, with a predominantly siliceous structure and a wide range of metamorphic and sedimentary rocks.

The relief of the Someș-Tisa hydrographic space is varied in morphology and geologically complex, being represented by mountains (~20%), hills and plateaus (~55%), and plains (~25%). Among the main relief units of the considered area, represented in Fig. 3, identify:

- the area of high mountains - present in larger areas in the north and south (Maramureș, Rodna, and Gilău-Vlădeasa Mountains), as well as in the southeast (Călimani Mountains); are mountains that exceed 1800 m with the maximum altitude in the peak Pietrosul Rodnei (2303 m), with relief with steep slopes.
- the area of medium and low mountains - represented in the north and northeast by the mountains of volcanic origin Oaș, Gutâi, and Țibleș, and in the southwest and west by the Meseș and Plopiș Mountains with altitudes between 500 and 1400 m.

- Someșan plateau area - characterized by a complex of gentle shapes, with medium altitudes (≈ 600 m), having the appearance of platforms with frequent shapes of monoclinic structures.
- the plain area - located in the western part and represented by the Someș Plain, which has a slight inclination from southeast to northwest; it consists of a higher portion ($\approx 180-200$ m), a piedmont plain with wide interfluves and fan terraces and a lower portion

($\approx 115-125$ m), represented by a floodplain, with valleys few deep and deserted whites.

Regarding the hydro-meteorological and climatic conditions (see Fig. 4), the Someș-Tisa hydrographic space presents, by reference to the weather station from Baia Mare, a moderate continental temperate climate with clear oceanic nuances and without exaggerated variations of temperature and precipitation (Marcu and Coman, 2005; Coman, 2006; Cioruța et. al, 2013).

Figure 3. Hypsometric map of the Someș-Tisa hydrographic area (ABAST, 2016-2019)

Figure 4. Temperature variation, relative humidity, precipitation, nebulosity, speed and wind direction in the Someș-Tisa hydrographic area (Cioruța and Coman, 2022)

Precipitation registers values between ≈ 1000 - 1400 mm on the tops of high mountains (Rodna, Gutâi, Tibleş, Bîrgău, and Călimani Mountains), between ≈ 800 - 1200 mm in the Apuseni Mountains area from west to east, and ≈ 600 - 700 mm in the low regions (Transylvanian Plain and Someş Plain, Someş Plateau). The average annual temperature varies from $\approx 0^\circ\text{C}$ in the mountain area to over $\approx 9.4^\circ\text{C}$ in the plain area (Coman, 2006; Cioruţa et. al, 2013; Coman and Cioruţa, 2017).

Regarding the total surface water resources, they amount to ≈ 6830 mil. m^3/year , of which the usable resources are ≈ 1287 mil. m^3/year . Of these, $\approx 70\%$ are insured in the natural regime, the main watercourses being: Tisa, Someş, Vişeu, Someşul Mic, Lăpuş, Iza, and Şieu, and their tributaries. The difference in water resources is ensured by accumulations.

The hydrographic network of the Someş-Tisa area identifies both an impressive number of hydrometric stations (Fig. 5) and a number of 580 cadastral watercourses totaling a length of 8423 km, with an average density of 0.376 km/km^2 .

The Tisza River (cadastral code I.1) with a length of 1592 km has its sources in the Forest Carpathians, in the western territory of Ukraine, and flows into the Danube. On the Romanian territory, the Tisza basin has an area of 4540 km^2 , with an average slope of 2‰, gathering a number of 123 cadastral watercourses. The left tributaries of the Tisza that drain the Maramureş Depression are Vişeu (L=82 km; S=1581 km^2), Iza (L=80 km; S=1293 km^2), Săpânţa, Baia, Valea lui Francisc and the rivers that enter the Tisza over the border are Bătarci with Tarna Mare, Egher with Hodoş, and Tur.

The Tur River (L=66 km, S=1008 km^2) is considered to belong to the middle course of the Tisza, as well as the Someş, but in the territory of our country, it enters the group of northern rivers, draining the western slopes of the Oaş-Gutâi volcanic group. It springs from an altitude of approx. 950 m, the slope of the watercourse in the mountain sector reached 20 m/km, decreasing to the values of 2-8 m/km at the bottom of the depression and below 1 m/km in the plain sector (ABAST, 2016-2019).

In the first convergence area located north of Remetea Oaşului, Turul receives on the right its largest tributary, Lechinioara (L=29 km, S=286 km^2), with its tributaries Valea Rea and Valea Alba, and on the left on Slatina or Strâmba. The next tributary is the Talna (L=35 km, S=186 km^2), (ABAST, 2016-2019) which

crosses the southwestern region of the Oaş Depression, flowing parallel to the Turul, after collecting tributaries from the southern branch of the depression.

The Someş River (cadastral code II.1) with a length of 376 km, drains a river basin with an area of 15740 km^2 , a general slope of 3‰, gathering the waters of a number of 403 cadastral watercourses. Someşul, by uniting Someşul Mare with Someşul Mic upstream of Dej, crosses to the N-V the Someşan Plateau, between Clujului and Ciceului Hills, receiving symmetrically a series of tributaries from both sides. The important tributaries of the Someş are Almaş (L=65.4 km, S=810 km^2) and Lăpuş (L=114.6 km, S=1820 km^2) (ABAST, 2016). Someşul Mare has its springs at the end of the Rodna Mountains and results from the union of several streams with a length of 130 km, which drains 5033 km^2 . Its largest tributary is the Şieu.

Someşul Mic with a length of 178 km and a basin area of 3773 km^2 is formed by two mountain streams: Someşul Cald and Someşul Rece, which join at the eastern foot of the Gilău Mountains. Given the large size of the Someşul Cald, it is considered the source of the Someşul Mic. The largest tributary of the Someşul Mic is Fişeşul.

Someşul Cald (L=66.5 km, S=526 km^2) springs from under the Piatra Arsă peak, from the central massif of Bihariei-Vlădeasa. Its largest tributary is the Belis. Someşul Rece (L=45.6 km, S=331 km^2) (ABAST, 2016), drains through its tributaries in the central part of the Gilău Mountains, having its source near the Great Mountain. Its largest tributary is Răcăţău.

The Crasna River (cadastral code II.2) with a length of 134 km and a basin area of 1931 km^2 , collects the waters of 54 cadastral watercourses. Its main tributaries are Zalău, Maja, and Maria, all with insignificant flows and with lengths not exceeding 38 km.

In the Someş-Tisa hydrographic area, there are also eight important accumulation lakes (with an area of more than 0.5 km^2), which have a complex use and which amount to a useful volume of ≈ 328.3 mil. m^3 . Compared to the population of the basin, the specific usable resource is ≈ 504 $\text{m}^3/\text{inhabitant}/\text{year}$, and the specific resource calculated from the available stock is ≈ 3426 $\text{m}^3/\text{inhabitant}/\text{year}$ (ABAST, 2016-2019).

The water resources in the Someş-Tisa hydrographic area are sufficient, there is a reserve potential, being evenly distributed in time and space. The average multiannual flows

for the main rivers in the Someș-Tisa hydrographic area are $\approx 130 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$ (Tisa river at the exit from the country), $\approx 129 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$ (Someș river at Satu Mare hydrometric station), $\approx 6 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$ Crasna at Domănești station). Of the total length of watercourses registered in the Someș-Tisa hydrographic area, non-permanent watercourses represent $\approx 54.6\%$.

The usable groundwater resources at the basin level are estimated at $\approx 316 \text{ mil. m}^3$, of which $\approx 59\%$ come from groundwater sources and the rest from deep sources (ABAST, 2016-2019; Gâștescu, 2010). Zonal climatic conditions and surface water resources ensure rich biodiversity. As such, the vegetation must be viewed both in terms of zonal dynamics and vertical layering.

Figure 5. Hydrographic network and location of hydrometric stations in the Someș-Tisa hydrographic area (ABAST, 2016-2019)

Figure 6. Land use in the Someș-Tisa hydrographic area (ABAST, 2019)

The territory of the Someș-Tisa hydrographic area is located almost entirely in the immoral area, except for some restricted parts of the Someș Plain located in the forest-steppe area and the territories under the influence of the altitudinal zoning (Carpathian chain and high hills), is delimited on the basis the presence of oak forests, located on forest soils. Some habitats specific to the area are mentioned: Dacian forests of pedunculate oak, Pannonian oak forests pedunculate, Dacian forests of oak, beech, and hornbeam with *Lathyrus hallersteinii*; southeastern Carpathian forests of beech with *Festuca drymeia* (Helindian and Cioruța, 2021). Along with the hydrographic space, the representative fauna is the one from the area of plains and plateaus, meeting mammal species such as the woodpecker, the gray grouse, the field mouse, the ferret, the lynx, the marten, the partridge, the badger, etc. Among the birds, the most common are the reeds, the quail, the woodpeckers, and the tit. The aquatic fauna is represented by scobar, clean, and barbel. The mountain fauna is represented by mammals: lynx, bear, wolf, black goat, marmot; through birds: capercaillie, scissor, blackbird; through aquatic fauna: trout, clean, grayling.

In accordance with the composition of biodiversity, at the level of the Someș-Tisa hydrographic area, 10 sites of community importance (S.C.I.) were designated, as well as 35 special avifauna protection areas (S.P.A.).

Along with the previously mentioned sites, within the Someș-Tisa hydrographic area, there are also lands that have other uses. Fig. 6 refers to land use in 2019, in order to have an overview of soils and their use in water catchment areas, where it is desired to apply the environmental information systems (software applications) proposed. In addition to the above, it can be mentioned that the hydrophysical properties of the soil are an essential factor in the water circuit, influencing infiltration, surface runoff, and water loss by evaporation; so that in the well-drained perimeter of the Someș-Tisa hydrographic space the following soil classes are found:

- the cernisols class includes soils chestnut, chernozem, phaeozium, rendzina);
- the luvisols class includes soils with polygenetic evolution, developed in good or moderate drainage conditions (intermontane and submontane depression areas, plateau and plain areas);
- the cambisols class includes eutricambosol, distrambambosol, and eutricambosol soils (common in mountainous areas, submontane and intermontane depressions, meadows, and wandering areas);
- the spodisols class includes prepodzol and podzol (present on a large scale in the Rodna Mountains, Maramureș, and Apuseni Mountains);
- the umbrisols class includes black soil and humosiosol (it appears in the Carpathians at altitudes of 1000-1400 m);
- the andisols class includes soils formed by volcanic ash, pumice stone, and other volcanic derivatives of different compositions, morphologically they are characterized by a vitreous and andic horizon (it develops especially on volcanic rocks);
- the hydrosols class includes gleisols (located in poorly drained low plains, meadows, lower terraces, and depressions and on flat surfaces covered with clay deposits within the wetlands);
- salsodisols and vertisols that do not show a significant spread, being present only in isolation.

Regarding the land use in the entire Someș-Tisa hydrographic area, there is an uneven distribution of forests, pastures, arable lands, urban and industrial lands, depending on the type of relief of the respective areas.

Agricultural lands are predominant in all three river basins, Tisza (~51.9%), Someș (~64.3%), and Crasna (~72.1%). The forests occupy a larger area in the Tisza sub-basin (~42.8%) compared to the other sub-basins - Someș (~28.3%) and Crasna (~18.2%). Urban areas together with the water gloss have a share of ~7% of the total areas (ABAST, 2016).

All these elements have been recorded in order to be able to easily correlate them with some of the basic ecopedological indicators that are necessary for carrying out agro-pedological studies. As such, some of the indicators set out in the Methodology for the Development of Pedological Studies - more precisely, indicators related to the characteristics of climatic zones (Table 1), the characteristics of relief categories (Table 2), the characteristics of non-uniformity of the territory (Table 3), to the degree of soil pollution (Table 4) and to the types of soil pollution, by nature and source of the pollutant (Table 5) - were extracted.

Table 1

Characteristics of the main climatic zones (Florea et. al., 1987; reproduction with changes)

Climate areas	Average annual temperature, (°C)	Solar radiation, kcal/cm ²	Average annual rainfall, mm	Identifiable elements in the Someș-Tisa area
warm-dry areas	10.5-11.5	124-132	400-600	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
moderately warm & semidry areas	8.0-10.5	114-128	450-700	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
cold-wet areas	5.0-9.0	110-117	550-800	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
very cold-very wet areas	-2.0-6.0	<110	800-1400	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

Table 2

Characteristics of the relief categories (Florea et. al., 1987; reproduction with changes)

Relief areas	Characteristics			Correlation with the main forms of relief	Identifiable elements in the Someș-Tisa area
	slope, %	fragmentation density	relief energy, m		
meadow relief (alluvial plain)	<1	extremely weak	<10	Meadow, wandering plain, coastal plain	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
plain relief	<2(3)	very weak	10-50	Plain (terrace), plateau and foothills, slightly fragmented	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
wavy relief	2(3)-5(8)	weak	50-150	Plain (terrace), plateau and foothills, poorly fragmented	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
slightly rugged terrain	5(8)-12(18)	moderately	150-300	Moderately fragmented hill, plateau, and foothills	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
moderately rugged terrain	12(18)-20(30)	strong	300-500	Highly fragmented hill, plateau, and foothills	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
strongly rugged terrain	>20(30)	very strong	>500	Mountain	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

Table 3

Characteristics of the classes of non-uniformity of the territory (Florea et. al., 1987; reproduction with changes)

Land areas	Characteristics	Identifiable elements in the Someș-Tisa area
uniform territories	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> practically without unevenness; does not require leveling; 	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
very weakly uneven territories	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> bumps below 0.28 m; for leveling requires a volume of less than 300 m³/ha of the embankment; 	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
weakly uneven territories	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> bumps of 0.29-0.50 m; for leveling requires a volume of 301-500 m³/ha of the embankment; 	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
moderately non-uniform territories	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> bumps of 0.51-0.75 m; for leveling requires a volume of 501-800 m³/ha of the embankment; 	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
strongly non-uniform territories	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> bumps of 0,76-1,50 m; for leveling requires a volume of 801-1500 m³/ha of the embankment; 	?
very strongly non-uniform territories	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> bumps of over 1,51 m; for leveling requires a volume of over 1501 m³/ha of the embankment. 	?

Table 4

Degree of soil pollution (Florea et. al., 1987; reproduction with changes)		
Pollution type	Quantitative and/or qualitative reduction of the crop production obtained, compared to the crop production that can be obtained in conditions where the soil is unpolluted	Identifiable elements in the Someș-Tisa area
(practically) unpolluted	≤5%	☑
poorly polluted	6-10%	☑
moderately polluted	11-25%	☑
heavily polluted	26-50%	?
very heavily polluted	51-75%	?
excessively polluted	≥76%	?

Table 5

Types of soil pollution - by nature and source of pollutant (Florea et. al., 1987; reproduction with changes; Cioruța and Coman, 2022)

Nature and source of pollution	Elemente identificabile în arealul hidrografic Someș-Tisa
no pollution (practically unpolluted)	☑
pollution by up-to-date excavation works (up-to-date mining operations, gravel pits, quarries, etc.)	☑
pollution with landfills, dumps, tailings ponds, floating tailings dumps, landfills, etc.	☑
pollution by inorganic wastes and residues (minerals, inorganic materials, including metals, salts, acids, bases) from industry (including extractive industries)	☑
pollution by airborne substances (hydrocarbons, ethylene, ammonia, sulfur dioxide, chlorides, fluorides, nitrogen oxides, lead compounds, etc.)	☑
pollution with radioactive materials	?
pollution with organic waste and residues from the food and light industry	☑
pollution with agricultural and forestry waste and plant residues	☑
pollution with animal and human residues	☑
erosion and landslide pollution	☑
salt and acidification pollution	?
excess water pollution	☑
pollution by excess or nutrient deficiencies	?
compaction pollution, including crusting, and sediment pollution produced by erosion	?
pesticide pollution	☑
pollution with contaminating pathogens (infectious agents, toxins, allergens, etc.)	?

As can be seen, in the research area (Someș-Tisa hydrographic area) there are almost all ecopedological indicators related to climate and relief (Florea et. al, 1987; Cioruța and Coman, 2022), except those related to strong and very strongly non-uniform territories (see Table 3), respectively those starting with a severe form of soil pollution - Table 4 and Table 5 (Cioruța and Coman, 2015; Hreniuc et. al, 2015, 2019; Coman et. al, 2016).

The results, according to the literature consulted (the Methodology for the Development of Pedological Studies) and the functionalities of some applications created in the App Inventor®, showed that in the considered area mobile applications can be used for agro-pedological studies because they

meet, in the most part, all the basic ecopedological indicators.

CONCLUSIONS

Due to the spatial conformation, size of the area, and altitudinal layer, there are significant differences between the depression and the mountainous area of the Someș-Tisa hydrographic area.

These differences in relation to the characteristics of climatic zones (Table 1), relief categories (see Table 2), non-uniformity of the territory (see Table 3), the degree of soil pollution (see Table 4), and the types of soil pollution, by nature and source of the pollutant (Table 5), extracted from the Methodology for the Development of Pedological Studies, showed

that the mobile applications can be used for agro-pedological studies. Consequently, it can be stated that the Someș-Tisa hydrographic area corresponds to the requirements of the research undertaken and that the incursion of mobile applications is more than welcome.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

We thank Mrs. Ioana-Elisabeta SABOU (from NUCBM-TUCN) for her support in reviewing, correcting, and beautifying this material. We would also like to thank the Someș-Tisza Basin Water Administration for their work and the provision of open-source materials on soil regime and land use.

REFERENCES

- Administrația Bazinală de Apă Someș-Tisa (ABA Someș-Tisa), 2016, Planul de Management al Riscului la Inundații, Baia Mare. Accesat la 01.12.2021. Disponibil: <http://www.inhga.ro/documents/10184/121027/1+PMRI+Somes-Tisa.pdf>
- Administrația Bazinală de Apă Someș-Tisa (ABA Someș-Tisa), 2019, Prezentare generală a structurii organizatorice <https://somes-tisa.rowater.ro>
- Administrația Bazinală de Apă Someș-Tisa (ABA Someș-Tisa), 2019, Evaluarea preliminară a riscului la inundații https://rowater.ro/wp-content/uploads/2020/11/PFRA_Report_RO9_2019-08-30.pdf
- Administrația Bazinală de Apă Someș-Tisa (ABA Someș-Tisa), 2021, Planul de Management Bazinal al Spațiului Hidrografic Someș-Tisa (2022-2027). Accesat la 01.12.2021. Disponibil: https://somes-tisa.rowater.ro/wp-content/uploads/2021/10/PMBH_Somes-Tisa_2021.pdf
- Agenția de Dezvoltare Regională Nord-Vest (ADRN), 2021, Planul de Dezvoltare Regională Nord-Vest 2021-2027, Extras: Profilul Socio-Economic al Regiunii (draft 1). Accesat la 01.12.2021. Disponibil: www.nord-vest.ro/wp-content/uploads/2020/02/0.-Profil-socio-economic-Regiunea-Nord-Vest.pdf
- Cioruța B., Coman M., (2015) Innovative possibilities to represent the Baia Mare Urban System soils pollution with heavy metals using G.S. Surfer, International Conference "Scientific Research and Education in the Air Force" (AFASES®), 28-30 mai 2015, Brașov, pg. 551-556 www.afahc.ro/.../afases2015/Cioruta_Coman.pdf
- Cioruța B., Coman M., (2019) Considerations regarding the implications of mobile-based Environmental Information Systems in contaminated soils characterization, Journal of Documentation, Research and Professional Training (ProEnvironment®/ProMediu®), vol. 12, nr. 38, pg. 127-131, Print ISSN: 1844-6698, Electronic ISSN: 2066-1363 <http://journals.usamvcluj.ro/index.php/promediu/article/view/13638/11227>
- Cioruța B., Coman M., (2021) Implications of Mobile-based Information Systems in the Contaminated Soils Characterization, Natural Resources and Sustainable Development (NRSD®), ISSN-L 2066-6276, eISSN 2601-5676, DOI: 10.31924/nrsd.v11i2.073, University of Debrecen - Faculty of Agricultural and Food Sciences and Environmental Management & University of Oradea - Faculty of Environmental Protection and Engineering Department, 11(2): 135-142. https://www.nrsd.com/issues-year-2021-2/implications-of-mobile-based-information-systems-in-contaminated-soils-characterization.html#_YIPqapFBxPY
- Cioruța B., Coman M., 2022, Definition, role, and functions of soil-related to the Knowledge Society and the Someș-Tisa hydrographic area (Romania), MDPI - Sustainability®, Switzerland, vol. 14, 8688, pg. 1-14, <https://doi.org/10.3390/su14148688>
- Cioruța B., Coman M., Cioruța A., (2013) Considerations regarding the last 3-5 years hydrometeorological conditions from the Baia Mare area, International Conference "Scientific Research and Education in the Air Force" (AFASES®), 23-25 mai 2013, Brașov, pg. 376-381 www.afahc.ro/.../afases2013/Cioruta_Coman_Cioruta.pdf
- Cioruța B., Coman M., Cioruța A., (2014) Studying Environmental Problematics and Hazards with help of Informatics Applications, International Conference "Scientific Research and Education in the Air Force" (AFASES®), 22-24 mai 2014, Brașov, pg. 289-292 www.afahc.ro/.../afases2014/Cioruta_Coman_Cioruta.pdf
- Cioruța B., Pop A.L., Coman M., (2020) On the philatelic circuit of the UNESCO churches from Maramureș, Asian Journal of Education and Social Studies (AJESS®), vol. 13, issue 3, pg. 60-84 <https://www.journalajess.com/index.php/AJESS/article/view/30335>
- Coman M., 2006, Depresiunea Baia Mare: protecția mediului din perspectiva dezvoltării durabile, Editura Risoprint, Cluj-Napoca
- Coman M., Cioruța B., (2017) Considerations about the influence of climate changes at Baia Mare urban system level, International Conference "Scientific Research and Education in the Air Force" (AFASES®), 25-27 mai 2017, Brașov, pg. 257-262 www.afahc.ro/ro/afases/2017/29-EE-ComanMirela,CiorutaBogdanVasile.pdf
- Coman M., Cioruța B., Pop R., (2016) Regarding the evolution of soils polluted with oil products in Săcel oilfield (Romania), AgroLife Scientific Journal, vol. 5., no. 2, pg. 44-49, ISSN 2285-5718; ISSN CD-ROM 2285-5726; ISSN ONLINE 2286-0126; ISSN-L 2285-5718 agrolifejournal.usamv.ro/.../art7.pdf
- Consiliul Județean Maramureș (CJ Maramureș), 2018, Strategia de Dezvoltare Durabilă a Județului Maramureș pentru perioada 2014-2020 - <https://www.cjmaramures.ro/attachments/strategie/Strategia%20de%20Dezvoltare%20Durabila%20a%20Județului%20Maramures%202014-2020.pdf>
- Covăsnianu A., 2011, Regiunile de dezvoltare în România europeană. Între deziderat politic și realitate teritorială, Universitatea „Al. I. Cuza” din Iași. Accesat la 01.12.2021. Disponibil: https://www.academia.edu/1165575/Regiunile_de_dezvoltare_in_România_europeană_între_deziderat_politic_si_realitate_teritorială
- Florea N., Bălăceanu V., Răuță C., Canarache A., (coord.), 1987, Metodologia elaborării studiilor pedologice: partea a III-a - indicatorii ecopedologici, Institutul de Cercetări pentru Pedologie și Agrochimie, București
- Gâștescu P., 2010, Resursele de apă din România: potențial, calitate, distribuție teritorială și management, în Resursele de apă din România. Vulnerabilitate la activitățile antropice, Conference Proceedings, 11-13 June 2010, Târgoviște (România), ISBN: 978-606-8042-65-7. <http://www.limnology.ro/water2010/Proceedings/01.pdf>
- Helindian A.N., Cioruța B., (2021) The Eco-Cinegetic Management in a Forest District from Maramureș (Romania), Asian Journal of Biology, 2021; 12(1): 10-19 https://www.journalajob.com/index.php/AJOB/article/view/30153_10.9734/ajob/2021/v12i130153
- Hreniuc M., Cioruța B., Coman M., (2019) An insight into the history of scientific concerns about soil pollution in Maramureș County, Journal of Documentation, Research and Professional Training (ProEnvironment®/ProMediu®), vol. 12, nr. 38, pg. 142-149, Print ISSN: 1844-6698, Electronic ISSN: 2066-1363 <http://journals.usamvcluj.ro/index.php/promediu/article/view/13643/11231>
- Hreniuc M., Coman M., Cioruța B., (2015) Considerations regarding the soil pollution with oil products in Săcel - Maramureș, International Conference "Scientific Research and Education in the Air Force" (AFASES®), 28-30 mai 2015, Brașov, pg. 557-562 www.afahc.ro/.../afases2015/Hreniuc_Coman_Cioruta.pdf
- Marcu M., Coman M., 2005, Aspecte privind unele particularități climatice ale Depresiunii Baia Mare și influența lor în procesele poluante, Buletin Științific al Universității de Nord Baia Mare, vol. XIX, pp. 479-483

THE LEVEL OF AIR POLLUTION WITH SUSPENDED PARTICULATE MATTER IN BIHOR COUNTY BETWEEN 2019 AND 2021

Nandor KÖTELES^{1*}, Ana Cornelia PEREȘ¹, Adela Olimpia TODEA¹

¹University of Oradea, Faculty of Environmental Protection, Gen. Magheru st., no.26, 410048, Oradea, Romania

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

This paper studies the degree of pollution with suspended particulate matter in Bihor County for a period of three years (2019, 2020, 2021). We used data from the Bihor Oradea Environmental Protection Agency, which deals with air pollution monitoring in Bihor County. Four air sampling stations are located in Bihor County. Of which two are located in Oradea, one at the headquarters of A.P.M. Bihor, BH₁ this being an urban station, and the second one is in Water Lily, near McDonalds- drive BH₃ being a traffic station. The other two are industrial stations BH₂ is located in the Episcopia Bihor, and BH₄ is located in Țețchea.

Keywords: maximum permissible concentration, monitoring, sampling points, suspended particulate matter.
#Corresponding author: kotelesnandor@yahoo.com

INTRODUCTION

Suspended particulate matter are formed from a complex mixture of very small particles and liquid droplets, they are formed in the atmosphere as a result of complex reactions of chemicals.

These particles can be very dangerous, and they can affect our health in the long run. Suspended particulate matter PM₁₀ is 10 micrometer in diameter (Köteles, 2011). Particulate matter can be of two natural and anthropogenic kinds.

Natural sources are volcanic eruptions, rock erosion, sandstorms, pollen dispersion, etc.

Natural sources are volcanic eruptions, rock erosion, sandstorms, pollen dispersion, etc. These particles in some cases may contain carbon particles, heavy metals, or more severely toxic pollutants, iron oxides, sulfates (Pereș, 2011).

MATERIAL AND METHOD

For this study we used data from the Environmental Protection Agency of Bihor Oradea. In Bihor county area there are 4 sampling stations that ensure the monitoring of air quality in Bihor County. The 4 sampling stations are strategically located, the first BH₁ is located in the A.P.M. Bihor Oradea headquarters, Dacia Boulevard nr. 25/A being an urban station. The second BH₂ station is

located in Episcopia Bihor, street Matei Corvin nr.106/A and is an industrial station. The third BH₃ station is located in the Nufăru Quarter, near McDonalds-drive being a traffic station. And the fourth BH₄ station is located in Țețchea, being an industrial station (www.apmbh.ro).

1. The monitoring and supervision of air pollution with particulate matter is carried out by the Environmental Protection Agency of Bihor Oradea (www.calitateair.ro).

In this paper we studied the variations, the level of pollution with suspended particulate matter, over a period of three years (2019 - 2021) (Köteles & Pereș, 2019). The limit value for suspended particulate matter PM₁₀, according to Law no. 104/2011 on ambient air quality is the average daily value of 50 µg/m³ (STAS 12574/1987).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

1. Annual evolution of suspended particulate matter

For 2019, the highest level of concentrations of suspended particulate matter was recorded in Episcopia Bihor BH₂ with a value of 20.499 µg/m³, followed by BH₁ in Oradea with 18.148 µg/m³. The value less than 4.825 µg/m³ was determined in BH₃ of Nufăru.

In 2020, the highest value was recorded in Oradea at BH₁ of 18.281 µg/m³, of 17.517 µg/m³ at the BH₃ station, followed by BH₄ in Țețchea with 15.861 µg/m³. The higher value

for 2021 was determined at the BH2 sampling point being 24.783 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$. Close values were also determined at BH1 (21.754 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$), BH4

(13.428 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) and BH3 (10.805 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) (Figure 1)

Figure 1 The evolution of suspended particulate matter average concentrations in Bihor county, 2019 – 2021

Following the analysis of the three years studied, the evolution of the multiannual average concentrations shows that the highest level was determined at the BH2 station 22.141 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, followed by the stations BH1 with

19.394 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, BH4 with 14.645 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ and BH3 with 11.049 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ (Figure 2).

From these data we can find that the maximum permissible concentration has not been exceeded.

Figure 2. Evolution of the multiannual average concentrations (2019 – 2021) of suspended particulate matter at the 4 monitoring points in Bihor county

2. Monthly evolution of suspended particulate matter

From the average concentration of the four sampling points during the period considered (2019 - 2021), for 2019 it appears that the highest value was recorded in January a value of 26.435 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, of 25.596 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ in October and of 23.925 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ in February. The lowest value was determined in May at 9.708 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$.

During 2020, the highest values were recorded in February of 30.188 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, November of 26.597 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ and 24.705 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ in December. The lowest value was recorded in March being 7.123 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$.

The highest values for 2021 were determined in February at 28.712 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, followed by November (25.727 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) and December (22.520 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Monthly pattern of suspended particulate matter in Bihor county (the average of the 4 sampling points)

The analysis of the evolution of the multiannual monthly average concentrations of the level of suspended particulate matter pollution for the studied period shows that the highest concentrations were determined in the

month of January $24.489 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, November $24.132 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ and December $21.818 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$. And the lowest values were determined in July $10.379 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, June $10.61 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ and August $11.206 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ (Figure 4).

Figure 4. The evolution of multiannual monthly average concentrations of suspended particulate matter in Bihor (the average of the 4 sampling points)

3. Evolution of particulate matter pollution at sampling points

Following the analysis of the pollution level, at the BH1 sampling station that is located in Oradea at the A.P.M. Bihor headquarters, it results that the highest value in 2019 was determined in January $38.981 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, followed

by February $36.910 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ and October $23.886 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ (Figure 5).

In 2020, the highest values were recorded in December $31.607 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ and January $23.755 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$. The highest values determined in 2021 were in February ($34.116 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) and December ($31.115 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$).

Figure 5 Monthly evolution of suspended particulate matter at sampling point BH₁

At sampling point BH1 in 2019, there were 10 exceedances of the maximum permissible concentration of 50 µg/m³. These exceedances were in January 4 overshoots, February 3

overshoots and October 3 overshoots. In 2020 there were 2 overshoots, and in 2021 also 2 exceedances (Table 1).

Table 1

Values of overshoots at the sampling station BH₁

Sampling point	Year	Month	Day	The values µg/m ³
BH ₁	2019	January	10	61.510
			20	55.460
			24	53.540
			26	64.490
		February	8	51.490
			10	52.930
			16	60.510
		October	17	70.810
			18	62.130
			25	57.720
	2020	November	7	56.060
			16	53.470
	2021	December	15	69.820
16			67.450	

At the BH₁ sampling station in the Episcopia Bihor locality, for 2019, higher values were determined in October 30.74 µg/m³ and in July 28.647 µg/m³. Close values were also recorded in 2020 in the months of November

(34.139 µg/m³) and December (30.032 µg/m³). In 2021 the determined values were higher, in November 41.848 µg/m³ and February 39.818 µg/m³ (Figure 6).

Figure 6 Monthly evolution of suspended particulate matter at sampling points BH₂

At the BH₂ monitoring point, 24 exceedances of the maximum permissible concentration of 50 µg/m³ occurred. In 2019,

there were 2 exceedances, but in 2021 there were 22 exceedances (Table 2).

Table 2

Values of overshoots at the sampling station BH₂

Sampling point	Year	Month	Day	The values µg/m ³	Sampling point	Year	Month	Day	The values µg/m ³	
BH ₂	2021	October	26	57.270	BH ₂	2021				
			27	56.730						
	2021	February	18	65.640				November	12	66.360
			19	51.090					13	59.820
			22	66.360					15	90.360
			23	66.730					16	75.450
			24	82.36					17	67.450
			25	88.180					18	65.450
			26	96.730					December	9
		March	26	56.360				14		53.090
			October	27				62.730		15
		28		66.000						
	29	75.450								
	30	65.090								
			31	50.730						

The concentration level of particulate matter at the BH₃ monitoring station, for the years studied, shows that in 2019 the highest concentration was in October 22.162 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, followed by November 21.701 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$. In 2020,

the highest values were also in October 21.165 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ and November 20.378 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$. In 2021, the highest values were in February 18,819 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ and January 18,088 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$. (Figure 7)

Figure 7 Monthly evolution of suspended particulate matter at sampling point BH₃

At the BH₃ monitoring point, there were 2 exceedances of the maximum permissible concentration in 2019 on 5 December 65.290 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ and on 7 December 62.050 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$.

No determinations were made at the BH₄ sampling point in 2019. In 2020 the highest level was in January 46.829 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ as of October 28.883 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$. And in 2021, the highest value was in January 22.096 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ (Figure 8).

Figure 8 Monthly evolution of suspended particulate matter at sampling point BH₄

In 2020 the highest level was in January 46.829 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ as of October 28.883 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$.

And in 2021, the highest value was in January 22.098 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ (Table 3).

Table 3

Values of overshoots at the sampling station BH ₄				
Sampling point	Year	Month	Day	The values $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$
BH ₄	2020	January	8	50.30
			10	67.18
			11	81.54
			12	64.69
			14	67.20
			17	78.39
			18	65.96
			20	60.12
			21	53.29

CONCLUSIONS

From the analysis of the pollution level of particulate matter, for the period 2019 - 2021, at the 4 sampling stations it results that from the evolution of the average and multiannual concentrations as well as, annual and multiannual monthly averages, the maximum permissible concentration of 50 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ has not been exceeded.

But from the daily measurements made at the 4 sampling stations were 45 days when the maximum permissible concentration was exceeded.

It was found that these exceedances were mostly in the cold period of the year, because during this period the houses in Bihor County are heated with wood.

Chimneys evacuate large amounts of particulate matter into the atmosphere, which in the absence of precipitation can remain long in the atmospheric air.

REFERENCES

- Köteles, N., 2011, Practical and Theoretical Notions of Air Pollution, Editor Universităţii of Oradea, ISBN 978-606-10-0694-6.
- Pereş, A. C., 2011, Pollution and Self-purification of the Atmosphere, Editor Universităţii of Oradea, ISBN 978-606-10-0693-9.
- Köteles, N., & Pereş, A. C., The Level of Air Pollution with Sediment Particles in Bihor County between 2016 and 2018, Annals of the University of Oradea, Fascicle: Environmental Protection, Vol. XXXIII, 2019.
(STAS 12574/1987.
www.calitateaer.ro
www.apmbh.ro

AN ANALYSIS OF THE IMPACT OF DROUGHT ON THE NATIONAL ECONOMY

Adelina VENIG^{1#}, Aurora VENIG¹, Nicoleta MATEOC- SÎRB²,
Elena PETI²

¹ University of Oradea, Faculty of Environmental Protection, Oradea

² University of Life Sciences, "King Michael I" from Timișoara, Faculty Management and Rural Tourism, Timișoara

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

Today, agriculture enjoys special attention in all countries of the world, regardless of the level of economic development. In the contemporary world, the most developed countries from the point of view economically, they are also the largest producers and exporters of agricultural products. As the basic branch of our national economy, agriculture asserts itself as a field of particularly complex and complicated activity. The complexity of agriculture, as a branch of material production, of the national economy, is determined by the role of agriculture in economic development and its technical peculiarities, economic and social, which gives general economic laws a specific manifestation in agriculture. Unfortunately, in recent years, agriculture is facing a threat, namely drought. The importance of the present research is obvious considering the increasing trend of annual average temperatures from year to year due to global warming - especially - but also a other factors such as pollution. Drought, even a temporary one of medium size can have catastrophic effects in all branches of the economy, especially in agriculture, but also in other fields related to human life.

Keywords: drought, agricultural production, cereal crops, economy

#Corresponding author: adelina_venig@yahoo.com

INTRODUCTION

Droughts can be considered the most complex climatic phenomena, because several factors participate in their triggering, namely: atmospheric precipitation, soil water reserve accessible to the plant, air humidity and temperature, evapotranspiration, wind speed, etc., these being the main climatic parameters that define the state of dry or dry weather (Riedel, 2018). To these are added other factors that define the characteristics of the active surface (relief, soil features, water table depth, degree of vegetation cover, etc.), factors that define the physiological characteristics of the plant (such as the variety and vegetation phase, the degree of drought resistance), as well as factors that highlight the anthropic influence on the environment (the state of the land and the agricultural techniques used that can facilitate the depletion of soil water) (Fohrer, 2020). As a complex meteorological phenomenon, drought is characterized, in general, by the absence of

precipitation, as well as by the increase in potential evapotranspiration (Prabhu, 2020). On the other hand, hot and dry winds (dry winds), with high speeds, also contribute to increasing evapotranspiration and reducing humidity, both from the soil and from the air. During the growing season, the various crops and plant associations have varying requirements for water, so that a period of drought does not simultaneously affect the entire cultivated or natural vegetal carpet (Rickmann, 2014). Drought leads to large losses of agricultural production. Its consequences were especially hard in the past, especially when there were two or three dry years in a row. The consequences of the drought are determined both by the degree of intensity and duration, as well as by the affected surface (Maurer, 2016). Droughts covering an area of up to 10% of the territory of Romania were evaluated as local; 11-20% are considered - vast; 21-30% - very large; 31-50% - extreme, and above 50% are considered catastrophic droughts, because they cause great losses to the

national economy. Agriculture is an important branch of any national economy with functions among the most various: biological, main source of economic activity and use of labor force, factor ecological protection of the environment and the fight against desertification in many areas of the Earth, a way of life, a technical and cultural tradition and, last but not least, agriculture is a civilization (Riedel, 2018).

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The key research methods employed were analysis and synthesis, analogy, and graphics to resemble the results.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

In Romania, agriculture is an economic branch of first importance, with an old tradition, which constitutes the basic occupation for a large part of the population, respectively 27.7%, in 2022. In fact, in our rural environment lives almost half (over 47%, in 2002) of the total population of the country. The importance of agriculture as a branch of activity is given by the agricultural potential of our country, represented, first of all, by the 14.8 million hectares of agricultural land, of which 8.7 million hectares (62%) are arable. In para secondly, of the good-medium quality of the soil, which, together with a climate mediocre, ensures agricultural productions able to cope with the food consumption of populations. Agricultural production, unlike industrial production, has a very high degree of insecurity, depending, to the greatest extent, on the climatic conditions. Under the in this aspect, Romania presents, as shown above, a great climate risk, especially with regard to the precipitation regime, a fact for which both droughts, as well as floods are frequent phenomena that greatly affect production agricultural. Specialists estimate that, at the level of the entire country, about 2% of the total of the agricultural area is affected by extremely severe drought (practically, in all years), 28% of very severe drought (in more than 40 out of 100 years) and 60% of reduced drought (in less than 10 out of 100 years). As is known, drought primarily affects plant production, and depending on the duration and intensity of this phenomenon, its negative effects are it also transfers to animal husbandry. The most

important losses are related to calamity grain crops, on which security depends to the greatest extent food of the population. This happens, in case of drought, also in Romania, known by the large share of vegetable agricultural production (62.8%), in the total production obtained in the agricultural sector. Regarding the profile of plant production, this it is given by the grain culture, dominated by wheat and corn, which have an old tradition in our country. At the moment, because cereal crops, practiced mainly by private agricultural sector, are carried out on small areas, with minimum expenses of establishment and maintenance, the harvests obtained are low and influenced by the conditions climate, especially drought. Consequently, the incomes of agricultural producers are in accordance with the low productivity, and the drought that is extending from one year in another, it puts many farmers in the impossibility of resuming the agricultural cycle. In the graphic below is presented how the drought affected wheat harvests and corn, in 2022, when this phenomenon manifested itself in the mod excessively, for long periods of time, and sometimes included the whole territory of the country. This caused the areas cultivated with cereals to be calamity on large areas, and the value losses to be significant.

Figure 1 Crops affected by drought in 2022

Within cereal crops, the strongest impact of annual droughts, from the analyzed period, it was manifested at the level of wheat and corn crops, which represent the main cereal plants on which food security depends the population of our country. Since drought can occur at different times of the year, and because the two cereals have different vegetation cycles and water requirements, this extreme weather phenomenon can affect, during an agricultural year, or only the culture wheat, or only that of corn. Exceptionally, as was the year 2022, when

excessive drought manifested itself over a long period of time, they were calamities both cultures.

The drought from 2022 brings a loss of over one billion euros in Romanian agriculture due to the lack of production on the 800,000 hectares affected by the drought. Thus, after a year with record production of 34 million tons of grain, like 2021, and maximum prices, agriculture is hit again. In this way, the losses that accumulate from one year to another, due to excessive and prolonged droughts, accentuates the decline in agriculture and contributes to the accentuation of poverty, especially at the level of over 4 million small holdings, of the peasant household type. It comes to the situation that, regardless of the price of sale of grain, a large part of the peasants will not be able to cover their expenses of production and therefore to be unable to resume the agricultural cycle. The impact of droughts in agriculture is also felt by the urban population, through the prices of agricultural products, which register increases immediate and constitutes a barometer of the intensity of these meteorological phenomena destructive. Among the negative effects of drought, poverty is the most serious dysfunction, in socioeconomic terms, from the areas affected by this climatic phenomenon extremely. Poverty is defined as a state of long-term lack of necessary resources to ensure a way of life considered decent, acceptable at the level of one

CONCLUSIONS

Drought, even a temporary one of medium size can have catastrophic effects in all branches of the economy, especially in agriculture, but also in other fields which are related to human life. Following the research, several solutions to combat the drought can be proposed: Investments in irrigation systems; reducing dependence on the international economic supply chain by developing the local supply chain; use of wastewater in agriculture. In this way, the consumption of drinking water from the groundwater table would be reduced; food storage system to combat food waste; diversification of food resources. In conclusion, it can be stated that in order to reduce the degree of vulnerability a of an economy to the socio-economic effects of drought phenomena can be implemented strategies for controlled

community. This definition suggests the idea of relating the phenomenon to the societal context more widely, in this case, to the state of poverty in our country.

The research undertaken in order to establish the level of community poverty in our country highlights the fact that it cantons, especially, in the rural environment, where the population lives, for the most part, from the incomes obtained from agricultural production (vegetable and animal), which can fluctuate significantly depending on the situation of climatic parameters. Although the factors of poverty are identified mainly in economic, political, social and cultural, it can also be based on a faulty drought management.

The phenomenon is sometimes also due to the low degree of awareness of the working condition by the population and its non-involvement in prevention and mitigation actions desertification and soil degradation. This explains the fact that the areas with bags of persistent poverty are also those that register a sharp degradation of irrigation systems or deforestation of protective forest curtains an agricultural land. Therefore, the socioeconomic impact of rural poverty translates by the low standard of living of the population, by the deficit of human capital, by high demographic dependence, through a poorly developed infrastructure, through poor living conditions and inadequate public services.

reduction of specific water requirements or identification of possibilities of increasing the water availability of the respective company, by increasing the capacities of storage (accumulations, artificial enrichment of aquifers) and identification of new water sources that can be transported to that area. Considering economic development exacerbated by human society over the past two centuries, with exponentially increasing demands of water, the only solution in maintaining an optimal and acceptable degree of vulnerability to drought is the social and economic development in balance with the environmental potential of the respective region, in other words, sustainable socio-economic development.

REFERENCES

- Abraham T., 2020. Principles and practices of agricultural irrigation, Unser Wissen Press, 16-18
- Fohrer N., 2016. Hydrology, UTB Press, 90-91
- Maurer J. & co., 2016. Handbook for organic fruit varieties preserved, Löwenzahn Press, Innsbruck, 57-58
- Prabhu N., 2020. Hydrology and Manegement, Unser Wissen Press, 64-65
- Rickmann M., 2014. Irrigation in agriculture, Erling Press, 124-125
- Riedel A., 2018. Improving nutrient efficiency through irrigation, Institut Julius Kühn, 45- 46
- Riedel A., 2018. Improving nutrient efficiency through irrigation, Institut Julius Kühn, 145-147